

SNDT Women's University

National Seminar Proceeding

**Development of 21st-century skills for 'Atmanirbhar Bharat'
(self-reliant India)**

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Forward

It is with great pleasure and pride that I extend my warmest greetings to all the participants, and contributors associated with the Two-Day National Seminar on the Development of 21st-century Skills for 'Atmanirbhar Bharat.' This seminar, organized by PVDI College of Education for Women, SNDT Women's University, in collaboration with the Indian Council of Social Science Research (ICSSR), stands as a testament to our collective commitment towards fostering a self-reliant India.

As we progress into the 21st century, the world has witnessed profound transformations in the realms of knowledge, technology, and societal dynamics. In this ever-evolving landscape, it is imperative for us to equip our youth with the necessary skills and competencies to navigate through challenges and capitalize on opportunities. The vision of 'Atmanirbhar Bharat,' envisioned by Hon'ble Prime Minister Shri Narendra Modi, emphasizes the integration of 21st-century skills as a cornerstone of modern education.

This seminar provided an ideal platform for researchers, educators, policymakers, and industrial professionals to engage in constructive dialogue, share their expertise, and explore innovative approaches to developing 21st-century skills. The thematic exploration of various sub-themes further deepened our understanding of the diverse dimensions of skill development and its alignment with the national goal of self-reliance.

I commend the Advisory board members and organizing committee for curating an enriching program comprising keynote sessions, plenary discussions, panel talks, and paper presentations. The diverse perspectives shared by the esteemed speakers and participants have undoubtedly enriched our collective knowledge and inspired us to embrace transformative pedagogies and practices.

I extend my heartfelt appreciation to the eminent keynote speakers, panelists, and paper presenters for their valuable contributions, which have set the stage for insightful conversations and future research endeavors. Moreover, I express my gratitude to all the participants whose active engagement and enthusiasm have been the driving force behind the success of this seminar.

As we move forward, I urge all stakeholders in the education ecosystem to take inspiration from the ideas discussed and resolutions made during this seminar. Let us strive to create educational environments that foster critical thinking, creativity, digital literacy, and other essential 21st-century skills in our students. By nurturing these skills, we empower our future generation to lead and contribute significantly to the progress of our great nation.

I hope that the proceedings of this seminar serve as a valuable resource for educators, researchers, policymakers, and stakeholders involved in shaping the future of education. May the insights gathered here inspire continuous efforts towards the holistic development of our youth and the realization of an 'Atmanirbhar Bharat.'

Once again, my heartfelt congratulations to **Dr. Mahesh Koltame** and team, and I look forward to witnessing the positive impact of the ideas shared during this seminar on the educational landscape of our nation.

Dr. Subhas Waghmare

Seminar Director

Preface

It is with great pleasure and honor that I present the proceedings of the Two-Day National Seminar on the Development of 21st-century Skills for 'Atmanirbhar Bharat.' This seminar, organized by PVDT College of Education for Women, SNDT Women's University, in collaboration with the Indian Council of Social Science Research (ICSSR), was held on 23rd and 24th December 2022, as a part of the 'Azadi Ka Amrit Mahotsav' celebrations.

The theme of this seminar, "Development of 21st-century skills for 'Atmanirbhar Bharat' (self-reliant India)," was carefully chosen to address the pressing need for nurturing and integrating 21st-century skills in our education system. In the rapidly evolving world, the acquisition of critical thinking, creativity, communication, and other essential skills is paramount for preparing the future generation to meet the challenges and embrace the opportunities of the 21st century.

The seminar witnessed the convergence of esteemed scholars, researchers, educators, policymakers, and professionals from various parts of the country, who shared their invaluable insights and experiences during the keynote session, plenary sessions, panel discussions, and paper presentation sessions. Their contributions not only enriched the discourse on 21st-century skill development but also provided a roadmap to realize the vision of 'Atmanirbhar Bharat.'

Throughout the two days, we delved into multiple sub-themes, exploring the integration of 21st-century skills in school education, teacher education, language education, science & technology education, and social science education, among others. The paper presentation sessions showcased evidence-based research and innovative approaches, thereby stimulating meaningful discussions on curriculum and pedagogical practices.

This publication is a compilation of all 34 research papers that are presented and discussed ideas and findings presented during the seminar. It serves as a comprehensive repository of knowledge, offering readers valuable insights into the current state of 21st-century skill development in the Indian context. It is our hope that these proceedings will ignite further exploration and inspire stakeholders to collaboratively work towards empowering our students with the essential skills required for an 'Atmanirbhar Bharat.'

I extend our heartfelt gratitude to all the participants, presenters, session chairs, and distinguished guests who contributed to the success of this seminar. Their active involvement and intellectual contributions have made this endeavor truly meaningful and impactful.

I also express our gratitude to the Hon'ble Prime Minister Shri Narendra Modiji for his visionary mission of 'Atmanirbhar Bharat,' which continues to inspire us to strengthen our education system for a self-reliant India.

Finally, we hope that the knowledge disseminated through this collection of proceedings will find its way into policy frameworks, curriculum design, and teaching practices to pave the way for a future generation equipped to lead India towards prosperity and self-reliance.

Dr. Mahesh Koltame
(Seminar Convener)

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1. 21st Century Learning Skills (the four C's)

Prof. H. B Patel¹, Renu Pandey²

Abstract

Life is all about learning and discovering. The ability to perform a specific task flawlessly is referred to as skill. There are 12 skills known as 21st century skills that are necessary for success in life and work in the information age. These abilities are meant to aid us in keeping up with the quick-moving modern markets of today. Each skill has a unique way of being helpful, but they all share a certain trait. In the era of the Internet, they are crucial.

Three groups comprise the twelve 21st Century skills like critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, communication, Information literacy, media literacy, technology literacy, flexibility, leadership, Initiative, Productivity, and social skills.

The three groups into which 21st Century skills are divided are learning skills, literacy skills and life skills. The four C's – Critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, and communication are known as 21st century learning skills curriculum teaches students the mental processes necessary to adapt to and enhance a contemporary work environment. Learning skills (the four C's) instructs students about the mental processes required to adapt and improve upon a modern work environment.

Present article focuses on the meaning and importance of 21st century learning skills and how to use the four C's in the classroom. Students can distinguish between facts, publishing platforms, and the technology that supports them.

Keywords: 21st Century skills, Critical thinking, Creativity, Collaboration and Communication

"The wisest mind has something yet to learn"

-George Santayana

The term 21st Century Skills is used very frequently. This phrase is more than just a fancy term. However, the precise meaning of this term and its relevance to employability, education, and the employment process are not often made evident. The abilities that our children will require to be successful in a world that is becoming increasingly linked and complicated are, to put it more simply, the skills of the 21st century. The academic and social skills that kids will need to succeed in the 21st century, both in school and in their future employment, are included in the concept of "21st century skills."

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The majority of "deeper learning" skills, such as critical thinking, problem solving, and teamwork, form the foundation of 21st-century competencies, which also include a mix of "soft" and "hard" skills, such as interacting with others, collaborating on projects, processing information, and managing people (with an IT focus. Digital literacy, media literacy, etc.).

We put a significant focus on the following four important qualities that assist students learn how to develop meaningful connections, particularly with individuals who come from a variety of various origins and cultures:

The four C's of 21st Century learning Skills are:

1. Critical Thinking
2. Creativity
3. Collaboration
4. Communication

Let us take a closer look at each of these abilities and examine them in more depth:

1. Critical Thinking

Critical Thinking is the process of actively and methodically communicating, problem solving, evaluating, and analysing information. It is a Synthesis of Individual and collective thought for the purposes of enhancing comprehension, facilitating effective decision-making, and directing appropriate action. Organizations put a greater value on individuals who can think critically. Critical Thinking helps in

- Analysing complex situations.
- Solving problems.
- Help in articulating our stance in a rational manner and
- Helps in making sound judgments, those are founded on facts and reason, rather than feelings and emotions.

Critical thinking is a talent that is important for students to learn and display in school since it will be required of them in the real world. And yet, educators typically present material in a rigid, crystalline fashion that encourages rote memory over critical thinking. The meaning of critical thinking can be interpreted in a variety of ways. People grab parts from other perspectives and then go with their own, often vague, and contradictory, a notion about what critical thinking is. It is important to note that the word "thinking" may be used to refer to a wide variety of cognitive processes, and that there is, in fact, or more than way to think. We are capable of analytical, creative, strategic, etc., thinking (Sousa, 2011).

Thinking analytically entails breaking down whatever it is we are looking at into its constituent parts, be it a phrase, a circumstance, or a scientific fact. The following step is to disassemble the whole and see how each part fits in. To better comprehend what the term "critical thinking means" for instance, we are now dissecting its component parts. When we are thinking creatively, we are not as concerned with how various components relate to one another or how the entire works.

Instead, we work to unfetter our thinking from constraints like norms and traditions. Instead, we rely on creative thinking and innovative approaches. Let us say you are in the kitchen, but you are missing a crucial component. If you put your mind to it, you will find anything in your fridge or pantry that can stand in for the missing component. However, to do this, we must abandon the desired end of the recipe and instead think of a different course of action. In planning process, we begin with the big picture in mind and work backwards, breaking down overarching objectives into more manageable sub goals that are structured to help us reach our ultimate goals.

Being critical does not mean we are rude or sceptical about other people. Instead, it is the practice of critically assessing information before accepting it as true, whether it is information we have received from others or information we have generated ourselves. Although the term may be used in a variety of ways, we shall use it to refer to the process of evaluating evidence and one's own reasoning before reaching a conclusion. Meaning, when we think critically, we take on the role of watchful protectors of our own thought processes. The most significant characteristic of critical thinkers is that they do not blindly believe the information presented to them, analytical minds always look for credibility in the information's origins. If they are not provided, or if they are weak or untrustworthy, they will seek it out independently.

At some point in our lives, we will all come to a fork in the road, and the decision we make at that juncture will decide the course of the rest of our journeys. When making choices, some people let their feelings to guide them. It is true that feelings are powerful, and that cannot be denied. The events and experiences that have left the deepest emotional impact on us are the ones we are most likely to recall in detail. A lot of people take their instincts as truth and let them guide them in making important decisions. Therefore, it is natural to believe that our feelings may guide us to the truth. In fact, feelings often provide light on hidden occurrences. For instance, the capacity for empathy allows us to feel what other people feel or at least understand how they feel (Stein, 1989). But the trouble is that feelings are not always accurate guides. Emotions can only guide you toward what seems good or incorrect, but they cannot prove that our gut feeling is correct. Feeling good about ourselves might lead us to engage in self-serving behaviours like stealing or lying

Logical reasoning is the primary tool for cultivating critical thinking, and it points the way to the most advantageous choice. Our internal emotional compass may not always be reliable, and we may never know if we made the right decision until it is too late. Furthermore, choosing decisions based on feelings rather than facts will not help us build trust in our own decisions when facing ambiguity. Instead of becoming victims of random events, we may take control of our lives by developing our capacity for rational thought. This ability, by itself, can determine whether one lives a happy or miserable existence. The capacity to defend one's beliefs without fear or a sense of inadequacy, as well as the ability to avoid being manipulated or deceived, are just two of the many tangible benefits of mastering critical thinking.

Practical reasoning skills are crucial. We cannot get by without the use of our logic. We can make better decisions with the assistance of logic. As a bonus, we will find that cultivating the habit of sound thinking makes you a more educated parent, partner, voter, and contributor to society at large. In contrast to widely held belief, rational argument has a core humanity that unites rather than divides individuals. This book will guide you through a systematic procedure in which every step is crucial to your development as a rational thinker.

2. Creativity

Creativity, defined, as the generation of a new concept or a different approach to an existing idea, is the driving force behind innovation, defined as the commercialization of creative ideas into marketable goods or services. Institutionalizing innovation requires careful attention to three interrelated factors: planning, organisational culture, and organisational structure.

Innovation, the turning of creative ideas into goods or processes that meet client demands, begins with the creative process, which is the development of a fresh concept or a new method of addressing an existing idea. Institutionalizing innovation requires careful attention to three interrelated factors: planning, organisational culture, and organisational structure.

An original thought might come from doing business. The ability to create that is, to build something out of nothing, to endow with a new shape, to produce by inventive skill—is a hallmark of creativity. Creating something from nothing is what we mean when we say "creativity." Devotion and enthusiasm are essential ingredients for original thought. Creativity in a product may be defined as originality and suitability.

Importance

Creativity is crucial for businesses to have a competitive edge. Creativity is the foundation of all innovative ideas.

- Entrepreneurs use innovation as a specialised tool to take advantage of shifts in the marketplace to create new products and services. Creating something from nothing is what we mean when we say "creativity."
- Devotion and enthusiasm are essential ingredients for original thought.
- Originality and suitability are necessary conditions for a creative product.

Creativity is the emergence of something new that serves a practical purpose. According to Novel Hypothesis Methodology, Creativity should yield substantial and original results. The creative process is best understood in terms of its methodology, which may be summed up as divergent thinking and the active pursuit of connections between unrelated ideas. Creativity is the willingness to share one's emotions and thoughts with others and to care about the world around them.

Creativity is not limited to any one person; it can be taught as well as innately present; it encourages risk-taking and original thought; it requires a healthy dose of ego investment; and it can be used to a broad variety of situations. Curiosity, inventiveness, adaptability, decision-making, communication, identity, inspiration, teamwork, and action are all necessary ingredients for creative success.

The elements that make up one's imaginative capacities

- The ability to provide several responses quickly and easily to an issue; in other words, fluency.
- Adaptability: the capacity to offer a wide range of responses to a given challenge.
- Creativity: the ability to think of something new that nevertheless fits the situation.
- Problem sensitivity, also known as the capacity, to detect the problem or notice the inexplicable or the unsatisfactory. Sensitivity to problems, or the awareness of the existence of an issue, is the fourth characteristic.
- Reasoning backwards from an effect to its source is an example of the fifth skill, which is the ability to find the underlying cause of phenomena by tracing its origins.
- Capacity to expand upon a subject is what we mean when we talk about your "elaborateness" in the sixth position.
- Ability to look beyond the obvious to the underlying cause of an issue (problem restructuring, number).

3. Collaboration

Collaborating is an established method of getting things done in which several people coordinate their efforts toward a common goal. Collaboration is the process of working together toward a specific and shared corporate goal. It can be either synchronous, where participants communicate in real time, as in an online meeting or asynchronous, where participants can choose when they share information with one another; examples include collaborating or storing documents in a shared workspace and annotating them later.

Collaboration is effective teamwork. This talent entails working together, respecting everyone's interests and viewpoints, and contributing to the result. Collaboration helps make teaching learning interesting. It expands cultural, social, and environmental limits and helps kids grasp social and environmental problems. Therefore, at the conceptual level, we do things like:

- Realization - We join a functional unit with a common goal.
- Passion - We push toward agreement to solve problems and create new things
- Individuals are capable of self-synchronization, in which they choose when it is appropriate for certain events to take place.
- Collaboration - We put out an effort and anticipate others doing the same. With the help of a mediator, the parties to a dispute can work together to reach a compromise.

- Sharing is based on the principle of reciprocity; we give in the hopes of receiving.

In addition to trust and information exchange, successful collaboration requires commitment and responsibility from corporate entities. The opening and closure of team workspaces, as well as the allocation of accountability for documenting the unanticipated outcomes of teamwork, should be governed by a set of rules.

Benefits of Working Together

- A rise in originality and insight.
- Enhancements to communication.
- Resource management and problem solving.
- Strong cooperation.
- Improved performance.

The necessity of working together is best illustrated by the success of a project like Wikipedia, where anybody may contribute a definition of any topic, so assisting the community. It is impossible to do anything worthwhile and substantial without working together. Nowadays, group work is the norm rather than the exception, making collaboration an absolute need in the classroom.

Members of Effective Teams:

- Encourage participation: We should not be fussy about contributions; just accept them and move on. Our natural inclination is to find fault with other people's suggestions when they provide an opinion. Those who cooperate effectively avoid this trap and instead ask clarifying questions and engage in in-depth discourse to build upon the work of others.
- Help others shine: Helping people around and building stronger reputations. They give priority to the success of the group and the contributions of others rather than to their own ego.
- Constructively manage conflicts: Manage conflict effectively contrary to our hopes; productive teamwork does involve the occasional conflict. Skilled collaborators recognise the potential in the friction that conflict creates and harness it to create something new or improved.

4. Communication

Skills in public speaking, including the ability to articulate one's ideas concisely, teach others, and inspire them to action, have traditionally been highly prized in business and society at large. However, these abilities have evolved in the 21st century and are now more vital than ever. Lack of reception and comprehension undermines the purpose of communication.

Multiple definitions have been proposed for the term "communication," including "the act of conveying information and understanding from one person to another" and "the process of interacting with others in a way that has significance." Individuals and organisations communicate with one another using standardised symbols to convey information and common language.

Communication is defined as "an action in which one party conveys to another party information regarding the other's wants, interests, opinions, knowledge, or emotional states." To do so necessitates the employment of symbols. Conversation between two people Exchange of thoughts and ideas between people or groups

Communications Traits

- It is both accidental and on purpose.
- It is always changing because of the dynamism involved.
- It is methodical, and it involves both engagement and transaction.
- It is either one-way or two-way.

The term "communication" refers to the practise of exchanging thoughts, feelings, and other forms of data between individuals. A human being's ability to communicate is essential to any meaningful interaction between individuals. It is a social and emotional process that uses tools for controlling and motivating people.

In today's world, students need to be able to critically evaluate, confront, and absorb information transmitted in a variety of forms. Developing effective communicators is more crucial than ever given the influence of the media and the pervasiveness of communication technology in every facet of modern life. Every student in the service sector must have the conversational skills essential for good client relations, making effective communication a crucial skill in the consumer economy.

NEP 2020 and 21st century learning skills

NEP 2020 recommends further changes to curricula and teaching methods. not a physical shift but one that occurs in the teaching methods and curriculum. Advantages include adaptability, a focus on interdisciplinary work, and the elimination of restrictive barriers. To that end, it places a premium on teaching students' practical knowledge and abilities, such as how to cook, clean, and manage money. Historically, educators have prioritised students' ability to do well on tests by putting an emphasis on material proficiency.

However, NEP 2020 focuses on a child's competency development, which in turn helps our kids learn to think critically. Our kids will be able to use what they learn more easily with the new format. Additionally, it is well known that a child's brain develops the most in the initial stage of their lives, throughout the formative years. Since a child's formative years are so crucial to his or her future success, the NEP 2020 has wisely placed a premium on them, prioritising not only

academic achievement but also the child's whole growth and development as a person and a citizen. To sum up, the NEP 2020 will mark a new era in the country's educational system by encouraging the full, individual growth of every child's creative potential by inculcating 21st Century skills.

Conclusion:

Working together is not always easy. If the task is to succeed, it must take precedence above any individual involved. As a result, we are urged to curb our natural inclination to compare ourselves favourably to others and instead seek individual fulfilment in the success of the group. But when teams work together effectively, they may accomplish remarkable feats.

The four Cs are essential for student success in any academic endeavour. Students learn to question and investigate assertions by using critical thinking skills. Creativity helps pupils develop their own style of thinking. In a group setting, kids learn that they can do more and make a greater impact than they could on their own. Learning effective methods of communication is a skill that can be taught. Each of the four Cs on its own is useful, but together they allow students to take ownership of the learning process and become independent learners.

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2. Literacy; ‘No more restricted to classroom’ –The 21st Century Literacy skills to be mastered by the young generation

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1. Introduction:

Abstract

Literacy skills are referred as IMT skills. IMT skills concentrates on various components related to the digital ecosystem. It focus on the methodology wherein the knowledge is gained through reading and using media and technology, which enables an individual to work efficiently with this knowledge at all levels. These skills emphasizes on how an individual can differentiate between facts, with respect to publishing outlets, and the technology behind them. There has always been a concern on determining reliable sources and genuine information to separate it from the false information that is flooded on the Internet. It's undoubtable that social media and technology have become a significant part of our life, in this situation, educationalists can leverage the availability of technology and create such a kind of environment which could meet the emerging informative requirements of this generation. Literacy shall no more be restricted to classroom, rather the opportunities offered by technology shall be used to educate the students. The top three 21st-century literacy skills are; Information literacy, Media literacy and Technology literacy.

Keywords: IMT, Literacy Skills, 21st Century Skills

The current digital transition and the new expectations are challenging the young generation. The techniques of learning, acquiring knowledge, understanding and putting things into practice are changing.

The tremendous upheaval changes of information and communication technologies have a great impact on educational world. Thus, learning in the 21st century has so much different than previous years [1]. The global requirement of an employable youth has put the learner as well as felicitator in a challenging position. In the 21st century, technologies support teaching, learning and assessment of learning in a variety of ways which were not believable several years ago.

IMT skills plays a very important role in making a youth ready to fit in today's global economy. It is a methodology where the knowledge is gained through reading and using media and technology, which enables an individual to work efficiently with this knowledge at all levels. IMT skills stresses on how an individual can segregate facts, with respect to broadcasting channels, behind them. On the other hand the educationalists can leverage the availability of technology and create such a kind of teaching learning environment which could meet the emerging requirements of this generation.

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The top three 21st century skills i.e. Information, media and technology literacy shall be used to educate and shape the youth in a way as required in today's world. Both the learner and facilitator shall not restrict oneself between the four walls of a traditional classroom, rather should make the use of these skills to acquire knowledge in real sense.

2. Literature Review:

Our 21st century students need to acquire the skills to appropriately access, evaluate, use, manage and add to the wealth of information and media they now have at their thumbs and fingertips. With today's and tomorrow's digital tools, our next generation students would have unprecedented power to amplify their ability to think, learn, communicate, collaborate and create. Along with all that power comes the need to learn the appropriate skills to handle massive amounts of information, media and technology. And so we return to the 21st century skill rainbow to consider [2]

Information is travelling through new routes today in the 18th and 19th centuries postal correspondence was an important vector of new ideas, as we are discovering with the publication of volumes of correspondence of 18th and 19th century authors. In much the same way today, syndicated information and blogs (weblogs) have become important trend setting avenues, mind openers and must read in the information world [3]

The development of the global knowledge society and the rapid integration of ICT make it imperative to acquire digital skills necessary for employment and participation in society. In addition, together with changes in the job markets, 21st-century skills such as searching and evaluating information, solving problems, exchanging information or developing ideas in a digital context are perceived as essential. Although 21st-century skills and digital skills are both seen as crucial, the combination is not yet sufficiently defined. In this respect, the concept of '21st-century digital skills' is introduced. Such skills are critical for both people and organizations for keeping up with developments and innovating products and processes. [4]

Today as never before, meeting our society's challenges demands educational excellence. Reinvigorating the economy, achieving energy independence with alternative technologies and green jobs, and strengthening our health care system require a skilled populace that is ready for the critical challenges we face. There is widespread consensus, however, that our education systems are failing to adequately prepare all students with the essential 21st century knowledge and skills necessary to succeed in life, career and citizenship. [5]

Employability skills are indispensable in the current era of technological disruption and globalization. Employers complain about the insufficiency of skills among the workers [1]. Approximately 75 million young people in devel-

oping countries are unemployed, and in most countries, youth unemployment rates are 2 to 4 times higher than adults. Further, education providers must support them

Employability skills are indispensable in the current era of technological disruption and globalization. Employers complain about the insufficiency of skills among the workers. Approximately 75 million young people in developing countries are unemployed, and in most countries, youth unemployment rates are 2- 4 times higher than adults. Further, education providers must support them with knowledge and skills either soft or hard skills relevant to the world of work to make them productive and able to be employed by the industry.[6]

3. Method of the Study

The research method used in this study was qualitative study. The rationalization for adopting the qualitative research design was because this study adopted qualitative research approach by various researchers. The objective here was to blend the opinions of those researchers on the topic " Literacy; 'No more restricted to classroom" –The 21st Century Literacy skills to be mastered by the young generation". The combined opinions were used to address the main and specific objectives as well as the research questions of this study.

Specific objectives are also used here to study the problem of the study based on the reviewed literatures.

4. Objective of the Study

The main objective of this study was to determine "The 21st Century Literacy skills to be mastered by the young generation". And this study specifically seeks to:

1. Find out how inculcating correct IMT skills helps to enhance the youth's employability skills
2. Find out how the trends of implementing IMT skills leads to help youth to work in different levels

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

1. How does inculcating correct IMT skills helps to enhance the youth's employability skills?
2. How does the trends of implementing IMT skills leads to help youth to work in different levels?

Review of Related Literature: Preparing Students for the 21st Century Economy

How inculcating correct IMT skills helps to enhance the youth's employability skills

IMT skills are each concerned with a different element in digital comprehension such as:

- **Information literacy:** Referring to understanding the facts, figures, statistics, and data
- **Media literacy:** Referring to understanding the methods and outlets in which information is published
- **Technology literacy:** Referring to understanding the machines that make the Information age possible.

Information literacy is the introductory skill. It helps the youths to recognise and understand the facts, specially all the data which they read online. It explains them how to differentiate between the factual data and fictional data. In the digital era the chances of fake and misinformation also exists, it depends upon an individual to understand between the real and fake.

The second skill i.e. Media literacy is the practice of knowing all publishing methods, resources as well as sources and then distinguishing between the ones that are reliable and the fake. Just like the information skill, media literacy is helpful for finding out the truth in a world.

These are the ways how a youth finds out reliable sources of information. Without it, anything that is made to believe real becomes real. Which means that, they can learn which media resources shall be ignored.

The third literacy skill is the Technology literacy which goes one step further to help the youth learn about the different type of machines and software involved in this information age. As with the growing use of electronic sources and mobile there arises a need of many more people to understand using it. The Technology literacy skill gives youth the basic information they need to understand in what kind of equipment or gadgets they need to use to perform and learn various tasks and why performing or learning the same is important. The knowledge and the understanding of the technology which is in use in current scenario helps them to boost their confidence level as it removes the fear from them about not being aware of current trends. So, the technology literacy reveals the efficient tools that run in today's corporate world. As an outcome of that the youth can become accustomed to the world more effectively and help themselves to be at par with the industry requirements.

The knowledge which cannot be obtained merely by reading books or restricting oneself to the curriculum would be enhanced and developed through sharpening the IMT skills which results in sharpening those skills as required by the corporate world.

How the trends of implementing IMT skills leads to help youth to work in different levels

The Literacy skills are the second category of 21st century skills which is to be mastered by youth today, it is referred as IMT skills which focuses on different components of today's digital world. These skills concentrates on acquiring the knowledge through reading and using media and technology this is how it enables them to work efficiently with these acquired information and technology at all levels of management.

With the complexities of growing businesses it is impossible to find every solution in the books and in the classroom, instead a facilitator as well as the receiver shall be open to find out various solutions of all the possible complexities existing and which may occur globally.

The best and the only way to do it is being very well versed with the literacy skills, these are the only skills which will help to find out the solution to every possible issues existing at various levels of management.

Based on the complexities in businesses, it is necessary for the institutions of education to prepare their students who not only have technical skills but also employability skills. The conventional ways, in are abandoned and moved to technology and digitalization.

A research in 2012 on Annual Literacy Survey shows that children and young people either own or have access to a wealth of technology (see Figure 1). Indeed, they are more likely to say that they have a computer of their own than a desk (77.1% vs 69.1%). This research was titled as “Technology in the lives of young people and how it supports employment Skills” showed the following results.

Figure 1: Technology resources in the lives of young people

Source: Young People’s Views on Literacy Skills and Employment Christina Clark and Susie Formby 2013

In 2012 it was unusual for young people not to engage with technology to read, with only 7.3% of young people saying that they only read using paper-based materials. Overall, more young people now read on a computer (67.1%) than use paper-based materials (such as books, magazines, newspapers; 61.8%). 63.8% of young people say that they read on a mobile phone or smart phone, 70.2% read on a Tablet and 37.9% read on a games console. Not only are children and young people more likely to say that they read on an electronic device rather than on paper, they also do it more often: more young people read daily using technology (38.9%) than paper-based materials

(27.9%), while 33.2% are omnivorous and read both daily. The majority of children and young people use their devices to network socially (81.3%) or to browse websites (85.4%). However, a large proportion of young people also use their devices to read fiction, non-fiction, magazines and news. Additionally, research by the Prince's Trust (201327) shows that a large proportion of young people also use technology to do work-related tasks, such as creating Word documents (55%), creating or updating their CV (55%) and searching for jobs online (53%). Overall, children and young people are technology-savvy, using it not only to communicate and to stay connected but also as part of their wider literacy lives. This savviness, as well as greater global awareness²⁸, ought to be a bonus to employers and should be harnessed accordingly.

It is worth mentioning here that recent research by the Prince's Trust (2013a29) has shown that unemployed young people in particular feel that they are being held back in finding employment because of a lack of digital literacy. 10% of unemployed young people said that they cannot send their CV online, while 17% believe they would be in work today if they had better computer skills. Also, 35% "rarely" or "never" look for jobs online. Overall, 10% of unemployed young people claimed that their computer skills have let them down more than their maths or English when applying for jobs

Conclusion:

If we pledge to a vision of 21st century literacy skills for all youths, it is very important for us to support the educators in learning these skills too so as to ensure positive learning outcomes for youth. These include:

- Aligning the different technologies with class content and methodology.
- Project oriented teaching pedagogy
- Case based methodology
- Refining the traditional way of assessment strategies to a methodology which helps to evaluate learner's performance.
- Participative learning environment
- Aligning Research based method for assessment

The premise of this study was that to understand the needs of 21st Century Literacy skills, it is essential to recommend a detailed conceptual framework that includes 21st-century Literacy skills. This study goes further than the basic abilities required for 21st-century literacy skills. The vision of IMT skills is to develop an individual holistically so that he/she can contribute to the advancement and growth of nation and world at large.

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3. Enhancing the goals of Education with Mindfulness and Psychological wellbeing in 21st century

Dr. Kavita Batra⁵

Abstract

21st century academicians are taking much interest in the mindfulness and its positive impact on psychological well-being in achieving the goals of education in this technological era. Students of 21st century have to face scholastic, finances, cultural distress and social living and these all collectively make the experience of college life challenging. This youth design the economic and social development, challenge values and social norms and shape the base of the country's future. But their Psychological well-being is threatened by the long lasting or extreme negative emotions that hinder the ability of a person to perform his/her routine life functions. These challenges generate waves of positive and negative thoughts simultaneously and cause distress at any specific moment in time. The greatly discussed aspect of consciousness in context of well-being is mindfulness. Many researchers found that college students who practice mindfulness are less emotional reactive and utilize their body as a provision for refining and recognition of cognitive and emotional reactions. The purpose of this study is to find the role of mindfulness in psychological well-being of 21st Century college students. Sample of 400 college students of age range between 17 to 22 years had been selected, out of which 200 male and 200 female students with exclusion criteria that no student has to be taken, who is under medication or having any diagnosed psychological problem. Data was collected by using Mindfulness scale by Brown and Psychological well-being scale by Ryff. Findings revealed that there is significant difference in psychological well-being of male and female students and positive relationship between mindfulness and Psychological Well Being. Positive correlation is also found in mindfulness and different dimensions of psychological well-being.

Keywords: Mindfulness, Psychological well-being

Introduction

College life is the greatest time of students' lives because there is hardly ever a time when students gain so much knowledge, meet so many new people, and practice much novel stuff at one time. But in 21st Century along with these positive aspects they also have to face scholastic, finances, cultural distress and social living and these all collectively make the experience of college life challenging. Therefore, college life has been linked with stress and it could be attributed to the

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added strain of coping up with lack of societal support, varied cultural values, high self-expectations and adjustment issues and physical complaints (Swagler and Ellis, 2003; Constantine, et al, 2004; Constantine & Okazaki, 2004; Kearney, Draper, & Baron, 2005; Mori 2000). Psychological well-being is threatened by these long lasting or extreme negative emotions that hinder the ability of students to achieve the educational goals as well as to perform their routine life functions. So to enhance the goals of education we must check the obstacles and identifies the ways to overcome them. The conception of psychologically effective functioning entails the development of individual's potential, encompasses little control over his/her life, include an intellect of purpose and enjoying relationships positively. Better way to understand the psychological well-being is to know the aspects associated with it. Therefore, it is vital to know various factors that affect psychological well-being of college students. The conception of "psychological well-being" gained more prominence in psychological field in last few years and in present years focus is on intense research on psychological wellbeing (Diener and Diener, 1995). Ryff (1991) stated that parallel features convergence of psychological positive functioning that comprises the fundamental psychological well-being are the basis of quality life. It comprises of what common people label "Happiness", "fulfilment", "life satisfaction" and "peace" and all these attributes are connected with consciousness because materialistic objects themselves does not bring these but it depends upon how we think and experience about the objects so the consciousness in well-being of humans is very important. The greatly discussed aspect of consciousness in context of well-being is mindfulness. Spiritual traditions of east propose that the nurturing of mindfulness during the usual meditation practice leads to a reduction in sufferings and improved well-being (Kabat-Zinn, 2000). It has been considered as upholding the well-being of persons; as it directly foster the experience of well-being by offering richness and indirectly by assisting self-governing physical behaviour which enclose better awareness and recognition of individual desires and principles and an elevated ability to perform stability with the principles & desires (Brown et al., 2007; Brown & Ryan, 2003). Capability to control negative feelings, non-affection and reflection was intervene in the association among mindfulness, psychological wellbeing and psychological distress (Coffey & Hartman, 2010). Latest researches revealed that the enrichment of mindfulness in the course of training make possible different wellbeing outcomes (Kirk warren Brown & Richard M. Ryan, 2003).

Review of Literature

Mindfulness and its positive effects on physiological well-being have gained significant interest amongst academics in the field of positive psychology (e.g., Brown & Ryan, 2003; Holas & Jankowski, 2012; Leary & Tate, 2007; Van Dam et al., 2010), with a prime focus on aspects such as mental health, optimal functioning, positive effect and positive character traits (Keyes, 2002; Seligman et al., 2005). Within the field of positive psychology, various studies have been conducted in the last few years on mindfulness and its positive effects on the overall well-being (e.g., Brown & Ryan, 2003; Grossman, Niemann, Schmidt, &Walach, 2004; Carmody & Baer,

2007; Josefsson, Larsman, Broberg, &Lundh, 2011), attracting the attention of famous positive psychologists who saw it as a way of improving the mental health as well as psychological well-being of individuals.

Earlier studies results found that effective management of daily stress is related significantly to alleviated stages of psychological well-being (Chida & Steptoe, 2008; Collins, Glei, & Goldman, 2008) and more self-confidence in the proficiency to face challenges and also an enhanced capability to realise specific ways to deal with life events (Andrews, 2001). Therefore, various researches have been done in many parts of the globe to find causes that are affecting psychological well-being of students'. A study on graduate students of America showed that doctoral students of different cultures were reported with less stress overall and better emotional well-being. On the other hand, PhD students were having less academic stressors than post graduate degrees (Yang, 2010). Additionally, Studies have revealed that there is significant positive effect of psychological well-being on the academic performance of the students' (Bowman, 2010).

Research found that mindfulness has the capability to stimulate young people's emotional and social functioning (Miners, 2008) and brings improvement in the performance in their academics (Semple, Reid & Miller, 2005; Beauchemin, Hutchins & Patterson, 2008). The promising nature of mindfulness training as an intervention to improve adolescent well-being is favoured by a recent research conducted by Huppert and Johnson (2010), that found significant improvements in adolescent well-being with as little as three hours of mindfulness training over a one-month period (as opposed to 16 hours for adults). More promising was the amount of students (43%) who would have preferred a longer training course. Additional studies supporting the idea of mindfulness practices as a promising intervention for use with adolescents were: (1) Semple, Lee, Rosa, and Miller (2006), who found that mindfulness training in adolescents caused significant reductions in inattention, conduct problems, aggression, and anxiety disorders; and (2) Kristeller et al. (2006), who found a substantial reduction in eating disorders amongst adolescents who participated in a mindfulness-based intervention programme. Similar findings were reported in a study conducted by Proulx (2008), who examined the effect of mindfulness-based treatment programme in a group of collage-aged women diagnosed with bulimia nervosa. Additionally, both of these studies also highlighted significant improvement in affect regulation skills and the adolescents' ability to utilise these when experiencing negative affective states. With the limited literature available on mindfulness and adolescent psychological well-being, the present study aims to further explore the relation of mindfulness to adolescent psychological well-being, as well as add to existing literature on aspects of mindfulness. Negative correlation has also been found between fear of emotion with mindfulness as well as with psychological well-being (Lykins & Baer, 2009). The last three decades have observed a drift change in the value of psychology of mindfulness in academic interest. Modern years researches focused on mindfulness benefits to psychological well-being indicates that it is very much beneficial for mental health (Baer, Smith, Hopkins, Krietemeyer, & Toney, 2006; Brown & Ryan, 2003). Mindfulness and resilience are also associated with

Psychological well-being (Pidgeon, Aileen, 2014)). Psychological well-being is the ability of a person to balance various emotions, thoughts, situations, to solve the problem and react to distress in a better way (Bradshaw, Hoelscher, & Richardson (2007).

This study is taken to make out that how mindfulness of college students is related to the psychological well-being in present information age.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

Major objective of this study is to find out the relation between mindfulness and six dimensions of psychological well-being of students of 21st century.

HYPOTHESES

1. There is no significant difference in mindfulness of male and female students.
2. There is no significant difference in psychological well-being of male and female students.
3. There is a significant positive relationship between mindfulness and psychological well-being.
4. There is a significant positive relationship between mindfulness and six dimensions of psychological well-being.

RESEARCH DESIGN

In the present study sample of 400 college students of age range between 17 years to 22 years selected from different institutions of Haryana. The sample consisted of 400 subjects, out of which 200 male students and 200 female students with an exclusion criterion that no student has to be taken, who is under medication or having any diagnosed psychological problem. Stratified random sampling method was employed to select the unit of sample.

SURVEY INSTRUMENTS

Mindfulness scale by Brown

The trait MAAS is a 15-item scale designed to assess a core characteristic of mindfulness, namely, a receptive state of mind in which attention, informed by a sensitive awareness of what is occurring in the present, simply observes what is taking place.

Psychological well-being scale by Ryff

Ryff's Psychological Well-Being Scales (PWB). This questionnaire, developed by Ryff et al., is divided into six subscales self-acceptance, positive relationship with others, autonomy, environmental mastery, purpose in life, and a sense of personal growth. Seven items were designed to measure each subscale on a six point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 6 (strongly agree).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The present study was meant to study the mindfulness and psychological well-being of college students on the basis of gender. In this study efforts were made to find the correlation between mindfulness and psychological well-being and the correlation between mindfulness and six different dimensions of psychological well-being given by Ryff, self-acceptance and positive relationship with others, environmental mastery, autonomy, purpose in life, and a sense of personal growth were also studied.

Table 1: Mean, S.D and t-value of Mindfulness and Psychological well-being of male and female students

Variables	Gender	N	M	S.D.	Df	't' Value	Level of Significance
Mindfulness	Male	200	52.16	10.13	398	3.92	Significant at .05 level
	Female	200	56.25	11.21			
Psychological Well-Being	Male	200	160.82	20.44	398	4.48	Significant at .05 level
	Female	200	170.24	18.77			

There is significant difference in mindfulness of male and female students. The result is in harmony with the earlier data. Differences on the basis of gender could be described with dissimilar cognitive functioning of males and females (Sturgess, 2012). Previous researches showed that females in general are better in observing the details than males, and in multitasking while male in general have the tendency to focus on one task only at the time and more aware while doing the task (Stoet et. al., 2013).

There is significant difference in psychological well-being of male and female students. Findings are supported by Akter (2015) who reported females to be higher on psychological well-being than male, Some illustrates higher scores for male (Stephens, Dulberg, & Joubert, 1999), whereas others illustrated higher scores for females on various sub-scales like which assesses social functioning (Huppert et.al., 1989; Ryff & Singer, 1998).

Table 2: Correlation between Mindfulness and Psychological Well Being

Variable	'r'
Mindfulness	
Psychological Well Being	0.287

the value of 'r' for mindfulness and Psychological Well Being is 0.287 that is significance at 0.05 level of significance revealed that there is positive relationship between mindfulness and Psychological Well Being as perceived by students. Pioneer research to find the correlation in positive mental health indicators and mindfulness in teenagers but without using mindfulness practices, was done by Tan and Martin in 2012. The research also found positive correlation between mindfulness, resiliency and self-esteem, and the negative correlation with anxiety, stress, psychological inflexibility and depression.

Table 3: Correlation between Mindfulness and dimensions of Psychological Well Being

Variables	Self acceptance	environmental mastery	positive relation with others	Autonomy	Personal Growth	life Purpose
	'r'					
Mindfulness	0.284	0.262	0.264	0.198	0.112	0.150

Positive correlation is also found in mindfulness and different dimensions of psychological well-being. The findings of this study are in accordance with the studies which are showing negative correlation among mindfulness and psychological distress which involves anxiety and depression (Giluk, 2009; Coffey & Hartman, 2008; Baer et al., 2006) and by mediating the non-attachment and emotion regulation (Coffey & Hartman, 2008). Mindfulness and autonomy may increase social, emotional and psychological well-being (Ryan, & Deci, 2006). The collaborative influences of the practices develop the people potential for self-regulation (Shapiro et al., 2008) and offer the chance for transferal of attention from anxious and depressive rumination to the present moment (Teasdale et al., 2003). By practicing skills of present moment awareness, people gain insight about the emotions and thought patterns and to select the valuable decisive responses as an alternative to reacting to unconscious procedures, habitual and automatic (Teasdale et al., 2003). Mindfulness practice may help people in decreasing their emotional reactivity and utilize their

body as a provision for refining and recognition of cognitive and emotional reactions. It increases psychological well-being through promoting the cognitive processes like control of attention (comprising improving the capacity of self-regulation, concentration, maintenance, start, internal and external shift in attention), improving awareness of mindful, working memory and cognitive execution and reducing rumination (Chambers et al., 2008).

Conclusion

India is at the top in the list of world's largest youth population, having 34.33% stake of youth in total population. This youth design the economic and social development, challenge values and social norms and shape the base of the country's future. Youth and adolescents of today have higher expectations for themselves as well as for their society. They are also expected to learn 21st century educational goals and skills, which creates unnecessary stress. students of the 21st century mature earlier than the previous generations, both socially and physically and adolescence is a tough period of time for a person. Physical changes, academic and social pressure, personal doubts, temptation and school violence cause many youngsters to feel confused, down and nervous (King et al. 2005; Weisz et al., 2006). Some healthy practices are required to keep them calm and able to enhance educational goals. Mindfulness practices make them able to be adept in facing challenges of life. Further research is required to explain and explore the gender differences on the effect of the mindfulness practices to lessen the stress and improve the coping strategies. Upcoming researches should emphasis on gender differences in the temporal order of modification, mechanisms of change as well as classroom dynamics that may possibly influence the outcomes.

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4. 21st Century Skills and Researchers: A Conceptual Model for Doctoral Program

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Abstract

Research is the cornerstone of the development of any nation. A country can move forward on the path of development only when information and the knowledge-based environment is created for its next-generation and adequate resources and facilities for research are provided at the level of higher education. Today's researchers are going to contribute to the development of the nation to a great extent. Hence their preparation has to be designed with at most thoughtfully and creatively.

Keeping in view the important role doctoral students play in current research, the substantial role they will play in future research and education, it is highly necessary for doctoral programs to take a closer look at the effectiveness of training practices for producing prepared and successful graduates. We can assume that the knowledge and skills they acquire and the experiences they receive in graduate school are preparing them for the academic job requirement of conducting quality research. At the same time they can opt for academic positions like teaching, research associate or they may pursue public or private-sector jobs, engage in consulting along with academia, or change career paths at some point by choosing to become entrepreneur or product/project managers.

Therefore, it is essential to have a better understanding of the experiences doctoral students have in graduate school and how they perceive these experiences contribute to their career preparedness.

The review of available perception studies bring forth the gap in the perceived preparedness of doctoral students for their future careers and the perceived contribution of experiences they gain during doctoral programs (Mitchell, 2007; Alicea, 2013; Wilkins, Hazzam & Lean, 2021; Smith, Williams, Yasin, and Pitchford, 2014). The results of our very small survey of the perceptions of the doctoral students about their preparedness for future career paths and need for re-envisioning the doctoral program framework are incongruent with available literature .

The challenging nature of the 21st century career scenario requires doctoral students to not only be specialised in a single discipline and independent researcher, but also open-minded, critically reflective thinker, creative problem solver and a collaborator.

Hence the 21st century doctoral training needs to be updated in order to place greater emphasis on development of key skill sets such as interdisciplinary, critical thinking, and collaboration among the future researchers. This paper makes an attempt to present a conceptual model of doctoral program for this challenging and complex global context.

Keywords: Doctoral students, 21st Century skills, Conceptual model, Teacher Education

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“As for the future, your task is not to foresee it, but to enable it.”
- Antoine de Saint-Exupery

1. INTRODUCTION

Research is the cornerstone of the development of any nation. A country can move forward on the path of development only when information and the knowledge-based environment is created for its next-generation and adequate resources and facilities for research are provided at the level of higher education. Today's researchers are going to contribute to the development of the nation to a great extent. Hence their preparation has to be designed with at most thoughtfully and creatively.

Keeping in view the important role doctoral students play in current research, the substantial role they will play in future research and education, it is highly necessary for doctoral programs to take a closer look at the effectiveness of training practices for producing prepared and successful graduates. We can assume that the knowledge and skills they acquire and the experiences they receive in graduate school are preparing them for the academic job requirement of conducting quality research. At the same time they can opt for academic positions like teaching, research associate or they may pursue public or private-sector jobs, engage in consulting along with academia, or change career paths at some point by choosing to become entrepreneur or product/ project managers (Mitchell, 2007).

Therefore, it is essential to have a better understanding of the experiences doctoral students have in graduate school and how they perceive these experiences contribute to their career preparedness. This paper focuses on studying these perceptions and suggests a conceptual model for doctoral programs. Pyhalto et al. (2012) studies results suggest that more attention should be focused on generic work processes in developing the pedagogical practices of doctoral education because doctoral studying is at the core of academic practices. There is a need to obtain a deeper understanding of the nature of the Ph. D. process and the problems students face as well as how these problems relate to their well-being during the Ph. D. process. Doctoral education is an essential place where novice doctoral trainees learn to become proficient in producing, transforming, and distributing disciplinary knowledge for society's application (Nerad, 2012).

2. A BASELINE LITERATURE REVIEW

A wide variety of career opportunities depend upon one's scholarly research record (Mitchell, 2007; Alicea, 2013). Hence, training doctoral students in a meaningful and conducive environment offering them the experiences to be highly productive researchers should be an important aim of any doctoral program (Fuhrmann et al., 2011). Similarly, today's doctoral graduates will train tomorrow's under-graduate, and doctoral students. Besides, they will contribute to the shaping of the direction of future theories, practice, and research. However, in comparison to other degree programs in colleges of higher education the effectiveness of the doctoral programs remains under-investigated (Mitchell, 2007; Alicea, 2013; UGC, 2021). According to Austin (2009) the theory of cognitive apprenticeship could inform those who teach and work with doctoral students in ways that enable them to provide students with more systematic

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preparation, more focused guidance and scaffolding, more explicit feedback, and enhanced preparation for participating in a collaborative way in communities of scholars.

The Partnership for 21st Century Skills (www.21stcenturyskills.com) has developed a framework for 21st century learning, which describes the skills that students need to thrive in today's global economy (Stehle & Peters-Burton, 2019). To adapt to the changing world, students, teachers & doctoral scholars must become 21st century learners and be equipped with 21st century learning skills. The student and the teacher must be in a 21st century school. The challenging nature of the 21st century career scenario requires doctoral students to not only be specialized in a single discipline and independent researcher, but also open-minded, critically reflective thinker, creative problem solver and a collaborator. Hence the 21st century doctoral training needs to be updated in order to place greater emphasis on development of key skill sets such as interdisciplinary, critical thinking, and collaboration among the future researchers.

This paper makes an attempt to present a conceptual model of doctoral program for this challenging and complex global context. Doctoral training needs to be updated in order to place greater emphasis on key skills such as interdisciplinarity, critical thinking, and collaboration. These multifaceted challenges of the 21st century require that PhD holders not only be specialized and independent, but also open-minded and critically reflective. It is thus important that PhD students be able to look beyond the confines of their disciplines and situate their research in a wider context (Rashid, 2019).

Keeping in view the complex and challenging employment landscape available for the doctoral students, it is highly desirable to have a better understanding of the experiences doctoral students have in graduate school and how these experiences contribute to their career preparedness is needed (Mello, Fleisher & Woehr, 2015). For this the research should focus on studying the perceptions of these students.

The review of available perception studies brings forth the gap in the perceived preparedness of doctoral students for their future careers and the perceived contribution of experiences they gain during doctoral programs (Mitchell, 2007; Wilkins, Hazzam & Lean, 2021; Smith, Williams, Yasin, and Pitchford, 2014). This paper is a small step in that direction.

Hence the aim of this paper is:

3. To study the perceptions of doctoral students about their preparedness for 21st century career paths;
4. To propose a conceptual model for the doctoral program for fulfilling doctoral students' expectations.

3. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Social constructivism propagated by Vygotsky (1978) is the theoretical base of this study. The social interaction may involve sharing, comparing and debating among learners and mentors. Role of teacher in social constructivism is also defined as motivator, guide and resource person and not as a sole source of knowledge (Abaniel, 2021). As rightly said any doctoral program has to be creating a community of learners. Such interactions will facilitate the learning from shared understanding and experiences. They will also help the learners to share and get inputs from the more knowledgeable others (e.g., the Faculty and senior colleagues). It will help the students to become acclimatized to their new learning environment.

Social construction of knowledge which will follow from the social interactions of the students and faculty will lead to create the dialogue both between students and students and between students and faculty (Darling-Hammond et al., 2020). It will serve to develop the significant discourses that will make the doctoral program successful.

This paper has two sections:

Section 1 presents the results of the survey about the doctoral students' perceptions about their preparedness for the 21st century career paths and

Section 2 presents a conceptual model of a doctoral program.

4. METHODOLOGY

- **Method:** It was a two phase study having the following phases:

- a. Exploratory phase
- b. Model design phase

- **Section one: Exploratory phase**

This phase aimed at conducting a qualitative survey about the perceptions of the doctoral students about their preparedness for 21st century career paths.

It aimed at answering the following research questions:

RQ.1. What skills do the doctoral students expect to be developed in them for the challenging employment landscapes of the 21st century?

RQ.2. What experiences from the doctoral program according to the doctoral students are aligned with their expectations with regard to skill development?

RQ.3. What are the doctoral students' suggestions for re-engineering the doctoral program?

This section reports on the findings of a study that sought to determine the perceptions of doctoral students from three university setups. An online survey invitation was sent to nearly 30 doctoral students registered in the doctoral programs in the field of education, Science education in 2019-22.

The survey sought to find out doctoral students' perceptions about 1. Their expectations about skills to be developed among the doctoral students for the 21st century career paths, 2. The alignment of their expectations and the experiences they receive in the doctoral programs and 3. Their suggestions for re-engineering the doctoral program.

Participants were asked 3 open ended questions related to these areas because these are the issues that have been identified in the literature to be important factors to be taken into account for designing the doctoral programs. The survey was piloted by two Ph.D. alumni. They were sent the survey and were asked for feedback regarding syntax, clarity, content, and tested the survey logic for consistency and accuracy. Any issues found during the pilot were resolved before the survey was distributed.

Participants

As mentioned above, in order to address the research questions, 30 available doctoral students were sent the invitation to participate in the online survey. Of these 30 students, 16 returned the survey within the stipulated period (15 days).

The return rate was 53.3% with years in the program ranging from first-year students to students who had been in their programs for over 3 years. The participants belonged to three set ups namely (private university-8), (deemed university- 4) and (state university- 4).

8 out of 16 were from education field, 4 from Science education and 4 from interdisciplinary field (Environmental education & Maths education)

Data analysis

The data was arranged question wise, and analysed according to qualitative research guidelines (Creswell & Poth, 2017). Reductive analysis (the identifying, coding and categorizing of data into meaningful units) was used to identify themes and patterns in the data.

5. FINDINGS & DISCUSSION

a. Doctoral Students' Expectations, Experiences and Suggestions with respect to Doctoral Programs

This section of the study explores the expectations from the Ph.D. program from the perspective of doctoral students; the activities which they consider valuable towards their professional preparation, comparing them to activities they typically experience as part of doctoral training; and their suggestions for the re-engineering of the doctoral program for their career. The analysis aims to deepen the understanding of the professional development needs of doctoral students, and to identify how they are being met and where there are gaps within the current training.

+ Generally speaking, an individual's understanding of professional preparedness may develop based on a number of factors, such as past experiences,

b. Knowledge acquisition, and on the basis of certain assumptions, expectations, and personal values.

The doctoral students' expectations about the usefulness of the doctoral program are multifaceted. They include gaining a broad knowledge base, multiplicity of skills, varied experiences for professional preparation and personal growth. They have aligned their experiences with these broad tiers and also given their suggestions across these tiers. Hence we have presented the findings in comparison with these tiers.

Table 1. Expectations, Experiences and Suggestions of Doctoral Students

Domain	Expectations	Aligned Experiences	Suggestions
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<p>Broad Knowledge Base</p>	<p>strong interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary knowledge base (N-13)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Opportunity to explore new knowledge fields (N-12) -Opportunities to stay updated in one’s knowledge field (N-12) - Developing strong foundation of content knowledge, pedagogy and technology literacy (N- 2) - Creating collaborative learning environment for course transaction (N 13) - Creating inquiry based learning platform in the course.(N12) - Using critical pedagogies for developing social orientedness among the doctoral students.(2) -Participation in seminars, conferences and research meets should be a mandatory part of the program.(4) - Every course work should be having research component.(N4) -Students should be assessed formatively 	<p>In this section the doctoral students have presented their experiences with respect to aligned expectations on one hand and have expressed strong disappointment on the other.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o. Positive experiences -Interactions with supervisor (N-10) -Good library facility (N-16) -Participations in guest lectures, research meets, seminars (N-16) -Opportunity to present papers in these events.(N-12) o. Disappointment - Use of rigid apprenticeship model of research work (N-8) - Suggesting time irreverent topics for research (N-7) -Lack of innovative approaches for 	<p>Suggestions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Giving across discipline fellowships i.e. teaching experience at masters level in different disciplines (N-3) - The doctoral students should actually be given a choice whether they opt for Teaching as well as Research or only doing Research apprenticeship. (N4) - Providing opportunity to participate in student-exchange programs in premier institutions in India and abroad. (N-6) - Creating platforms for peer mentoring for the socialisation of the doctoral students.(N-9) -Diversity of faculty interests and collaboration could be more desirable (N-6) -Allow the research scholars to transfer their projects to new universities provided their research work is better suited as per the requirements of the
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	<p>based on important learning thresholds (N-5)</p> <p>-Conducting workshops for using digital technologies for qualitative and quantitative data analysis (N-13)</p>	<p>curriculum transaction (N-11)</p> <p>- not aligning to the challenges of the future as well as the needs of the present times in terms of course content, pedagogy and research areas (N-8)</p> <p>- Not introducing latest research based concepts (N-7)</p> <p>-Lack of exciting and intellectually stimulating activities (N-7)</p> <p>-Loneliness and stressful feelings due to uncertainty of future (N-11)</p> <p>- Apprehension about usefulness of chosen research work for society (N-6)</p> <p>-Lack of flexibility and rigidity in rules and regulations.(N-5)</p> <p>-Feeling of dropping out from the course due to the emotional ups and downs (N-8)</p>	<p>project.(N-2)</p> <p>- Co-guides should be a mandatory aspect and not an option(N-4)</p> <p>- Course assignments should be more research based.(N-8)</p> <p>- dynamic selection of research topics with outside collaborations,(N-5)</p> <p>-structured progress report and feedback every 3 months. (N-8)</p> <p>-- Concepts and metrics to measure the Project progress and Success should be understood by doctoral students (N-3)</p> <p>- the scholars should be encouraged to pick sustainability topics that have an impact not only demographically, but also should be accepted as a solution worldwide. (N-3)</p> <p>- Developing modular programs on research methods and conducting them in a workshop mode (N-6)</p> <p>- Involving the scholars in field</p>
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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Feeling of unpreparedness for conducting research even after pre-Ph.D. course (N-8) 	<p>work. This field engagement will help the scholars to select research area.(N-4)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training in qualitative data analysis softwares like NVIVO , ATLAS.ti, Dedoose , Quirkos etc. (N-2) - Giving opportunity to collaboratively work with some researcher who has worked or pursuing research at present, in other countries on the similar topic.(N-2) -Active involvement of the research scholars in centre activities.(N-3) - Orientation to survival techniques- like stress management, time management.(N-6) - PhD program should make doctoral learners for
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			having the skills and competencies for pursuing future research works and for becoming a research supervisor.(N-3)
Skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Developing latest industry required ICT skills(N-11) - Developing application skills for Use of Modern Technology to use smartly various data analytics tools (N-7) - Developing 21st century skills : such as critical thinking, Problem-solving, communication, collaboration, creativity and innovation. They should become a mandatory aspect of all doctoral programmes.(N-3) - Developing writing and publication skills for developing scholarly voice of the researchers.(N-9) - Developing critical thinking skills , foundational for doctoral 	All the participants unanimously expressed that no such aligned experience exist in their doctoral program. (N-16)	<p>Giving opportunity to participate in various institutional and social research projects (N-9)</p> <p>Use of Training in computer applications. Internet and relevant software's should be the part of pre-PhD program.(N-9)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development of presentation skills by providing exposure to various visualisation techniques.(N-5) - Introducing Software for Collaboration (maybe by Blog creation), survey taking methodologies and softwares(N-3) - Paper writing software like LaTeX, Scrivener, EndNote, etc. can be introduced.(N-2)

	and post-doctoral research.(N-8)		
Professional Preparation and Personal Growth	<p>Developing dynamic professional skills for the jobs that are not even into existence today. (N-4)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Exposure to -current job opportunities (N-13) -Involving in various job related tasks like interviewing, analysis, reporting etc.(N-7) -Equipping with the experiences for being employable for non-academic jobs like corporate or NGO sector.(N-9) - Preparing for multi-domain researches with varied skills sets to be industry ready(N-8) -Team management and project management skills(N-5) - Orientation to self-management skills(N-8) 	<p>According to all the participants ,no any such aligned experience is provided to them during their doctoral training.(N-16)</p>	<p>Awareness about various opportunities by discussing them with students.(N-11)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Opportunities to create networks outside of academia can be facilitated by the institute.(N-10) - A placement department can be created in the research institution.(N-6) - Opportunities to participate in national and international collaborative projects.(N-8) - Fostering alumni network for providing mentoring to the doctoral students.(N-11)

6. Discussion

The table above has presented a detailed depiction of the expectations, perceived experiences and suggestions of the doctoral students about their doctoral programs. In knowledge tier, their

expectations are with regard to developing multi-disciplinary and interdisciplinary knowledge foundation, using inquiry based, collaborative, ICT enhanced pedagogical strategies for course transaction and formative assessments of learners based on major learning thresholds. In skill tier their expectations include developing 21st century skills, transferable skills that can transcend across various knowledge areas. In professional preparation tier the participants expect to create platforms for network and collaborations, making professional development as a mandatory component of the doctoral program and scaffold their entry in the job market (St. Clair et al., 2017). With regard to their perceptions about aligned experiences related to their expectations they have pointed few positive experiences (like participation in academic events, interaction with supervisors and good library facility) as well as mentioned their disappointment about rigidity, time-irrelevance and lack of innovations in courses, research and intellectually non-stimulating environment (McDowell et al., 2015). Their suggestions for re-engineering the doctoral programs express their concern for their uncertain future and their preparation for the same (McAlpine et al., 2020). The gap observed in the doctoral students' perceptions about their preparedness for the future career paths and the aligned experiences they receive during their course, shows congruence with the findings from the literature (Mitchell, 2007; Wilkins, Hazzam & Lean, 2021; Smith, Williams, Yasin, and Pitchford, 2014). The small size of available sample and their affiliation to only education field being the limitation of the study, we do not claim to generalise the results. We only wished to hear the voices from the field. Nevertheless, the results of our small study are eye opening. They have helped us to conceptualise our model of the doctoral program which is presented in next section.

Section- 2: Model design phase

At this stage, we conducted in-depth review of some existing frameworks of Ph.D. programs across different universities of India and abroad. We compared them with the aim of identifying common ideas on learning outcomes of courses that might help us to formulate our own design.

This program design will have the following phases:

1. Formulate the key program outcomes,
2. Determine key features of the program,
3. Design the model,
4. Decide performance indicators, study design and assessment plan,
5. Program evaluation, disseminate the findings and adapt program.

Being a work in progress paper, at present we will present information with regard to only first three phases. The information about remaining phases will be the part of our future publications.

1. Formulate the key outcomes

The proposed conceptual model of the doctoral program will aim at attaining the following outcomes:

- To develop insight among the doctoral students in to the interrelated and interdependent nature of global knowledge systems and their impact on socio-economic, political and cultural spears of the world.
- To enable the doctoral students to acquire broad and deep expertise, across chosen fields.
- To enable students to become qualified researchers with a comprehensive interdisciplinary knowledge base- This includes the ability to engage with, plan, and conduct interdisciplinary research, this includes conducting independent and exemplary research, presenting their work in public settings, and publishing their work in a peer-reviewed platform.
- To develop a critical and reflective orientation toward several social and cultural differences intersecting with each other leading to creation of a complex web of influences. This orientation will help the students to do ethical and responsible research.
- To develop among the doctoral students leadership skills for effective community engagement- This will be achieved by involving them in disseminating their knowledge to others, by teaching courses or conducting workshops, and through outreach and service activities.
- To prepare the doctoral students for multiple academic and non-academic career paths by developing in them transferable skills and positive attitude towards 21st century job roles.

2. Determine the key features of the program:

- Following are the key Features of the Program:
- Putting interdisciplinary at the centre of the training
- Focus on developing transferable interdisciplinary skills among the doctoral students
- Promoting learner agency in all the activities
- Formative assessment based on the sequentially arranged learning thresholds
- Creating structures for promoting collaboration among supervisors, peers, key practissioners and the doctoral students
- Involving the students in community oriented field engagement.

3. The model

Fig: Conceptual Model of the Doctoral Program

As shown in the figure, our model is based on three main domains: 1. Knowledge 2. Interdisciplinary skills and 3. Attitude

A. **The knowledge domain of the model:** It has the following components:

- a. Perspective components-
 - Interdisciplinary Foundation Core: It will consist of core and elective courses based on their chosen interdisciplinary fields.
- b. Tool component
 - Research Core: It will consist of research methodology courses.
- c. Practicum components
 - Teaching Core: It will consist of curriculum design, instructional practices, assessment planning and teaching experience.
 - Field Engagement Core: It will expect the doctoral student to participate in field based activities like- undertaking project, developing experiment, modules, learning resources etc.

-Dissertation: It will consist of proposing; conducting and reporting a research based on an issue of interdisciplinary nature and publically disseminate its results.

B. Interdisciplinary skills Domain

According to American Association of Colleges for Teacher Education (2008) rapid advances in scientific knowledge and changing employment landscape call for today's scientists to be not only technically advanced in their disciplines, but also readily adaptable and responsive to evolving and emerging career opportunities. Hence, the Twenty-first century scientists must possess skills that not only enable them to reach beyond the traditional areas but reach across disciplines and into communities to identify issues and develop solutions that increase sustainability. To prepare this new kind of leader, graduate training must embrace innovative approaches that inculcate critical professional skills that transcend disciplines and prepare students for a diverse range of career choices (Wendler et al., 2012).

This domain suggests skill sets to be developed among the doctoral students for this purpose. Here we suggest four sets of skills namely a. Foundational skills (These are skills required for the scientists irrespective of any field) b. Technical / Scientific skills (associated with specific interdisciplinary knowledge fields), c. professional skills and d. self-management skills.

a. Foundational skills:

- i. Creativity: The ability to generate ideas; move from design to implementation creating solutions and ability to propose new approaches to existing problems.
- ii. Communication: Ability to communicate the research results both in writing (in articles, reports or thesis) and orally (in conference presentations or defines of articles or thesis)
- iii. Collaboration: The ability to function effectively in a team (preferably multidisciplinary and multicultural), and creating a collaborative and inclusive environment.
- iv. Critical Thinking: It includes elements of the scientific method, such as raising question, discovering truth by using scientific method.
- v. Information Literacy: It includes the ability to search and relate information, recognize reliable sources, compare information critically.
- vi. Professional conduct and ethics: They include the following consideration of autonomy and safety of study participants, informed consent-

- Seeking approval from ethics committees

- Responsibilities toward stakeholders and scientific community (publication, authorship, plagiarism)

b) Technical/Scientific skills:

i) Broad conceptual knowledge of a scientific discipline: It includes the ability to engage in productive discussion and collaboration with colleagues across a discipline and the ability to develop a solid theoretical framework for tackling a problem or situation in an interdisciplinary field's environment.

ii) In-depth knowledge of interdisciplinary context: This includes

- Philosophy of the knowledge field

- Knowledge of other subjects

iii) Design the research in an interdisciplinary field of knowledge: It includes the ability to design and conduct research in chosen field of knowledge using the most appropriate methods, and using relevant statistical analysis methods for given situation.

c. Professional skills

i) Leadership Skills: They include-

- Developing own ideas

- Ability to take risks

- Accepting responsibility

ii) Organisational and managerial skills

iii) Project Management: This include the abilities to-

- Plan and design research

- organise required infrastructure and logistics

- ensure the Quality

iv) Teaching: Most of the doctoral students work in the academic field as teachers. Hence this skill includes abilities to:

- effective transfer of knowledge

- curriculum design

- assessment for learning.

d) Networking skills: They include the ability of personal communication, relationship management and professionalism, as a means of building connections with others to help career development.

i) Self-management skills: They include the following abilities-

- Career planning
- Developing Personal qualities: enthusiasm, self-confidence, and reflection
- Work–life balance, time management, stress management

C. The attitude domain of the model:

According to the Cyclopedic Education Dictionary (Houle, 1998) attitude refers to the “disposition to behave favorably or unfavorably toward some object, person, event or idea” and the Greenwood Dictionary of Education (Collins & O'Brien, 2003) defines attribute that which directs “a person’s aspirations and ambitions.” Attitude is a main driving force in any activity and especially an important factor in research. Doctoral program requires systematic and step by step procedure for its successful completion and needs area specific knowledge and skills to carry out research effectively. This requires sustained efforts and of course positive attitude towards the activities of the doctoral program. No doubt, the conducive environment created by the availability of several structures (pedagogical, technological, facilitation and support) in-built in the model design is expected to develop the positive attitude among the doctoral students towards program activities (Vekkaila et al., 2018).

Specifically, the program is expected to develop the following attributes of attitude among the doctoral students:

- a). Self-directed career attitude attributes
 - Initiative taking
 - Focus on the goals
 - Commitment for the completion of the task
- b). Psychological mind-set career attitude attributes
 - Flexibility
 - Receptivity towards innovative ideas and suggested changes
- c). Value driven career attitude attributes
 - Tolerance towards diversity existing in the team
 - Embracing inclusion.

The following structures should be created for the successful execution of the program:

- i) Pedagogical structure: Experiential learning, inquiry learning and problem solving approaches to the course transaction.
- ii) Technology structure: LMS, Blended mode of students' engagement and collaboration, discussion forums, website and promotional tools.
- iii) Facilitation structure: Participation in interdisciplinary research meets, national and international conferences, Interdisciplinary collaboration and networking, mentoring by qualified supervisors and co-supervisors., alumni network, students initiated academic events.
- iv) Support services structure: Scholarship and Contingency Grant, Medical Facilities, Psychological Counselling facility, Hostel Facilities, Library Facilities, Wi-Fi, etc.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The perspectives of the doctoral students captured in this study are important to inform the need for re-engineering of doctoral programs in order to facilitate job transitions, provide accountability to students, and for program retention (Ganapati & Ritchie, 2021). A shift in the employment landscape for doctoral students beyond academia has created new challenges for their job transitions (Pyhalto et al., 2012).

In order to embark on a stable and intentional career path, it is necessary for the doctoral students to be aware of the various career options during their doctoral program and be provided the opportunities and support to take active steps in the direction of their desired career path, such as building a professional network, providing professional mentors inside as well as outside academia, and gaining experience through field engagement and internships along only with building research and teaching skills (Golde & Dore, 2001). The gaps and suggested avenues for improvement identified through this study require a concerted effort from key stakeholders such as, developers of doctoral programs, research funding agencies, university career cells and the active involvement of the doctoral students themselves for aligning the required professional development in doctoral programs with reference to the employment landscape (Davis, 2016). This avenue certainly requires deep investigation for the coming future.

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5. 21st Century Life Skill

Dr. Shalu Tiwari⁸

Abstract

The talents you require to get the most out of life are referred to as "life skills." The ability to manage and live a better quality of life is typically referred to as having life skills. They support us in realizing our goals and reaching our full potential. Life skills do not have a set order. Depending on your circumstances in life, your culture, your beliefs, your age, your region, etc., some talents may be applicable to you. By developing new skills, we broaden our comprehension of the environment in which we live, give ourselves the resources we need to lead more fruitful and fulfilling lives and discover ways to deal with the challenges that life will inevitably present. According to educators, school reformers, college professors, employers, and others, the phrase "21st-century talents" refers to a broad range of information, abilities, work habits, and character qualities that are crucial for success today, notably in postsecondary programs and modern vocations and workplaces. In general, students can use 21st-century talents throughout their lives in all academic subject areas, educational, career, and civic situations. The term "21st-century skills" does reflect a general—if rather flexible and shifting—consensus, even though the exact talents considered to be "21st-century skills" may be defined, classed, and assessed differently from person to person, place to place, or school to school. Students must acquire a set of competencies known as 21st-century talents in order to Students must acquire a set of talents called "21st-century skills" if they are to succeed in the information era. The presentation will throw light on how to combine life skills with 21st-century abilities, which are crucial for adolescents to lead successful lives. Life skills are a necessary component of the modern day that must be learned in order to survive the world's fierce competition.

Keywords: Life Skills, 21st century skills,

Life Skill-

These are "the abilities for adaptive and positive behavior that enable individuals to deal effectively with the demands and challenges of everyday life". Life Skills can be taught or learned. They enable us deal with the daily challenges of life:

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“Life Skills are abilities for adaptive and positive behaviour that enable individuals to deal effectively with the demands and challenges of everyday life”. - WHO

Categories of Life Skills

- a. Skills necessary to have a good relationship with yourself: The ability to cope with emotions, Self-esteem, Assertiveness, Self-awareness and stress
- b. Skills necessary to have a good relationship with others: Good social manners, Friendship formation, Peer resistance skills, Effective communication, Negotiation
- c. Skills necessary for making good decisions: Critical thinking, Creative thinking, Decision making Problem & solving

Benefits of Life Skills

They improve our ability to stay focused and pay more attention, can help us become more self-aware, and support the growth of a positive self-image. They enable us to develop self-control and self-regulation, as well as the ability to take care of our bodies, recognize and express our emotions, and empathise with others. They also teach us how to communicate effectively, as well as how to make wise decisions and plan for the future. They also teach us how to take criticism and praise in stride, as well as how to bounce back from failure. They aid in the shaping of sensible activity.

Possessing the capacity and desire to learn is perhaps the most significant life skill. By acquiring new skills, we deepen our comprehension of the world around us, prepare ourselves with the resources we require to lead more productive, satisfying lives, and discover strategies to deal with the obstacles that life, inevitably, presents to us. Life skills are frequently acquired indirectly via experience and practice rather than being explicitly taught.

Defining 21st-century skills

Before we understand the logic behind efforts being made to inculcate 21st Century Skills into the curriculum across the globe, let us understand what 21st Century Skills are. The Glossary of Education Reform defines 21st Century Skills as “A broad set of knowledge, skills, work habits, and character traits that are believed—by educators, school reformers, college professors, employers, and others—to be critically important to success in today’s world, particularly in collegiate programs and contemporary careers and workplaces. Generally speaking, 21st-century skills can be applied in all academic subject areas, and in all educational, career, and civic settings throughout a student’s life”. CBSE says 21st Century skills are those skills that contribute to the holistic development of students, resulting in the contribution to the progress and development of society/ nation and the world.

The term "21st century skills" refers to a broad range of knowledge, skills, work ethic, and character traits that are thought to be crucial for success in today's world, particularly in college

and university programmes and modern careers and workplaces, by educators, school reformers, college professors, employers, and others. Generally, students can use 21st century talents throughout their lives in all academic fields of study, as well as in educational, professional, and social settings. CBSE says 21st Century skills are those skills that contribute to the holistic development of students, resulting in the contribution to the progress and development of society/nation and the world. The idea of 21st-century skills in the age of information and digital literacy can be largely divided into three categories. Information, media, and technology literacy is a part of literary skills, whereas critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, and communication are learning skills. Flexibility, leadership, initiative, productivity, and social skills are examples of life skills.

NEP 2020 does throw light on the need for integrating 21st Century Skills into the education system.

The following list provides a brief illustrative overview of the knowledge, skills, work habits, and character traits commonly associated with 21st century skills:

- Critical thinking, problem solving, reasoning, analysis, interpretation, synthesizing information
- Research skills and practices, interrogative questioning
- Creativity, artistry, curiosity, imagination, innovation, personal expression
- Perseverance, self-direction, planning, self-discipline, adaptability, initiative
- Oral and written communication, public speaking and presenting, listening
- Leadership, teamwork, collaboration, cooperation, facility in using virtual workspaces
- Information and communication technology (ICT) literacy, media and internet literacy, data interpretation and analysis, computer programming
- Civic, ethical, and social-justice literacy
- Economic and financial literacy, entrepreneurialism
- Global awareness, multicultural literacy, humanitarianism
- Scientific literacy and reasoning, the scientific method
- Environmental and conservation literacy, ecosystems understanding
- Health and wellness literacy, including nutrition, diet, exercise, and public health and safety.

Linking 21st-century skills with life skills

The idea of 21st century skills is generally driven by the conviction that teaching students the most important, practical, in-demand, and universally applicable skills in today's schools should be prioritized, and by the related conviction that many schools may not sufficiently prioritize such skills or effectively teach them to students. The central aspect is that children who will enter adulthood in the 21st century need to learn skills that are distinct from those acquired by students

in the 20th century, and that the skills they learn should consider the particular demands that will be made of them in a complex, competitive, knowledge-based, information-age, technology-driven economy and society.

What skills will learners require in the twenty-first century

The 21st century has brought about a significant change in the educational system because of its new dimensions, openings, limitless chances, and wild developments. Survival skills alone won't help children thrive in this world; they also need particular skills, which must be taught and fostered from an early age. Children will be prepared to survive in the world with a traditional education, but the 21st century calls for particular skills that will enable them to master all aspect of life, from life skills to digital skills, to meet the difficulties of the unclear probability the future holds. Schools are key in teaching children these essential 21st-century abilities

Creativity and Innovation- Creating new ways of thinking by using information and insight to solve new challenges and develop new goods and services.

Critical Thinking and Problem Solving- Critical thinking and problem solving are terms used to describe the capacity to use information, facts, and data to solve problems. This doesn't imply that you must respond right away, but it does You must be able to think quickly, analyse issues, and come up with answers. However, companies place a high value on the capacity to produce a well-considered answer in a reasonable amount of time.

Communication- Collaboration 21st Century Skill, is about working together to reach a goal and putting talent, expertise, and smarts to work. Just like with communication, technology has made collaboration easier. Collaboration is important because whether students realize it or not, they'll probably work with other people for the rest of their lives. Practicing collaboration and teamwork helps students understand how to address a problem, pitch solutions, and decide the best course of action. It's also helpful for them to learn that other people don't always have the same ideas that they do.

Communication- Communication is the practice of conveying ideas quickly and clearly. It is expressing thoughts clearly, crisply articulating opinions, communicating coherent instructions, motivating others through powerful speech.

Effective Use of Technology- Creating the capacity to identify and use technology efficiently, effectively and ethically as a tool to access, organize, evaluate and share information.

Career and Life Skill - Life skills are nothing but capabilities that enable us to adapt positively to the changes in the environment. Learning how to be self-directed, active learners and professionals

who can adapt to change, organize projects, take ownership of their work, lead others, and create achievements

Cultural Awareness- Cultural competence is the capacity to interact, collaborate, and forge deep connections with people from different cultural backgrounds. The values, traditions, and conduct of individuals belonging to various groups might be considered cultural background. Increasing one's self-awareness, acquiring social abilities and diversity-aware actions, and becoming able to speak up for others are all parts of the lifetime process of becoming culturally competent.

“Exemplary science education can offer a rich context for developing many 21st-century skills, such as critical thinking, problem-solving, and information literacy. These skills not only contribute to a well-prepared workforce of the future but also give all individuals life skills that help them succeed.” (NSTA, 2011)

Life skills are an important aspect of the 21st century

In this century, life skills are an important factor. Every person's life depends on it in some way. It is crucial for the future as well as the twenty-first century. Many people never manage to follow their dreams. The biggest cause of failure is the way they presented their knowledge. Every achievement has two components: the talent and the way it is presented. It is possible only when you become an expert in your interest and also good life skills to present it. Personal and social ethics are both developed as a result of life skills. Ethics are important for both the betterment of society and the development of your individuality. Life skills will help children develop their moral in the future toward others. Therefore, life skills are crucial for every child.

Preparing Students for Success in the 21st Century

It has always been our goal for students to be creative thinkers and problem solvers with the abilities to contribute to society and succeed in the professional. However, how these skills are used in the classroom and how technology is used will significantly alter the manner that instruction is delivered. In fact, thanks to technology, the modern classroom transcends geographical boundaries and extends across the world. In addition, we need to plan instruction with an understanding of the “digital natives” (Prensky, 2001) who have grown up in the Digital Age and who expect learning to be interactive, engaging and up-to-date. Instruction that meets the needs of today's students will incorporate

Activities and opportunities for learning -

- Project- and problem-based learning;
- use of appropriate technological tools to achieve learning objectives
- Inter connections, a focus on inquiry and student-led investigations,
- cooperative learning environments inside and outside of the classroom,
- A lot of visual representation and the use of illustrations to improve understanding,

- frequent, formative assessments that include self-evaluation are all part of effective teaching.

The role of the teacher will change from knowledge transmitter to that of learning facilitator, collaborator, guide, coach and mentor. Students in the learning process will have greater responsibility for their own learning in this environment as they search for, discover, create and share their knowledge with others for solving problems. The teacher's position is crucial for influencing the globalizing world and enhancing quality teaching. The purpose for a teacher is to motivate and assist the students in developing competence through digital tools. A 21st-century educator will therefore be a digital educator. Teachers are no longer simply responsible for facilitating students' learning; they are also in charge of preparing them for the workforce by developing their employability skills, as well as their critical thinking, creativity, and digital citizenship. Thus, the teacher's thought is focused on engaging the learner.

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6. Development of Creative Thinking Skills Education Program for Would Be Teachers and its Effective

Dr. Usha Prakash More⁹

Abstract

Education in 21st century is expected to contribute for generation of information, its storage and its dissemination. Everyone must be aware of and must be ready for taking benefits of future opportunities using his knowledge, skills and attitude and also adjusting himself to various situations. . Creativity allows us to view and solve problems more openly and with innovation. Creativity opens the mind. A society that has lost touch with its creative side is an imprisoned society, in that generations of people may be closed minded. It broadens our perspectives and can help us overcome prejudices creativity is important and impart of each person's day to day life. So its need and impart of our curriculum. Its Need of development of creative thinking skills for would be teachers. when he/she developed creative thinking skills then he//she applied creative thinking during an educational transaction Also would be teachers inculcating creative thinking skills once own himself he definitely applied for school students .while teaching learning process. Teacher Knows about how to use creative thinking skills and ' application. Also he know about its essential for student and teachers. so researcher define to develop creative thinking skill Education program for would be teachers and its effectiveness Creative Thinking Education program

A Special program developed by the researcher to impart creative thinking skills amongst the would be teachers.

Total duration of the program was 8 clock hours in which 4 hours was Theoretical orientation of creative thinking skills given through worksheets and printed self-learning material. 4 hours was assigned to practical work. The practical was provided practice to would be teachers for applying skills during teaching and interactions with students in school environments in simulated condition. Practical work was included role play, simulation and games, group discussions, group interaction, brain storming, sharing experiences, self-demonstrations, activity by PMI technique The activities used according to the nature of the skills.

After implementation of creative thinking skills education program researcher studied the positive difference in the mean scores of would be teachers on pertest and post-test about creative thinking skills developed by the researcher. Then analysed data interpretation qualitatively

Keywords: *Would be teacher, Creative thinking skills, Education Program*

Introduction

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Education in 21st century is expected to contribute for generation of information, its storage and its dissemination. Everyone must be aware of and must be ready for taking benefits of future opportunities using his knowledge, skills and attitude and also adjusting himself to various situations. Creativity allows us to view and solve problems more openly and with innovation. Creativity opens the mind. A society that has lost touch with its creative side is an imprisoned society, in that generations of people may be closed minded. It broadens our perspectives and can help us overcome prejudices creativity is important and impart of each person's day to day life. So its need and impart of our curriculum. Its Need of development of creative thinking skills for would be teachers. when he/she developed creative thinking skills then he//she applied creative thinking during an educational transaction Also would be teachers inculcating creative thinking skills once own himself he definitely applied for school students

Creative thinking Skills- are Thinking skills and they are directed towards personal actions or actions towards others. Its empowering individual to interact with the self as well as others and develop healthy lifestyle and responsive and responsible behaviour.

Creative Thinking – Creative thinking is the process of sensing gaps or disturbing, missing elements, forming ideas or hypotheses concerning them, testing these hypotheses and communicate the results possibly modifying and retesting the hypotheses.

Need and Importance of the Present Research

Teachers need to Development of Creative thinking Skills and express effectively information or thought using to their students written verbal or visual medium in teaching learning process . It is also to develop capacity of understanding current problems and prevention effectively.

creative thinking skills education to would be teacher to make them able to accept such responsibility in future. Review of related researches underlined the need for development of creative thinking skills education program. There are no tools and tests available to measure these creative thinking skills. So, it's essential to a special training for student teacher .so researcher prepare a "Development of Creative thinking Skills program' for B, Ed student teachers."

Hence there is a need to prepare such creative thinking skill program for imparting these skills and study it's effectiveness.

The plan of present study is developed keeping in view all these intensions.

Objectives of the study

- 1) To develop a 'Creative Thinking skills Education' Programme for would be teachers.
- 2) To study the effectiveness of the ' Creative thinking Skills Education' Program

Operational definitions of the terms

- 1. Would be teache:** All the students enrolled for B.Ed. course. of S.N.D.T. college of Education Pune.
- 2. Creative Thinking:** Creative thinking is the process of sensing gaps or disturbing, missing elements, forming ideas or hypotheses concerning them, testing these hypotheses and communicate the results possibly modifying and retesting the hypotheses. Creative Thinking will be measured in terms of score obtained on test of Creative Thinking developed by the researcher.
- 3. Creative thinking Skills Education Program:** A Special program prepared by the researcher to impart Creative thinking Skills amongst the would-be teachers.

Total duration of the program was 8 clock hours in which 4 hours was given Theoretical orientation of Creative thinking Skills given through worksheets and printed self-learning material. 4 hours are assigned to practical work. The practical will provide practice to would be teachers for applying skills during teaching and interactions with students in school environments in simulated condition. Practical work will include role play, simulation and games, group discussions, group interaction, brain storming, sharing experiences, self-demonstrations, SWOT analysis and visits to social institutions.

The activities were used according to the nature of the skills.

Effectiveness: - The positive difference in the mean scores of would-be teachers on pretest and post-test about developed by the researcher.

Research Hypotheses

There will be positive and significant difference in pre-test and post-test mean scores of would-be teachers after implementation of Creative thinking Skills 'Education Program.'

Research Method

The experimental method was used.

Experimental Design

Single group pretest test post design was used.

Variables in the research

- 1. Independent Variable:** A Creative thinking Skills education program for the would-be teachers of secondary level developed by the researcher.
- 2. Dependent Variable:** An aggregate score of would-be teachers on the tests of.
- 3. Controlled Variable:** The pretest and post tests on Creative thinking Skills prepared by the researcher was parallel.

Sample:

An Incidental sampling was used. All the students enrolled for B.Ed. course in S.N.D.T. College of Education Pune, was included.

Tools and Techniques used data for analyses

1. 't' Test: Significance of the difference between mean scores of Creative thinking Skills measurement in pretest and post-test was tested by using 't' test.
2. Qualitative analysis: open responses on training program test and feedback questioner were analysed qualitatively.

Implementation of Study

1. Creative thinking Skills Education” program was prepared by collecting information from various sources.
2. Pertest prepared and administered before the implementation of the program.
3. Creative thinking Skills Program :- A Special programme developed by the researcher to impart Creative thinking Skills amongst the would be teachers. Total duration of the program was of 8 clock hours in which 4 hours was assigned to Theoretical work. Theoretical orientation given through worksheets and printed self-learning material. 4 hours was assigned to practical work.
4. Identifying various Activities, like Practical work was include role play, simulation and games, group discussions, group interaction, brain storming, sharing experiences, self-demonstrations, listing, used PMI technique. According to activity the practical was completed in whole class or in small groups partials of Creative thinking Skills included in syllabus was implanted along with routine timetable. Researcher was conduct reaming practical work through extra periods.

After implementation of Creative thinking Skills Education program parallel post-test was administered. Feedback was taken with the help of a questionnaire.

Pertest on Creative thinking Skills was developed and administered to before the implementation of the program in the beginning of the test also was given. After implementation of program

Qualitative analysis:

Qualitative analysis based on open responses of the question in Creative thinking Skills test, selected activities of self-learning material in teaching program and open responses of feedback questionnaire.

Creative thinking Skills pre-test and post-test included seven open ended questions. Responses of the would-be Teachers to these questions were analysed based on frequently

Responses of the training program feedback questionnaire of the would-be Teachers on the various activities included in the training program were analysed qualitatively.

Conclusion of the Research (Limited to the sample in experiment)

1. The post-test means score of Creative thinking Skills Measurement of student teachers is found significantly higher than that of pretest mean score. That means Effective communication skills education program prepared by the researcher based on Creative thinking Skills given by WHO was in developing Creative thinking Skills of Would be Teachers.
2. Open responses of post-test are qualitatively better as compared to responses on pretest regarding fluency, flexibility, and originality. Hence the Creative thinking Skills Education Program implemented by the researcher has proven to be effective for developing Creative thinking Skills.

The researcher proved to be effective for developing, Creative thinking Skills

Scope and limitations of the study

- 1) Creative thinking Skills included in the present study.
- 2) Duration of the Creative thinking Skills education program was of 8 clock hours in which 4 hours assigned to practical work. 4 hours Theoretical orientation was given through worksheets and printed self-learning material.
- 3) Creative thinking Skills education program is short duration.
- 4) This program included 46 B.Ed. students of S.N.D.T. collage of Education (IASE) Pune 38
- 5) Sample included only female students.
- 6) Data collection tools are not standardized prepared by researcher.

There were limitations to broader generalizations of the conclusions due to incidental sample and tools prepared by researcher.

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7. Enhancing Critical Thinking in Student Teachers

Farzana Y. Khambatta¹⁰

Abstract

The current paper examines the effectiveness of a programme developed to enhance critical thinking skills of student teachers. A researcher-developed critical thinking tool was administered to study the level of critical thinking. An intervention programme on critical thinking included the skill of interpretation, analysis, synthesis, argument and evaluation was conducted. The various activities are designed to develop these skills among student teachers. The intervention programme was carried for 16 hours. At the end of the programme, a post test using the same tool was administered to the student teachers.

Results revealed that the programme enhanced critical thinking with respect to the above-mentioned skills.

Keywords: student teachers, critical thinking

1. Introduction

Teacher education needs urgent and comprehensive reform. An important question put forth by the National Curriculum Framework for Teacher Education (2009) is “What value does teacher education add to the prospective teacher’s ability to face challenges of facilitating the development of critical and creative students and subsequently adults?” (NCTE,2009)

The ability to engage with subject content, examine disciplinary knowledge and social realities, relate subject matter with the social milieu of learners and develop critical thinking are essential. Teacher education programs need to broaden the curriculum to include different traditions of knowledge; educate teachers to connect school knowledge with community knowledge and life outside the school. (NCTE, 2009)

One of the most important things a teacher can do in the classroom is to make students aware of the processes involved in their own thinking. Students should be able to examine what they are learning about and, raise questions, accept challenges, find solutions that are not immediately apparent, explain concepts, justify their reasoning, and seek information. (Costa & Kallick, 2009). These skills equip students to make purposeful and organized efforts to make sense of their world.

Educators have been aware of the importance of critical thinking as an outcome of student learning. There is a need for a coherent, cohesive and consistent approach to teach critical thinking skills.

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Teaching students how to think critically is essential in educational settings (Facione, 2007; Şendağ & Odabaşı, 2009).

2. The concept of Critical thinking

The critical thinking movement begins with contributions from Socrates, who developed a method of asking meaningful questions. Socrates questioned the assumptions and beliefs of those in authority and established a methodology that advocates the importance of asking probing questions and seeking evidence to examine rhetoric. (Paul, Elder, & Bartell, 1997).

Dewey (1916) perceived critical thinking as a process that starts with a problem and ends with a solution. Kurfiss (1988) defined critical thinking as an investigation whose purpose is to explore a situation, phenomenon, question, or problem to arrive at a hypothesis or conclusion about it that integrates all available information and that can therefore be convincingly justified. Halpern (1997) defines critical thinking as purposeful, reasoned, and goal-directed. Facione (1990) asserts that critical thinking is focused self-judgement that results in interpretation, analysis, evaluation, and inference, as well as an explanation of the evidential, conceptual, methodological, or contextual thoughts upon which such judgement is based.

Most of the understanding of critical thinking comes from the field of philosophy and psychology. Philosophers tend to conceptualize critical thinking in an abstract way and focus on the qualities and characteristics of a critical thinker rather than the capacity for certain behaviours or actions. (Lewis & Smith, 1993; Thayer-Bacon, 2000). In contrast, the psychological perspective focuses on how people think and the mechanisms they use. The psychological perspective emphasizes the importance of skills and their utilization in problem-solving in practice. (Sternberg, 1986).

Despite how scholars define critical thinking, most agree on the characterization of critical thinking skills (Kuhn, 1999). These skills generally include the ability and propensity to analyse complex issues (Ennis, 1985; Facione, 1990); to identify and examine assumptions (Ennis, 1985; Paul, 1992); interpreting (Facione, 1990); seeing both sides of an issue (Willingham, 2007); evaluating (Tindal & Nolet, 1995); making inferences (Paul, 1992; Willingham, 2007) and to develop conclusions based on reliable information. (Facione, 1990; Paul, 1992; Halpern, 1998).

2.1. Critical thinking in education

Educators need to be responsive to an increasingly complex society by developing critical thinkers (Holley, 2009). Grossman and McDonald (2008) state that teachers should be critical thinkers to make contextual decisions on the curriculum and their pedagogical choices. In addition, Slameto (2014) and Pithers and Soden (2000) mention that teachers are expected to assist their learners to think well by questioning, examining, evaluating and challenging assumptions and ideas that fail to explain contextual realities.

A way to promote critical thinking in subject matter courses is to structure them around critical thinking models (Allegretti & Frederick, 1995; Reed & Kromrey, 2001). Educators have been designing instructional programmes that focus on the transfer of critical thinking skills through systematic and well-designed instruction. (Halpern, 1998). Early researchers like Bloom et al. (1956) describe an increasing complexity of kinds of thinking, including knowledge, comprehension, application, analysis, synthesis and evaluation, with evaluation being the most complex integrating all the other levels (Stanny, 2016). Lorin Andersen (2001), a former student of Bloom, published a revised version of Bloom's taxonomy. Anderson's version presents the use of verbs instead of nouns as in Bloom's original format. Paul (1992) constructed a critical thinking model that organizes content and instructional activities conducive to critical thinking in teacher education courses. Arend (2009) emphasis on the fact that critical thinking must be conceptualized as the goal of the education and in this regard, educators should overtly teach critical thinking strategies.

Various researchers have studied the effect of critical thinking skills on student teachers and the findings suggest that emphasis on critical thinking can have a positive effect. To teach critical thinking skills, teachers should choose a strategy that encourages learners to understand and apply such skills. This can be accomplished by asking them to consider multiple perspectives, question those perspectives, observe if they have enough evidence or research to back up their claims while assessing if there is any bias in the information presented. Teachers need to provide opportunities for students to identify the material that they are working with, and be capable of analysing, characterizing, and considering similarities and differences between them. There are several different instructional strategies that can be used with learners to promote critical thinking skills. Some of the strategies can be used simultaneously. For example, case studies, questioning techniques and discussion. When teaching critical thinking skills educators need to expose their learners to situations and experiences where they can exercise the principles of critical thinking.

Critical thinking is part of one's educational journey; therefore, it is only appropriate that educators work with learners to help them develop cognitively.

An understanding of the many ways we can help students to make their thinking more clear, accurate, consistent, relevant and fair is required.

The review indicates that there are various methods and activities which can be used to enhance critical thinking skills. Student teachers are at the crux of their professional journey and will impact future learners. Inculcating critical thinking skills in them would go a long way to ensure that their learners are critical thinkers.

For this paper, critical thinking is operationalized as a skill which is transferable and can be developed. The critical thinking skills consists of the following:

- Interpretation

- Analysis
- Synthesis
- Arguments and
- Evaluation.

3. Objectives of the Study

- To assess the critical thinking skills of student teachers through a researcher developed tool.
- To study the effectiveness of the intervention programme for critical thinking skills.

4. Hypothesis of the study

- There is no significant difference in the pre-test and post test scores of critical thinking skills of student teachers.

5. Research Methodology

5.1 Design of the Study

A one group pre-post-test design was used. A researcher developed tool to measure critical thinking and an intervention programme was conducted.

The experimental design used is indicated symbolically as follows:

O1 X O2

Where O1 = pre-test, X = treatment, O2 = Post-test.

5.2 Sample and Sampling technique of the Study

The sample was selected using non-probability type of sampling technique from which the incidental sampling technique was used. The study consisted of 35 B.Ed. students from an English medium B.Ed. college in Mumbai.

5.3 Tool used and Data collection

The critical thinking tool consisted of various scenarios. The critical thinking skills assessed on the test included the skills of:

- Interpretation
- Analysis
- Synthesis
- Arguments
- Evaluation

Permission was sought from the head of B.Ed. college and consent was taken from student teachers prior to the conduction of the study. The programme consisted of various activities along with , group discussions, powerpoint presentations which assisted in the understanding of the critical thinking skills of interpretation, analysis, synthesis, argument and evaluation. The presentation

included explanations, examples and activities which helped in understanding the skill. Various techniques were used throughout the conduction of the programme in the form of cooperative learning, brainstorming, gallery walk, role playing which helped the student teachers understand the skills in detail. Reflection was carried out at the end of each activity.

6. Data Analysis

A comparison of the percentage pre-test and post-test scores of student teachers is presented in table 1.

Table 1- Percentage of student teachers who scored low, moderate and high on the critical thinking test. (N=35)

Critical thinking test	Low (%)	Moderate (%)	High (%)	Total (%)
Pre-test	3	97	0	100
Post-test	0	74	26	100

Interpretation:

Table 1 indicates the percentage scores for critical thinking test of the student teachers. The pre-test percentage scores indicate that the student teachers had only low (3%) to moderate (97%) level scores. The post-test percentage scores indicate a higher number of students getting moderate (74%) to high (26%) percentage scores.

Conclusion:

There is a difference in the percentage scores of student teachers scoring high to moderate marks post the intervention programme indicating that the intervention programme has helped in developing the critical thinking skills of the student teachers.

Hypothesis testing

For the hypothesis stating there is no significant difference in the pre-test and post test scores of critical thinking skill of student teachers, t-test was used.

Table 2-Difference in the pre-test and post-test scores of the group for critical thinking.

Single group	N	Mean	SD	Obtained t-ratio	Tabulated t- ratio	l.o.s
Pre-test	35	13.43	2.78	7.69	2.75	0.01
Post-test	35	17.97	3.58			

Interpretation:

Table 2 shows the obtained 't' of 7.69 is greater than the tabulated 't' at 2.75. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. There is a significant difference in the pre-test and post test score on critical thinking skills of the student teachers after the implementation of the intervention program.

Conclusion: There is a significant difference in the pre-test and post-test scores of student teachers' critical thinking skills. The post-test mean score is higher than the pre-test score of the group. This implies that the intervention program has helped in increasing the critical thinking skills of student teachers

Based on the results, it can be stated that changes in the critical thinking skills in student teachers was due to the implementation of the critical thinking programme.

7. Discussion and conclusion

The present study used a general approach to enhance critical thinking. Explicit instruction in critical thinking skills assisted the student teachers in enhancing their critical thinking skills viz., the skill of interpretation, analysis, synthesis, argument and evaluation as seen from the results.

There is a general agreement that the ability to interpret, analyse, synthesis, understand arguments and evaluate information are part of critical thinking. (Kuhn, 1999).

Instruction in critical thinking is to be designed to help student teachers be able to have the ability to analyse, interpret, to reason and to reach a conclusion based on sound inferences drawn from assumptions. To have the ability to distinguish fact from judgment, belief from knowledge, and skills in inductive and deductive processes, including an understanding of the formal and informal fallacies of language and thought. (Ennis, 1985; Facione, 1990; Paul, 1992; Willingham, 2007; Tindal & Nolet, 1995; Halpern, 1998 and Willingham, 2007)

The current study examined whether critical thinking skills can be enhanced through an intervention programme. The results of the study revealed that critical thinking scores post intervention were higher compared to the pre-test scores.

8. Suggestions

The findings of the present study indicate that critical thinking skills of student teachers can be enhanced. Educational research related to pedagogy needs a shift in how critical thinking teaching-learning research is undertaken. An emphasis on process-based studies with a strong theoretical orientation and practical insights into the classroom would lead to better understanding of critical thinking.

Teachers need to be prepared to meet the demands of a rapidly changing world. It is important to identify skills which teachers can develop among students. Student teachers are at the beginning of their professional journey. When they have the necessary aid to think critically and apply, they can create a safe environment for their future students to develop thinking skills.

Student teachers should have opportunities to pursue effective, convenient ways to extend and strengthen their knowledge of critical thinking and how to help individuals to develop at the fullest.

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8. Can Problem Based Learning be a magic bullet for developing pedagogical repertoire among pre-service teachers towards 21st-century educational requirements?

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Introduction

After two decades in the 21st century, today, the world education system is evolving as a new wave - Education 4.0 to address the emerging unforeseen challenges due to robust and ubiquitous changes in social, economic, political, technological, and environmental spheres. The present/near future education system needs to prepare the learners for complexity, uncertainty, hyper-connectivity, diversity and many more. With this background, the teacher education system needs to evolve and prepare the pre-service teachers to engage the information/visual rich, non-linear, multitasking, collaborative, interactive technology-based school classrooms in the immensely connected world. Problem based Learning can be one of the learning approach that appear to be very useful and relevant to the future learning situations.

What is PBL?

The Problem Based Learning (PBL) approach uses a problem as the beginning point for acquiring new knowledge. The PBL are ill-defined and located in a real-world context. The role of the students in pbl environment is visualized as a problem solver by taking ownership of the learning process. According to barrow (1996,2002), the PBI environment allows the learners to integrate concepts from various disciplines to solve a particular problem. PBLs are: (1) multiple ways to solve the problem based on the way the different student groups conceptualize the problem; (2) allows the learners to determine what they require to learn; (3) teachers serve as facilitators and tutors, and; (4) problems are authentic and reflect professional practice.

In a nutshell, PBL allows students to work in a group to find a solution to complex problems (Ferreira & Trudel, 2012). The process starts with an unstructured problem which students are expected to solve. After reviewing the problem, students identify the information they already know and the information they need to learn to find a solution. The three necessary components for PBL are a problem in context, teachers as a facilitator, and learners as problem solvers (Carrió, Larramona, Baños, & Pérez, 2011).

The significant learning outcome (LO) of PBL process is learning and applying new information/knowledge, organizing the information to present or further use, building cognitive capacities, and becoming lifelong learners (Woods, 2012). PBL allows the learner to participate actively in the learning process, applying their understanding in a given context, building their cognitive development and making decisions as per the requirement to solve the problem (Yeo, 2008). Specifically, PBL holds students accountable for their learning and the learning of their group (Chagas et al., 2012), allows students to try out more than one correct answer (Karantzas et

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al., 2013), and encourages students to use learned knowledge to arrive at a solution (Mykytyn et al., 2008). Second, PBL can enrich students' learning outcomes, better preparing them for the work environment (Deeter-Schmelz, Kennedy, & Ramsey, 2002). When knowledge is deficient, PBL encourages students to identify the missing information that must be utilized to complete their task (Mykytyn et al., 2008).

Historical accentuate of PBL

Problem-based learning was first developed in medical education in the 1950s to facilitate medical students to solve problems in the clinical setting. In the 1980s, the GPEP (General professional education of the physician and College preparation for Medicine) report on PBL, which the United States accelerated, recommended promoting independent learning, problem-solving, minimizing lecture hours, and evaluating learners on their independent learning ability (Barrows, 1996). Besides this, now it is being implemented in higher education which includes preservice education and K-12 education as well. The adoption of PBL in higher education outside of the medical field and K-12 settings gradually occurred throughout the 1990s. PBL has been applied globally in a variety of professional schools (Boud & Feletti, 1991; Gijsselaers et al., 1995; Wilkerson & Gijsselaers, 1996), such as architecture (Donaldson, 1989; Maitland, 1998), business administration (Merchand, 1995), chemical engineering (Woods, 1996), engineering studies (Cawley, 1989), law schools (Boud & Feletti, 1991; Kurtz et al., 1990; Pletinckx & Segers, 2001), leadership education (Bridges and Hallinger, 1992, 1995, 1996; Cunningham & Cordeiro, 2003), nursing (Barnard et al., 2005; Higgins, 1994), social work (Bolzan & Heycox, 1998), and teacher education (Oberlander & Talbert-Johnson, 2004). Moreover, the study by Moust et al. (2005) indicated that the PBL approaches generally integrated into a broader range of disciplines. That includes biology (Szeberenyi, 2005), biochemistry (Osgood et al., 2005), calculus (Seltzer et al., 1996), chemistry (Barak & Dori, 2005), economics (Garland, 1995), geology (Smith & Hoersch, 1995), psychology (Reynolds, 1997), science courses (Allen et al., 1996), physics, art history, educational psychology, leadership education, criminal justice, nutrition and dietetics, and other domains of post-secondary education (Edens, 2000; Savin-Baden, 2000; SavinBaden & Wilkie, 2004).

Theoretical lenses through PBL

The constructivist framework provides the foundation of the instructional principles of PBL (Savery, 2006). Schmidt (1993) points out that constructivism's philosophical roots are in Dewey's work of fostering independent learners and Brunner's concept of intrinsic motivation as a force that pushes one to know more. The notion of constructivism based on the assumption that actively engagement of the learner in the learning process to make meaning and construct knowledge for learning to occur. This shows a paradigm shift for teachers and students, who are required to be active participants instead of passive recipients of knowledge (Forrester & Chau, 1999).

PBL is grounded by theories of situated learning, which assume that learning is most effective when it is embedded in authentic tasks that are anchored in everyday contexts. In everyday lives, peoples have multiple perspectives, ill-structured problem, solution methods, and criteria for solving the problems. Because learners derived meaning from interactions with the contexts in

which they are learning, knowledge that is anchored in specific contexts is more meaningful, more integrated, better retained, and more transferable. One reason for this phenomenon is the ontology that students use to represent their understanding (Jonassen, 2006). Knowledge constructed for solving problems results in epistemological (task-related procedural knowledge) and phenomenological (the world as we consciously experience it) knowledge types. These are richer, more meaningful, and memorable representations. In addition to supporting more meaning by anchoring learning in authentic problems, problems provide a purpose for learning. Without an objective to learn, which is provided by problems, meaningful learning rarely occurs. When studying course content, students who are unable to articulate a clear purpose or intention for learning seldom learn meaningfully. When knowledge is evaluated based on its similarity to an authority, students' epistemological development is retarded. They fail to understand or accommodate multiple perspectives and make no effort to construct their own culturally relevant understanding.

Introducing the problem in the PBL-based classroom

By considering the content, learner background, and context, the teacher will design a PBL problem that can be ill-structured and more realistic so that learners can associate with the problem efficiently. Once the teacher designs the problem around a theme, the teacher introduces the problem in the classroom either through an overhead/ LCD/LED projector/ interactive whiteboard or by providing a problem sheet to each group of learners. Making cooperative/collaborative learning groups in the classroom is a prerequisite for PBL based classroom. The problem is read individually and collectively and discussed in various aspects within the groups. Each group devise learning tasks that can facilitate them in finding the solution to the problem. Each group can vary in approaching the problem and may suggest/locate different solutions to solve the problem. The group dynamics and roles each member performs will influence the learning outcome.

Structure of Organizing PBL?

The most commonly used structure for PBL learning is KWL (Know-Want-Learn). The KWL is designed for group instruction and can be used with either whole classes or smaller groups. It can be used in all curricular areas and at all grades. Ogle described this (Know-Want-Learn) strategy in 1986 as a framework that connects a student's prior knowledge to actively learning. The Student begins by thinking about (i) what the Student already Knows about the topic, (ii) what the Student Wants to know, and finally, (iii) the Student actively Learns something new about the topic. It can be a teacher-directed activity, or students can do it independently.

Fact	Idea	Learning need/Issue	Action plan
What do we know?	What do we think?	What do we need to know?	What should we do?
Information extracted from the problem scenario	Possible causes/effects/ideas/solution based on the fact identified	Phrase as question that led to the problem solution	Activities to be carried to answer the questions

Identification of term and notion	Consider experience and knowledge	to use own and previous	Determine which question is worth researching and list out those irrelevant	Possible resources to consult the answer the questions
Ambiguous notion				Task division

Source: Adapted from Dean (2001), pg11 as cited in Borhan & Hasin 2013

As the students are a novice and newly exposed to the K-W-L structure, they need to determine the facts, develop possible hypotheses underlying the problem, and identify and comprehend the learning issues with the help of the teachers in the initial days. The changes observed and reflected in the PBL processes, such as both roles of teachers and students, group dynamics and assessment processes, are described below.

Student's Role Transition in the PBL process

In the PBL learning process, the students take ownership of their learning and perform the role of analyzers, inquirers, and problem solvers; they become active knowledge constructors than passive information receivers. The students redefine their roles in the learning process and must reframe their learning habits. Woods (1994, 1996) speculated that uncertainty about their grades was one possibility accounting for students' uneasiness about a new instructional method, resulting in some resistance to change and making the initial Transition from the traditional curriculum to the PBL curriculum more difficult. Although the sense of discomfort and anxiety is common among students during the initial stage of PBL implementation, Schultz-Ross and Kline (1999 as cited in Tawfik & Wayne 2013) found that the students' discomfort and dissatisfaction levels decreased significantly by the end of a PBL course. Their study indicated that some students expressed uneasiness during the initial transition stage of the PBL curriculum. Nonetheless, once the students adjusted to PBL environments and realized the merits of PBL, their perceived comfort levels about the learning issues of testimony, liability, and competence improved significantly, as did their perceptions regarding the subject matter learned in the course. Dabbagh et al. (2000) confirmed Schultz-Ross and Kline's observation.

Teachers' Roles in PBL

Barrows (1992) asserted that the two primary responsibilities of teachers/instructors in PBL are facilitating the students' development of thinking or reasoning skills that promote problem-solving, metacognition, and critical thinking, as well as helping them to become independent and self-directed learners. As Maudsley (1999) stated, the effectiveness of teachers is essential to the success of PBL. Maudsley suggested that PBL allows educators to redefine the nature of learning and, in turn, reposition their roles in teaching from knowledge transmitter to facilitator. This shift requires PBL teachers to recognize their educational roles fully, including conceptual shifts in educational processes. Based on their data, Donaldson and Caplow (1996) described the PBL

teacher's precarious position as a dilemma. Their research on the role expectations of PBL teachers revealed two major dilemmas perceived by PBL instructors/tutors: the conceptualization of facilitator and the tensions that arise as teachers redefine their role in PBL compared to their previous role as traditional teachers. Aguiar (2000 as cited in Hung et al 2008) conducted an exploratory qualitative case study that examined teachers' perceptions and experiences as PBL tutors. Five main themes emerged describing how tutors perceived their roles within PBL: (1) facilitating group work, (2) role modelling, (3) providing feedback, (4) imparting information, and (5) supporting students' professional development. Furthermore, Wilkerson and Hundert (1998) described the challenge of multiple roles experienced by PBL, like information disseminator, evaluator, professional consultant, co-learner, and mediator.

Group Dynamics, small groups, and Collaboration:

The most elegant part of the PBL is that it promotes the space for small-group learning and Collaboration, which also considers the group dynamics among the group scenario (Azer 2001). Small-group work is better for higher-order activities, such as analysis, evaluation, and synthesis. This may reflect increased motivation in small groups. Active preparation, with face-to-face contact, may ensure that a member seeks to understand at a deeper level. Group discussion activates previously acquired understanding, helping identify deficits and facilitating new comprehension. Group dynamics also facilitate developing a thematic-based approach by integrating diverse disciplines. Other benefits of small-group learning include the promotion of an adult style of learning and the development of collaborative learning and other transferable skills (e.g., leadership, teamwork, organizations, giving support, prioritizing, setting tasks, problem-solving, motivating climate, and managing time).

The assessment process in PBL

Changes in educational goals, content and approach to teaching and learning of a course will also require a change in assessment methods since these educational elements are mutually interdependent (Holgaard & Kolmos, 2009). The PBL approach emphasizes knowledge acquired through teamwork, communication skills, self-directed learning, and information sharing. Hence, assessment in PBL should go beyond solely relying on factual recall. As Woods (2003) proposes, assessment in PBL should adopt the fundamental principles of testing the student about the learning outcome and range of assessment methods. Group assessment is essential for the PBL process. In PBL, *Rubrics based assessment is used for the subject knowledge, content organization, vital elements of content, and other mechanics.* Reflection is an opportunity for students to reflect on how they learn and how they could improve as team members to enhance collaboration and efficiency of group work. Furthermore, the opportunity for reflection on the learning process is an essential aspect of PBL (Holen, 2000).

Challenges and Experiences in PBL:

The teacher educator experienced the following challenges while engaging with the PBL environment at the pre-service teacher education programme.

Structural and resource accelerated:

PBL requires significant structural changes in planning, curriculum, and assessment. Curriculum changes must be integrative, bringing various academic areas together; they cannot just be cosmetic inclusion or tokenism kind of an initiative (Villegas & Lucas, 2002). First, this process would involve constructing a problem or selecting a problem scenario, aligning it with teacher education content, and assessing and evaluating them. Second, it requires multiple learning resources, including internet-based resources. When a more complex problem scenario is made as a PBL and employed in large classes, it requires a team of teachers to engage and support the complexity arising from different subject perspectives and the classroom size. PBL, in teacher education classes, emphasizes that the students take on the role of facilitator and design the problem. Teachers require constant professional training in designing and engaging with the PBL problems because sometimes PBL will only work for experienced teachers. It requires everyone to update themselves with the newer ways of learning constantly.

Problem processing and facilitation skills:

One of the most critical problems encountered in using PBL is the development of PBL process skills. These include skills such as thinking skills and information searching skills. It is reflected in the PBL classroom that students are fragile in using thinking skills, lacking in "think out of the box", and not resourceful in searching for information. Here the teacher educator's task is to understand the students in the classroom context, levels, and background variables. Teachers also facilitate the students to decode and contextualize the problem by making the problem more general than specific. It is essential to teach them about mind mapping tools and facilitate them to acquire information literacy skills. The learners must be encouraged to use the library and trained to cite journal articles. Most importantly, stress the importance of primary sources of information.

Coherence and consensus problem in group

During the PBL class, the PBL group assign tasks to individual group members as part of the group task. The teacher educator observed that some pre-service teachers find participation challenging, especially during individually assigned tasks. It is sometimes observed that uneven distribution or sharing of work among group members. Some members have become very responsible, while others have become mere 'co-passengers.' Some group members show an indifferent attitude to the work. As members are of mixed abilities with varied backgrounds (academic and social), maintaining group motivation is challenging. Most of the time, a lack of coherence is observed because each group member develops their outlook regarding the problem. Sometimes individual absenteeism and disagreement in the group create conflict in arriving at a consensus.

Attitudinal issues

Dealing with students' attitudes is another very challenging task. In many cases, the students' negative attitudes hinder their learning process. Some students are very pessimistic about PBL, even though they are good at academics. They observed PBL as complex and felt they were wasting their time. Some students are willing to learn, and they manage to produce creative assignments. To overcome negative attitudes, the teacher educator played many roles-as a friend, a mentor, a facilitator, a motivator and sometimes a strict deadline setter.

Curriculum coverage and time constraint

PBL takes up much time, resulting in fewer topics being covered over a given period compared to the traditional approach. For each assigned problem, the students need a longer time to understand and find a possible solution to the problem. Engaging in PBL-based learning in a specific subject becomes challenging. Hence, adopting PBL approaches to the whole teacher preparation programme, where PBL-learning scenarios are designed to address multiple subject areas through some themes, could be a better alternative. Various teachers can collaborate to support the pre-service teachers to understand the problem holistically and address it by acquiring course-specific knowledge or skills for addressing it.

Discussions

It is evident from the pre-service teacher education classroom experiences that PBL implementation brings the opportunity to meet the demands of 21st-century educational reforms. Introducing the PBL approach at a very early stage of education is essential for the learner to acquire competencies such as analyzing the problem from one's perspective, collaborating with others, and problem-solving. Initially, it will be challenging for both teachers and students. However, they will learn to work together and know each other's strengths over time. PBL allows the nature of collaboration, which promotes the learner-centered process and a way for teachers to think about learner issues and broader systematic issues such as assessment. The idea can penetrate through collaboration among schools and teacher education institutions. Perceiving the PBL through an existing structure (by focusing on their content, context, and learner) gives the authentic learning experience to the teachers.

Excessive students' reliance on teachers for learning becomes a significant challenge for student ownership over learning. The researcher perceives that the culture of learning may be one of the problem points where learners never get an opportunity to think on their own and make a decision for their learning. Thus, it requires the role reversal of teachers and students, which demands the inculcation of a new learning culture among the learner. Thus, it needs to start from the beginning of the primary and secondary levels.

Small-group learning allows multiple perspectives of the content for solving the problem and benefits for locating the curriculum in diverse contexts. As a researcher, it is a strength that people will learn more and more new things by which they can contextualize the problem and comprehend the content in various situations.

Teachers have a significant problem: they view themselves as experts and do not wait to listen to the learner. The teacher does not wait for the learner to solve the problem. Instead tend to help the learner to solve the problem. By being an expert, teachers must enable the students to problem determination, monitor their decisions collectively and individually and inculcate an idea of how it could be solved. In the classroom, teachers formulate the problem for an intended objective, but the problem can take its course and a new destination, newer things beyond; that is the beauty of PBL. It provides the space to learners for the individual trajectory of learning, showing that they

can have a different path. Teachers need to facilitate the learners in those situations, focusing not only on the pre-defined objective of things but also on the processes. Libraries should be used to enable learning and are supposed to provide multiple formats of learning resources.

Conclusion

The above discussion depicts that PBL has the potential to make the learning process livelier and more contextual. However, PBL brings newer challenges related to learning resources and the need for group cohesivity. In the same way, problem determination and design have many benefits, like guiding teachers to meet the new demands of the learning process, such as problem-solving, group collaboration and self-directed learning. It is also reflected in the discussion so far. PBL gives space to the learner for active participation, becoming a skilled learner, analyzing, synthesizing, and drawing out the solution to the problem.

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9. Exploring the Students' Experiences of Using Gamified Homework Strategy in Indian Mathematics Classroom

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Abstract

Mathematics is perceived as a fear among students resulting in drop outs. The fear of it escalated during Covid-19. Online mathematics classrooms became a challenge for teachers to engage students. One of the investigators, being a mathematics teacher herself, conducted online mathematics classes for a semester year using gamification for engaging the students during the pandemic. This research aims to investigate students' performance, and their experiences about gamified homework in mathematics. A mixed method of quantitative and survey were used with t-test to analyze the data. Survey explored the experience of using gamification with gamified online tools such as Math Playground, 99math and Quizizz. The participants of the study consisted of 24 students of age group 12-14 yrs. The results indicated significant improvement in the achievement. The findings of the study reveals that students showed a positive response in using gamification for practicing math problems as homework. Gamified homework enriches the experience, gives practice, improves confidence, interest and performances. It helps in the acquisition of 21st century skills such as critical thinking, creativity, and problem solving.

Keywords: Gamification, Homework, Mathematics, Quizizz

1. Introduction

Social distancing during Covid-19 pandemic resulted in incorporation of technology in every sector including education. It presented serious challenges for teachers, specifically mathematics teachers for engaging the learners in the online classroom and motivating them for doing the homework. The purpose of mathematics homework is to promote learning outside of the classroom Richards-Babb (n.d.). Homework helps in practicing the concept and makes them ready for the following classes. Unfortunately, despite the benefits of homework, many students choose to spend little time or exert little effort or not to do homework at all (Belden, 2007). To mitigate the challenge of students' disinterest towards mathematics homework the present study uses gamified homework strategy.

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2. Literature review

2.1 Gamification

Gamification is the concept of applying the principles and mechanisms of play in non-game activities, especially in education Lestari & Noer (2021). It provides an alternative way to engage and motivate students during the process of learning and to assess individual abilities. It helps students with the type of learning environment that they prefer, as opposed to the traditional classroom, and allows them to develop the skills Thiruchelvam (2018). Gamification in Classroom includes assigning of badges instead of grades, grades conversion into points, crossing levels, problem based learning with the challenge of choosing from more than one solution, tracking progress and collaboration having social value.

2.2 Use of Gamification in Mathematics Classroom

Various studies show the majority of students struggle and fail to find interest in mathematics classroom. On the other hand, practicing the content gives confidence for solving the problems. Ability to recall basic math facts which is Math fluency (Benjamin et al. 2013) requires practice. Gamification provides both a practice for developing skills and an entertainment in mathematics classroom. The entertainment factor in learning motivates and engages students and enriches overall learning experiences. Divjak & Tomic (2011) revealed the use of computer games for teaching creates pupils' positive attitude toward mathematics.

2.3 Challenges during Covid-19

The outbreak of Covid-19 increased the anxiety and stress among teachers and students. Alsamawi & Kurnaz (2021) observed student's engagement and participation as a challenge during Covid-19. Rincon-Flores et al. (2022) found loneliness, increased levels of stress, anxiety, and depression. These negative effects were reflected on the performance of students especially in mathematics which requires application and practice of knowledge and skills (Antonio & Tamban, 2022).

2.4 Gamification in Mathematics during Covid-19

During Covid-19 pandemic, decision makers suggested gamification features of teaching and learning to reduce anxiety and achieve a better learning process (Alsamawi & Kurnaz, 2021). A study conducted by Nieto-Escámez & Roldán-Tapia (2021) reviewed a total of 11 studies that found gamification was innovative, engaging, and an efficient strategy to deliver curricula material; moreover, it was perceived as a fun activity by students.

2.5 Gamification and 21st century skills

Education should prepare today's digital natives with 21st century skills to cater the demand of future workforce and technologies. According to Soeiro & Amirnuddin (2022) gamification can

be a suitable alternative pedagogic tool to learn skills such as critical thinking, creativity, innovation, leadership, or communication.

One of the investigators of the present study, observed incomplete homework of her students in the mathematics classroom. As various studies suggested a positive impact of implementation of gameful experiences in mathematics homework and increased motivation and performance as an effect of gamification (Craig et al. 2020; Elshemy 2017). ; the present study was conducted to understand the effect on achievement and the experiences of students in using gamified homework.

The questions that the research is going to address and the hypothesis are as follows:

RQ 1. What is the effect of using gamification in completing the mathematics' homework on achievement scores?

RQ 2. What are students' experiences of using gamification in completing the mathematics' homework?

H₀ There is no significant difference due to gamified homework between mean scores of pre and post mathematics achievement tests.

3. Methodology

3.1 Study design and Sample

The investigators conducted a mixed method using the Embedded Design approach. A single group pretest posttest quasi experimental design was used and data was analyzed using t-test for paired samples. It was used to measure the difference between before and after mean scores of the same individual (Antonio & Tamban, 2022). Online survey was conducted using google forms. Purposive sampling was used to know the experience of using gamified homework in mathematics classrooms. Earlier the sample included 25 students ranging from 12-14 years of age but as one of the students was unable to attempt the post test, the t-test analysis used 24 as a sample.

3.2 Data collection Tool

At the end of the semester, a survey was administered to know the students' experience of using gamified homework. It was collected using google form on a five-point Likert scale consisting of 15 Likert-type statements, and a free-response question. Free-response question was structured so that students could provide detailed comments on their use of gamified homework (Richards-Babb, n.d.). e-quiz using Quizizz.com was designed to collect data on pre and post achievement tests. 25 questions were framed based on the topics covered.

3.3 Gamification Tools used in the study

The intervention provided students with gamified homework using three online gamification tools which are discussed in the section below.

1. Math Playground.com (<https://www.mathplayground.com/>) is an online free mathematics gamification tool. It offers numerous practice opportunities for developing the understanding of basic concepts in mathematics.
2. 99math.com (<https://99math.com/>) engages students and provides practice in solving problems of higher difficulty level thus challenging each student based on their level of understanding.
3. Quizizz.com (<https://quizizz.com>) is an educational app that enables students to participate in fun multiplayer class activities (Zhao, 2019). It is used as a formative assessment tool and for data collection on pre and post achievement tests.

3.4 Process

The present study was conducted during the pandemic for a whole semester in a mathematics classroom using Quizizz, Math Playground and 99math as gamification tools. The topics covered in the present study included Order of operations, Perimeter and Area, Equations, Fractions, Integers and Exponents. All the classes were conducted on the Zoom platform. In the beginning an introductory session was conducted in which students were given hands-on practice on using gamification tools. Daily one hour online class was arranged. Prior to the implementation of the program e-quiz was administered as a pretest to test the content knowledge. The same test was again administered at the end of the semester as a post test. After every class a game link of 99math or Math Playground was shared on the school's Whatsapp group for practicing the concept as homework. At the end of each topic a game was conducted in a live mode using Quizizz.com to know the understanding of the learners. And a survey was conducted at the end of the semester.

Figure 1: Screenshot from Quizizz.com on L.H.S. and 99math.com on R.H.S.

Figure 2: Screenshot from 99math.com - Student' Individual report on L.H.S. and Leaderboard on R.H.S.

Figure 3: Screenshot from Math Playground.com

4. Results and Findings

4.1 Findings of t-test analysis

Before proceeding to the t-test, a normality test was performed by the Shapiro-Wilk test. It shows a statistic of 0.96 and a p-value of 0.33 before intervention, and a statistic of 0.96 and a p-value of 0.38 after intervention. The results indicate normal distribution, $p > 0.05$. No violation of the homogeneity of variances was detected in a Levene's test, the f-ratio value is 3.93 and the p-value is 0.053.

Table 1: Results of t-test as reflected by the Pretest and Posttest

Tests	M	SD	t-value	P-value
Pre-test	10.48	1.88	27.82	.00001
Post-test	17.48	2.8		

The results demonstrate that there was a significant difference in the scores of pretest ($M=10.48$, $SD=1.88$) and posttest ($M=17.48$, $SD=2.8$); $t(24)=27.82$; $p\text{-value}<0.05$. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus the gamified homework shows a significant improvement in the performance of the learners.

4.2 Online Survey exploring the Effects of Gamified Homework

This research sheds light on the effectiveness of games related to student understanding, confidence, interest, performance, problem solving skills, speed and accuracy. All 24 students completed the online survey.

Among the student respondents (Fig. 4), most (60%) students believe that games help to improve understanding of the concepts in mathematics followed by 28% agree, while a few (8%) disagreed and a single participant was neutral.

In the view of the improvement of confidence in mathematics by playing gamified homework 40% of students strongly agreed that it builds their confidence. 44% of students agreed while 12% of students remained neutral and 4% disagreed (Fig. 5).

In correspondence with the Interest of students for mathematics in online classrooms (Fig. 6), students' experience of gamified homework plays an important role. 60% of students revealed that games help to build interest in mathematics, following 24% were in agreement while 8% of students were neutral and a single participant disagreed and another strongly disagreed.

Regarding the improvement in performance using gamified homework in mathematics tests (Fig.7) 44% strongly agreed while the same proportion of participants (44%) agreed. In contrast 8% disagreed while a single participant was neutral.

Most of the students (84%) enjoyed the gamified homework, only a few (8%) moderately enjoyed it while 4% slightly enjoyed and the same proportion of students did not like gamified homework (Fig. 8).

36% of students strongly agreed that games help in practicing the content during exams followed by 32% were neutral while 28% agreed and a single participant strongly disagreed (Fig. 9).

Most of the students (68%) strongly agreed that gamified homework is more helpful as compared to traditional homework using pen and paper. 16% of students agreed. In contrast a few (12%) disagreed and a single student (4%) was neutral (Fig. 10).

Practice helps to improve the problem solving skills in mathematics. 64% of students strongly agreed while 20% of students agreed. 12% students remained neutral while a single student strongly disagreed (Fig 11).

Speed and accuracy both play a major role in problem solving. Most of the students (88%) strongly agreed that playing games improved their speed of solving problems. A very few (4%) of students agreed and the same proportion of students remained neutral. On the contrary 4% of students strongly disagreed about the improvement in speed while solving mathematical problems (Fig.12). In consideration to accuracy in solving mathematics problems most of the students (76%) strongly agreed that playing games improved their accuracy. 16% agreed while very few (8%) students remained neutral (Fig.13).

A vast majority (92%) of students strongly agreed that games made the learning fun and engaging. While a few (4%) students were neutral and the same proportion did not find games in learning as fun and engaging (Fig. 14).

Most of the students (84%) strongly agreed that games motivated them to do the homework while 4% of students agreed, in same proportion (4%) students were neutral, 4% of students disagreed and 4% of students strongly disagreed they did not found games as motivation for doing homework (Fig. 15).

32% of students disagreed that leaderboards gave stress. 28% of students strongly disagreed and 36% of students were neutral about the stress that comes while playing the game and looking at the position of peers on the leaderboard. On the contrary very few (4%) students strongly agreed that leaderboards gave stress while playing (Fig. 16).

Nearly 76% of students strongly agreed that the leaderboard motivated them for doing homework. Very few (4%) disagreed; they do not think the leaderboard motivated them. While 8% agreed and 12% of students were neutral (Fig. 17).

Most of the students (88%) strongly agreed that games should be included in other subjects. A very few (4%) of students agreed also the same proportion of students remained neutral. On the contrary (4%) of students disagreed about the inclusion of games in other subjects (Fig. 18).

Below are some of the opinions of using gamified homework shared by the students (Fig. 19).

- मला असे वाटते की असे गेम खेळतच अभ्यास करावा, म्हणजे जास्त स्ट्रेस येणार नाही. अभ्यास सोपा जाईल
- I like this games because in maths first step is to understand the problems and in this games I understood the problem. Thank you
- Learning by playing games gives good practice.
- Earlier I use to avoid maths homework, but using games I love to solve problems
- I like to chase my friends, hence I practice for speed and accuracy
- First two live games were quite stressful for me as my focus was on my friends position on leaderboard, but afterwards I shifted focus on self improvement. and slowly by practicing my speed and accuracy is increasing.
- Though online games helps me to increase my interest, build my confidence but practice on paper is essential for me.

Figure 19: Screenshot of few more students' experiences

5. Discussion

The study shows gamified homework motivates students to complete their homework; it imparts practice which brings out confidence. Immediate feedback helps the student to focus on the mistakes, learn and try as many times. They do not have to wait until the next day to know what they did right or wrong. The real time feedback helps students and teachers to know the difficulties. Thus students move forward at their own pace without feeling shame. It helps in the acquisition of 21st century skills (Herrewijn, 2018).

The below section discusses effects of gamified homework-

i) Learning outcomes using gamified homework

Replacing paper homework with gamified homework, significantly improved ($p < .005$) performance of students, it is also supported by Kacmaz & Dubé (2022). Increase in performance may be attributed to- students enjoying the online experience, appreciating the opportunity to receive instant feedback, and multiple attempts (Penner et al., n.d.).

ii) Effectiveness of using online tools

The study shows the utility of Quizizz.com as an online achievement test tool and 99math.com as a formative assessment tool. The study shows 99math and Math Playground can be considered as effective mathematics gamification tools for giving the practice; both the tools increased students' fluency, speed and problem solving skills. According to Benjamin et al. (2013) selecting the correct answer in a certain amount of time increases fluency. On the contrary, Bonham (2001) found that due to multiple submissions students do not carefully think about the problem instead they adapt a trial-and-error strategy. Penner et al. (n.d.) stated retries may actually reduce students' effort to solve the assigned homework. The study found 99math and Math Playground mitigates the challenge of retrieval. The present study suggests that teachers should avoid the gamified quizzes which have only a certain number of questions and which gives students a chance for attempting the same quiz as many times by making only random arrangements of questions each time they attempt.

iii) Students' experiences of using the gamified homework

Free response questions revealed, gamified homework gives practice to the students. Gamification motivated them to do homework and made the learning fun and engaging, it increased their speed and accuracy and also improved their problem solving skills. Earlier they avoided gamified homework but later enjoyed it. They liked to chase their friends hence they practiced more for speed and accuracy and also for self improvement. Maximum students shared their experiences as improvement in understanding of the concepts in mathematics, increase in confidence, interest and performance. It is also reflected in their post test achievement scores. Increase fluency in mathematics, develops more confidence and less dependence (Benjamin et al., 2013). Though gamified homework has many advantages, one of the students believes that practice on paper is essential for building the concepts. Also, most of the students found gamified homework is more helpful than doing it on paper. On the contrary it was also shared that practicing on paper during exams is more helpful, it may be due to school exams allot marks for each step. Some of them agreed that the leaderboard motivated them to do homework, and they did not find the leaderboard as stressful. It is also supported by Fotaris et al. (n.d.), which further reported that some students study the course material on a weekly basis in order to appear high in the leaderboard rankings. As students had an enriching experience they want gamification in other subjects also.

6. Conclusion & Implications

The study concludes a positive response of students in using gamification for practicing math problems as homework. Gamification enriches the learning experiences, gives practice, improves confidence, interest and performances. It promotes 21st century skills such as critical thinking, creativity, and problem solving.

This study will give teachers an idea about gamification tools and their use for gamifying the homework in the mathematics classroom. It will also help teachers to reinforce and consolidate topics both in the classroom, and as homework (Thiruchelvam, 2018).

Limitation

The present study has a limited sample size and is an exploratory analysis, generalization of results is not possible but it can serve as a starting point for further research on the application of gamified homework.

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10. Study the use of 21st Century skills in teaching during the Internship programme by B.Ed. Student-teachers.

Mrs. Pratibha Ursal¹⁵

Abstract

This survey method study's objective was to determine if the B.Ed. Student-teachers of PVDT College of Education for Women at SNDT Women's University in Mumbai is in accordance with current standards. This study evaluated the school's alignment with 21st century methods using quantitative data from surveys and nonparticipant observations of 86 second year B.Ed. student-teachers.

The finding indicated that the student-teachers were consistently teaching 21st century skills, utilizing some 21st century learning facilities and using 21st century pedagogical approaches. The statistics also revealed that most of the components were being used or implemented. This study demonstrated that the school has implemented structures and is maintaining practices that support a school students and teachers becoming employable in the 21st century.

Keywords: 21st Century skills, 21st Century learning environments, 21st Century curriculum, pedagogical practices, and B.Ed. student -teachers etc.

Introduction:

In today's world, the countries willing to be more democratic, successful and developed than others need to educate generations having the required skills of the 21st century. In this sense, a learning and teaching environment appropriate for the 21st-century and teachers need these skills. With the changing conditions, a change in the education system and the roles of the teachers within this system also takes place. The development of a country can be enhanced by having qualified human resources. For the new generation to be qualified, the existing education system should be reorganized in the light of the needs of today and the future (Gocke, 2000). In the past, a student-centred education system has taken the place of the teacher-centred education system, says Kyasolu (2019). Teachers are expected to guide and encourage their students' production readiness, curiosity, problem-solving abilities, and critical thinking when it comes to 21st-century skills.

Students must adopt 21st century learning strategies and become students of the twenty-first century in order to adapt to the changing global environment. A teacher must educate such students who is a teacher in the 21st century. Both the teacher and the pupil must attend a 21st-century

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school. Students entering the workforce require skills for the twenty-first century that will open doors to employment, entrepreneurship, job training programmes, and/or military duty (Davis, 2016). The manner that current educational practices are established discourages students from learning transferable skills. Children require assistance not only in remembering information, but also in using learned skills and knowledge. Students today can handle the problems of the future by if they have been adequately educated in the classroom to become critical citizens, workers, managers, parents, volunteers, and entrepreneurs (Pellegrino & Hilton, 2012).

A 21st century curriculum should incorporate "mathematics, science, history, geography, English, reading, world languages, arts, economics, government, and civics," according to the Partnership for 21st Century Learning Skills (2013). (Partnership-for-21stCentury-Skills, 2013).

Title of the study

Study the use of 21st Century skills in teaching during the Internship programme by B.Ed. Student-teachers

Aim of the study

To study the use of 21st Century skills during the Internship programme by B.Ed. Student-teachers

Research Questions:

1. What skills do student-teachers identify as the skills required for the 21st century schools?
2. What 21st century skills do student-teachers identify as part of the educational process in their schools?
3. To what extent are the skills taught aligned with the skills needed for employment in the 21st century?

Significance of the Study

This study examines whether Student-teachers' perceptions of 21st -century learning skills and what the research showed about just what institutions expect from students are in accordance.

Schools can use this study to create resources, learning environments, teacher pedagogy, and teaching methodologies.

Operational Definitions

A **student** who fulfils Wagner's (2008) concept of 21st century learning and the Partnership of 21st Century Learning framework is described to as a 21st Century Student.

A **Student-teacher** who is familiar with 21st century learning strategies and who teaches students those strategies with a mind toward 21st century learning is described to as a 21st century student-teacher.

A **school** that emphasises 21st century learning and imparts 21st century skills is described to as a 21st century classroom or school.

The **internship programme** that puts a focus on the student- teachers of the twenty-first century requires them to participate in teaching, classroom management, school observation work, and an overview of various school scenarios that are prevalent in the twenty-first century.

Research Review

The third industrial revolution is now taking place across the world. According to Cataldo (2014), the world is undergoing a digital revolution that is bringing about significant changes. The educational system is the motivating factor that will encourage competitive participants to contribute to the digital revolution. To compete in the digital revolution, educational systems need to generate and teach 21st century learners. Castaldo (2014) claims that the first industrial revolution, which took place in the 18th century, changed how different resources, energy, people, and raw materials were assigned. Materials. The second industrial revolution gave rise to the modern technology that 21st-century individuals use every day, including cars, cell phones, planes, and microprocessors. Moreover, that revolution led to the development of computer-aided lasers, fibre optic, biogenetics, and design (Castaldo, 2014).

Ironically, current society and economic systems are now at the discretion of technology due to the digital age. Government, professional, and educational institutions that depend largely on computing technology have reached a point of no return where they can no longer serve and be successful without them, according to Castaldo (2014). Due to the digital era's dependence on technology to prepare students for the upcoming challenges and to provide as adult role models as employees, managers, parents, volunteers, and entrepreneurs, educational systems must prepare them for the revolution (Pellegrino & Hilton, 2012).

For students to achieve their full potential as adults, educational systems must prepare them to be 21st century learners. In order to help students, understand and apply English, math, and other topics, schools must "provide students with a variety and knowledge that facilitates this" (Pellegrino & Hilton, 2012). Additionally, "corporate and political leaders are increasingly calling on schools to teach 21st century skills" like problem-solving, critical thinking, communication, cooperation, and self-management (Pellegrino & Hilton, 2012).

Teaching and learning environments have shifted as a result of the world's constant change and evolution (Derya Orhan & Kurt, 2017). Furthermore, technological advancements and better career markets have significantly changed the world and economy (Ellis, 2012). Global

collaboration and interconnection have increased as a result of developments in information and communications technology: The evolution of technology and the connection of the

The skills needed to succeed in the twenty-first century have changed significantly transformation as a result of the global market (Ellis, 2012). People are using technology as the main means of communication, and via it, they are growing their networks of co-workers and friends (Ellis, 2012; Wagner, 2008).

Methodology

The quantitative research method was employed in the present study which was carried out to investigate the use of 21st century skills during the Internship programme by B.Ed. Students. To do so, survey design, one of the quantitative research methods, was used in the present study. According to Fraenkel and Wallen (2009), survey design is research that aims to determine the presence and/or degree of change between two or more variables.

Population and Sample

The research population consisted of all student- teachers taking training in the PVDT College of Education for women, SNTD Women's University Mumbai 2022-2023 academic year. The research sample was made up of 86 student-teachers taking training in education college. A convenient sample strategy was used for data gathering. Convenience sampling improves up data collecting by making it simple for more participants to participate in greater numbers (Büyüköztürk, akmak, Ak maz, Karadeniz & Demirel, 2018). The student- teachers were included in the study for the two reasons. First, they teach 21st -century skills to young learners, which makes monitoring the development of these skills easier. Second, they have an adequate amount of classroom time and free activities to teach these skills. Therefore, the use of 21st Century skills during the Internship programme by B.Ed. Students was investigated in this study. Total 86 student -teachers out of 96 were selected for this study.

Limitations

This study is limited to the methodology of the data collection and the timeframe in which the data was gathered. Additionally, the data are limited to B.Ed.

student- teachers. Due to the limited time factor, data was collected from only 86 student-teachers.

Delimitations

The delimitations of this research study included defining 21st century skills and the school in which the study took place. This study was limited only the topic, study of use of 21st century skills by B.Ed. student-teachers. The study was limited only 86 student-teachers only. The school in which this study took place was practice teaching high schools in south Mumbai only.

Data Collection Tools

In selecting the data collection instruments, a literature review was first conducted to identify the scales suitable for the aim of the present study. Then, these scales were compared in terms of the constructs they measured, sub-dimensions, response time, timeliness and suitability for the research method. As a result, one scale was prepared by the researcher determined and used in the research: Use of 21st -century skills by the student-teacher in the internship programme.

Research tool

The variables of this study that are medium of instruction, age group and teaching subjects were determined with the Personal Information Questionnaire with 21st century skills used by the teachers prepared by the researcher.

Data Analysis:

Data were collected from student- teachers through the Personal Information Questionnaire; the 21st century Teacher Skill Scale used in the 2022-2023 academic year. The data collection tool was distributed and collected electronically via online tool. The data was analysed by using statistical technique percentage.

Questions	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I have an excellent understanding of 21st Century learning skills.	29.8%	59.5%	6%	4.8%
I engage students in learning experiences That promotes motivation.	37.3%	56.6%	2.4%	3.6%
I provide students with learning experiences That promotes critical thinking.	37.8%	53.7%	3.7%	4.9%
I involve students with learning experiences That promotes collaboration.	32.5%	62.7%	0%	4.8%
I engage students in learning experiences That promotes economic responsibilities.	21.4%	58.3%	15.5%	4.8%
I engage students in learning experiences That promotes entrepreneurship.	19%	66.7%	10.7%	3.6%

I provide students with learning experiences That promotes curiosity and imagination.	48.2%	47%	0%	4.8%
I involve students in learning experiences That promotes transference of knowledge.	34.9%	57.8%	1.2%	6%
I engage students in learning experiences That promotes agility and adaptability.	28.9%	62.7%	3.6%	4.8%
I utilize the technology resources within my pedagogy.	26.5%	65.1%	4.8%	3.6%

Findings:

This section presents the findings of 21st-century teaching skill used in the classrooms at the time of internship programme by B.Ed. student teachers.

Research Question 1

1. What skills do student-teachers identify as the skills required for the 21st century schools? The skills that the teachers thought were most important were evaluated by them on a scale of 1 to 7 in the survey. The researcher included motivation, critical thinking, the capacity for collaboration, self-reflection, curiosity and imagination a(creativity), Transference of knowledge and Effective oral and written communication were used in the survey. The ability to interact was given the lowest average score, whereas motivation received the best.

Research Question 2

2. What 21st century skills do student teachers describe as being taught in their schools as a part of the educational process?

Whether teachers had a comprehensive understanding of 21st century learning skills was one of the survey's questions. This investigation can be used to Research Question 2 even if it was used to answer Research Question 1. The teachers responded the following percentages: 29.8% strongly agree, agree 59.5% disagree 6%, strongly disagree 4.8%. The student-teachers were then questioned about whether they incorporate the following abilities into their lessons: drive, critical thinking, collaboration, self-awareness, financial responsibility, imagination and creativity, transfer of knowledge, effective oral and written communication, agility, and adaptability (see Table 1).

1. The teachers were asked whether they use technology within their lesson: 26.5% were strongly agree, 65.1% were agree 4.8% disagree and 3.6% were strongly disagree.

2. The student-teachers were asked whether they use technology, networking, and local and

national/international partnerships as resources within their pedagogy: 96.4 % of the Student-teachers use technology.

3. According to the survey, the use of technology is prevalent within the school. The survey revealed that approximately 100% of the student-teachers have implemented the use of technology within their lessons.

Research Question 3

3. How closely do the abilities being taught match up with those required for a job in the twenty-first century?

Motivation, critical thinking, collaboration, self-reflection, imagination and curiosity, information transfer, effective oral and written communication, agility and flexibility, and motivation were the skills that could be seen being taught in the session. Student-teachers gave the task to students in different subject to prepare their presentations, the students were told to work in groups of four to five. When presenting their projects, students used technology like Google Slides, and they were all completely focused throughout the lecture. The following resource-related observations were made during the non-participant observation: The teacher used Google Sheets to communicate her course to the class using technology.

Summary

This researcher presented the data in a structured format and was organized based on the research questions designed by the researcher. Each research question was answered with data from the survey taken by 86 student- teachers, as well as random non-participant observations.

Discussion

This research addresses the interpretations of the data through each research question. The data presented in data analysis answered each research question. The data collection was done via a survey and non-participant observations. The data collection method allowed the researcher to analyse the data to answer each research question. The data are supported (or not) by the literature review. The researcher then draws conclusions.

Discussion:

1. What skills do student-teachers identify as the skills required for the 21st century schools?

The researcher surveyed the student -teachers and asked them to rank the most important to least important skills Motivation, critical thinking, collaboration, self-reflection, financial

responsibility, imagination and creativity (creativity), knowledge transfer, and effective oral and written communication were the skills that were ranked. The researcher then requested the top three talents that schools should emphasise from the student teachers.

In the study, teachers were asked to rank from 1 to 7 the abilities they thought were most important. The skills from the researcher's conceptual framework—motivation, critical thinking, collaboration, self-reflection, curiosity and imagination, knowledge transfer, and effective oral and written communication—were employed in the survey. The ability to collaborate received the lowest score, and motivation received the highest. The results match elements from Wagner's (2008) "Seven Survival Skills for the 21st Century," which include good oral and written communication, problem-solving, and critical thinking. Davis' (2016) research indicates that the

The primary competency required for employment is critical thinking. According to the research, the most crucial abilities are communication, assessment, and adaptation.

2. What 21st century skills do student teachers describe as being taught in their schools as a part of the educational process?

Numerous responses to the poll that identified the various skills used in the school were disclosed. Using a Likert scale, the student-teachers' responses were evaluated. The surveys revealed

that 37 of teachers strongly agree, and 53.7% agree, that they provide students with learning experiences to promote critical thinking. Furthermore, 32.5% strongly agree and 62.7% agree that they involve students in learning experiences that promote collaboration. Finally, they give pupils learning opportunities that promote curiosity and imagination, with 48.2% strongly agreeing and 47% agreeing. All of the student-teachers said they had used technology in their teaching in response. And 70% of respondents said they regularly use technology. The right student groups made it possible for cooperation. According to Pearson (2014), pupils would have learned how to operate in teams, becoming more flexible under challenging circumstances.

3. How closely do the abilities being taught match up with those required for employment in the twenty-first century?

The non-participant observations revealed that the students- teachers were used teaching skills and using practices. All the student-teachers were teaching skills aligned with the 21st century skills. These skills include motivation, critical thinking, ability to collaborate, self-reflective, curiosity and imagination, transference of knowledge, effective oral and written communication, and agility and adaptability.

Conclusion:

This study showed that the school under examination used and put it into practices of 21st century skills. The school was honestly teaching 21st century skills and integrating certain 21st century

technologies. Learning environments, a 21st century curriculum, and teachers utilizing 21st century pedagogy were all adopted. While not all of the components were used or implemented constantly.

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11. Teachers of social science in the middle and secondary levels in Sikkim's schools and their use of 21st-century skills

Manorath Dahal¹⁶

Abstract

The necessity of the hour is for teachers and students to have 21st-century abilities. As a result, the study was carried out in Sikkim with social science teachers from 06 districts who were teaching at the middle and secondary levels. The questionnaire, which was given to social science teachers via Google Form and consisted of sixty questions in three levels—learning and innovation skills, information, media, and technology skills and life and career skills—included 20 questions each. It is a standardized tool by (Bukidnon State University). A five-point scale (Likert) with ratings (1, 2, 3, 4, and 5) and qualitative descriptions (always, often, frequently, rarely, never) was utilized (Practices all the time, Practices most of the time, Practices when necessary, Practices rarely and does not practice 21st century skills at all). Five teachers from each school were chosen as a representative sample. The sample consisted of five teachers from each school. There are ten schools overall, with five from each district. From 60 sampled schools, 300 teachers were selected randomly to serve as the study's sampled teachers but responses received 324. Data interpretations have been done both graphically and tabulatically. Three objectives have been set and then come the research questions. Due to time constraints, the sample is restricted to 300 social science teachers exclusively. All 06 Sikkim districts were included in the study to see how teachers are using 21st century skills in their regular teaching and learning contexts. Study revealed that it has a favourable impact on the teachers who teach social science in Sikkim's schools.

Keywords: media, technology, skills, innovation, career

Introduction

21st century education is the need of the hour. Why is this needed in the recent teaching learning process? It's a big question before us to improve our educational scenario. "Classroom procedures must change if learning is to be innovative. For educators to experiment, educational institutions need to provide a space. Roshan Gandhi, CEO of City Montessori Schools, continued, "We need to improve the curriculum that will aid children in learning. Dr. Amrita Vohra, executive principal at GEMS International School, said in this regard, "Students need to think critically. Thinking is how we learn. There will be a chance if there is an issue. The students must address their issues. Vohra continued by advising students to develop the ability to identify and articulate the true cause of any issue. Children should be able to resolve these issues on their own and develop attention.

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Children need to learn how to think critically, according to Dr. S. K. Rathore, founder, chairman, and managing director of the SANFORT Group of Schools. These abilities are necessary for 21st century learning and will foster a positive learning environment that will prepare students for the future. It is acknowledged that new teaching techniques introduced by 21st century learning will influence students' futures. Learning new skills will aid in achieving 21st century learning objectives.

Objectives of the study

- To find out how the teachers are integrating 21st century skills in social science subjects in their classroom teaching learning.
- To incorporate media literacy, which involves being aware of the channels and strategies used for information dissemination.
- To be aware of the tools to teachers that enable the information age is a requirement for using technological literacy.

Research questions:

1. To study how teachers are integrating 21st century abilities into their social science teaching and learning in the classroom?
2. How to incorporate media literacy, which requires knowledge of the platforms and methods used for information dissemination?
3. Why understanding the tools that enable the information age is a requirement for using technological literacy?

Methodology

In the present study, a normative survey method was employed and the three levels of sixty questions consisting of: Learning and innovation skills, Information, media, and technology skills and Life and career skills-included 20 questions each. Due to time constraints it was administered through Google forms.

Sample

As per the study, a questionnaire was supplied to 300 teachers but responses were received from 324 social science teachers of 60 elementary and secondary level schools of 06 districts. 05 teachers from each school have been chosen randomly for answering the questionnaire.

Tools used

Standardized tools by (Bukidnon State University) have been utilized for assessing the three levels of skills of social science teachers to collect data for carrying out the present research work. A five-point scale (Likert Scale) with ratings (1, 2, 3, 4, and 5) and qualitative descriptions (always, oftenly, frequently, rarely, never) was utilized (5 is Practices all the time, 4 is Practices most of

the time, 3 is Practices when necessary, 2 is Practices rarely and 1 is does not practice 21st century skills at all).

Procedure

Since the schools were selected as per the availability in different districts and the list provided by the district authority to the investigator. Before the actual testing began, rapport was established with the school authorities to explain the real purpose of the test items contained in the questionnaire. After briefing the required information data were collected and for assessing the results and interpret the same in accordance with the objectives and research questions formulated in this research work.

Review of related studies

The Glossary of Education Reform, (2016); Rajaratenam, (2019); Davis, (2021) the previous studies defined the 21st century skills as a broad range of knowledge, skills, work habits, and character traits that educators, school reformers, college professors, and employers believe to be crucial for students to succeed in today's world, particularly in collegiate programmes as well as contemporary careers and workplaces.

According to Enakrire (2020) & Palsdottir (2021) Researchers who possess data literacy skills are more likely to comprehend the supplied data and integrate different types of data together to create information that is valuable for their own purposes.

According to several authors in the field of education (Furino, (2012); Karakoyun & Lindberg, (2020); Demir, (2021). problem-solving has been identified as a crucial skill in schools after digital literacy and is now being incorporated into the teaching process to help students develop their higher-order thinking abilities.

According to Azid and Md-Ali (2020) having a fluid thought process, which is related to creative thinking, enables people to come up with a variety of solutions for challenges. This is due to the fact that when presented with difficulties, they are able to generate ideas and solutions with ease. Instead of just coming up with one or two broad ideas in such a situation, more solutions can be produced thanks to their capacity for creative problem-solving.

Results and discussion

As per the responses received from 324 social science teachers from different districts, data have been tabulated and converted into percentage form to understand the meaning clearly. In the present study out of 324 teachers 176 are female teachers and 148 are male teachers have been included.

Participation of teachers in the following manner in this research study:

Fig. 1: Participation of teachers

The above table shows that the ratio of female teachers is a little higher. Out of 324 teachers, 176 i.e. 54.76% female teachers were included in this study. On the other hand 148 that mean 45.67% male teachers have participated. 80% of rural schools that means 48 schools have been included as sampled schools and 12 schools from urban areas that mean 20% in totality.

Percentage analysis (%) of the total samples of 300 social science teachers of Sikkim on 21st century skills related to **Life & Career Skills**

Table 1

Components	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
1	43.5	25.2	09.4	08.4	13.5
2	51.5	19.5	07.8	19.5	51.5
3	41.9	24.0	11.4	08.8	14.0
4	52.4	17.2	07.8	05.5	17.2
5	29.2	27.9	27.9	13.3	01.3
6	23.2	25.7	25.1	14.1	11.9
7	27.1	31.9	19.7	11.6	09.7
8	46.1	21.9	10.0	07.4	14.5
9	41.8	23.2	12.5	07.7	14.8
10	23.8	31.2	26.0	13.8	07.7
11	33.7	27.8	16.2	11.7	10.7
12	35.2	24.8	16.5	14.5	09.0
13	26.7	32.9	19.2	13.4	07.8

14	47.7	20.6	11.6	09.0	11.0
15	25.6	31.4	24.3	11.7	07.1
16	50.8	19.7	08.7	07.8	12.9
17	29.7	32.3	19.7	10.3	08.1
18	45.8	23.5	10.6	09.4	10.6
19	24.3	33.7	21.4	14.9	05.8
20	39.0	27.3	15.6	08.8	09.4

Fig.2: 21st century skills related to Life & Career Skills

The above table contains 20 questions related to Life and Career Skills and the following percentage of practices was found out in the following components: less than 36.95 % of the sampled teachers integrating life and career skills always in all the twenty components in the schools of Sikkim. Accordingly, 26.1% of teachers integrate oftenly, 15.3% teachers are incorporated sometimes, 11.1% teachers are practicing very rarely and 11.95% sampled teachers not at all incorporated life and career skills in the schools. Altogether all sampled teachers are not in a position to utilize life and career skills in a best fitting manner to their life of students.

Percentage analysis (%) of the total samples of 300 social science teachers of Sikkim on 21st century skills related to **information, Media & Technology Skills**

Table: 2

Components	Always-5	Often-4	Sometimes-3	Rarely-2	Never-1
1	29.9	31.5	17.9	11.7	09.1
2	16.9	24.7	37.0	16.6	04.1
3	32.9	30.3	18.6	10.1	08.1
4	32.5	31.8	15.6	12.3	07.8

5	32.9	30.6	16.3	14.0	06.2
6	27.1	27.5	26.1	11.4	07.5
7	15.7	32.7	33.0	14.7	03.9
8	34.2	20.8	21.5	13.4	10.1
9	12.1	34.6	33.3	14.4	05.6
10	21.5	30.9	28.0	13.0	06.5
11	13.7	24.8	39.7	16.6	05.2
12	21.8	33.1	26.6	11.0	07.5
13	21.5	27.0	30.0	13.7	07.8
14	10.1	27.0	43.3	16.3	06.5
15	20.8	30.6	29.3	12.4	06.5
16	12.1	29.0	36.5	16.6	05.9
17	07.5	18.6	41.7	10.1	07.1
18	28.3	31.9	22.5	09.8	07.5
19	15.6	25.3	37.7	17.2	04.2
20	13.4	23.5	38.2	18.0	06.9

Fig.3: 21st century skills related to information, Media & Technology Skills

Information, media and technology skills are the need of hour but as per the responses of the teachers they are integrating 21.05% always, 28.30% very often, 29.65% sometimes whereas 13.70% they practice very rarely and 6.70% teachers not at all integrated technology skills in their teaching learning processes. This signifies that our teachers be trained in ICT based skills to make them competent enough. Teacher educators and the role of SCERT here is more crucial to train them for further development.

Percentage analysis (%) of the total samples of 300 social science teachers of Sikkim on 21st century skills related to **Learning & Innovation Skills**

Table 3

Components	Always-5	Often-4	Sometimes-3	Rarely-2	Never-1
1	19.8	31.2	29.5	11.4	08.1
2	11.3	30.4	36.2	17.2	04.9
3	28.6	30.8	24.4	09.1	07.1
4	22.7	28.6	30.8	12.0	05.8
5	42.2	26.9	12.3	09.1	09.4
6	19.2	34.4	28.9	12.0	05.5
7	18.6	33.6	30.0	12.4	05.5
8	18.2	33.1	26.3	16.2	06.2
9	22.7	32.4	28.5	09.7	06.8
10	14.6	32.7	30.7	18.1	03.9
11	26.3	31.8	26.3	09.7	05.8
12	30.4	30.1	21.4	12.0	06.1
13	31.8	27.3	20.8	10.4	09.7
14	32.2	26.4	22.1	12.1	07.2
15	15.6	30.0	33.9	14.7	05.9
16	42.1	24.3	15.2	07.8	10.7
17	38.2	26.9	15.9	10.7	08.4
18	30.6	28.4	23.5	11.3	06.1
19	25.8	25.5	26.5	14.8	07.4
20	17.4	25.8	29.0	11.0	06.8

Fig.4: 21st century skills related to Learning & Innovation Skills

The above table shows that teachers of social science integrating learning and innovation skills is 29.45% always, 29.55% very often, and 25.65% sometimes in their day to day teaching and learning practices. 12.10% of teachers integrate innovation skills very rarely and 6.90% of teachers

they never integrate innovation skills in their teaching practices. NEP-2020 also focused on innovation skills to improve so that the training part is more important for the teachers teaching social science.

Findings of the study

- Only 36.95% of teachers are integrating life and career skills, **always** in their teaching learning processes.
- 26.1% of teachers incorporate life and career skills in day to day practices in their classroom **very oftenly**.
- Only 21.05% of teachers are **always** integrating technology skills in their classroom situations.
- 29.65% of teachers are incorporating (ICT) technology skills **sometimes** in the classroom transactions.
- In innovation skills teachers are integrating, **always** found out was 29.45% only in the classroom transactions.
- Teachers incorporating learning and innovation skills in classroom situations very **oftenly** was found out at 29.55%.
- **Sometimes** teachers are incorporating learning and innovation skills which were found to be 25.65%.
- 12.10% of teachers integrated learning and innovation skills **very rarely** in their day to day activities in the classroom.
- 6.90% of social science teachers **never** integrate learning and innovation skills in classroom transactions.

Conclusion

It is concluded that the present study was carried out in Sikkim state with 324 social science teachers teaching at elementary and secondary levels. It has been seen that in three levels of 21st century skills related to Life & Career Skills, information, Media & Technology Skills and Learning & Innovation Skills respectively. Each level contains 20 questions and sampled teachers have responded to their skills as per their own understanding. It is also observed that teachers need more training on all the three levels as per NEP 2020 to improve 21st century skills. Maximum number of teachers needs ICT based training for further improvement. This study is need based to see the problem areas of the teachers teaching social science. Need based training on learning outcomes and especially teachers who have more than twenty years of teaching experience. They need training on ICT and innovation skills. Therefore, it is concluded that the present study found out the problem areas of the teachers where to improve in the days to come.

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12. Investigating Attitude of Pupil Teachers towards Mobile Learning

Dr. Joyti Sehwat¹⁷

Abstract

The purpose of the present paper is to investigate pupil teachers' attitude towards mobile-learning. The present study is quantitative descriptive in nature conducted with survey method. The sample of the study is 212 pupil teachers from teacher education institutions in Haryana. Different factors are examined to find the attitude of pupil teachers towards mobile learning, such as gender, age, type of institution, educational qualifications, academic streams and locality. Findings indicated significant differences among the pupil teachers' attitude towards mobile learning in terms of their age, educational qualification and type of institution. Findings supported that mobile technologies implementation can be proved as a favorable techno-pedagogical innovation to be employed in teaching learning environments.

Keywords: M-Learning, Mobile Technologies, Attitude of Pupil Teachers, Technologies in Education

Background of the Study

Information technology has a huge impact on daily life, and its importance in education is also undeniable. Due to the closure of educational institutions, which created obstacles for students' learning, information technology's role in the COVID 19 pandemic was undeniable. Through cutting-edge learning management systems, information technology is helping to solve the problem of continued learning during this quarantine period (Muzaffar et al., 2020; Zayabalaradjane, 2020). It has given educators the chance to use various mobile technologies for both teaching and evaluating the students' activities. In every area of education, in both developed and developing nations, the usage of wireless, mobile, portable, and handheld technology is progressively growing and diversifying (Traxler, 2007). According to Al-Hunaiyyan et al. (2018), "M-learning is also providing us with an opportunity that is to change the existing learning strategies to give students a much more flexible approach to managing their learning experiences". Many scholars and professionals have used mobile technology into their teaching and learning environments as mobile devices have become more ubiquitous (Park, 2011). Additionally, Kinash et al. (2012) defined m-learning as the use of mobile devices in education and acts as an important for both teaching and learning in the classroom (Kinash et al. 2012; Klassen et al., 2013). According to Zhang (2016), mobile learning is "the learning activity on mobile devices or learning

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anytime and anywhere". Mobile learning is described as "any educational provision where the sole or dominant technologies are handheld or palmtop devices" (Traxler, 2005). Schelur, Winters, & West (2012) described mobile learning as the process of learning that is mediated by portable devices like smartphones and tablet computers. Alzaza and Yaakub (2011) characterised M-learning as the next generation of E-learning that employs mobile technology, in contrast to Mirski and Abfalter (2004) who defined it as a distinct subject developing from distance education. Homan and Wood (2003) defined M-learning more generally as the technology that altered how students engage, communicate, and behave with one another as well as how they perceive their learning. Al Emran and Shaalan (2014) show how M-learning encourages knowledge exchange between students and instructors as they connect with one another. The terms E-learning and M-learning have their differences. M-learning is a subset of e-learning (Winters, 2006). M-learning is "the acquisition of any knowledge and skills via mobile technologies, wherever and whenever possible" (Hashemi, Azizinezhad, Najafi, & Nesari, 2011, p. 1). According to E-learning communities, M-learning could improve student collaboration and foster communication between them and their teachers (Dascalu, Bodea, Lytras, De Pablos, & Burlacu, 2014). Thus, mobile learning (M-learning) has become an essential element of instructional technology in higher education. Students can study, collaborate, and share ideas through M-learning by utilizing the internet and modern technologies. But, implementation of mobile-learning by learners and educators is crucial to the use of M-learning systems. A major factor in determining whether students and teachers are ready to embrace M-learning is attitudes toward the technology. Such attitude will support the development of technology infrastructure as well as the identification of its strengths and weaknesses.

Review of Literature

Today, both developed and developing nations utilize mobile devices on a daily basis in many facets of life. Mobile learning enables us to improve both teaching and learning capabilities (Al-Hunaiyyan et al., 2017). It helps students strengthen their learning capacity, enhance their technology proficiency, and aid in knowledge exchange (AlEmran, Elsherif, & Shaalan, 2016). In a pilot course at a Turkish university where each student received a tablet device outfitted with Google and Hangout Apps to aid in student communication, Erkollar and Oberer (2012) addressed the integration of M-learning with Geographic Information System (GIS) module. Gikas & Grant (2013) investigated the positive effects of mobile devices and its social media applications like Blogs, Skype, Twitter on learning of students. As per Glackin, Rodenhiser & Herzog (2014), learners get more familiar with digital library with the help of integrating mobile technologies and E-books in teaching and learning. Azar and Nasiri (2014) highlighted the benefits of utilizing Mobile Assisted Language Learning (MALL) in English classroom. Additionally, Jaradat (2014) investigated the usage of mobile devices in teaching French Language. Two studies regarding the effectiveness of use of iPads in undergraduate Mathematics course, were led at American University of Sharjah, UAE. Cost, adaptability, and scalability concerns, as well as the rising body of research on using mobile technology for lifelong learning, are some of the top justifications for

employing mobile technologies in education (Nordin, Embi, & Yunus, 2010). Al- Emran, Elsherif & Shaalan (2016) found significant differences in the attitude of students and educators towards mobile learning in terms of their nationality, age and mobile ownership in Oman and UAE. Fozder & Kumar (2007) revealed that mobile learning supports the learning experience of B.Sc. students and more than half of the respondents showed positive attitude towards its effectiveness. According to Al-Fahad (2009) students agreed that wireless networks promote the flexibility of access to resources for independent learning anywhere. As a result, students can save money as well as time and effort. Muhanna & Al Sha'r (2009) found out that the undergraduate students has more favorable attitude than graduates in Jordanian university, Also, male students showed more positive attitude than females towards cell phone learning. Pollara & Broussard (2011) presented a review focusing specifically on how students view mobile learning. Instead than measuring only student achievement gains with mobile learning technology, these studies were primarily designed to gauge students' attitudes toward mobile learning. Nassuora (2013) did another survey to look at Saudi Arabian college students' attitudes about mobile learning. To identify the elements influencing students' intentions to use mobile learning, the author used a framework i.e. UTAUT (Unified Theory of Acceptance Use of Technology) model based. The statistical findings demonstrated that pupils accepted mobile learning at a high degree. Biswas, Roy & Roy (2020) examined how students, particularly university students, perceive using mobile devices for studying during COVID-19 in Bangladesh. The results of the survey indicated that the majority of university students see mobile learning favorably. The study showed that mobile learning is extremely beneficial for filling up study gaps during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Following a review of related literature, it was realized that there has been a dearth of empirical studies on present theme following the COVID outbreak in India, particularly in Haryana, because issues relating to the use of mobile technologies in teaching and learning needed to be investigated at the micro and macro level, encompassing both rural and urban areas of society, with the aim of using those models in various contexts. Additionally, there are very few studies, particularly in the field of mobile technologies in teacher education. Nevertheless, some studies conducted abroad do not directly relate to the areas the investigator chose because they were conducted in nations with quite different educational systems and socioeconomic structures. Therefore, present work will perform a study that is similar to the ones stated above, focusing on pupil teachers' attitudes towards mobile learning, in accordance with recommendations made in the literature

Need of the Study

Mobile learning is significant in the present situation of technological revolution that provides more learning opportunities to students (Trifonova, 2003; Patil & Sawale, 2012). Mobile learning is a recent revolution that gives students more options to learn. As a result, the investigator believes that, in particular, the attitudes of pupil teachers from teacher education institutions cannot be ignored and should instead be periodically reviewed or re-explored. Therefore, this study has been

conducted to fill the existing gap by investigating the attitude of pupil teachers towards mobile learning in a region of Haryana. Although this study is small, it is anticipated that it will be able to put significant contribution to the sphere of teacher education. The following research questions are addressed by the study:

- 1) Is there any significant difference in the attitude of pupil teachers towards mobile- learning in terms of gender?
- 2) Is there any significant difference in the attitude of pupil teachers towards mobile-learning in terms of age?
- 3) Is there any significant difference in the attitude of pupil teachers towards mobile-learning in terms of educational qualifications?
- 4) Is there any significant difference in the attitude of pupil teachers towards mobile-learning in terms of type of institution?
- 5) Is there any significant difference in the attitude of pupil teachers towards mobile-learning in terms of locality?
- 6) Is there any significant difference in the attitude of pupil teachers towards mobile-learning in terms of academic stream?

Methodology

The present study is quantitative descriptive and conducted using survey method. The population of the study is the pupil teachers from teacher education institutions of Haryana. The online questionnaire was prepared using Google forms application for analyzing pupil teachers' attitude towards mobile learning. The questionnaire format was prepared and modified on the basis of studies conducted earlier (Al-Fahad, 2009; Al-Hunaiyyan et al., 2016; Alwraikat & Al Tokhaim, 2014; Cavus, 2011; Dashti & Aldashti, 2015; Liaw & Huang, 2012; Nassuora, 2013). There are three sections to the questionnaire. Part 1 includes basic demographic information about pupil teachers, Part II includes the information regarding the usage and availability of mobile devices and its applications like information about their operating systems, how often they use the internet, how much time they spend each day on their phones, and whether they use them for school and teaching learning purposes or not. Part III of the survey instrument includes sixteen items regarding the attitude towards mobile learning, which are represented in the form of five-point Likert Scale where, 1-Strongly Disagree, 2- Disagree, 3- Neutral, 4- Agree and 5- Strongly Agree. The data was collected with the sample of 212 pupil teachers who have responded to the questionnaire. To verify the items clarity as content validity, survey have been shared with subject experts. To measure the internal consistency, Cronbach's alpha value was computed for the attitude scale which is 0.84 which makes the Likert scale survey reliable. For the collection of data, the prepared questionnaire was randomly distributed in different teacher education institutions through online platforms, especially different social networking sites played important source.

Details of the sample are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Details of Sample

		Frequencies (f)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Female	160	75.5
	Male	52	24.5
Age	20- 24 Yrs	156	73.6
	25-30 Yrs	56	26.4
Academic Qualification	Graduate	143	67.5
	Post Graduate	69	32.5
Locality	Rural	145	68.4
	Urban	67	31.6
Academic Stream	Science	97	45.8
	Commerce	42	19.8
	Arts	73	34.4
Type of Institution	Private	113	53.3
	Government	99	46.7

Results and Discussion

Today's learners, especially those who use them for educational purposes, depend heavily on their mobile phones (Rahman, 2014). Students' access to mobile devices is also enabling them to shift their focus to mobile learning for their coursework (AlHajri, Al-Sharhan, & Al-Hunaiyyan, 2017).

Demographic Information about Pupil Teachers

After analyzing the data, findings revealed that female pupil teachers were 75.5% in comparison to male pupil teachers (24.5%). 73.6% of pupil teachers range between 20-24 years and 26.4 % come under 25-30 years. Then, 32.5% pupil teachers have done their post –graduation whereas, the rest are graduates. 68.4% pupil teachers belong to rural belts of Haryana whereas 31.6% belong to urban areas. 45.8 % pupil teachers are from science stream and 34.4% are from arts stream. Pupil teachers from private institutions contribute 53.3% of sample rest are from government teacher education institutions.

Information regarding Usage and Availability of Mobile Devices and Applications

After

analysis, it was indicated that 100% of the pupil teachers own mobile devices and possess internet facilities at home.

Figure 1: Years of using mobile devices

In terms of number of years of using mobile devices, 44% of pupil teachers have been using mobile devices less than five years, 43% pupil teachers have been using mobile devices for past 6-10 years, whereas, 13% pupil teachers are having mobile devices for more than 10 years (as shown in Figure 1). 96.7% of respondents are using the Android operating system. As shown in Figure 2, 73.3% learners use the internet always whereas 16.7% say they use it frequently. All the students have responded that they all use their mobile phones for academic purposes.

Figure 2:

Frequency of Using Internet

Figure 3: How much time spent on mobile phone every day

As per the analysis, 44% pupil teachers spend around 3-4 hours every day using their mobile phones as shown in Figure 3. 23% of students spend around 5-6 hours. Most popular social networking applications used by the pupil teachers are Google(93.3%), Google+(10%), Facebook, Whatsapp (60%), Youtube (90%), Twitter (6.70%) and others (20%).

Figure 4: Technological devices used for E-learning activities

Figure 5: Use of social networking applications for academic learning purposes

Attitude of Pupil Teachers towards Mobile Learning

After data analysis of 16 items of pupil teachers' attitude towards mobile learning, it was found out that the total mean score of pupil teachers' attitude was 3.84. The attitude score ranges from 4.12 to 3.17 which indicates that pupil teachers have favorable attitude towards mobile learning. 82.1% of pupil teachers responded that mobile devices allow them for flexible learning anytime or anywhere. 85.9% respondents agreed that mobile learning helped to bridge the study gap especially during COVID outbreak. 76.4% pupil teachers accepted that mobile devices are easier to find relevant learning materials related to their subjects. Further, 88.2% learners admitted that mobile applications help to enhance their study skills. 81.1% of pupil teachers believe that mobile devices advance their knowledge in their subject of study. Also, 83.3% students mentioned that mobiles are convenient for sharing information and class related conversations with teachers and peers especially at the time of COVID outbreak. 87.8% pupil teachers admitted that mobile applications help to solve their study related issues. 84.9% respondents confirmed that Mobile learning provides them a variety of learning opportunities and alternative ways to study. Additionally, 77.8% pupil teachers believe that use of social media applications helps in their educational fulfillment while 72.2% pupil teachers think that mobile application also improves interpersonal communication. Faster feedback can also be obtained through mobile learning and learning is unaffected by the screen size of mobile devices as acknowledged by 68% pupil teachers. Furthermore, 70.2 % of pupil teachers believe that they find learning a lot of fun while using mobile devices. The results that address the research questions are presented below:

RQ1: Is there any significant difference in the attitude of pupil teachers towards mobile- learning in terms of gender?

Results were analyzed using independent samples t-test. Perusal of Table 2 indicates that the mean values of female and male pupil teachers' attitude towards mobile-learning is 61.150 and 62.576

respectively. Also, the t-value (-1.157) is found non-significant at 0.05 level of significance. This implies that female and male pupil teachers do not differ significantly in their attitude towards mobile-learning. Results have shown congruence with previous studies conducted by Cavus (2011), Wang Wu and Wang (2009), Uzunboylu, Cavus & Ercag (2009), Yang (2012). However, a study conducted by Taleb & Sohrabi (2012) found significant difference in students' attitude towards mobile learning in terms of gender. Females showed more positive attitude.

Table 2: Differences between attitude of pupil teachers on the basis of gender, age, educational qualifications, type of institution and locality

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	Df	Sig.
Gender	Female	160	61.150	7.799	-1.157	210	.249
	Male	52	62.576	7.492			
Age	20-24 Yrs	156	62.467	6.315	3.104	210	.002 *
	25-30 Yrs	56	58.803	10.338			
Educational Qualifications	Graduate	143	62.195	7.295	1.898	210	.050 *
	Post-Graduate	69	60.058	8.439			
Type of Institution	Private	113	62.858	6.311	2.776	210	.050 *
	Government	99	59.949	8.867			
Locality	Rural	145	60.917	8.035	-1.621	210	.107
	Urban	67	62.761	6.919			

*Sig. at 0.05

RQ 2: Is there any significant difference in the attitude of pupil teachers towards mobile-learning in terms of age?

Perusal of Table 2 indicates that the mean and standard deviation of attitude of pupil teachers age group 20-24 years is 62.467 and 6.135 respectively. Whereas, mean and standard deviation of pupil teachers with age group 25-30 years is 58.803 and 10.338 respectively. Also, the t-value (-3.104) is found highly significant at 0.05 and 0.01 level of significance. This implies that there exists significant difference in the attitude of pupil teachers towards mobile learning in terms of

age. Pupil teachers with age group 20-24 years (Mean= 62.467) showed more positive attitude in comparison to those with age group 25-30 years (Mean=58.803).

RQ3: Is there any significant difference in the attitude of pupil teachers towards mobile-learning in terms of educational qualifications?

From Table 2, the t-value (1.898) is found significant at 0.05 level of significance. This implies that there exists a significant difference in the attitude of pupil teachers towards mobile learning in terms of their educational qualifications. Graduate pupil teachers (Mean= 62.195) showed more positive attitude in comparison to those with post -graduation (Mean=60.058).

RQ4: Is there any significant difference in the attitude of pupil teachers towards mobile-learning in terms of type of institution?

From Table 2, the t-value (2.776) is found significant at 0.05 level of significance. This implies that there exists a significant difference in the attitude of pupil teachers towards mobile learning in terms of their type of institution. Pupil teachers from private institutions (Mean= 62.858) showed more positive attitude towards mobile learning in comparison to those studying in government institutions (Mean=59.949).

RQ5: Is there any significant difference in the attitude of pupil teachers towards mobile-learning in terms of locality?

Table 2, indicates that the mean values of attitude of pupil teachers from rural and urban areas are 60.917 and 62.761 respectively. Also, the t-value (-1.621) is found non -significant at 0.05 level of significance. This implies that pupil teachers do not differ significantly in their attitude towards mobile-learning in terms of their locality. Both rural and urban prospective teachers showed favorable attitude.

RQ6: Is there any significant difference in the attitude of pupil teachers towards mobile-learning in terms of academic stream?

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation for attitude of pupil teachers on the basis of academic stream

Stream	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Science	97	61.680	8.201
Commerce	42	60.904	6.214
Arts	73	61.602	7.954
Total	212	61.500	7.732

Table 4: Pupil teachers' attitude on the basis of academic stream

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	18.809	2	9.404	.156	.856

Within Groups	12596.19	209	60.269
Total	12615.00	211	

From Table 3, indicates that the mean values of attitude of pupil teachers from science, commerce and arts stream are 61.680, 60.904 and 61.602 respectively. Also, ANOVA Table 4, the F-value (-.156) is found non-significant at 0.05 level of significance. This implies that pupil teachers either from science, commerce or arts do not differ significantly in their attitude towards mobile-learning.

The answer to this research question may be related to the fact that practically all students irrespective of their academic streams use their mobile devices (smartphones and tablets) for multiple educational purposes like checking their email, use of social media, sharing files etc. No significant difference has thus been found out. Similar results were found out by Taleb & Sohrabi (2012) and Mostafa Al Emran, Hatem M. Elsherif & Khaled Shaalan (2015).

Conclusion and Discussion

The development of ground-breaking mobile technologies had a big influence on educational technology. In this research, emphasis is given on the most recent developments in mobile learning as they relate to the attitude of prospective teachers toward the usage of mobile learning in the teacher education institutions. The primary contribution of this study is an examination of the attitudes of pupil teachers, which will assist the decision-makers and administrators of teacher education institutions in developing the necessary mobile-learning infrastructure and facilities. When assessing pupil teachers' attitude, gender, age, type of institution, locality, academic stream is all taken into consideration. Data was collected from 212 pupil teachers from teacher education institutions from Haryana using questionnaire being prepared through Google forms. Both descriptive and inferential statistical techniques were applied for data analysis using SPSS software in order to find out the significant difference in the pupil teachers' attitude towards mobile learning with regard to above mentioned factors. Results showed significant difference in attitude of pupil teachers in terms of age. Pupil teachers with the age group 20-24 years have more favorable attitude towards mobile learning. Results showed statistical significant difference in the attitude of pupil teachers in terms of type of institution. Pupil teachers from private institutes showed more positive attitude. Also, graduate pupil teachers showed more positive attitude towards mobile learning than those with post-graduation. These findings can have educational implications for the decision makers and curriculum planners for implementing mobile technologies and applications in the future. The use of smartphones/tablets in teaching and learning would improve the in-service teachers' attitude towards mobile technologies. Findings related to age difference could influence the curriculum planners and decision makers to develop tailored mobile learning programmes that could be utilized by learners of all ages. However, no statistical difference was found in the attitude of male and female pupil teachers towards mobile learning

which indicates that mobile devices can be adopted by both genders for their teaching and learning purposes. Also, non-significant effect of locality and academic streams indicates that mobile learning can be implemented by all the learners from different academic or demographic backgrounds.

Additionally, findings showed that 100% of the pupil teachers possess smartphones/tablets possibly because of the reasonable cost and readily availability of mobile devices in the present Indian market. Due to the fact that they are already using mobile technologies for their educational purposes, this may serve as a strong indicator that pupil teachers are extremely motivated to use it for their future learning as well.

Limitations of the Study

While the findings of the present study are having theoretical and pedagogical repercussions, but, the study is not without certain limitations. Firstly, it only focused on pupil teachers of Haryana state with a small sample of only 212 pupil teachers. Further studies could be carried out with larger samples and other populations like teacher educator, teachers, special educators etc. A survey questionnaire method was used for data collection. Further research can be done to improvise the instrument and sampling method and carry out the same research in other parts. The results of this study indicate that our next step should be to integrate the mobile- technologies in the process of teaching and learning. As a result, additional surveys should be carried out to look at the attitudes of both students and teachers towards mobile applications.

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13. 4Cs & LSRW: 21st Century Skills in a Language Classroom

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The illiterate of the 21st century will not be those who cannot read and write, but those who cannot learn, unlearn, and relearn.

-Toffler, 2006

Introduction

The periphery of literacy keeps evolving with time and is in sync with various social developments. It is a dynamic concept. It is an individual's capacity to comprehend something. The concept of multi-literacy has evolved in the recent times. In order to succeed in the present scenario of volatile changes, one needs to possess multi-skills like analytical skills like critical and logical thinking; creativity and innovation; systematic thinking; collaboration and cooperation. These would prepare individuals to tackle the global challenges practically. Multi-skills in addition to the knowledge are the constituents of the 21st century skills. Global Task Force (2008) stated in its report, "In order to educate the generation of students who will face the challenges of the 21st century, universities need to provide students with the skills, knowledge, and attitudes to work effectively in our increasingly interdependent world". 3Rs i.e. reading, writing and arithmetic are not enough. Rapid technological evolution has impacted each and every domain of development, raising the need for learning technology and digital skills. It has redefined the concept of 21st century skills which is much beyond the 3Rs.

Current educational reforms are focusing on skill development, research and innovation. National Education Policy 2020 has emphasized great deal on this aspect and has suggested various steps which would help in achieving it. Such reforms would provide impetus to achieving the vision of self-reliant India. To build atmanirbhar bhara we need to equip our students with self-confidence. This confidence originates from the knowledge and skills of an individual, and one more important component, the language. Overcoming linguistic barrier opens-up unlimited horizons for individuals.

This global arena has also provided impetus to the need of communication skills resulting in the need of learning and mastering the language skills. An individual with competence in communication would achieve much more than those who are not competent. Specifically, the English language for it being the global language of business and connection. It provides a

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common platform for different cultures to come on a single plain and connect. Ability to express, articulate and communicate are the key to achieve success. The learning and innovation skills- the 4Cs i.e. critical thinking and problem solving, creativity and innovation, communication, collaboration are prominent among various 21st century skills. We need to promote these skills among our learners, teachers and mentors.

Objective

The objective of the present paper is to explore the dimensions of the 21st century learning skills i.e. 4Cs in English language classrooms focusing on the development of LSRW: listening, speaking, reading and writing skills.

The present paper would discuss and review the 21st century learning skills 4Cs with reference to language skills LSRW.

21st Century Learning Skills (4Cs) in Language Classroom

These learning skills include:

- Critical thinking and problem solving
- Creativity and innovation
- Communication
- Collaboration

“Critical thinking skill is an individual’s ability to use a number of his or her general cognitive processing skills which fall into high-order thinking levels of analyzing, evaluating and constructing new ideas or creating and which enables students to think deeply to solve non-familiar problems in different ways” (Kivunja, 2015). Thinking critically implies looking at a situation or problem from its multiple perspectives and analyzing it. This analysis is evidence and fact based. Critical thinking and problem solving requires exercises involving students in problem-based tasks. It persuades an individual to use reasoning, rational and reflective thinking while interpreting and evaluating the given information. Every individual has different learning styles including their major and minor learning styles. Some learn by seeing (visual), some by listening/speaking (auditory), some through reading/writing work and some by doing (kinesthetic). Being aware of these helps in acknowledging and incorporating these into classroom activities. It helps in critical thinking and problem-solving activities being conducted by the students as per their own learning style.

In a language class tasks such as comprehension exercises, creative writing based tasks involves analytical skills like critical thinking and finding solution to the present questions. While conducting such tasks, display questions should be avoided. Rather, exploratory questions should

be used. It stimulates the critical discourse among the students. Using such kind of tasks is an integral component of a language class. All the four language skills are activated when students are allotted the tasks like discussions or debate. While discussing or during debate the students will read texts, make notes, listen to the other side and speak-out their thoughts on the given topic as per their research or study. Listening and speaking; reading and writing shall be used in continuum in such tasks. Providing more and more of such kind of exercised to the students would assist in learning and developing the critical thinking and problem-solving skills.

Creativity and innovation is an individual's capacity to produce an original and distinct product, or finding a distinct way or solution to a problem. Creativity and innovation follows once critical thinking and problem-solving tasks are completed. While finding the solutions for the given problem an individual is required to think in different and new ways.it exercises their creative thinking skill and the final product would be an innovation or creation of a new knowledge. "Creative activities in a classroom teaching-learning process are the tools which gives opportunities to the students to express their learnings in a new way" (ELT, Oxford University Press, 2013). There are three type of creative thinking- Combinational thinking: producing new ideas by associations of old ideas; Exploratory thinking: exploring the possibilities in current conceptual space using the existing rules; and Transformational thinking: altering the current concept.

Creative writing tasks, completion tasks, open-ended questions, cloze test items and tasks requiring students to suggest different plausible plot or series of events are used in language classes. In addition the activities involving brainstorming, group projects, essay writing, poem writing and visual representation of the idea through its drawing, promote creativity in a language class. Such tasks are aimed at promoting the creativity and innovation skills among the students. These tasks provides students the opportunity to innovate. Integrating creative thinking in language lessons develops cognitive skills like observation, inquiry and hypothesizing; metacognitive skills like evaluation and reflection (Read, 2015).

Communication being the most crucial skill for learning, is the ability of an individual to interact with their fellow people and share their thoughts and state of mind with them. It is also one of the basic needs of an individual, as in the absence of it the person feels isolated from its surrounding. This makes them feel wandering uselessly. It enables individuals to connect and articulate their thoughts and ideas orally, in writing and using non-verbal cues. An individual should be able to express themselves clearly and appropriately using the correct structures of language and appropriate words. In various life spheres and in career these skills are crucial and the determining factors of success.

All the language class tasks are aimed at developing the communication skills of the students so that they can interact with their surroundings meaningfully and to their most satisfactory extent.

Though it involves the above two skills as well. As, an individual while communicating is required to think critically and creatively to proceed with the process.

“Collaboration is defined as working together to achieve common goals” (Applied Educational Systems, 2019). It is the ability of the person to work in cohesion with their peers or team, taking the responsibility of the allotted tasks. This helps in understanding the fact that each individual thinks differently and have different ideas. Various critical thinking and problem-solving tasks in a language class requires the students to work in collaboration with their peers. Various collaborative tasks require students to coordinate, communicate, take decisions, resolving conflicts and doing negotiations while solving the problem.

Communication exercises in a language class involve a small group of students to practice listening, speaking, reading and writing tasks in collaboration with their peers. Writing short stories in groups, completing the story, drawing conclusions or endings are the activities which can be used in a language class to promote collaboration among students. Students should also be motivated to discuss their course of path while performing the given tasks and analyze; compare the strategies used by the other groups or students; suggest the ways to improve these collaborations.

Communication and collaboration are the two Cs about which the language teachers are well aware. As these are the basis of all the language classes, in the absence of which the language classes are meaningless as it would not be able to develop the desired language skills.

Developing Language Skills

Language is a means of communicating thoughts. Language has two forms; spoken and written. Mainly a language proceeds from spoken to written form. To acquire a language and to learn a language one need to possess the language skills. There are four language skills i.e. listening, speaking, reading and writing (LSRW). These language skills are classified into two categories- receptive skills also known as passive skills and productive skills also known as active skills. Listening and reading are the receptive (passive) skills, while speaking and writing are productive (active) skills.

Listening being the passive skill is very important for developing its counterpart speaking a productive skill, as it provides the input for processing. Listening influences the multicultural sensitivity and helps in developing empathy a crucial component of social and emotional development. Practicing listening in a language class involves various activities based on active listening. Classroom discussions contribute a great deal in exercising the listening skill of the students. This pose a challenge also, the challenge of the conversation veering off the course. So in order to provide successful listening experience to the students, the teacher needs to engage students into purposeful listening by telling them which part needs their attention, how they can

do so what to respond to, how to respond and when to respond. Audios and supporting visuals compose the listening exercises. Such tasks should integrate both audio and video providing multisensory inputs to grasp the attention of the students as well as using more than one sense to generate the meaning out of the given situation. Technology proves to be a useful tool for such exercises. The 21st century listening lessons are tech-enabled which can be accessed as and when required, replayed with ease and fully controlled by the students to adapt as per their level.

Speaking comes in quick succession to the listening skill. We learn a language more naturally in speaking form first as it serves our primary communication purposes very well. Also, it provides the immediate practical implementation of the language learnings. This language skill is more about fluency, pronunciation and verbal oral drill. Our classroom interactions are more reliant on this skill in comparison to the other language skills. Also it helps us to use our class time more economically. Various function-based tasks and activities help in developing speaking skills. Rhymes repetition, oral composition, pronunciation drills, look and say, read aloud, open-ended stories, narrations, description, dialogue, role play, interviews, debates and discussions, rhymes, talks and picture comprehension are speaking skill activities which can be used in classrooms (Jyothsna & Rao, 2009).

Reading skill is an important receptive (passive) skill as it provides the input and basis for the other skills. An important 21st century skill, as we are facing a bombardment of information- true and fake. To identify we need to possess the reading skill and should be a well-informed reader. Understanding the context of a text is crucial to make a meaning and to draw out the wholeness of the content. Reading exercises and tasks in a language class involves to read the story, novel, essay, poem, newspaper, letters etc. and to understand it from various perspectives by analyzing the text structure, vocabulary, text forms, reference, direct and indirect contexts, feeling and emotion represented through that piece of text. Reading comprehension exercises are also crucial tasks being used in a language class.

“Writing is a powerful tool to open up communication and allow change to be initiated” (Anae, 2014). Writing is a productive (active) skill of a language. It is creative task where students gather their thoughts and ideas; analyze; process and generate new thoughts and ideas. Stories, rhymes, quotes, letters, songs, etc. are the some of the writing tasks used in a language class to develop the writing skill among students. Creative writing is the most used tool among these. Creative writing lessons creates motivation, imagination and inspiration among the students. It develops the competence and skill to create knowledge and process it individually, in pairs and in groups. It requires students to brainstorm, identify and organize their ideas into a written piece. In addition to developing the language skill and its fluency, this also provides the opportunity to think critically, create, communicate and collaborate among themselves while producing a new piece of work. Also, drama, dialogues, autobiography, memoirs, travelogues, music, storytelling, projects and creative writing tasks together gives a lot of opportunities for students to exercise the 21st

century learning skills the 4Cs. Creative writings facilitate the social and literacy skills it also provides the device to explore the social and personal issues.

Conclusion

The 21st century learning skills are the pillars of the vision: Self-reliant India (Atmanirbhar Bharat). The 4Cs of these learning skills are the crucial components of a language class. In integration these 4Cs helps an individual conquer various tasks both at workplace and at home; social and personal sphere. These are the indicators of success and helps in further developments. All the knowledge acquisition processes are dependent on these and in turn the development of these skills are dependent on the knowledge acquisition tasks. All these aspects makes it very important to focus on these 4Cs and language skills not only in language class but also beyond that i.e. in each and every task performed at school or college level.

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14. Effectiveness of learning resources developed using VSDC and Piktochart to facilitate learning while curriculum transaction

Dr. Madhuri Bendale¹⁹

Abstract

Technological advancements and innovation go hand in hand and they have brought about incredible changes in the way the students learn. Students are more exposed to technology and hence traditional methodology and traditional classroom settings are transforming, expanding beyond the four-walled cubes into the “virtual” amorphous cyberspace classroom. The use of ICT focuses on student-centered learning. Due to technology-driven communication and growing student diversity, we as teacher educators have a great responsibility to be more innovative and technological in our pedagogical approaches. The use of ICT offers a constructivist approach to learning through the provision of interactive learning experiences and thereby providing students with a repertoire of resources to enhance learning. The purpose of this paper is to provide ways to create a learning environment by using innovative teaching-learning strategies. This paper reveals the use of VSDC and Piktochart software to prepare learning resources to make the learning environment facilitate learners. The study is conducted on IX Std students by carrying out the teaching-learning process through traditional ways as well as by using ICT resources. The interpretation of the result is done by comparing the mean values of two groups, the one taught in a traditional way and the other by using ICT resources. Further, the paper discusses the major findings of the study.

Keywords: Innovation, Technology, Incredible, VSDC, Piktochart, Student-centered, Pedagogical approaches

Introduction

21st century skills are tools that can be universally applied to enhance the way of thinking, learning, working and living in the world. “The skills include critical thinking/reasoning, creativity/creative thinking, problem solving, metacognition, collaboration, communication and global citizenship. 21st century skills also include literacies such as reading literacy, writing literacy, numeracy, information literacy, ICT, digital literacy, communication and can be described broadly as learning domains.”¹

For the progress and development of students these skills should be inculcated in them. It is very difficult tasks for teachers to link these skills to our teaching-learning process. Learning materials should be planned keeping in mind all these skills as they support student learning and increase student achievement. Clay P. Bedford says, “You can teach a lesson for a day, but if you can teach him to learn by creating curiosity, he will continue the learning process as long as he lives.”² The power of learning environment to promote learning is significant and provide ample opportunities

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for students to explore ideas and knowledge, collaborate, solve problem and develop knowledge and skills.

Audio-visual aids play a very important role in the teaching-learning process. When we keep students engage using technology, it arouses interest in the learners and helps the teacher to explain the concepts easily. Here, the researcher uses two groups, for one group the teacher delivers the content by using traditional methods and for the other group by using ICT tools such as VSDC and Piktochart

Review of Related Literature

1. **Allen Jim and Rolf Van der Velden (August 2012)³**. *Skills for the 21st century: Implications for education*. In this paper the authors say that the world is changing rapidly in a lot of ways, but the dominant change is in ICT. They say that these changes play an important role or are a driving force for the major changes such as globalization and flexibilization. They bring into sight the importance of 21st century skills in education and says that educational policy and practice should proceed from the insight that skills of individual human beings form a complete interdependent package of all these three kinds of skills ; basic skills , specific skills and 21st century skills
2. **C. Cigdemoglu, H. Akay (2016)⁴**. *Use of ICT tools and their effect on teaching and learning; students' and instructor's views*. This paper studied the use of Information Communication Technology (ICT) tools that contribute to high quality lessons since they have potential to increase students' motivation, connect students to many information sources, support active in-class and out-class learning environments, and let instructors allocate more time for facilitation. Therefore, use of ICT tools in the teaching and learning process becomes a great area of research for many educators. These technologies increase students' motivation, self-confidence and self-esteem to learn. Additionally, new technologies usually encourage independent and active learning, as a result, the students feel more responsible for their own learning. Considerable number of research on the contribution of ICT in modernizing learning and teaching, triggers attempts to incorporate these technologies in order to benefit in terms of quality of education, flexibility, access, and its cost.

Statement of the Problem

Effectiveness of learning resources developed using VSDC and Piktochart to facilitate learning while curriculum transaction

Variables of the Study

1. **Dependent variable** or the variables also kept constant to observe the result or act as the effect in the presence or absence of the constant.
 - Questionnaire on useful microbes
2. **Independent variable** or the variable manipulated by the researcher for the present study to act as a treatment or the condition that is supposed to be the cause.

- Teaching-learning process by using ICT tools such as VSDC and Piktocha

Aims of the Study

1. To develop the teaching-learning process by using learning materials prepared by using ICT tools for IX std students.
2. To implement the teaching-learning process by using learning materials prepared by using ICT tools for IX std students.
3. To study the effectiveness of teaching-learning process by using learning materials prepared by using ICT tools for IX std students.

Objectives of the Study

1. To develop the teaching-learning process by using learning material prepared by using ICT tools for IX std students.
2. To develop the teaching-learning process by using traditional method for IX std students.
3. To compare the mean scores of both the groups of IX std students I.e., group A taught by traditional method and group B taught using ICT tools.

Scope of the Study

Defining the scope of the study and demarcating its frontiers ensure greater specificity and precision besides keeping at bay the unwarranted inferences. Therefore the researcher has spelled out the following boundaries for the present study.

Being an experimental study, the study is focus on the students studying in IX std. The study concentrates on developing the teaching-learning process by using learning materials prepared by using ICT tools such as VSDC and Piktochart.and study its effectiveness.

The study includes only the English medium IX std students of Dr, Babasaheb Ambedkar Municipal school.

Delimitations of the Study

Delimitations are the boundaries of study, which restrict the conclusions of the study to the sampled population.

- The study does not take into account the other medium of IX std students.
- The study included English medium IX std students from Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Municipal school only .

Sample

Group A :- 30 students (both boys and girls) of Std IX A from Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Municipal English medium school, worli for traditional way of teaching.

Group B:- 30 students (both boys and girls) of std IX B from Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Municipal English medium school, worli for teaching-learning process by using ICT tools such as VSDC and Piktochart.

Subject:- Science

Topic:- Useful and Harmful microbes

Sub-topic:-

1. Different types of microbes
2. Concept of useful microbes
3. Examples of useful microbes
 - i. Lacto bacilli
 - ii. Rhizobium

Medium of Instruction:- English

Lesson Plan:-

Group A:- Teaching-learning process planned by traditional method.

Group B:- Teaching-learning process planned by using learning materials prepared by using ICT tools such as VSDC and Piktochart.

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Tool:- Questionnaire on useful microbes

Treatment: -

- The research commenced after selection of school, standard, subject and lesson to be taught.
- The school selected was totally untouched for carrying out the teaching-learning process by using ICT tools.

- The class of IX std was selected as the objectives of the study matched with the age level of the students.
- The subject chosen was science and the topic was useful and harmful microbes.
- Teacher carried out the teaching-learning process for both the groups i.e., Group A was taught by the traditional way and Group B was taught by Using ICT tools.
- Questionnaire was prepared on useful microbes and given to both the groups to solve after implementation of the teaching-learning process.
- Students' performance and achievement was evaluated by scores achieved by them.
- Mean scores are compared of both the groups and results were interpreted.

Analysis and Interpretation

- To compare the mean scores of both the groups.

Groups	Sample	Method of Teaching-learning process	Mean scores
Group A	30	Traditional way	5.72
Group B	30	By using learning materials prepared by using ICT tools	7.79

From the above table and graph it can be interpreted that the mean scores of Group B (content taught using ICT tools) is greater than the Group A.(content taught by traditional way). Therefore we can interpret that the teaching-learning process planned by using ICT tools is effective and makes students understand better.

Discussion

VSDC Free Video Editor does not require any specialized hardware to run properly. The layout consists of timeline area, scene area, status bar, quick access toolbar, editing tools, command bar with media library, properties window and resource window^{5a}.

Any digital object may be dragged and dropped anywhere on the timeline. Once on the timeline, video can be duplicated, split, cut, muted, cropped, flipped, rotated, played backward, resized, etc., its speed can be slowed down or increased; audio may experience amplitude and delay effects, filters, tempo and rate change, reverse effect, etc. color corrected and enhanced. VSDC Free Video Editor gives the opportunity to save an output file to a computer hard disk drive. Cropping, rotating, transparency, and creating picture-in-picture video effects are quite easy in VSDC^{5b}.

Piktochart is a web based infographic application which allows users without intensive experience as graphic designers to easily create professional-grade info graphics using themed templates. An important feature of Piktochart is its HTML Publishing capability, which generates infographics that are viewable online with multiple clickable elements for users. Additionally, the program provides tools to add interactive maps, charts, videos and hyperlinks. It provides many templates which can be edited by using more advanced functions and can be customized as desired.⁶

Hence both these tools can be used for making learning materials and can be used during the teaching-learning process to make the lesson more effective and support students to enhance their achievements.

These tools can also be used for revision purposes and can be sent to students by mail so that they can refer to it at their own pace.

Conclusion

Usage of innovative learning resources is the need of the hour, from the above write-up we gain an insight on developing learning resources using VSDC and Piktochart that would benefit students to do self paced learning and be an active participant in the process of learning.it will not only help to enhance quality of teaching and learning but also helps the learners to achieve desired outcomes.

It helps students to feel more motivated and confident and they would be stimulated to be life long learners.

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15. Community involvement through School Management Committees in 21st Century Education system

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Abstract

Schools where community people with diverse knowledge and skills are connected can bring a positive change in attitude and outlook of students. Indian communities are divided into different classes, castes, gender and religions. These factors affect the children's access to education and their participation in the learning process. So community involvement is very important in 21st century education. The participatory school management committees involve parents, local authority, communities, and local philanthropists. The RTE Act, 2009 has made the formation of School Management Committee mandatory in every school. It plays an immense role in functioning, strengthening, monitoring and developing relationships between the schools, teachers and communities. This research study primarily intends to study the evaluation of School Management Committees in Haryana. Sample of 80 Head Teachers had been selected from 4 districts of Haryana. Data was collected by a self-made non-directive interview schedule for head teachers. Findings of the study revealed that the majority (73.75 per cent) of head teachers viewed that the school management committee always helped in school management for smooth working of the school. It was deeply observed that some committee members were very active; they always helped in the smooth working of the school. The majority (53.75 per cent) of head teachers opined that school management committee members are active towards monthly meetings as they always took interest in attending the meetings of SMC and gave useful suggestions for smooth working of the school management committee. It was found that the majority (72.50 per cent) of head teachers viewed that school management committee members were aware about teaching learning activities. Conclusion of this study was that the majority of School Headmasters are satisfied with the involvement of school management committee members but along with this they also expected them to be more active.

Keywords: S.M.C. , Community involvement, Headmasters

Introduction

There is a need of community to make the transformation in education in 21st Century. Need of transformation arises from the community which develops our sense of purpose. Schools where community people with diverse knowledge and skills are connected can bring a positive change in attitude and outlook of students. Indian communities are divided into different classes, castes, gender and religions. These factors affect the children's access to education and

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their participation in the learning process. So community involvement is very important in 21st century education. The participatory school management committees involve parents, local authority, communities, and local philanthropists. These all play an important role in promoting the social change and when we integrate them in our classrooms they evoke the capacities of learning. students also have rich environment outside the classroom or school too. so there must be connection between the two so that improve the quality of education.. Many provisions have been made in the act to ensure quality education for all children in the age group of 6-14 years. Specific provisions have been made for democratization of schools and for parents and local communities to play their due roles in shaping and running of the schools in the form of School Management Committees (SMC) and preparation of School Development Plan. Sections 21 and 22 of the RTE Act, 2009 made an important provision for empowering SMCs to ensure active participation of the community at the school level. At least 75 per cent of the SMCs are to comprise parents. Additionally, proportionate representation is to be given to disadvantaged groups and weaker sections of society and they are to have a minimum 50 per cent representation of women. The SMC in the school is assigned to monitor the working of the school and grants received by the state and local governments.

There was a need to clarify the roles and practices of the SMC and to provide insight into how to make judgments about school and community improvement. So, the researcher wants to study on SMC which was rarely taken by the researchers in India. Another reason for taking this study is that there are years of gap among the studies those were already done on VEC and SMC and a very few studies have been conducted on SMC. Although some studies on the working of VEC and SMC have been carried out in some States of the country, but no any comprehensive study, as such, has been undertaken in Haryana so far. Therefore the above background provides the necessary basis and justification for this research study, which primarily intends to study the evaluation of School Management Committees in Haryana.

Review of Literature

Kalhotra (2013) found that involvement of VEDC in the management process of elementary education may lead to smooth functioning of school, most of the VEDC members are in the view that Sarpanch of their area is playing an impressive role in managing the elementary education. Verma & Singh (2014) carried out a study on the Functioning of Village Education Committee (VEC) in Educational Management. The result of the study find out that fifty two (52%) of VEC members of Cheema and 33% VEC members of Lehra block accepted that meeting (*Aam Sabha*) was held for selection of VEC members. Rout (2014) found that SMC members asked the children about their difficulties in learning. Singh (2016) found that 90% SMC members say that they check the Mid-Day-Meal. But 10% members don't check the Mid-Day-Meal. Kumar (2016) revealed that the majority of SMC members are well aware of the post and position held by them in the SMC.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to study the functioning of the school management committees and to study the views of head teachers regarding the functioning of the school management committee in 21st century education system.

Research Methodology

Descriptive Survey Method was adopted by the investigator.

Tool Used

A self developed non-directive interview schedule for the head teachers was used to collect the views regarding the functioning of the school management committee.

Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1 : Views of Head Teachers about the functioning of School Management Committee

Sr. No.	Views of Head Teachers (No. of Head Teachers =80)	Yes (%)	No (%)
1	Knowledge about School Management Committee under RTE Act, 2009	100	00
2	Knowledge about School Building Construction Committee (SBCC)	53.75	46.25
3	Responsibility about Formation the School Management Committee	67.50	32.50
4	Knowledge about the Taking Signatures on Oath Letter	78.25	21.25
5	Giving the Details of Income & Expenditure	100	00
6	Helping in Organizing the Health Checkup Camps	61.25	38.75

From the above table it may be concluded that all the head teachers knew about the school management committee constituted under RTE Act, 2009. It also shows that 53.75 per cent head teachers knew about the school building construction committee while 46.25 per cent head teachers did not know about the school building construction committee. The above table clearly shows that 67.50 per cent head teachers admitted that they are responsible for the formation of the school management committee which is constituted after every two years in school while 32.50

per cent head teachers did not know about who is responsible for the formation of the school management committee. It may also be concluded that the majority (67.50 per cent) of head teachers admitted that they are responsible for the formation of the school management committee which is constituted after every two years in school but, some head teachers did not know about the rules and regulations of school management committee. It also shows that 78.25 per cent head teachers viewed that they took the signature of committee members on the oath letter while 21.25 per cent head teachers viewed that they did not take the signature of committee members on oath letter. It also confirms that 100 per cent head teachers opined that the details of income & expenditure of the financial year were given in general meeting of the school management committee in March month. It may be concluded that the majority (61.75 per cent) of head teachers opined that school management committee helped to organize the health checkup camps for school children.

Table 1.2

Sr. No.	Response	Always (%)	Sometime (%)	Never (%)
1	Helping in Admission of Deprived Children	55.00	42.50	2.50
2	Making Efforts to Enroll the Dropout Children in School	57.50	33.75	8.75
3	Providing Special Facilities to the Children with Special Needs	75.00	18.75	6.25
4	Helping in Achieving the Objectives of the SSA & RTE Act, 2009	52.50	47.50	00
5	Helping in Enrollment of all Children of the Age Group of 6 to 14	77.50	21.25	1.25
6	Helping in the Fulfillment of Basic Needs of the School	55.00	41.25	3.75
7	Helping in Improvement of Academic Achievement of Students	51.25	46.25	2.50

8	Attending the General Meetings of School Management Committee by Parents	67.50	32.50	00
9	Giving Information Regarding Meetings	100	00	00
10	Monitoring the Mid-Day Meal by School Management Committee Members	70.00	30.00	00
11	Inquiry about the Academic Progress of Students by Members	42.50	51.50	6.25

The above table depicts that 55.00 per cent head teachers opined that school management committee always helped in admission of the deprived children in proper class according to their age while 42.50 per cent head teachers opined that school management committee sometime helped in the admission of deprived children but, a few (2.50 per cent) head teachers opined that school management committee never helped in the admission of deprived children. It also indicates that 57.50 per cent head teachers viewed that school management committee always made the efforts to enroll the dropout children in school while 33.75 percent head teachers viewed that school management committee sometime made the efforts to enroll the dropout children but, 8.75 per cent head teachers viewed that school management committee never made the efforts to enroll the dropout children in school and also shows that 75.00 per cent head teachers responded that the facilities were always provided to the children with special needs in the school with the help of the school management committee while 18.75 per cent head teachers responded that the facilities were sometime provided to the children with special needs in the school but, 6.25 per cent head teachers responded that facilities were never provided to the children with special needs in the school. It also indicates that 52.50 per cent head teachers responded that the school management committee always helped to achieve the objectives of the SSA & RTE Act, 2009 while 47.50 per cent head teachers responded that committee sometime helped to achieve the objectives of the SSA & RTE Act, 2009. It also confirms that 77.50 per cent head teachers viewed that school management committee always helped in enrollment of all children of the age group of 6 to14 while 21.25 per cent head teachers viewed that committee sometime helped in enrollment of all children of the age group of 6 to14 but, few (1.25 per cent) head teachers viewed that committee never helped to enrollment of all children of the age group of 6 to14. It also observes that 55.00 per cent head teachers admitted that the school management committee always helped in fulfillment of basic needs of the school while 41.25 per cent head teachers admitted that committee sometime helped in fulfillment of basic needs of the school but, a few (3.75 per cent) head teachers admitted that the committee never helped in fulfillment of basic needs of the school.

It also shows that 51.25 per cent head teachers viewed that school management committee always helped to improve the academic achievement of students while 46.25 per cent head teachers viewed that committee sometime helped to improve the academic achievement of students but, a few (2.50 per cent) head teachers viewed that committee never helped to improve the academic achievement of students. It also depicts that 67.50 per cent head teachers responded that parents always attended the general meetings of the school management committee while 32.50 per cent head teachers responded that parents sometime attended the general meetings of the school management committee. It clearly shows that 100 per cent head teachers responded that they gave timely information of meetings to members. It also shows that 70.00 per cent head teachers admitted that members of the school management committee always monitored the Mid-Day Meal while 30.00 per cent head teachers admitted that members of the school management committee sometime monitored the Mid-Day Meal. It also shows that 42.50 per cent head teachers admitted that school management committee members always inquired about the academic progress of students while 51.25 per cent head teachers admitted that committee members sometime inquired about the academic progress of students but, a few (6.25 per cent) head teachers admitted that committee members never inquired about the academic progress of students.

Table No. 2: Problems Faced by Head Teachers Related to School Management Committee

Item No.	Problems	No. of Head Teachers	Percentage
1	Majority of the members not educated	40	51.25
3	No remuneration given to school management committee members for attending meetings	42	52.50
4	Training given at blocks and district level.	41	51.25
6	Lack of cooperation/coordination between school management committee members.	29	36.25
7	Some members were laborer so they unable to give time for school.	24	30.00

The above table shows that 51.25 per cent head teachers faced problem that members were not educated. So, they had no knowledge about functioning of school management committee. The table also confirms that 52.50 per cent head teachers faced problem regarding remuneration that no remuneration given to the school management committee members for attending meetings. So, they did not take interest to attend meetings. It also reveals that 51.25 per cent head teachers faced problem that the training was given at block and district level only as members were not able to attend the meetings at block and district level. It was observed that 36.25 per cent head teachers faced problem regarding lack of cooperation/coordination

between members of school management committee. It also showed that 30.00 per cent head teachers admitted that most of the members were laborer so they unable to give time for school.

Table No. 3: Suggestions Given by Head Teacher Regarding School Management Committee

Item No.	Suggestions	No. of Head Teachers	%
1	Members should be educated	52	65.00
3	Awareness programmes should be organized for members	32	40.00
4	Training should be given at school level	27	33.75
6	Active participation of members should be required	18	22.50
7	The tenure of school management committee should be increased	14	12.50

The above table shows that 65.00 per cent head teachers suggested that members should be educated because educated members can improve the functioning of school management committee. This also confirms that 40.00 per cent head teachers emphasized that awareness programmes such as seminars/workshops should be organized for school management committee members. This also indicates that 33.75 per cent head teachers suggested that training should be given at school level because members did not want to go for training at block level and 22.50 per cent head teachers suggested that there should be active participation of members in the school management committee and 12.50 per cent head teachers suggested that the tenure of the school management committee should be increased.

Conclusion:

It was observed from the analysis that all the head teachers knew about the school management committee constituted under RTE Act, 2009 and school management committee always helped to enroll all children of 6 to 14 age group. Head teachers admitted that they are responsible for the formation of school management committee which is constituted after every two years in school. Majority of head teachers admitted that only 50% school management committee members were attending the meetings, cultural programmes in school and committee member always check the quality of Mid-Day Meal and other activities of the school. Majority of head teachers also admitted that committee helped in the admission and cleanliness of the school. Majority of head teachers

viewed that the training was done in the block and district level so members did not want to go there. Most of the members were laborer so they unable to give time for school. Majority of head teachers suggested that all the members should be educated and remuneration should be given to committee members. Some head teachers suggested that awareness programmes should be organized for members and the tenure of school management committee should be increased. SMC is a step towards exploration of educational goals of 21st century but SMCs are not properly functioning according to this study. So there is a need to create a grievance redressal mechanism for its effective functioning. So that they can participate regularly in the meetings for empowerment of school.

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16. Emerging Technologies of the 21st century education

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Abstract

The 21st century is an era of technology, also termed the information age as during this century the world shifted from traditional practices to knowledge based practices fueled by information and communication technology(ICT). The advent of technological innovations across industries has been an important aspect of the 21st century which needed Emerging technologies. Emerging technologies represent technical advancements that indicate progressive developments within a sector for competitive advantage. The field of education is the most influenced with the goal of the mastery of information needed for 21st Century skills. The continuous advancement in technology in the 21st century is instrumental in evolving the nature of education from teacher-centered to student-centered. Learners need to develop the skills needed in the 21st century. To inculcate these required skills in students effectively, 21st century teachers must use multimodal content in an interactive, collaborative and techno-savvy method of teaching. Use of the Emerging technologies is disrupting the whole educational system and therefore is anticipating an ICT integrated teaching-learning process. ICT is an effective tool for this emerging learning paradigm, making the learner active and self-directed. This study draws attention to the emerging technologies that is shaping the schools and universities to become smart educational campuses fostering the best educational practices ever. This paper discusses applications of technologies like Artificial Intelligence, Internet Of Things and Blockchain in the educational system.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Technology literacy, ICT Education

Introduction

Emerging technologies are those that are currently being developed or will be developed in the next 5 to 10 years, and which will alter the business as well as social environment, hence emerging technologies have significant socio-economic implications towards a progressive future.

3D printing , Cancer vaccines, Nanotechnology, Robotics are commonly known examples of emerging technologies.[31]

Emerging technologies are characterized by radical novelty(in application even if not in origins), relatively fast growth, coherence, prominent impact, uncertainty and ambiguity.[26]

From the historical perspective, we know how the digital revolution has transformed society. We have witnessed the applications of digital technologies in the form of robots, mobile sensors, autonomous vehicles, and many such exciting innovations. 21st century inventions like

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smartphones, social media, GPS navigation, cryptocurrency are all outcomes of digital innovations. These inventions have touched so many aspects of our life, that today one cannot imagine a world without these.

The digital revolution created new opportunities for technical change and technological learning for industries.[19] The advent of technological innovations across industries has been an important aspect of the 21st century which needed Emerging technologies and the field of education is the most influenced.

The education systems of the 21st century must be ready for constant technological changes. It calls for change in the role of educators and learners, the methods of teaching-learning, as well as the nature of infrastructure. The systems must be equipped for inculcating the 21st century knowledge , skills and attitudes such as communication , critical thinking and problem solving, leadership, teamwork, etc.

In such a system, the role of teacher will change from knowledge transmitter to a learning facilitator, collaborator and mentor. Students in the learning process will have greater responsibility for their own learning as they search, discover, create, collaborate and communicate the knowledge with others for solving problems. To inculcate required knowledge and skills effectively, educators are using ICT integrated teaching and learning process.[5] The ICT tools used can be integrated effectively in the education system using emerging technologies. The continuous advancement in technology in the 21st century is instrumental in evolving the nature of education from teacher-centered to student-centered. In this paper, four emerging technologies of 21st century and their applications in education are presented.

Research Methodology

The methodology applied is descriptive in nature. Data is collected using secondary resources. The data has been collected from sources like research papers, web resources and other published material.

Literature review

1. Artificial Intelligence (AI):

Artificial Intelligence is focused on creating computer systems that simulate human intelligence. AI helps in the development of models for forecasting and decision making. Whether we are aware or not, AI is our new companion today. E.g. AI is used for searching results from Google, music suggestions by Spotify, and Facebook facial recognition.[36] Game playing, Expert systems, Language understanding and robotics are some areas in which AI is being developed for many years now.

Today, AI powered applications have a lot more impact on our everyday life. Accurate weather prediction using AI software, use of Robotic vacuum cleaners, safer transport using driverless cars,

increased Personal safety with Modern home alarm systems, improved medical care by Robotic surgery assistants to quickly and accurately passing the correct surgical tools to doctors are a few examples.

In the field of education, AI has the ability to transform many aspects of teaching-learning as well as educational systems. AI can create immersive virtual learning environments, produce “smart content,” ease language barriers, fill gaps between learning and teaching, create specialized plans for each student and much more. Some examples of AI tools are presented in table 1.

India is also using AI in the field of education."Unprecedented availability of data points in the second most populous country in the world combined with access to heavy computational power can turn India into one of the strongest beneficiaries of the AI wave" (NitiAayog, 2020) The target set under the Quality Education agenda states that by 2030, our nation must significantly increase the supply of qualified teachers. While it is not possible to fill a huge demand-supply gap in existing provision, it is possible that teachers will be made more efficient using AI.[10]

Following few ways are suggested

Real-time text to speech and text translation systems: can be used to spread information in regional languages. These can be integrated with DIKSHA, a digital infrastructure developed by MHRD or by e-PATHSHALA(The Hindu, 2020). The language barrier can be removed and the inter-operability of teachers in all states can be achieved. (epathshala, 2020).

Biometric authentication: Mundane functions like attendance and administrative tasks can be taken over by AI. For example, student biometric authentication and the records can be used to easily track for monitoring national indicators such as youth and adult participation rates and the proportion of men and women enrolled in higher education, technical and vocational education in turn to help monitor quality of education in schools (m2sys.com, 2020).

Chatbots: can be trained on subject matter and a good percentage of student doubts can be answered immediately, thus reducing the current workload of teachers for focusing on more creative activities (ai-chatbot-education, 2020)

TABLE 1: AI tools

AI Tool	Main feature	Advantage	University
Gradescope	AI-assisted Student-specific grading	Increased efficiency and fairness	Boston Univ. Stanford centre for learning
Nuance's Dragon Speech Recognition	Accessibility features Voice to assess student work Dictate class work with 99% accuracy	helping students who find it difficult to write or type	Univ of California Georgia Institute of Technology Univ of Texas Carnegie Mellon Univ
Ivy Chatbot	Integrations for Facebook, ERP, CRM, and SIS Become smarter over time	assist in many parts of the university process plan recruitment ability to develop specialized chatbots for each department	Partnered with over 125 colleges & univ (developed over 500 bots)
Altitude Learning	"Learner-centered" model that enables self-learning	An online platform for professional learning	Odyssey Stem Academy-CA Higher ground by Montessori
Cognii	Tvirtual tutor for K-12 and higher education institutions, also for corporate training	T improves critical thinking skills Adaptive personalization	California State University E Florida International University
Knowji	an audio-visual vocabulary application	designed for language learners	Many Universities
Carnegie Learning's Platforms	relies on AI and machine learning Mimics human tutors	helps students develop cognitive skills.	has won "Best Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning App" Award.

Automated grading: Natural language processing can be used on a large scale on platforms like DIKSHA, E-PATHSHALA and SWAYAM (NitiAayog, 2020).

Automatic content creation: for the vast online resources like e-learning websites (algorithmia.com,2017).

Personalization: personalized feedback and recommendations on a large scale for students can be possible.

In fact, AI-enabled educational infrastructure would bless each Indian student with a personalized tutor (hbr.org, 2019). AI can also be of help in increasing number of higher education enrollment ratio, ensuring that the majority of adults achieve literacy. (NitiAayog, 2020).eliminating gender inequality in education, supporting Inclusive Education for Children with Special Needs (CWSN) (modev.com, 2019).[24]

Some real life examples depict the promising picture of AI being used effectively in Indian education:[16]

- "The state of Andhra Pradesh had conducted a pilot to predict drop-outs based on past student scores and student backgrounds" as per Sarkar
- Personalized Learning using adaptive assessment software used for Class VIII students of Mount Zion School, Gangtok.
- Next Education, an edtech company in Hyderabad, developed an AI driven assessment platform that is used by more than 50 schools.
- IIM, Rohtak used Remote Proctoring while conducting its executive MBA entrance exam.

The sunny side of the picture is that in spite of all these, Teachers' jobs will never be at risk, instead AI programs can teach basic lessons or math skills, while complex knowledge transmission of social, emotional skills will be the domain of humans (GetSmarter Blog, 2019). Lots of articles in the media have repeatedly highlighted that students in India are denied of good quality education. AI can be a boon and a viable solution to this problem(blog.epravesh.com,2020).[34]

2. Blockchain

Blockchain is an indestructible, distributed ledger related with an asset that is created over the time, and remains with the asset. Bitcoin or cryptocurrency is a popular example of blockchain.

The main features of Blockchain are decentralization, immutability, security, smart contracts, payment registry and transparency.

A blockchain helps to keep data private and safe. Hence blockchain is utilized in applications like recording personal health data where privacy, flexibility, and authenticity are ensured. Blockchain has been useful in the management of the COVID-19 pandemic, in the form of a contact tracing system [30]. The Chinese University of Hong Kong proposed a concept of a blockchain-based vaccine passport [29].

The blockchain concept is used in various government application areas like Foreign aid, smart contracts, Law enforcement, Record keeping, Central banking, Public healthcare.

Following are some prominent cases:[8]

Organisation	Location	Use case
United Nations	New York	The United Nations World Food Program created Building Blocks, a platform using ethereum blockchain to deliver aid. It transferred cryptocurrency-based food vouchers to 10,000 refugees in Pakistan and one million refugees in Bangladesh and Jordan
GOVCOIN Systems	London, England	The UK teamed up with GovCoin in order to develop a blockchain for welfare payments.
ANKR	Berkeley, California	Ankr is a cloud-based blockchain infrastructure for businesses.
Denmark's Ministry Of Foreign Affairs	Copenhagen, Denmark	Denmark's Ministry of Foreign Affairs partnered with virtual currency platform Coinify to use blockchain in foreign aid delivery.

The characteristic of a blockchain as a distributed Public Ledger that can automatically record and verify records, is an essential requirement of the Education system where the transcripts, certificates need authentication for the employment procedure.[18] Blockchain's immutable ledger technology is ideal for storing academic data and records. Even educators have found the technology helpful for creating smart contracts, distributing student loan payments and sharing crypto incentives. These processes increase accountability, transparency and engagement in the edtech sector.[7]

The authors of NOTA(a Novel Online Teaching and Assessment scheme using Blockchain for emergency cases) mention advantages of using Blockchain technology for educational purposes such as:[4]

- Worldwide courses can be accessed anytime and ensuring, both students and teachers will always be updated.
- Responses to exams and scores will always be available, and cannot be changed.
- The incentive mechanism will encourage teachers to work more and be more productive.
- Students applications to a new degree will be more fluent as all their information and curriculum are already available on the blockchain.

Thus Blockchain enables students to completely own their records and manage their academic identities.

Furthermore, the blockchain, with its distributed ledgers, promises to improve educational institution management and administration. [11]

Some examples of blockchain based platforms are presented in following table :

Blockchain platform	Function
Sony Global Education (SGE) global assessment platform developed by IBM	to store, protect, and exchange information related to students' performance and progress
BitDegree , a gamified online education platform	connects students with teachers and employers. The system uses its own token and blockchain certificates and provides users with courses and learning incentives like tokenized scholarships
ODEM	offers direct connections with educators, courses, and access to professional opportunities that meet students' personal profile while, by the use of tokens, ensuring the validity of their continuing education certificates
Institute for Blockchain Studies	For Coursera MOOCs accreditation, applying a "pay for success" model. The system uses smart contracts and provides a proof-of-truth mechanism to confirm that the students who signed up completed the course, as well as a payment mechanism
Competencies and learning outcomes management Farah et al	to trace the performance of students for their activities. The system produces a learning block containing the total learning profile of each student.
Student-Centered Learning Blockchain (SCi-B), a three element system (E-Course, E-Portfolio, and E-Assessment) proposed by Purnama et al	can enhance the learning process and increase the credibility of student assessment.

3. Augmented Reality/Virtual Reality (AR/VR)

Augmented reality (AR) is an emerging technology that integrates digital information, such as text, images, videos, and 3D objects, into the real world.[2]

Virtual Reality is the use of computer technology to create a simulated environment which can be explored in 360 degrees. Unlike traditional interfaces, VR places the user inside the virtual environment to give an immersive experience. It uses VR headsets or closed head-mounted displays (HMDS) to completely insulate and transpose the user to an alternative world.[25]

At the preliminary stage of AR/VR development, heavy computers and large projectors were often used for presenting AR/VR effects. With the rapid development of handheld devices, smartphones and tablets are used so that users can experience AR/VR effects through their own handheld devices.[2]

Augmented reality is a technology, which seeks to enhance the virtual reality environment by integrating the real world with added virtual elements. These can include sounds, sensations, or images generated by a computer system. Augmented Reality brings virtual object to indirect view of user's real world environment for enhancing user's perception and interaction with the real world.[12]

VR/AR technologies are gradually transforming the learning experience. VR/AR technologies are remodeling the education system of today. Students enjoy 3D technologies and experience more engaging learning with AR/VR systems.

The necessity of practical learning in technical courses like engineering, medical, architecture, etc. is a major hurdle for online classes. Technological disruption plays a very important role in such cases. Emerging immersive technologies like AR/VR prove to be helpful in transforming the Indian higher educational system.[23]

It allows medical education without the need for live patients, and overcomes cost, availability, and ethical restrictions. It also gives novel and more effective ways at assessing medical knowledge and competency. These technologies have been used in outreach initiatives for recruiting interested secondary school students into the medical profession.[21]

4. Internet of things (IOT)

The IoT is a global physical network which connects devices, objects and things to the Internet infrastructure. The 'things' are able to interact with the internal and the external environment, and can exchange information through the information sensing devices according to specific protocols. Thus, IoT enables connectivity for anything and anyone to be networked around the world anytime, and anywhere using any network or any service to achieve the goal of intelligent identifying, tracking, and managing things . It is an extension and expansion of Internet-based

network, which expands the communication between human to human (H2H), human to things (H2T) or things to things.[37]

We can have a number of IoT applications in our daily life. Some of the examples are :

- Home automation, components management and security implementation.
- In tracking and scheduling the logistic service
- In the E-Health system spanning from blood pressure, heart rate monitoring to remote surgeries.
- In Environmental monitoring including air, water quality, soil, wildlife monitoring.
- In Infrastructure management and monitoring of urban and rural assets.
- In Smart parking, smart traffic control, a vehicle to vehicle communication etc.
- In Industrial projects in the food industry, agriculture, surveillance etc.[32]

Applications of IoT in education include: [22]

- SMART boards - an interactive whiteboard
- Class Dojo - an education app, allows parents to see student schoolwork via photos and videos - used in 95% of all K-8 schools in the U.S. and 180 countries and messages can be translated into 35 languages automatically.[15]
- voice command systems for teachers, speech to text-based note-taking systems for the students, smart security cameras, GPS tracker equipped school buses, disaster alarms and tablets, and smartphones with educational applications
- Automated Attendance Recording
- Safety in Premises - infrastructure to detect red flags for theft, abuse, sexual assault, and other crimes that can occur within the institution
- Distance Learning - online course material, open booklet-based assessment
- Enhanced Interaction and Productivity (e.g. revise the taught topic again at their own convenience from their educator's web portal)
- Special Education (e.g. can seek help from a system of sensor-connected gloves and tablet to generate verbal speech, translated from sign language which the teachers can use)

These features make education safer, convenient, and accessible for the students, teachers, and parents.

Conclusion

Education using modern technology like Artificial Intelligence, Blockchain, Augmented Reality-Virtual Reality and IOT is making the learning process more collaborative and engaging. An article by Schindler et al., 2017 states that "Technological application in education engages the student to involve in high-order thinking, develop communication and discussion, and reflect on

the gist of the content. It also enhances digital competency." [33] All of these skills are the required 21st century skills.

It is possible to design a Smart education solution using the emerging technologies to meet the requirements of all the stakeholders in an educational system. The smart education enabled by the emerging technologies will improve the classroom, campus, management and decision-making in an educational set-up. The effective adoption of technology can build a scalable as well as cost effective smart education solution. [9]

A Smart University is a university that utilizes innovation technology (ex. IoT, smart devices, etc.) within its organization to achieve its strategic objectives. Emerging technologies are valuable for converting traditional universities to smart universities. [3]

A statement of John Dewey "If we teach today's students as we taught yesterday's we rob them of tomorrow" (Agnello, White, & Fryer, 2006) sums up the importance of emerging technology in education system. [33]

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17. Comparative Study of Social skills Among the NSS Volunteers

Mrs. Priya Bhushan Kapadne²⁴, Dr. K.V.Deore²⁵

Abstract

21st Century is the age of competition, rapid growth & development. For living in such a century & creating our own identity in it, every student needs some abilities, skills that will definitely be helpful for them to succeed in their careers. The 21st Century has accepted 12 abilities or skills which are divided into three categories. Today's students supposed to imbibe these skills to achieve success in their field. Each skill is unique in how it helps students.

Firstly, Learning skills are related with four C's- Critical thinking, Creativity, Collaboration and Communication. Learning skills are related to the IQ or the mental processes. Secondly, Literacy skills (IMT) , that is Information literacy, Media literacy and Technology literacy which focus on how students can discern facts, publishing outlets, and the technology behind them. There's a strong focus on determining trustworthy sources and factual information to separate it from the misinformation that floods the Internet. Lastly, Life skills (FLIPS) the skills like Flexibility, Leadership, Initiative, Productivity and Social skills included in it which focus on both personal and professional growth of an individual.

For the present research study researcher has selected social skills among life skills. Through this present research study researcher wants to study the growth of social skills among the NSS (National Service Scheme) volunteers of a renowned institute. Social education through service is the main purpose behind NSS and the primary objective of NSS is to develop the personality and character of the student through voluntary community service. Under NSS many social activities, camp, drives were organised by many colleges here researcher wants to study the comparative status of social skills among the NSS second year volunteers and Non NSS students (S.Y.B.A/ B.Sc.B.Ed students)

Keywords: Social Skills, NSS volunteers Non NSS students

Introduction

21st Century is the age of competition, rapid growth & development. For living in such a century & creating our own identity in it, every student needs some abilities, skills that will definitely be helpful for them to succeed in their careers. The 21st Century has accepted 12 abilities or skills which are divided into three categories. Today's students supposed to imbibe these skills to achieve

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success in their field. Each skill is unique in how it helps students. According to a well-known European organization there are mainly six principles of education in the 21st century such as;

- Learning is the essential part of everyday human activity like our basic needs.
- Access to learning is now universal.
- Technology in learning provides flexibly to the learner
- Learning suppliers in the 21st century adopt new ways to fulfil maximum demands of their clients.
- Providing learning infrastructure plays an active role
- Collaborative learning plays a vital role in it.

If we carefully study all these principles we'll understand that they all are related to 21st century skills. In this research study researchers want to study social skills which come under the Life skill domain.

Various subjects are taught in the colleges. Through academics we want to inculcate various values, morals, discipline and many more things. Along with academics students should be aware about the various happenings in their surroundings. To achieve this goal many times colleges planned various educational and social activities. In this perspective researchers feel that NSS would be truly useful in student empowerment.

The present educational system is expected to develop the contemplative, mental and intellectual students. It is necessary that students should understand the society of which they are living. If a student understands the problems, needs and woes of the society he/she would truly understand the meaning of life. NSS has been helpful in making the students aware of the status of the society in our country. It is responsible to a large extent in moulding the character of the youth and also in cultivating the values of love, compassion and courage in them. NSS is a source of creative future social reformers.

According to researchers, NSS programs have this capacity to nurture our country's future and inculcate various skills in them which are adopted in the 21st century. For present research study researchers used the Social skill inventory (SSI) which was first introduced to the psychological research community by Riggio (1986).

Need

From the last two years researcher is appointed as a NSS Program Officer. During and post pandemic scenario researchers planned so many social activities in which NSS volunteers willingly contributed a lot. Under the NSS basically two types of programmes are conducted. The first type includes the regular activities and the other type is special camps. The objective of

both these programmes is to have a direct interaction between the student and the society and to coordinate the efforts of the student for the progress of the society. Every year each NSS volunteer spends 120 hours on NSS activities. This creates a curiosity in researcher's mind to check the social skills status of NSS volunteers by comparing it with the non NSS volunteers (regular S.Y.B.A/ B.Sc. B.Ed. students of Ashoka College of Education, Nashik)

Importance

In 1967 National educational policy of India decided that work experience and National Service should be made a part of education. In May 1969 in the joint meeting of the Ministry of Education and UGC it was accepted that National Service could be an effective medium for national integration. Accordingly in the 4th five year plan NSS was accepted as a pilot scheme and was started in a few chosen institutes and universities. On 24th September 1969, the Central Minister for education Dr.V.K Rao inaugurated the NSS which was started in 37 universities in India with 40,000 volunteers

For this present research study, Social skill inventory (SSI) was used to check the Social skills among the NSS volunteers and Non NSS students (S.Y.B.A/ B.Sc. B.Ed. students) of Ashoka College of Education, Nashik. Through such study, researchers get a chance to know the effectiveness of programmes which were planned and executed under NSS. In the 21st Century only teacher training institutes have the responsibility to create responsible teachers who will create a responsible future for our nation. Teacher training institutes are the best centres who strive hard to inculcate maximum 21st century skills among the student teacher. Present research is a small attempt to know the social skills among the NSS and non NSS students.

Title of Research

Comparative Study of Social skills among the N.S.S Volunteers.

Statement of Research

A comparative study of social skills among the NSS volunteers and Non NSS students of Ashoka College of Education, Nashik

Definitions

A-Conceptual Definitions

1. Social Skills:

Social skills are the skills we use to communicate and interact with each other, both verbally and non-verbally, through gestures, body language and our personal appearance.

2. Non NSS students:

Students those who are not a part of NSS program or various activities in academic year 2022-23

3. NSS volunteers:

Students who join National Service Scheme in academic year 2021-22

4. Comparative Study:

Comparative study is the act of comparing two or more things with a view to discovering something about one or all of the things being compared. This technique often utilizes multiple disciplines in one study.

5. Social Expressivity:

Social Expressivity refers to the skill with which individuals communicate or send messages to others. It has access to verbal expression and the ability to engage others in social discourse.

6. Social Sensitivity:

Social Sensitivity refers to the skills with which to receive and interpret the communicated message of others. It has the ability to interpret the verbal communication of others.

7. Social Control:

Social Control refers to the skills with which they are able to regulate and manage the communication process. Social control assesses role playing and social self-presentation.

B-Operational Definitions

1. Social Skills:

Social skills are a set of skills including cooperation, hard work understand other's problem or feel happiness, leadership qualities, etc.

2. Non NSS students:

S.Y.B.A B.Ed. and S.Y.B.Sc.B.Ed students of Ashoka College of Education those who are regular students but didn't join National Service Scheme in academic year 2022-23 (having no experience of social service)

3. NSS volunteers:

Ashoka College of Education's Final Yr.B.A B.Ed. and Final Yr. B.Sc. B.Ed. students who join the National Service Scheme in academic year 2021-22 and completed 18 months in it under SPPU. Students who physically and actively participated in various NSS activities.

4. Comparative Study:

For present research study, comparative study is a technique through which by making comparisons between NSS volunteers & Non NSS students of ACE researcher aims to check the status of social skills.

5. Social Expressivity:

Social Expressivity is an ability to initiate conversations with others. Socially expressive individuals can speak spontaneously.

6. Social Sensitivity:

Socially sensitive individuals are attentive, good observers and patient listeners. They are always conscious about social norms and rules.

7. Social Control:

Socially Control individuals are tactful, self-confident, socially sophisticated and wise.

Objectives

- To check Social Expressivity of NSS volunteers & Non NSS students of ACE
- To check Social Sensitivity of NSS volunteers & Non NSS students of ACE
- To check Social Control of NSS volunteers & Non NSS students of ACE
- To do comparative study of social skills of NSS volunteers & Non NSS students of ACE

Assumptions

NSS helps to develop the social skills of the volunteers.

Scope and Limitations

A. Scope:

- This research study is about NSS volunteers & regular students of ACE
- This research study focuses on three major aspects of social skills like Social Expressivity, Social Sensitivity and Social Control.
- A comparative study of social skills

B. Limitations:

- This research study is only limited to the NSS volunteers and regular S.Y.B.A/ B.Sc. B.Ed. students of Ashoka College of Education, Nashik
- The conclusions of research are depending on the data of respondents collected after the survey.

- Data conclusion is totally based on the responses given by the sample.

Research Method

This research is based on the Survey Method.

Objectives	Method	Sample	Methods of sampling	Tools of data collection
To check Social Expressivity of NSS volunteers & regular students of ACE	Survey	25 NSS volunteers & 25 regular students of ACE Total no. of respondent 50	Convenient, Purposive sampling method.	Social skills Inventory (SSI) standardise Psychological Test by Ronald E. Riggio and Dana R.Carney
To check Social Sensitivity of NSS volunteers & regular students of ACE	Survey.	25 NSS volunteers & 25 regular students of ACE Total no. of respondent 50	Convenient, Purposive sampling method.	Social skills Inventory (SSI) standardise Psychological Test by Ronald E. Riggio and Dana R.Carney
To check Social Control of NSS volunteers & regular students of ACE	Survey.	25 NSS volunteers & 25 regular students of ACE Total no. of respondent 50	Convenient, Purposive sampling method.	Social skills Inventory (SSI) standardise Psychological Test by Ronald E. Riggio and Dana R.Carney
To do comparative study of social skills of NSS volunteers & Non NSS students of ACE	Survey	25 NSS volunteers & 25 regular students of ACE Total no. of respondent 50	Convenient, Purposive sampling method	Social skills Inventory (SSI) standardise Psychological Test by Ronald E. Riggio and Dana R.Carney

Data Collection tools

For data collection Social skills Inventory (SSI) standardized Psychological Test by Ronald E. Riggio and Dana R.Carney was used. The SSI is designed to measure the position of basic

emotional and social communication skills. The SSI is based on a theoretical model of communication skills that presumes that there are three basic types of skills: expressive skills (encoding), sensitivity skills (decoding), and control skills (regulatory). The SSI consists of 6 skills that measure skills on two dimensions or two levels: emotional and social.

Data Analysis tools

For present research study, researcher has used following data analyse tools

Mean

Standard Deviation

Process:

The Social skills Inventory (SSI) standardised Psychological Test was used on two different groups the first one is NSS volunteers group and the second one is non NSS students of Ashoka College of Education, Nashik. The assurance was given to the respondent that their responses will be used for research purposes only. The SSI questionnaire along with the answer sheet was provided to the both respondents. The instructions were given to the respondent to solve each and every question by giving their best judgement on a five point scale. Sufficient time was provided to the respondent that is 30 to 45 minutes after that the responses were collected and the research tools were used on them to get the analysis. Finally a comparative chart was prepared to understand the difference between Social skill ratio among the NSS volunteers and non NSS students (S.Y.B.A/ B.Sc. B.Ed. students).

Data/ Factor Analysis of the SSI

Scale	NSS Volunteers (N=25)		Non NSS students (N=25)	
	M	SD	M	SD
EE	43.8	7.28	43.08	7.28
ES	59.12	11.5	45.68	7.48
EC	52.6	10.4	44.16	7.28
SE	56.6	13.17	52.44	13.15
SS	57.2	11.5	45.36	7.28
SC	52.8	10.51	49.32	7.28
Total E	155.52	29.18	132.92	22.04
Total S	166.6	35.18	147.12	27.71

Total Ex	100.4	20.45	93.52	20.43
Total Se	116.32	23	91.04	14.76
Total Co	105.4	20.91	93.48	14.56
Total SSI	322.12	64.36	280.04	49.75

Note. EE = Emotional Expressivity. ES = Emotional Sensitivity. EC = Emotional Control, SE = Social Expressivity, SS = Social Sensitivity. SC = Social Control

Findings

In this present research study, the conclusions are presented as per the objectives-

Objective 1: To check Expressivity of NSS volunteers & Non NSS students of ACE

Data Analysis:

In table 1. Total Expressivity mean of NSS volunteers is 98.4 whereas non NSS student's mean is 91.04. According to the Self-Description Inventory of SSI, NSS volunteers & Non NSS student's expressivity status is the same; both are in the medium category.

This indicated that NSS volunteers and Non NSS students are good in verbal and nonverbal communication. They have the ability to engage others in social interaction, initiate conversations with others or speak spontaneously. They are more energetic and emotionally charged as they can inspire others.

Objective 2: To check Sensitivity of NSS volunteers & Non NSS students of ACE

Data Analysis:

According to the table 1- Total Sensitivity mean of NSS volunteers is 116.32 whereas non NSS student's mean is 91.04. According to the Self-Description Inventory of SSI, NSS volunteers' Sensitivity status is in the higher category and & Non NSS students are in the medium category.

Sensitivity is related with the ability to decode or understand verbal along with non verbal cues. Sensitive individuals are attentive, Conscious about their public behaviour and the behaviour of others.

Objective 3: To check Control of NSS volunteers & Non NSS students of ACE

Data Analysis:

According to the table 1- Total Control mean of NSS volunteers is 105.4 whereas non NSS student's mean is 93.48. According to the Self-Description Inventory of SSI, NSS volunteers' Control status is in the higher category and & Non NSS students are in the medium category.

Control refers to skills like social self-presentation. Individuals high in Co are more tactful, self-confident, good emotional actors, particularly, socially sophisticated and wise. Their adjustment and flexible nature helps them to maintain balance in adverse situations also as they have the ability to control and regulate emotions.

Objective 4: To do comparative study of social skills of NSS volunteers & Non NSS students of ACE

Data Analysis:

According to the table 1- Total Control mean of NSS volunteers is 322.12 whereas non NSS student's mean is 280.04. According to the Self-Description Inventory of SSI, NSS volunteers' total SSI scale is in the higher category and & Non NSS students are in the medium category.

The total SSI scale indicates that NSS volunteers are more social and NSS programs help them to imbibe different social skills.

Conclusion

This present comparative research study shows that the social skills adoption in NSS volunteers is higher than Non NSS students of ACE. It also concludes that the NSS program is more effective to inculcate social values and to develop social skills among the volunteers. The NSS programme has a distinct role in college and social fields.

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18. Comparative study of Listening proficiency of B.A.B.Ed students and B.Sc.B.Ed students

Mrs. Smita Arjun Borade²⁶

Abstract

Skill is the ability to use one's knowledge effectively and readily in execution or performance. The skills are the talents and abilities one needs in order to complete a specific task. Whereas proficiency is a high degree of skill or expertise. Listening proficiency is the assessed proficiency of the individual in understanding a given spoken language. Listening skill will help the students to perform their task of listening and getting meaning as per their understanding but listening proficiency will help the students to identify literal meaning, to understand vocabulary, making inferences, identifying main idea, determining purpose, drawing conclusions, analyzing reasoning, finding evidence, summarizing the content, criticizing the ideas. Listening is fundamental skill in language learning. Listening skills helps to develop speaking, reading and writing skill. By understanding the importance of listening proficiency, researcher decided to compare listening proficiency of B.A.B.Ed students and B.Sc.B.Ed students. The objectives of the study are 1) To study listening proficiency of B.A.B.Ed students 2) To study listening proficiency of B.Sc.B.Ed students 3) To compare listening proficiency of B.A.B.Ed and B.Sc.B.Ed students. Survey method used for collecting data. Convenient sampling method is used to select sample.

Keywords: Listening proficiency

Introduction

Language is important part of culture that helps not only in the development of culture and transmission of culture. Language allows development and evolution of culture from generations to generations. This indicates that language has lot of importance in human's personal life and therefore occupies important place in education. At school level minimum three languages are taught namely mother tongue, national language(Hindi) and international language (English). English language is taught in schools formally. Naturally functional use of English is less or very limited. Like other languages, it includes Listening, Speaking, Reading and Writing that are basic skills of language learning.

Listening is the prime skill in language learning. Listening is also called as receptive skill as it helps in receiving information, knowledge. Listening is the primary means through which students' access information from the teachers, their classmates in school. Listening is the ability to receive accurately and interpret messages in the communication process. Generally, listening is

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the ability to identify and understand the speaker's saying, pronunciation, intonation patterns, vocabulary, grammar, grasping his meaning etc. There is difference between hearing and listening. Hearing is the listener's ability to recognize the language elements in the stream and sound and through the knowledge of phonological and grammatical systems of the language in order to relate to each other and understand the meaning.

Purdy (1997) defined listening as "the active and dynamic process of attending, perceiving, interpreting, remembering, and responding to the expressed (verbal and nonverbal), needs, concerns, and information offered by other human beings" (Ref: Journal of Language Teaching & Research, Vol.2, No.5, pp. 977-988)

Due to listening, students get knowledge about phonetics, tone pattern which helps for reading comprehension. Similarly, listening skill helps to develop speaking and writing skill. Whatever listened by an individual, if it is written in print or electronic media then it will be for long life. So listening skill makes effect on speaking, reading and writing.

The concept of listening proficiency

skill is the ability to make use of knowledge effectively. It is a talent to complete specific task whereas proficiency is a high degree proficiency. It is more advancement in skill and knowledge. Listening proficiency can be assessed. As listening is a fundamental skill in language learning, teacher should take more efforts to develop listening proficiency rather than just developing listening skill

Need and importance

When researcher was doing review of various research articles, she observed that few researches done listening skill as compare to speaking, reading and writing skill. Listening is the fundamental skill of language learning. Proficiency of listening skill helps to develop speaking, reading and writing skill. Researcher is an educator of college of education and teaches to student teachers. These student teachers will be future teachers. So to study their listening proficiency, researcher have chosen this topic for the study. Present research will help to understand at what level student teachers have developed their proficiency. It will help to plan various activities or programs to develop listening proficiency. It is useful for all the teachers and students. It will help the institution to make use of 21st century requirements in the institution

Title of the study

Comparative study of Listening proficiency of B.A.B.Ed and B.Sc.B.Ed students

Research questions

1. What is the level of the listening proficiency of B.A.B.Ed students?
2. What is the level of the listening proficiency of B.Sc.B.Ed students?

3. Is there difference between listening proficiency of B.A.B.Ed students and B.Sc.B.Ed students?

Objectives of the study

1. To study listening proficiency of B.A.B.Ed students
2. To study listening proficiency of B.Sc.B.Ed students
3. To compare listening proficiency of B.A.B.Ed and B.Sc.B.Ed students in terms of
 - i)Meaning of words
 - ii)Meaning of idioms
 - iii)Contextual meaning
 - iv)Memory based answers
 - v)Descriptive answers
 - vi)Overall listening proficiency

Hypothesis of the study

H0- There is no significant difference in scores on finding the meaning of words of B.A.B.Ed and B.Sc.B.Ed students

H0- There is no significant difference in scores on finding the meaning of idioms of B.A.B.Ed and B.Sc.B.Ed students

H0- There is no significant difference in scores on finding the contextual meaning of sentences of B.A.B.Ed and B.Sc.B.Ed students

H0- There is no significant difference in scores on finding the memory based answers of B.A.B.Ed and B.Sc.B.Ed students

H0- There is no significant difference in scores on writing the descriptive answers of B.A.B.Ed and B.Sc.B.Ed students

H0- There is no significant difference in total scores of B.A.B.Ed and B.Sc.B.Ed students

Methodology of the study

Objectives	Method	Sample	Sampling method	Data Collection Tools
1.To study listening proficiency of B.A.B.Ed students	Survey	25 B.A.B.Ed students	Convenience sampling	Researcher made questionnaire

1.To study listening proficiency of B.Sc.B.Ed students	Survey	25 B.Sc.B.Ed students	Convenience sampling	Researcher made questionnaire
3.To compare listening proficiency of B.A.B.Ed & B.Sc.B.Ed students	Survey	25 B.A.B.Ed & 25 B.Sc.B.Ed students	Convenience sampling	Researcher made questionnaire

Sample for the study

For the present study, researcher has used convenience sampling method. 25 students of B.A.B.Ed and 25 students of B.Sc.B.Ed are selected

Tools of the study

For the evaluation of descriptive question, researcher used researcher made rubric

Questionnaire

‘t’ value

Data Collection

Researcher has collected data with the help of questionnaire. For data collection 25 students of B.A.B.Ed and 25 students of B.Sc.B.Ed were selected.

Analysis of Data

Researcher has analysed data with the help of percentage and ‘t’ test value. for descriptive question rubric is used.

Objective1. To study listening proficiency of B.A.B.Ed students

Components	Below Average (Below 39%)	Average (40% to 59%)	Moderate (60% to 79%)	Excellent (80% above)
Meaning of words	10(40%)	0	9(36%)	6(24%)
Meaning of Idioms	7(28%)	0	7(28%)	11(44%)
Contextual meaning	2(8%)	7(28%)	0	16(64%)
Memory based question	4(16%)	13(52%)	0	8(32%)
Descriptive question	8(32%)	10(40%)	4(16%)	3(12%)
Summary	9(36%)	13(52%)	2(8%)	1(4%)

Objective2. To study listening proficiency of B.Sc.B.Ed students

Components	Below Average (Below 39%)	Average (40% to 59%)	Moderate (60% to 79%)	Excellent (80% above)
Meaning of words	6(24%)	0	10(40%)	9(36%)
Meaning of Idioms	6(24%)	0	9(36%)	10(40%)
Contextual meaning	5(20%)	5(20%)	0	15(60%)
Memory based question	3(12%)	12(48%)	0	10(40%)
Descriptive question	4(16%)	9(36%)	6(24%)	6(24%)
Summary	11(44%)	9(36%)	5(20%)	0

The figure outside bracket indicates the number of students and the figure inside bracket indicates the percentage of students

Findings

Objective1. To study listening proficiency of B.A.B.Ed students

1. 40% students of B.A.B.Ed have below average listening proficiency,36% students has moderate listening proficiency and 24% students have excellent listening proficiency with respect to meaning of words component
2. 28% students of B.A.B.Ed have below average listening proficiency,28% students has moderate listening proficiency and 44% students have excellent listening proficiency with respect to meaning of idioms component
3. 8% students of B.A.B.Ed have below average listening proficiency,28% students has average listening proficiency and 64% students have excellent listening proficiency with respect to contextual meaning
4. 16% students of B.A.B.Ed have below average listening proficiency,52% students has average listening proficiency and 32% students have excellent listening proficiency with respect to memory based answers
5. 32% students of B.A.B.Ed have below average listening proficiency,40% students have average listening proficiency, 16% students have moderate listening proficiency and 12% students have excellent listening proficiency with respect to descriptive answers
6. 36% students of B.A.B.Ed have below average listening proficiency,52% students have average listening proficiency, 8% students have moderate and 4% students have excellent listening proficiency with respect to summary question

Objective2. To study listening proficiency of B.Sc.B.Ed students

1. 24% students of B.Sc.B.Ed have below average listening proficiency,40% students has moderate listening proficiency and 36% students have excellent listening proficiency with respect to meaning of words component

2. 24% students of B.Sc.B.Ed have below average listening proficiency,36% students has moderate listening proficiency and 40% students have excellent listening proficiency with respect to meaning of idioms component

3. 20% students of B.Sc.B.Ed have below average listening proficiency,20% students has average listening proficiency and 60% students have excellent listening proficiency with respect to contextual meaning

4. 12% students of B.Sc.B.Ed have below average listening proficiency,48% students have moderate listening proficiency and 40% students have excellent listening proficiency with respect to memory based questions

5. 16% students of B.Sc.B.Ed have below average listening proficiency,36% students have average listening proficiency, 24% students have moderate listening proficiency and 24% students have excellent listening proficiency with respect to descriptive questions

6. 44% students of B.Sc.B.Ed have below average listening proficiency,36% students have average listening proficiency and 20% students have moderate listening proficiency with respect to summary question

Objective3. To compare listening proficiency of B.A.B.Ed and B.Sc.B.Ed students

1. There is no significant difference in listening proficiency of B.A.B.Ed and B.Sc.B.Ed students at 0.5 and 0.1level in terms of meaning of words. So null hypothesis is accepted

2. There is no significant difference in listening proficiency of B.A.B.Ed and B.Sc.B.Ed students at 0.5 and 0.1level in terms of meaning of idioms. So null hypothesis is accepted

3. There is no significant difference in listening proficiency of B.A.B.Ed and B.Sc.B.Ed students at 0.5 and 0.1level in terms of contextual meaning. So null hypothesis is accepted

4. There is no significant difference in listening proficiency of B.A.B.Ed and B.Sc.B.Ed students at 0.5 and 0.1level in terms of memory based answers. So null hypothesis is accepted

5. There is no significant difference in listening proficiency of B.A.B.Ed and B.Sc.B.Ed students at 0.5 and 0.1level in terms of descriptive answers. So null hypothesis is accepted

6. There is no significant difference in total scores of B.A.B.Ed and B.Sc.B.Ed students at 0.5 and 0.1level. So null hypothesis is accepted

Conclusion

Listening skill will help the students to get meaning as per their understanding but listening proficiency will help the students to identify literal meaning, to understand vocabulary, identifying main idea, recall memory, drawing conclusions, finding evidence, summarizing the content,

criticizing the ideas. Enhancing listening proficiency is the need of 21st century teachers and students. Students need to be given proper directions.

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19. 21st Century Skills and Social Science Education

Ms. Sarita soy²⁷

Abstract

Education is the most powerful weapon you can use to change the world. Said by Nelson Mandela .Education is a means of fullness .Education has always been recognized, through with varying degree of conviction, as a vital element for individual self-fulfillment and development of society .Education ensures excellence and ascent of humankind.

By Education I mean an all-round drawing out of the best in the child and man-body ,mind and spirit; by Gandhi .Well defined by Gandhi ,education is an essential and perhaps unique vehicle of vibrant advancement of humanism has been critically explained .Education sensitized in values in education adorned in elegance. So we need education for 21st century and more education skills. So, we can say the role of education in 21st century to educate cradled and nurtured in every aspects of life .The Indian context may be a pointer to the opposite role of education for cultivation of perennial values for effulgence in fullness through 21st century skills and social science education .Well said by the Aristotle 'man is a social animal ' .and through education we ensures excellence and ascent of humankind.

Keywords: Education ,cultivation ,development

Introduction

21st century skills means a set of skills that students need to develop in order to succeed in the 21st century. Skills which are highly advanced and sophisticated. The skills revolve around technology and scientific world and also critical thinking advanced learning and decisions making skills.

The term '21st century skills' is generally used to refer to certain core competencies such as collaboration digital literacy, critical thinking and problem solving that advocates believe schools need to teach to help students thrive in today's world .21st century skills refer to the knowledge life skills, career skills habits and traits that are critically important to student success in today's world ,particularly as students move on to college the workforce and adult life.

In today's world, its more important than ever for students to be able to communicate and work with people from other cultures.21st century learning helps students develop the global perspective they need to be successful in an increasingly connected world.

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21st century education skills is term used to describe a shift in education from the traditional methods of the past to a more modern approach .This new approach focuses on preparing students for the future by teaching them the skills they need to a successful in a global economy.21st century education skills is not memorization or recitation but critical thinking creativity and collaboration .It is about preparing students for the real world, not just for a test.

21st century skills is essential for every individual to be successful in a ever-changing global economy.21st century skill is not simply an update to traditional education it is fundamental shift in how we think about and prepare students for their future.

21st century learning more than just the 3Rs-reading, writing and arithmetic but 21st century skill emphasizes the importance of critical thinking, creativity ,collaboration and communication skills.21st century skills cannot occur in a traditional classroom setting. Students need to be actively engaged in their learning with all skills and have opportunities to apply what they have to face the real-world situations.

21st century skills is broad set of knowledge ,skills ,work habits ,and character traits that are believed by educators ,school reformers ,college professors employers ,and others to be critically important to success in today's world .The 21st century skills can be applied in all academic subject areas ,and in all educational, career and civic settings throughout a student's life.

21st century skills may be defined ,categorized, and determined differently from person to person ,place to place or school to school. Some of the knowledge, skill, work habits ,and character traits commonly associated with 21st century skills.

- Critical thinking ,problem solving, reasoning ,analysis ,interpretation, synthesizing information
- Research skills and practices ,interrogative questioning
- Creativity ,artistry ,curiosity ,imagination ,innovation ,personal expression
- Perservance,self-direction,planning,self-discipline,adaptability,initiative
- Oral and written communication, public speaking and presenting listening
- Leadership ,teamwork ,collaboration ,cooperation ,facility in using virtual workspaces
- Information and communication technology literacy, media and internet literacy, data interpretation and analysis ,computer programming
- Civic, ethical and social-justice literacy
- Economic and financial literacy entrepreneurialism

- Global awareness, multicultural literacy ,humanitarianism
- Scientific literacy and reasoning
- Environmental and conservation literacy, ecosystem understanding
- Health and wellness literacy ,including nutrition ,diet ,exercise and public health and safety

So, all these skills are intended to help students keep up with the lightning-pace of today's modern markets. Each skill is unique in how it helps students, but they all have one quality in common.

According to The World Health Organization identifies the fundamental life skills as decision-making and problem solving, creative thinking and critical thinking ,communication and interpersonal skills ,self- awareness and empathy ,and coping with emotions and stress. The WHO focuses on broad psychosocial skills that can be improved over time with conscious effort.

We can categories 21st century skill into three categories:

- Learning skills; The four C's are by far the most popular 21st century skills. These skills are also called learning skills. Learning skills include, critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, communication.
- Literacy skills; Literacy skills are the next category of 21st century skills are: Information literacy, Media literacy, Technology literacy. This skills give them better understanding to the technical world to know more. They might even guide its future.
- Life skills; life skills are the final category, also called FLIPS, these skills all pertain to someone's personal life, but they also bleed into professional settings. The five 21st century life skills are:

Flexibility, leadership, Initiative, productivity, social skills. With 21st century skills, our students will have the adaptive qualities they need to keep up with a good environment and give them life readiness. The American Association of School Administrators argues:

“Being life ready means students leave high school with the grit and perseverance to tackle and achieve their goals by demonstrating personal actualization skills of self-awareness, self-management, social-awareness, responsible decision-making ,and relationship skills. Students who are life ready possess the growth mindset that empowers them to approach their future with confidence, to dream big and to achieve big.”

Importance of Social Science Education

Aristotle the legendary Greek philosopher said, ” Man is by nature a social animal; an Individual who is unsocial naturally and not accidentally is either beneath our notice or more than human. Society is something that precedes the individual. ‘Man cannot live alone. He must satisfy certain

natural basic needs in order to survive. He has to enter into relationships with his fellowmen for living a life. No man can break the shackles of mutual dependence. The human beings interact with each other on a daily basis, having a deep impact on each other's life. The human infant ,at his birth is not fully aware of his own self. He develops the idea of self through the interaction with others and society.

Man is social because he depends on social heritage which is a mixture of customs beliefs and ideals etc. Society preserves social heritage and transmits it from one generation to another. Social heritage molds man's attitudes, beliefs, morals and ideals. It is said that man only becomes man among men. Man is born with some inborn potentialities. It is the social heritage, which his innate potentialities express themselves in society. Emotional development, intellectual maturity is not possible without society. Therefore, society determines our mental equipment's. It shapes our identity our thought and our emotions.

Man has a variety of needs. If he leads a cooperative life with his fellow beings in society he can easily get his needs fulfilled. Necessity compels man to live in society. Many of his needs will remain unsatisfied if he does not lead a cooperative life with his fellow beings. Without proper care he cannot develop himself. It is society which extends protection, attention, and opportunities necessary for his survival and growth. The society fulfills various needs like educational, protection nurture opportunity and equipment's etc. The need for self-preservation which is felt by everyone is fulfilled by society. So, the prolonged dependence of human child compels him to live in society.

Society is important for every individual in a variety of area, such as politics, citizenship, cultural awareness, and some general knowledge of world affairs. Society provide family for all human being live together; family is the first school of any individual. After family school will play role of shaping the individual and take care of their development. we know over all development come from various academic discipline, various discipline like science, math's, literature, and social science. Social science is the study of how people interact with one another.

Social science, a group of academic disciplines dedicated to examining human behavior and specifically how people interact with each other, behave develop as a culture, and influence the world. Social science is a group of academic disciplines that focus on how individuals behave within society. Social science is to teach students to become good citizens. Social sciences connect students with the real world. In today's interconnected world, students must be prepared to interact with people of all cultures and communities, and social sciences prepares them for this. Students will need to interact with others from different cultural and socioeconomic backgrounds. Students must study how society works, and how people work in a society. Students learn skills through social studies that help them succeed in further education as well as life. Students become better learners because they are asked to use analysis, critical thinking, critical thinking is one of the most important skill to succeed in life. Students should know responsibilities and values in society.

Students need an understanding of history, political science, culture, and all humanities to be able to understand why it is important to be a good citizen. Students should be exposed to cultures far beyond what they experience personally every day. We need to learn cultural understanding and interaction with people of all background in the future. Students also learned economics, young people understand how their financial decisions have an impact on their future, as well as the future of society. Studying social sciences gives students an understanding of the real world around them. Students learn about places, cultures, and events around the world. From social sciences, students learn about government, political ideas, country economy and resources, and more. Students gain political skills by analyzing and evaluating existing systems and imaging the future of the place in which they live. Learning about history is what makes it possible to learn from the past and plan. So, we can say the reason for teaching social science is for them to be able to participate civilly in a democratic society. When children start as early as kindergarten to understand the world around them, and schools should follow suit and start teaching social science concepts such as communication, critical thinking and culture as early as possible.

Conclusion:

21st century skills refer to the knowledge, life skills, career skills, habits, and traits that are critically important to student success in today's world. 21ST century skills focus more on making sense of that information sharing and using it in smart way. 21st century skills require to succeed in the new age of learning environment. 21st century skills require some core competencies like collaboration, critical thinking, digital literacy and problem solving that is requisite for students to thrive in today's world. 21st century skills like critical and creative thinking community participation, cultural understanding, broadens global perspective and promotes values formation. All these skills still relevant in society that is related to social science education. Social science education develops skills such as critical thinking, creative thinking, communication skills, collaboration, cultural awareness leadership, citizenship, empathy, integrity.

Hoping in on 21st century skills is essential to ensuring students civic life and career with the help of social science education.

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20. Flipped Classroom and Moodle: An aid to support teaching and learning

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Abstract

Over the last two digits, technology has drastically changed the way people live, work communicate and learn (Fondo & Konstantinidis, 2018). Besides, Rapid changes in knowledge created as massive need for teaching and learning. Teachers are adopting new techno pedagogy's approaches for the beneficial of the learners.

New technologies approaches are emerging in recent years that are presenting positive effect on the students learning. In recent years flip classroom approach has gained widespread popularity and there is growing body of literature that is investigating the implementation of this method. Flipping a course simply means reversing classroom lecture into self-paced and collaborative learning environment. Online learning material is provided to the student in order to gain necessary knowledge before in class discussion while classroom time is utilised for the clarification of misconceptions and doubts. This paper presents design consideration for arranging flip classroom that is pre-class, In-class and Post-class instructions and discuss how Moodle platform help in facilitating communication and information sharing in these classroom. This paper concludes with a discussion of the guidelines and challenges in implementing flipped classroom in virtual learning environmental like Moodle.

Keywords: Flipped classroom, Instructional approach, Online learning Platform, Moodle

Introduction

The technology movement has always been the catalyst of change from electricity to computer from computer to internet and internet to 5G networks. As these technologies are adopted and creating changes in our society with all the connected channels. Our education system is not excluded from these technological changes these technological advancement affect our lifestyle and educational practices.

By the production of new knowledge with the help of new technology in this 21st century our educational system is changing our teacher centred to learner centered by adopting new technology enabled approaches. Online learning rapidly taking shape in our schools and college and covid 19 phases is the successive example of online learning. Where every school, College, university is fully depended on the online learning online learning platform online content delivery and self-learning habits.

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National Education Policy, 2020 also emphasis on Online Mode of Education for the purpose of arranging the building of digital infrastructure, a dedicated unit will be created in the Ministry of Education to look after the e-education needs of different education levels. Since technology is rapidly changing, it is the need of the hour to encourage an ecosystem that creates solutions for solving India's challenges of scale, equity and evolve in keeping up with the rapid changes in technology.

As a technology – enhanced pedagogy is gaining popularity in recent years (Enfield, 2013). A new Techno enhanced pedagogical approach come across that is flipped classroom that promote self-learning habits in learners in flip classroom the traditional lecture and homework sessions are inverted an important study materials are provided to the student before the classroom with the help of any online learning platform like Moodle, Edmodo etc. in order to gain necessary knowledge before class, while Class time is utilised to clear students misconceptions and doubt and give clarification of that contain an application of that material. The contain material may be in the form of videos, audios ,PPTs or any other format that is delivered for the pre class activity while class time is used for collaborative group work group discussion or group activities.(Berret, Managan, Neshyba, Talbert & young 2015).

Flip courses does not mean only the use of videos as a content material but it mainly focuses on putting learners at the centre and give full attention to the learning progress(Bergman & Sams ,2012). In other word we can say that flip classroom is to create learner centre environment that enable students in higher order thinking skills. On the other hand flip classroom provide the opportunity to the teacher to create activities, assignment content for the learner based on the diversification of their interest and needs.

The most beneficial aspect of flipped classroom is peer interaction and collaborative activities when students share their ideas with each other and offers their perspective on the content it helps them to gain deeper knowledge and also help them in resolving their misconception regarding content.

Design and implementation of flipped classroom

As the time is changing, educators are creating new varieties of teaching that suits the needs of their learners. The effectiveness of teaching and learning depend on the proper planning and designing of instruction activities so as we know that flip classroom is focusing on student centred learning rather than the just teaching tends to ignore students teachers two way interaction. So the design of flipped classroom is divided into – Pre class Instruction, In -class Instruction, Post class Instruction. Figure 1 show the generic framework of the flipped classroom.

Figure 1: The Flipped classroom Framework

Pre class Instructions

Initially it is important for the teacher to decide how to distribute the learning process in the 3 phases of the flip classroom. teacher decide that which part of the content accomplished successfully in pre class instruction ,which topic is most suitable to deliver online and which type of activity we prefer in post class session. After deciding pre class, post class, in class distribution Instructors to decide the mood of delivering the content which platform we can use to deliver material in Meaningful way (like Moodle, Edmodo etc) .

Another important aspect of pre class instruction preparation is how to motivate learners to involve in self-regulated learning so they can complete their pre class task in order to ensure that students watch the video content at home and they are coming to attend the class with full preparation, instructor should use exercise (online) diagnostic test and (obligatory) hands -ins to judge their performance.

In class instructions

First of all, instructor should finalize in class activities, play how much time it received to complete one activities, how much time will spend on lecture (if any) and what is the role of instructor using and What is the role of instructor during in class session. Teachers should design the in class activity in such a way that it will fulfil the aim of the learning and to encourage meaningful learning. Teachers should keep in mind that all activities that is performing in the class should be integrated with out of class activities so it can be helpful in optimal learning.

Post class instructions

An activity that was done during in class instruction is the continuation of post class activities. It is like a supplementary activity that is required to carry out by the students. Post class activities

are carried out to check the students learning and understanding and give reflection over their own practice of that topic. Post class performance of the students also helps the educator in assessing the effectiveness of the new instruction approach adopted by the teacher.

Flipped classroom and the Moodle

Moodle is an open source learning management system (LMS) that allow Educator to create their online content for the learners. Basically Moodle act as an active communication between educator and learner. The main function of Moodle includes three aspects- Administrator, educator and Learner.

Administrator maintains the entire model platform, administrator is fully responsible for the site information, it includes course registration, course management, course enrolment, creating a new course, appointment of teacher, and many more management function as shown in the figure

Figure 2: The Functions of Administrator in MOODLE

The educator is responsible to design a course content, make preparation for the course content like build quizzes consisting of different questions types including multiple choice questions True and False etc., After that we prepared for the implementation and then evaluate the students

learning and give feedback of their work. Teachers play a significant role in the whole teaching learning process. Teachers should be active and good in teaching management so they can view the log on the site, provide feedback to the student, solve the problem of the students and provide a significant answer for the questions received by the students.

Figure 3: The Functions of Educator in MOODLE

Learner’s responsibility is to download and read the content provided by the educator on the platform. Learner take part in the group discussion provided on the platform they can share their work progress with teacher.

Therefore we can say that Moodle is an information exchange platform that is very helpful in flip classroom. Apart from that model can provide information to educator and help in hosting online educational activities which are very relevant for flipped classroom. Moodle report that is generated by the Teacher is useful for checking students' performance and login of the Moodle land gives insight for the flip classroom.

Challenges in implementing flipped classroom based on Moodle

Challenge: unfamiliar Instructional Approach

Most of the students as well as the teacher are unfamiliar with the new concept of flipped classroom and Moodle. Students may not unaccustomed to learn New material or contain outside of the classroom they may not understand the basic logic of using Moodle in the teaching learning process.

Suggestion: Before flipping the classroom strengthen teachers- students communication

If a student does not understand the basic logic and benefit of any new instruction method or technique they may resist accepting the changes. So before flipping the classroom, teacher suit communicate with the students, explain the purpose and benefit of the flipping the classroom and convey them how this new approach help them to learn more thoroughly and effectively.

Additionally, teachers should give proper time to the students to learn how to be successful in the new format of learning. Teachers should provide adequate instructions time to time to the students that how to use Moodle platform, how they can enrol in the course provided on the Moodle, How they get contained material from the Moodle platform and how to play and pause the video content and many more.

Challenge: Disengagement during pre-class instructions

Some students become disengaged while watching the long video they did not keep attention on the video if the video is too long and do not watch the video in its entirety. Some student's complaint that video is impersonal so they feel disconnected from the screen .As a result, Student did not watch the video properly and they develop miss concepts regarding concepts. So poorly developed pre class instruction material is a big challenge in developing flip classroom.

Suggestion: Take proper training and practice cognitive theory before production video content.

Teachers should research properly in multimedia learning and in designing video content. Keep in mind that students have a proper engagement time of about 6 minutes while watching the video. So design your content in short segments and conclude your video content in 6 minutes. And if some topics are in length format break them in short segments and design them properly.

Challenge: Overwhelming workload for students

Previous study results shows that some students complain that flip classroom exceed their workload as they have to engage in pre class activities and they have to complete this activity in their free time at home.

Suggestion: Retain the workload of traditional classroom

Before framing the pre class activities teachers should estimate the time requirement to complete the pre class activities as compared to the traditional homework. We have to keep in mind that flipped classroom should maintain the same amount of workload as a traditional course. So before giving any assignment on the model the assignment is in concise form and video content is not exceed from the 10- 15 minutes.

Challenge: Lack of out-of- class support

Some student's complaint that they are not free to ask their queries during pre-class activities and this leads to misconception or knowledge gap an effect there in class activities performance.

Suggestion: Provide students Flexible communication platform for out of class support

It is difficult for a student to learn you contain in isolation. students need extra out of class support in flip classroom create online discussion forum on Moodle this will help students to communicate with the educator and the peer group also and instructors also assist them and provide necessary assistance outside of the class.

Challenge: Unfamiliar instructional technique for teachers

If you previous studies have found those teachers are not familiar with this new approach of flipped classroom they do not understand the technique of this approach although teachers also feel difficulty in operating online learning platform like model, blackboard, canvas, Edmodo etc. Teachers complain that it is an extra workload to create the videos, audios, activities and to operate the Moodle or any other online learning platform.

Suggestion: Increased professional development training

As we know that online learning is growing popularity day by day. So it is beneficial to increase pre service teacher's instructions. Flipped classroom approaches also popularity gaining approach nowadays so training in videos construction, designing a Lesson plan for flipped classroom, adopting online learning platform could expose new teachers to adopt new diverse instruction method. On the other hand, teachers who are already flipping their classroom should initiate other colleagues to adopt this new approach and development material collaboratively, with group of teachers working together.

Challenge: Limited student's accountability for pre class activities

One of the difficult task in adopting flip classroom is to motivate and monitor the participation of students in the pre class learning activities., the success of flip classroom approach is depend on

the pre class activities and inadequate preparation may dramatically reduce the performance of the students in the in class activities.

Suggestion: Incorporate a learning management system that includes communication

Gamification, seems positive effect on the motivation of the students and increase their engagement in self-regulated learning activities. Moodle learning management systems have built in Game elements we use these specification with our students so they kept motivated to get involved in their pre class activities.

Conclusion

The national curriculum framework 2005 strongly advocated for the child centred pedagogical approach so that student's participation is increased in the classroom. The right to Education Act 2009 also re-emphasise the use of their student centred practices they also recommend the shifting away from the rigid classroom teaching structure to the flexible learning environment. According to Mishra et al. (2020), the implementation of e-Learning in the field of education began with UGC, MHRD and university and colleges initiatives. Motivation plays a vital role in the adoption of e-Learning platforms for fulfilling the needs of the learners.

National Education Policy, 2020 also emphasis on Online Mode of Education for the purpose of arranging the building of digital infrastructure, a dedicated unit will be created in the Ministry of Education to look after the e-education needs of different education levels. While in this paper we have discussed about the various aspect of flipped classroom and we have also discussed the various features of model that can be very helpful in creating effective and engaging flipped classroom. The flip classroom approach it seems to be an important pedagogical approach in increasing student achievement, improving student motivation. However, the implementation of flip classroom shows some challenges also. Initially, teachers face problem in uploading videos in Moodle and student also face issues with playing instructional video in Moodle .Difficulty in assessing instruction material demotivate a student to work on Moodle. As the previous researches results shows that despite of model great potential learner do not use model effectively as a communication channel but mainly perceive it as a repository of learning materials (Costa, Teixeira & Alvelae 2012) .Therefore it is recommended, that if educator is using Moodle as a delivering flip classroom material, they have to provide proper guidelines for the students for the use of Moodle And introduce the possibilities of this environment to the learner. For future research it is interesting to investigate how teacher's and student experiences in such learning environment in flip classroom and how other platform is helping in creating effective flip classroom environment.

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21. Beyond Networking - Use of Social Media for Language Teaching and Learning

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Abstract

We live in times when social media has permeated the weft and warp of our lives. Teachers as leaders of the knowledge economy, can no longer deny the impact social media, used in the right amount with the right intention can have in imparting education. Social media platforms have created an exciting realm in the digital environment which can be tapped to invigorate and enhance new-age learning. With increasing access and a considerable drop in operation costs, social media platforms sometimes work better than costly apps and language learning software. The study was conducted at the undergraduate level with students of engineering in Mumbai city. The sample comprised 220 students. A survey was conducted to ascertain the impact of social media platforms on learning the English language and communication. The study findings can serve as a fundamental indicator for implementing pedagogical reformations. Another equally crucial pedagogical implication is to design and provide professional development and training sessions to both students and educators on the ultimate utilization of social media as instructional technologies in the context of English language teaching and learning.

Keywords: Social media, language, learning, teaching, digital, environment

Introduction

The moment the word ‘social media’ is uttered many in the field of education develop cold feet and a sense of aversion for a platform which seems to have influenced young learners in a negative way. Studies have proven that many young students with the privilege of access to social media in particular and the internet in general waste their time indulging in either unhealthy particles like stalking, trolling and other means of online abuse or simply lurking around, trying not to miss out on the happening across their circles as the fear of missing out (FOMO) is a major deterrent in their lives. Social media platforms which provide the flexibility and ease of creating video content are also used and abused by youngsters to create content to fulfil their hidden aspirations of glamour, instant fame and popularity through likes and followers and posts and reels becoming viral. It is a known and accepted fact that the cell phone is now like an extended limb for modern-day youth and they cannot perceive their lives without it. Keeping in mind the largely ubiquitous presence of the cell phone and social media in our lives, educators as knowledge leaders can no longer ignore the immense and exciting possibilities social media platforms offer and use social media for teaching learning practices.

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Social media Platforms for Teaching Learning

Several studies conducted across the globe speak about how social media platforms have created new avenues to enhance the teaching-learning process. Platforms like Instagram and Snapchat provide the opportunity to present visual material with supporting text and also provide the opportunity for educators to use these mediums to make students aware of means by which texts can be changed to visuals and visuals to text providing ample opportunities for intersectional use of aspects of language and visual presentation and representation. LinkedIn can be used to teach aspects of formal and business communication, Twitter to present thoughts in a compact and lucid manner and Facebook and WhatsApp to create groups for dissemination of information, sharing of resources and ideas and as discussion boards for the entire class or groups created for specific purposes. Because of the ubiquitous nature of social media, many researchers have used and recommended the use of social media for uploading and sharing educational content like videos etc. to complement and enhance classroom learning and facilitate the speed of communication (Everson et al., 2013; Greenhow & Robelia, 2009; Roblyer et al., 2010). Balakrishnan and Lay (2016).

The use and success of social media platforms in the teaching-learning process is also directly proportional to the awareness of the teachers of the learners' style of learning and the awareness of teachers about these styles. Students who have limited exposure to the English language can be encouraged to use social media platforms, especially platforms like YouTube to listen and watch content explicit to language acquisition and hence enhance their English language and communication skills. Chartrand (2012. 150). Balakrishnan and Lay (2016) speak about the Social Learning Theory (SLT), which posits that learning is most effective when learners are allowed to observe and interact with other learners, as well as form or participate in small study groups compared to the lecturers' teaching styles (Bandura, 2002; Gong et al., 2014). They argue that "this theory has become popular with the widespread use of social media and mobile technology" (Balakrishnan & Lay, 2016, p. 810). Out of the three types of learning styles – participatory, independent, and collaborative – Balakrishnan et al. (2015) state that students with a participatory learning style might favor Facebook and YouTube as learning tools as they permit them to acquire information anywhere and virtually instantaneously. Independent learners, too, can benefit from social media, as these students tend to rely on themselves in retrieving information when they can access it, either through Facebook or YouTube. Umrani-Khan and Iyer (2009; cited after Balakrishnan and Lay, 2016) argue that independent learners prefer to do things in a self-paced manner and work on projects that appeal to their specific interests. The fact that social media platforms are available for easy use and reference can make it possible for them to design and make their own study schedules. Social media platforms and applications available on the internet act as excellent tools for collaborative learning as students can indulge in sharing of information and also healthy discussions on topics of common interest.

Theoretical Framework

One of the major theoretical frameworks used in this project was that of Experiential learning which talks about the philosophy and methodology of purposefully engaging with students with the aim of direct experience and focused reflection in order to increase knowledge, develop skills and clarify values (Wurdinger and Carlson 2010). The basic principle being learners pick up more by action and doing as there is an intimate relationship between education and actual experience. Educational psychologists like John Dewey (1952) have emphasized the importance of experiential learning through problem-solving and critical thinking. The idea is to take an informed step from structured classroom instructions which at times leave the learners less motivated and less involved to a more cooperative and learner-centric environment where the teacher plays the role of a facilitator, providing the necessary handholding and scaffolding to students in a semi-structured approach designing instructions in such a way as to facilitate maximum interaction between the learners as they grapple with real-world problems and direct experiences.

With more emphasis on the process rather than the product of learning (UC Davis, 2011) As the focus of experiential learning is on the process a lot of importance is given to -

1. Doing - experiencing/ learning
2. Sharing - speaking, learning, writing, discussing, arguing, agreeing
3. Processing of information and experiences
4. Forming Hypothesis
5. Applying

All these actions aid language learning and communication skills and are therefore of interest to the project of making students more involved, interested and engaged in the process of acquiring and using language for the purpose of business, professional and technical communication. Along with the theory of experiential learning the social interactionist approach to language acquisition suggested by Lantolf (2002) and Vygotsky (1978,) with possibilities of cultural and linguistic exchange (Harrison and Thomas, 2009; Harrison, 2013) are of special significance to this project as social media provides an apt platform and contextual clues for language learning and can thus be viewed as an appropriate site or tool to teaching language. One of the thrust focuses of language learning is acquiring the vocabulary of the target language and social media provides the necessary platforms for vocabulary building through resource-dense platforms. Social media when aided by podcasts and videos also play the role of enhancing student motivation to learn.

The Project

The pandemic forced teachers to use aids to help teach languages and communication, which triggered the current study and how social media and other platforms available on the internet can

be used to enhance language learning and communication among first-year students of engineering who had English as a subject prescribed in their curriculum. The number of students for the study was 220. Who were then decided into two groups, the Experimental group (A) and the Control group (B). Group B was taught the module on Business communication using traditional methods like lecturing and sharing of notes while Group A was introduced to social media use for language learning only for the said topic. It was assumed that significant differences were to be found between the two groups (A and B); the one which was taught via social media platforms and the other which took the same course in a traditional classroom.

Methodology

In terms of its epistemic position, this research makes use of the interpretivist position based on social media-assisted language learning to a group of students taking a course in English at the first-year B. Tech level only for the topic of Business Communication. The research question of whether the use of social media aids language use and communication would be explored using the qualitative method as it provides complex textual descriptions of how learners react to the experiences shared and also because several other factors such as the demographics-based information - e.g., gender, ethnicity, socio-economic status etc. can also be traced which might be lost in the quantitative method. The collection of data was done through observation of the facilitator and also through interviews and survey conducted and comparison of student's performance in role play and pre and post-tests. The reason behind the choice of these techniques was to use diverse techniques of investigation for better triangulation possibilities. The interview technique was used to make sure that the learners speak without reservation and share their actual experiences in a free and genuine manner. Groups A and B were taught the same content related to the theory and practices of Business Communication and etiquette and vocabulary used for the same. While all information provided to the students was the same, group B was exposed to traditional techniques like lecturing and sharing notes while group A was added to a WhatsApp and Facebook group and had to submit assignments on the WhatsApp group and use the Facebook group for resources which were varied e.g., podcast, videos etc. By the end of the module, all the students would have learnt the same vocabulary items and were asked to do the same assignments. Both groups were given the same tests.

Results and Findings

Both groups took the same exercises and activities though the tools used for the dissemination of information and strategies were different. The pre-test results revealed that the students understanding of concepts of business was limited.

Pretest scores

Post-test scores

The Post-test scores though showed a significant improvement in the performance of both groups in terms of understanding key concepts. However, there was no significant difference in the overall performance of the groups. The interviews conducted and the survey revealed that the majority of the students were happy with the resources provided and ascertained that the information

shared helped them in their overall understanding of business communication and practices. However, the observation of the facilitator revealed that the overall involvement and participation of the Experimental group which used various digital tools was much better than that of the focus group which was taught using traditional means. A few of the participants in the interviews also shared that -

Participant A “I would have never imagined that social media especially platforms like Twitter and Instagram can be used in a regular course and that too so effectively. My understanding of the use of such tools for the purpose of learning has improved significantly.”

Participant B “I was amazed that I was actually using a group like WhatsApp to submit assignments and also appreciate the work of my peers. It helped a lot in understanding and analyzing concepts”.

The survey conducted also revealed that the students of the control group were looking for more interventions from the facilitators in making the learning process more interesting and found the process of learning by rote and use of notes a little outdated.

It is to be noted that the participants of the Experimental Group displayed a more positive attitude towards the new style of learning and their performance was also slightly better than that of the Control Group. Perhaps our students need more motivation and scaffolding to improve their overall performance. Also, the scope of this study and project is slightly limited as it involved students being observed for their performance only in one module of their course. If their performance and scores of the entire course are taken into consideration perhaps the results would be different. Also, only one facilitator was involved if the facilitators are varied and have the support of the management in carrying out the study it would result in new interpretations of how social media platforms can be effectively used for language learning and acquisition. The study findings if taken up at a larger scale can serve as a fundamental indicator for implementing pedagogical reformations. Another equally crucial pedagogical implication is to design and provide professional development and training sessions to both students and educators on the ultimate utilization of social media as instructional technologies in the context of English language teaching and learning.

Conclusion

Language teaching and learning is a complex process especially when it concerns second language teaching and learning. Multiple factors have to be taken into consideration for the same. However, the motivation and involvement of the learners in the process play a significant role in how successfully the learners have incorporated and applied the concepts learnt and acquired during the course. There has been a lot of criticism about how the traditional lecture method fails to involve learners and motivate them to participate wholeheartedly in the process of learning. New and innovative use of ICT tools is the need of the hour. However, most of these tools are expensive and there is the matter of access and affordability. Making use of tools which are ubiquitous and in tune with the pulse of young learners is the need of the hour. As most learners make extensive use of the mobile phones and digital devices and since interconnectivity has significant penetration in the country. The cell phone and social media platforms offer immense scope as tools to enhance the process of teaching learning and increase learner engagement. However, these tools have to be used with discretion and by facilitators who understand that use of the medium and are trained in the same. Young learners tend to get distracted by social media and this is one fact that the facilitators can never forget. The activities included in the use of social media have to be interesting enough to hold the learner and attention and also engaging enough to enhance learner involvement and bring about significant change in learner performance, if not the entire exercise would end up being futile.

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22. ASSESSMENT OF 21ST CENTURY SKILLS

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Abstract

The modus operandi in performing the job in a routine and conventional way is being by twelve 21st century skills which need to be implemented with reference to the education system. These 12 skills range from critical thinking to social skills taking within its ambit creativity, information, productivity etc. Designing any curriculum or training the teachers for equipping students with 21st century skills will be highly ineffective if these skills are not assessed first hand. This study applied qualitative data analysis taken from various sources and literature. The analysis showed that 21st century skills can be applied to any curriculum that is addressed to achieve learning and innovation skills and also technology and information media skills competence. Based on the description above it can be fairly concluded that 21st century skills needs problem solving, productivity and being accountable, entrepreneurship, collaborative and team work, digital literacy etc. The same can be clustered down into domains of cognitive, interpersonal and intrapersonal skills. These skills once assessed will provide hands on learning experience to the students which in turn will reflect real world problems and the opportunities for interdisciplinary work.

Keywords: Learning skills, literacy skills, life skills, Education

Introduction

Technology in 21st centuries has taken by storm when it comes to development of any industrial sector. In fulfilling the 21st century's skill needs, we cannot know whether the hurdles that the student will be face and what kind of job that the student needed when they entered the workforce. Skill is very dependent on highly context dependent and multifaceted [1]. Individual's creative mind depends on working environment, knowledge and problem-solving skill. The questions arise about how will the teacher design his/her learning activities? What is the effective strategy that the teacher needs to apply to the class? How does the teacher prepare a skilled millennium generation? Because of the need to gain access to fast information and fulfillment in 21st centuries, skill demands which are different from the past, making the knowledge-based education becomes important and needs a reformation in the education section. A good education is one that encouragingly makes a change by providing students with adequate knowledge and skills to face the future challenges.

Although these skills are not new, it was not until very recently that educators and policy makers agreed that they should be explicitly included in academic content standards, directly taught

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alongside the regular academic curriculum, and routinely assessed for all students. Despite widespread agreement on their importance, however, there still appears to be disagreement as to which particular skills matter for college and career readiness. The National Research Council initiated an investigation into the topic of teaching and assessing 21st century skills, hosting several workshops and seminars beginning in 2005. Out of this work came a framework for categorizing the types of knowledge and skills students need for career readiness: (1) *cognitive skills, including critical thinking, non-routine problem solving, and systems thinking*; (2) *interpersonal skills, including complex communication, social skills, teamwork, cultural sensitivity, and dealing with diversity*; and (3) *intrapersonal skills, including self-management, time management, self-development, self-regulation, adaptability, and executive functioning* (Committee on the Assessment of 21st Century Skills, 2011).

2. 21st Century Skills in Education – Literature Review

The life of current students is very different with the pattern of life developed in the existing educational system. It shows lack of concerns towards knowledge and skills needed to understand existing perspective. Teachers, students, and authorities put forward a number of important skills for the student's future. Emiliana Vegas [1] stated that a successful education system is one that attached problem-solving and combined the problem context with information, as for example, the use of mathematics and science to solve a practical problem. This skill had to be known and owned by all employees in order to be skilled in the workforce. Harvey [3] viewed skill needs from individual and institutional perspective. Individual skills are skills or attribute of graduates to get a job. While institutional skill is related to the level of performance of educational institution's graduates. Baruch [4] stated that individual has the responsibility for their own skill, while authorities provide a chance to develop them. It means every individual manage their careers based on the opportunity to their surroundings. Overtoom [5] stated that employee needs skills about self-management, teamwork, interpersonal ability, problem-based, and critical thinking in order to increase the productivity of their company.

Knowledge is an important asset for job seeker when they initiate their work, yet what is really sought is teamwork. Teamwork can be developed from an early age by enabling students to work in a team. Besides, communication is also an important aspect and is different for each person. An effective verbal communication is a fundamental tool of work. Currently, a verbal communication is not the only important aspect, but also writing skill, such as individual's ability in terms of writing sentences. Survey outcomes stated some of difference in college student's perspective on how this skill where almost half of the USA and Britain with range age from 18-25 years old show that their problem-solving skill is superior to Chinese college student [1] it may be a reflection on how this skill has or hasn't been a priority inside the education system in both countries.

Digital literacy is an important skill to help on codify information, problem-solving, and find meaning in word or data based on the study from The Economist Intelligence Unit (EIU). Every graduate assumed that they have already supplied with digital literacy because generally, the teacher had developed digital literacy to their students.

Entrepreneurship is an important skill for students who will prepare them self in the workforce inside uture's network. Entrepreneurship and creativity skills have been provided by the teacher in school, but still in theoretical context and less of implementation. A low level of digital literacy, entrepreneurship, and creativity in employee indicate that those skills still rated as personal responsibility so that they are out of the curriculum.

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) innovations play a role in changing learning processes, but the educational system controls the progressive transformation. Data states that many teachers claim that the advancement of ICT has changed the way they teach. The teacher can apply technology in creative ways.

3. Method of the Study

This study applied qualitative data analysis. The data were taken from different sources and literature. The data then were discussed and analyzed using objective point of view related to the needed skills in education.

4. Assessing Cognitive Skills

This set of skills also generates debate about whether they are domain general or domain specific. A predominant view in the past has been that critical thinking and problem-solving skills are domain general: that is, that they can be learned without reference to any specific domain and, further, once they are learned, can be applied in any domain. *More recently, psychologists and learning theorists have argued for a domain-specific conception of these skills, maintaining that when students think critically or solve problems, they do not do it in the absence of subject matter: instead, they think about or solve a problem in relation to some topic. Under a domain-specific conception, the learner may acquire these skills in one domain as he or she acquires expertise in that domain, but acquiring them in one domain does not necessarily mean the learner can apply them in another.* Source: Kuncel and Hezlett (2007)

Figure I shows the correlations between scores on the standardized tests and the various outcome measures, including (from bottom to top) first-year graduate GPA (1st GGPA), cumulative graduate GPA (GGPA), qualifying or comprehensive examination scores, completion of the degree, estimate of research productivity, research citation counts, faculty ratings, and performance on the licensing exam for the profession.

Of the 34 correlations shown in the figure, all but 11 are over .30. It shows that verbal and quantitative skills are important predictors of success based on a variety of outcome measures, including performance on standardized tests, whether or not people finish their degree program, how their performance is evaluated by faculty, and their contribution to the field.

FIGURE I Correlations between scores on standardized tests and academic and job outcome measures

SOURCE: Kuncel and Hezlett (2007)

Figure II shows the correlations between performance on a measure of general cognitive ability and these outcomes. All of the correlations are above .30, which characterized as demonstrating a strong relationship between general cognitive ability and job performance across a variety of performance measures. Together, these two reviews present a body of evidence documenting that verbal and quantitative skills along with general cognitive ability are predictive of college and career performance.

FIGURE II Correlations between measures of cognitive ability and job performance

SOURCE: Kuncel and Hezlett (2011)

5. Assessing Interpersonal Skills

One way to assess these skills, Fiore explained, is to look separately at the different components (attitudinal, behavioral, and cognitive). For example, as the model in **Figure III** indicates, previous life experiences, such as the opportunities an individual has had to engage in successful and unsuccessful social interactions, can be assessed through reports (e.g., personal statements from applicants or letters of recommendation from prior employers). If such narratives are written in response to specific questions about types of interactions, they may provide indications of the degree to which an applicant has particular skills. *However, it is likely to be difficult to distinguish clearly between specific social skills and personality traits, knowledge, and cognitive processes. Moreover, Fiore added, such narratives report on past experience and may not accurately portray how one would behave or respond in future experiences.*

FIGURE III Model of interpersonal performance

NOTE: Big Five personality traits = openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism; EI = emotional intelligence; IPS = interpersonal skills.

SOURCE: Stephen Fiore’s presentation. Klein, DeRouin, and Salas (2006)

Correlation between cognitive and interpersonal skills (Figure IV)

Figure IV

Correlations between cognitive and interpersonal components (situational judgment test, or SJT) of the medical school admission test and medical school GPA

SOURCE: Filip Lievens’ presentation.

Figure V

Correlations between the cognitive and interpersonal components (situational judgment test, or SJT) of the medical school admission test and internship/job performance.

SOURCE: Filip Lievens' presentation.

Lievens summarized that while cognitive assessments are better at predicting GPA, the assessments of interpersonal skills were superior at predicting performance in internships and on the job.

6. Assessing Intrapersonal Skills

Assessing Integrity in Job Applicants:

Sackett then turned to empirical evidence documenting the validity of integrity tests. He has conducted several literature reviews on this topic. In the first review (Sackett and Decker, 1979), he found six studies of tests of honesty. In subsequent reviews, he found 40 (Sackett and Harris, 1984), 70 (Sackett, Burris, and Callahan, 1989), and most recently 665 (Sackett and Wanek, 1996). At this point, the field of employment testing considers the validity of integrity tests to be well established.

Generally, the findings show validity coefficients in the .20 to .30 range. He said the three types of tests appear to have similar levels of validity. While most of the tests originally focused on identifying job candidates likely to steal, the tests predict a wide array of counterproductive work behaviors. Some behaviors (e.g., absence from work) are more predictable than others (e.g., theft).

Sackett closed by noting that integrity testing developed from an applied standpoint, but the field has now shifted to a theoretical orientation. Initially, employers simply sought a device to identify job candidates likely to participate in wrong-doing on the job; they simply wanted a method that worked. The objective of more recent research has been to investigate why integrity tests work and to understand the underlying mechanisms by which they predict counterproductive work behaviors

Assessing Antisocial Behavior and Conduct Disorders:

Research shows antisocial behavior in children is a robust predictor of a number of problematic behaviors in adults, including poor physical health, school failure, and economic problems (Moffitt et al., 2002; Odgers et al., 2008). Odgers noted, antisocial behavior is relatively easy to diagnose.

Odgers presented the graph shown in **Figure VI** that displays the incidence of conduct problems for the males in the sample, following them from ages 7 to 26. The researchers identified four patterns of behavior: (1) individuals who were consistently low in conduct problems (solid line); (2) individuals who exhibited conduct problems in childhood, but the problems diminished over time (line with triangles); (3) individuals who began exhibiting conduct problems during adolescent years (line with circles); and (4) individuals who persistently exhibited conduct disorders from childhood on into adulthood (line with squares). The researchers have compared outcomes for these four groups.

Figure VI

FIGURE VI Incidence of conduct problems between ages 7 and 26 for longitudinal sample of individuals.

SOURCE: Odgers et al. (2007). Reprinted from Odgers, C.L., Milne, B.J., et al. (2007). Predicting prognosis for the conduct-problem boy: Can family history help? *Journal of American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*, 46(10), 1240–1249

Assessing Emotional Intelligence:

Matthews talked about two commonly used strategies for assessing emotional intelligence—trait questionnaires and ability tests—though he cautioned that each strategy has drawbacks. He said many trait questionnaires are available and most are personality-like scales that provide scores for various emotional intelligence traits. He noted these are self-report assessments, which he thinks raises a paradox that undermines their validity. As Matthews put it, “If having good self-awareness of your emotional functioning is central to emotional intelligence, then if you lack emotional intelligence, how can your questionnaire responses be very meaningful?”

7. Results and Discussion

According to Soulé, "Education systems need to provide students with hands-on learning that mirrors real-world problems and work opportunities in an interdisciplinary way." [6] The education system should provide a hands-on learning experience of the real world and employment opportunities in a variety of interdisciplinary ways to students. The 21st -century skills must be integrated into each subject, so the development of skills becomes integrated. Development of oral communication skills can be done by applying the use of dual-language; local language and international language, in the learning processes of all disciplines. It encourages students to gain public speaking experience, network developing, writing, and critical thinking. The key to skill development is the cross-curricular approach. *According to Soulé, students with communication skill, collaboration, critical thinking, and problem-solving, and creativity and innovation related to their knowledge content will tend to be more successful, both at college, at work and as part of society* [7].

The education system should provide a hands-on learning experience that reflects real-world problems and the opportunities for interdisciplinary work. This skill cannot be taught in a separate model but should instead lie along the curriculum. For students, they should be able to analyze information, manage resources, assess individual contributions to teams, and be responsible for specific tasks on all subjects. The implications for teachers are: (1) Teachers can develop this skill themselves and change their pedagogical aspects, (2) Teachers need to improve skills to enable them to effectively teach content and skills, and (3) Teachers should teach students how to work effectively. *The greatest obstacle to incorporate 21st-century skills more broadly in education precisely lies in the rigor of the existing curriculum.* The teacher found that the curriculum was too rigid on the development of wider skills for sufficient time allocation.

According to Trilling and Fadel [8], 21st-century skills are grouped into three types, namely (1) life and career skills, (2) learning and innovation skills, and (3) media skills and information skills.

Cognitive Skills

With regard to skills in the cognitive cluster, such as critical thinking and problem solving, Kuncel pointed out, *“We have a good understanding of these constructs when they are considered from a domain-specific perspective.”* As he described, “we know what it means to think critically in certain contexts, such as when considering a physics problem or evaluating a study in cognitive psychology, and we have a good understanding of how to assess these skills from a domain-specific perspective.”

Interpersonal Skills

With regard to interpersonal skills, Fiore reminded the audience of the complexity of interpersonal interactions. Interpersonal skills involve a mix of attitudinal, behavioral, and cognitive factors, all of which are used to read the person in the context of the interaction and determine the most appropriate way to respond. Designing assessments to measure these processes is challenging. Fiore said situational judgment tests are also susceptible to faking in that test takers can make guesses about the most socially acceptable response.

Intrapersonal Skills

Assessment of intrapersonal skills is also challenging because of the complexity of the processes involved. Hoyle reminded audience members that intrapersonal skills involve planfulness, self-discipline, delay of gratification, dealing with distractions, and adjusting the course when things do not go as planned.

8. Conclusion

Education in the 21st century is becoming increasingly important to ensure students have skills in learning and innovation, use of information technology and media, and can work and survive by utilizing life skills. As a first step, the implementation of 21st-century education concept can be applied to curriculum structure consisting of compulsory subjects aimed at achieving the competence of learning and innovation skills and technology and information media skills. While the supporting subject group is directed to achieve the competence of life and career skills. All subjects are a derivation of the 3R core subjects of reading, writing, and arithmetic.

Based on the above description, it can be concluded that the needs of 21st century skills include (1) having life planning, (2) flexibility and adaptability, (3) initiative and self-management, (4) entrepreneurship, (5) social and cultural interaction, (6) productivity and accountability, (7) leadership, and responsibility, (8) critical thinking, creative and innovative, (9) problem solving, (10) communication, (11) collaborative and teamwork, (12) life and (13) digital literacy.

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23. Assessment of 21st Century Skills Practiced by Secondary School Teachers in U.T. of Dadra and Nagar Haveli, Daman & Diu

Dr. Sarika M. Patel³³, Dr. Vinu Agrawal³⁴

Introduction:

21st Century Skills include various skills like creativity, communication, critical thinking, collaboration, thinking, character, citizenship, computational thinking, technology literacy, and more. Modern time demands various skills in order to achieve excellence at the workplace. 21st Century Skills are very essential in the field of education. Teachers need to practice the skills in order to develop their students for a better career. Teachers should play the role of a resource provider by using different skills. However, it is difficult to assess 21st century skills unlike other skills which can be evaluated through various types of tests. The 21st century skills assessment can be done with assessment rubrics, multiple choice knowledge-based questions, demonstration, content proficiency, psychomotor interaction, performance-based test, observation, test in simulated applications etc.

In the present study, researchers tried to focus on 21st century skills practiced by the secondary school teachers.

Objectives

1. To find out the ratio of teachers using 21st century skills in day-to-day practices.
2. To know the various 21st century skills practiced by the teachers in the classroom.
3. To analyze the degree of utilization of 21st century skills by the teachers.
4. To give suggestions for using 21st century skills by the teachers.

Methodology

There are various methods to conduct research. Out of different methods, a descriptive survey method was applied by the researchers to fulfil objectives of the present study. For the present study fifty teachers were selected through random sampling technique from seven secondary

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schools of the U.T. For the data collection three self constructed inventories 1. Check list 2. Opinionnaire and 3. Questionnaires were administered by the researchers. To collect the data permissions were taken from the authorities of the Education department and school management. Collected data was analyzed by statistical method of percentage and data collected through questionnaire was analyzed by qualitative analysis.

Sample

The sample of study comprised 50 teachers from secondary schools of U.T. of Dadra and Nagar Haveli. The researchers selected samples in two steps. In the first step seven schools were selected through random sampling technique and in the second step teachers from each school were selected through random sampling technique. To select the teachers randomly, a lottery method was applied by the researcher. Thus, a total of fifty teachers were selected as a sample for the present study. The details of sampling are shown in the table: 1.

Table: 1

Sr. No.	Name of the School	No. of teachers	No. of teachers selected (Male)	No. of teachers selected (Female)
1	Prabhat Scholars' Academy, Chanand devi rd., Silvassa	15	12	03
2	Anand International School, Dadra.	4	4	0
3	Govt. High School, Tokarkhada, Silvassa	10	8	2
4	Gyanmata English School, Khanvel.	5	2	3
5	BAPS Swaminarayan Vidymandir, Silvassa	6	5	1
6	Govt. Model School Silvassa	5	3	2

7	Shiv Prakash School, Silvassa	5	5	0
Total		50	39	11

Tools

For the present study, self-constructed inventory was used by the researcher to collect the data.

The inventory consists of following aspects:

- Part 1: Checklist to know availability of resources to maximize the utilization of 21st century skills.
- Part 2: Opinionnaire consists of twelve statements related to utilization of 21st century skills by the teachers.
- Part 3: Questionnaire consists of five open ended questions related to utilization of 21st century skills.

Analysis of the Data

- Part 1: Check list

Table: 2

Technological resources	School							Percentage
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Computer	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	100%
Internet	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	100%
Wi-Fi	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	100%
Interactive white board	√		√		√	√	√	71%
Mounted projector	√		√		√	√	√	71%
Educational Apps.	√		√	√	√	√	√	85.7%
UPS	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	100%
Availability of software	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	100%
Maintenances of ICT tools	√		√	√	√	√		71%
Smart Class	√		√	√	√	√	√	85.7%

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Table: 2 shows that selected schools have basic facilities related to information communication technology and other resources related to teaching learning process and activities. From the above mentioned table, it can be concluded that all the schools have facilities such as computers, internet, wifi, UPS and softwares. It was noticeable that Government schools of the territory are well equipped with smart classrooms. ICT tools are well maintained by the various institutions. It is found that some schools are not having interactive boards and smart class room facilities. It is found that some schools are not maintaining ICT resources.

- Part 2: Opinionnaire

Table: 3

Statement	Never	Sometime	Always
I am aware of 21 st century skills.	19%	72%	9%
I ask thought provoking questions in class.	0%	63%	37%
I criticize while explaining concepts in the classroom.	52%	25%	23%
I use a demonstration method in teaching.	8%	81%	11%
I use different methods of teaching.	3%	64%	33%
Teachers try innovative practices in school activities.	22%	49%	29%
Various educational Apps. are used in school during teaching practice.	9%	72%	19%
Teachers use powerpoint presentations.	4%	86%	10%
It is very difficult to access the internet in school for various academic activities.	9%	76%	15%
I use a smart board in teaching practice.	16%	57%	27%
The Internet is useful only for social networking.	96%	4%	0%

Required facilities are available in school to practice various 21 st century skills.	0%	34%	66%
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As per data received through opinionnaire and analysis shown in table: 3, it can be concluded that majority schools in the territory have facilities to practice 21st century skills. Teachers believe that internet facilities are not only for social networking. Teachers are creating a thoughtful environment in class using thought provoking questions. Majority of the teachers don't criticize during explanation in the teaching learning process. The teachers use different methods of teaching but somehow they are lacking in innovative practices. Few teachers are not using smart boards and some are using it frequently.

- Part 3: Questionnaire

Five open ended questions were asked to the selected teachers to collect information regarding practicing 21st century skills. Teachers' responses were taken in writing and qualitative analysis was done by the researchers. After the data collection, qualitative analysis was done by the researchers as follows:

Table :4

Skills	Qualitative measures
Critical thinking	Teachers use positive as well as negative examples while teaching in the classroom.
Communication skills	It is used promptly by Language teachers.
Creativity	Teachers show creativity in extracurricular activities.
Problem solving	It is frequently used in subjects like Science and Mathematics.
Perseverance	Due to the Continuous Comprehensive Evaluation teachers are bound to achieve goals of the curriculum despite difficulties..

Collaboration	Teachers conduct collaborative activities with other schools. They also follow activities like team teaching, conduct competitions together and collective celebrations of cultural fests.
Information literacy	Inclusion of ICT is practiced by the Majority of the teachers.
Technology skills and digital literacy	Teachers use smart boards and do computer-based teaching.

Major findings:

- Majority of the teachers are using 21st skills in the classroom. It was found that some teachers are not aware about these skills though they are practicing them in the classroom. So, it can be concluded that all the teachers are not aware about 21st skills in the classroom.
- Teachers are using various methods of teaching in the classroom but they are not trying for some innovative and challenging teaching strategies for teaching learning process.
- It can be concluded that teachers should increase the use of illustration and demonstration methods in the classroom.
- Teachers are practicing some 21st century skills such as communication, collaboration, information literacy and digital literacy promptly.
- There is a lot of scope for teachers to practice ICT literacy skills to their fullest as the majority of schools have ICT tools and smart classes in school with proper maintenance.
- The hectic annual schedule of academics and non-academic activities is the major hurdle described by the teachers in order to practice 21st century skills.
- Less participation in Inservice training sessions create hurdles in improving digital literacy skills.
- Sometimes teachers find it difficult to utilize technology in the classroom due to lack of competency.
- Teachers are agreeing that students find it very interesting with the computer assisted teaching learning process. But sometimes it becomes so entertaining that the main content is left aside.

Suggestions:

- Teachers should arrange and participate in debate, conferences etc.
- Teachers should find out scope to utilise problem solving skills and direct experience other than science and mathematics subjects.
- Training sessions are needed to develop creativity skills.
- Assignments should be given related to problem solving.
- Teachers need to focus on personal development through participating in seminars, workshops, and FDPs.
- Teachers are participating at a local platform, they need to initiate national and international collaborations also in order to develop collaborative actions.
- In-service training sessions to upgrade ICT literacy should be arranged by the education department.

Conclusion:

Using 21st century skills is the need of the hour. They are important to gain motivation, to increase confidence, to beat boredom, to maintain health, happiness and flexibility. The teachers of present time are facilitated with all the ICT tools and other equipment in order to practice 21st century skills. But the challenge for teachers is to regularly upgrade these skills and inculcate them in the day-to-day teaching learning process. As teachers develop skills such as critical thinking and perseverance, they will be more confident, flexible and adjustive in the present constantly changing workforce, increase their ability to work in a multicultural environment and would be able to take on positions of leadership.

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24. 21 वीं शताब्दी के जनजातीय समुदाय के बच्चों के साक्षरता कौशल का अध्ययन

प्रिन्स कुमार³⁵

शोध सार

प्रस्तुत आलेख में 21वीं शताब्दी के जनजातीय समुदाय के बच्चों के साक्षरता कौशल पर प्रकाश डाला गया है। मूलतः इस लेख में इन बच्चों के पृष्ठभूमि के संदर्भ में अगर हम यह देखें कि साक्षरता कौशल कैसी है? तो इसके उत्तर में यह कहा जा सकता है कि अनुसूचित जनजाति समुदाय के बच्चे जो मुख्यधारा के बच्चों के संपर्क में निरंतर आते हैं चाहे खेल के मैदान के द्वारा या एक साथ विद्यालय में शिक्षा प्राप्त करते समय। ऐसे बच्चों का जो साक्षरता कौशल है वह सामान्य बच्चों के जैसा ही है। किंतु वे बच्चे जो आज भी मुख्यधारा के बच्चों से कटे हुए हैं जैसे- पर्वतीय क्षेत्र के बच्चे, वनवासी क्षेत्र के बच्चे इत्यादि। इन बच्चों तक अभी भी शिक्षा की तथा शिक्षा संबंधी जागरूकता नहीं पहुंच पाई है। ऐसे बच्चों की अभी भी साक्षरता कौशल सामान्य से नीचे ही है। अर्थात् उनकी स्थिति भी जस की तस बनी हुई है। अवलोकन में यह देखा गया है कि बच्चों को श्रम से जोड़ दिया जाता है। अधिकांशतः लोग इन्हें बाल मजदूरी से जोड़ देते हैं। इनको पता ही नहीं है कि शिक्षा का महत्व क्या है? इसके अतिरिक्त अनुसूचित जनजाति का एक तबका वह भी है जिनका आधार कार्ड, पैन कार्ड इत्यादि तक नहीं है। इनका नाम, जाति इत्यादि के आधार पर पहचान क्या है? कोई भी जानकारी नहीं है। ये बंजारा की तरह जीवन व्यतीत करते हैं। उनके यहां लाइट की व्यवस्था नहीं है। रहने या खाने-पीने की व्यवस्था नहीं है। 21वीं सदी के भारत को देखा जाए तो साक्षरता कौशल के रूप में राष्ट्रीय शिक्षा नीति 2020 यह बताती है कि सभी को सारे आमूल-चूल परिवर्तन करने की जरूरत है। अब शिक्षक को बहुभाषी होना पड़ेगा। जनजातीय समुदाय की भाषा तथा स्थानीय भाषा सीखनी पड़ेगी। प्रायः यह देखा जाता है कि जो शिक्षक होता है वह एक आदर्श भाषा को ही जानता है। उसे जनजातीय भाषा को बोलने में बहुत मुश्किल होती है। बच्चे शिक्षक की भाषा नहीं समझ पाते और शिक्षक बच्चे की भाषा नहीं समझ पाते हैं। उदाहरण- उत्तर प्रदेश का कोई एक शिक्षक जिसकी नियुक्ति महाराष्ट्र राज्य में हो जाए तो महाराष्ट्र में मराठी बोलना उसके लिए चुनौतीपूर्ण होता है जबकि बच्चे मराठी आसानी से बोलते हैं। ऐसे दृष्टांत बताते हैं कि अगर हमें अनुसूचित जनजाति के बच्चों की साक्षरता कौशल को सामान्य बनाना है या ऊपर उठाना है तो उसकी भाषा को शिक्षक के द्वारा कक्षा में अपनाना पड़ेगा साथ ही जो शिक्षा से वंचित बच्चे हैं तथा जिन बच्चों का प्रवेश नहीं हुआ है। ऐसे बच्चों को भी स्कूल आने वाले बच्चे के द्वारा तथा उनके माता-पिता को संदेश के माध्यम से बुलवाया जाए। शिक्षक खाली समय में खुद घर जाकर पता लगाएं कि ऐसे बच्चे स्कूल क्यों नहीं आ रहे हैं? और हर संभव प्रयास के द्वारा उन्हें विद्यालय से जोड़ें। जहां पर विद्यालय नहीं है वहां पर अनौपचारिक शिक्षा पद्धति अपनाना चाहिए और खेल के माध्यम से जागरूकता फैलाया जाए। इस प्रकार से इनके शिक्षा स्तर को तथा साक्षरता कौशल को बढ़ाया जा सकता है।

Keywords: जनजातीय समुदाय, साक्षरता कौशल, विद्यालयी शिक्षा

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प्रस्तावना

जनजातीय बच्चों की साक्षरता कौशल की बात करें तो हम यह देख सकते हैं कि ये वे बच्चे हैं जो आज भी मुख्यधारा के बच्चों के संपर्क में आने से कतराते हैं। कतराने की वजह क्या है कि आज भी कोई कुलीन परिवार का बच्चा आता है तो उनकी जो ड्रेस है अलग होती है, प्रायः नए कपड़े होते हैं। वही जब ऐसे बच्चे आते हैं जिनके कपड़े गंदे, फटे-पुराने, कॉलर नहीं होता, तमाम प्रकार के विसंगतियाँ देखने को मिलती है। अवलोकन में पाया गया है कि ये बच्चे नहा कर या साफ-सफाई से नहीं आ पाते हैं। कुछ बच्चों को अगर देखा जाए तो उनके शरीर से दुर्गंध भी आती है, क्यों? क्योंकि इनके माता-पिता भी जागरूक नहीं हैं और जब स्कूल में शिक्षक-अभिभावक मीटिंग होती है। तब ऐसे बच्चों के अभिभावक उपस्थित होने से डरते हैं। स्कूल बहुत कम आना चाहते हैं। उनका कोई ना कोई बहाना होता है। लगातार शिक्षा के प्रयास करने के बावजूद भी बच्चों के अभिभावक स्कूल में शिक्षक-अभिभावक मीटिंग में उपस्थित नहीं होते हैं और इसके साथ-साथ शिक्षकों का व्यवहार उन बच्चों के साक्षरता कौशल को प्रभावित करता है, क्यों? क्योंकि शिक्षक की मानसिकता बनी हुई है कि जो बच्चा स्कूल आ रहा है वह तो जनजातीय समुदाय का बच्चा है उनके माता-पिता को पढ़ाई-लिखाई से कोई लेना-देना नहीं है तो ऐसे शिक्षकों का रुझान भी बच्चों के प्रति उदासीन हो जाता है जबकि ऐसा होना नहीं चाहिए। प्रायः ऐसा देखा जाता है कि बच्चा स्कूल आता है तो वह कक्षा में पीछे की बेंच पर शांतपूर्वक बैठा रहता है। शिक्षकों के लाख प्रयास करने के बावजूद भी वह बच्चा कुछ सीख नहीं पाता, या सीखने की ओर उन्मुख नहीं हो पाता। शिक्षक की समस्या क्या है कि उसको पढ़ाने के लिए 40 मिनट का समय मिलता है लेकिन माता-पिता की जिम्मेदारियाँ इस रूप में बढ़ जाती हैं कि बच्चा 24 घंटे में से 12 घंटे से ज्यादा समय परिवार के बीच में रहता है। परिवार का कोई भी सदस्य अपने बच्चों से पूछ ले कि तुम क्या पढ़ रहे हो या क्या पढ़े थे या कुछ भी बताओ जो आज दिनभर में पढ़े हो, तो एक अच्छा खासा बच्चों का समुदाय है जिसको आज भी क, ख, ग या फिर गिनती का अता पता नहीं है।

इसके अतिरिक्त प्रधानाचार्यों का जो व्यवहार होना चाहिए ज्यादातर स्कूलों में देखा जाता है कि अगर उच्च वर्ग के प्रधानाचार्य हैं तो वह भी भेदभाव करता है और यहां तक कि लोगों के पानी-पीने के बर्तन भी अलग-अलग होते हैं अगर अनुसूचित जाति/जनजाति का शिक्षक है तो उसका बर्तन अलग होता है, अगर सवर्ण है तो उसका बर्तन अलग होता है। तो यह जो व्यवहार है कहने को तो भेदभाव नहीं है लेकिन नियमों को बना देना अलग बात है और उसका धरातल पर औसत रूप में नजरियों का आकलन करना दूसरी बात हो जाती है। हकीकत यह है कि आज भी शिक्षकों का एक हुजूम वह है जो इस आधार पर भेदभाव करता है। ये बच्चों के साथ अन्याय करता रहता है कि ये सब मलिन बस्ती एवं झुग्गी झोपड़ी से आते हैं। इनको पढ़ने-लिखने से मतलब नहीं है। इनकी जाति और कौम ही ऐसी है। इसका नतीजा यह है कि अगर आप देखें कि किसी भी राज्यों में चाहे वह झारखंड, छत्तीसगढ़, मध्य प्रदेश, महाराष्ट्र, या अन्य राज्य की बात हो तो पाएंगे कि जो दूर-दराज का क्षेत्र या गांव होता है जहां पर लोग पढ़ने के लिए दूर जाना नहीं चाहते हैं। वहां पर कई जनजातीय समुदाय के लोग मिल जाएंगे। हमारा समाज आज भी उन्हें मुख्यधारा में ला ही नहीं पाया और ये उस परिवार के बच्चे हैं जो आज भी शादी-विवाह जैसे उत्सव में एक दिन भोजन खाने के लिए तरसते हैं। उनके लिए विश्व का आठवां अजूबा है कि किसी पार्टी में शामिल हो जाना और गलती से भी ऐसी झुग्गी झोपड़ी से निकलकर बच्चा किसी फाइव स्टार होटल में पहुंच गया या बड़े घर के शादियों में चला गया तो ऐसे बच्चों को मारते-पीटते हैं और अपमानित करके भगा दिया जाता है। तो यह जो शिक्षा का प्रावधान है हमें जरूरत है कि हम सबसे पहले अपनी सोच को बदलें फिर स्कूल के शिक्षकों की सोच

बदले, प्रधानाचार्य की सोच को बदलें, जब शिक्षक राष्ट्र का निर्माता कहा जाता है तो उसकी कोई जाति, धर्म, या मजहब नहीं होता। शिक्षक ब्रह्मा, विष्णु, महेश के समान पूजनीय होता है। उसकी जिम्मेदारियां भी बढ़ जाती है। इस रूप में कि बच्चों के साथ भेदभाव ना करें। जाति, राजनीति या आरक्षण, धर्म इत्यादि में जो विसंगतियां हैं उस पर चर्चा ना करें।

अनुसूचित जनजाति वर्ग में शिक्षा के प्रति रुझान तभी बढ़ सकता है जब शिक्षा का स्वरूप निर्धारित करते समय जनजाति समाज की पृष्ठभूमि को केंद्र में रखकर पाठ्यक्रम का निर्माण इस प्रकार से हो ताकि जनजाति समुदाय का बालक शिक्षा के साथ-साथ अपने परंपरागत मूल्यों को कायम रख सके क्योंकि विद्यालय के साथ उनका समायोजन न होने के कारण इन बच्चों में स्कूल जाने की रुचि कम होती है। आदिवासी बच्चे अपनी अलग भाषा व सांस्कृतिक विभिन्नता के कारण स्कूली जीवन से जुड़ने में असहज महसूस करते हैं। आज यह भी जरूरी है कि इन क्षेत्रों में इन वंचित बच्चों के लिए लिखने-पढ़ने और सीखने को एक आनंद प्रद अनुभव बनाया जाए और ऐसा करने के लिए यह जरूरी है कि विशेष रूप से दूर-दराज के जनजाति क्षेत्रों के स्कूलों में दृश्य माध्यमों और दूरदर्शन फिल्म आदि के साथ ही दूरस्थ शिक्षा पद्धति की सहायता से भी उनको शैक्षिक गतिविधियों से जोड़ा जा सकता है। आदिवासी बच्चों के शिक्षा स्तर को बढ़ाने के लिए हमें इन विचारों पर चिंतन करना अत्यंत जरूरी है (यादव,2013)

जनजातीय समुदाय की परिभाषा

जनजातीय समुदाय सामूहिक जीवन व्यतीत करते हैं। इनका निवास स्थान अनिश्चित होता है। ये ज्यादातर पर्वतीय अथवा जंगलों में रहते हैं जिनकी एक संस्कृति होती है तथा जो आज भी आर्थिक रूप से से काफी पिछड़े हुए हैं। प्रमुख विद्वानों ने जनजातीय को निम्न प्रकार से परिभाषित करने का प्रयास किया है- “मजूमदार का कहना है कि एक जनजातीय परिवारों तथा परिवारों के समूहों का संग्रह है और जिसके सदस्य एक ही भू-क्षेत्र में निवास करते हैं, एक भाषा बोलते हैं और विवाह, वृत्ति या व्यवसाय के प्रति कुछ निषेधों का पालन करते हैं तथा उनमें परस्पर आदान-प्रदान एवं दायित्वों की पारस्परिकता की एक सुनिश्चित व्यवस्था विकसित होती है” (श्रीवास्तव,2013)।

साक्षरता कौशल

साक्षरता कौशल अर्थात् पढ़ने-लिखने का कौशल एक आत्मविश्वास देता है, चीजों को समझने का एक जरिया होता है। किसी लिखी हुई सामग्री के बारे में सोचने और उसका विश्लेषण करने का प्रयास होता है। इसलिए साक्षरता कौशल को केवल अक्षरों तक सीमित नहीं करना चाहिए।

साक्षरता का अर्थ है साक्षर होना अर्थात् पढ़ने और लिखने की क्षमता से संपन्न होना। अलग-अलग देशों में साक्षरता के अलग-अलग मानक हैं। भारत में राष्ट्रीय साक्षरता मिशन के अनुसार अगर कोई व्यक्ति अपना नाम लिखने और पढ़ने की योग्यता हासिल कर लेता है तो उसे साक्षर माना जाता है।

साक्षरता दर का क्या अर्थ है?

किसी देश अथवा राज्य की साक्षरता दर वहाँ के कुल लोगों की जनसंख्या व पढ़े-लिखे लोगों के अनुपात को कहा जाता है। अधिकांश यह प्रतिशत में दर्शाया जाता है परन्तु कभी कभी इसे प्रति-कोटि (प्रत्येक हजार पर) भी दिखाया जाता है।

अनुसूचित जनजातियों की साक्षरता दर

जनगणना आंकड़ों के आधार पर, अखिल भारतीय अनुसूचित जनजातियों की साक्षरता दर 2001 के 45.1% से बढ़कर 2011 में 59.1% हो गई है। अनुसूचित जनजातियों की साक्षरता दर 2011 में समग्र साक्षरता दर (73%) की तुलना में लगभग 14% कम थी। बहरहाल, इस अंतराल में 1991 के 22.6% एवं 2001 के 17.7% के मुकाबले 2011 में 14% तक कमी आ चुकी है।

- पुरुषों की साक्षरता प्रतिशत: 69.7%
- स्त्रियों की साक्षरता प्रतिशत: 48.8%

मानव संसाधन विकास मंत्रालय द्वारा प्रकाशित आंकड़ों के अनुसार उच्च माध्यमिक स्तर की कक्षा दसवीं एवं कक्षा 12 स्तर पर एसटी छात्रों के लिए सकल नामांकन अनुपात 2013-14 के 35.4% से बढ़कर 2015-16 में 45.1% तक पहुंच गया है। उच्च माध्यमिक स्तर पर ऐसे छात्रों के लिए लैंगिक समानता सूचकांक भी 2013-14 के 0.93% से बढ़कर 2015-16 में 0.97% तक पहुंच गया है (स्रोत: जनजातीय कार्य मंत्रालय)।

भारत में अनुसूचित जनजाति की साक्षरता दर राष्ट्रीय औसत की तुलना में 58.96 प्रतिशत है, यानी 72.99 प्रतिशत। साक्षरता दर 1961 में 8.53 प्रतिशत थी जो 2011 में एसटी के लिए 58.96 प्रतिशत हो गई है, जबकि कुल जनसंख्या की इसी वृद्धि 1961 में 28.30 प्रतिशत से 2011 में 72.99 प्रतिशत थी। एसटी के साक्षरता स्तर में सुधार हुआ है लेकिन जनजातीय महिलाओं और पुरुषों दोनों के लिए अंतर स्तर में उल्लेखनीय गिरावट नहीं आई है। भारत और एसटी में साक्षरता दर के बीच प्रतिशत में अंतर 1961 में 19.77 प्रतिशत से घटकर 2011 में 14.03 प्रतिशत हो गया। 68.53 प्रतिशत पुरुष और 49.35 प्रतिशत महिलाएँ अनुसूचित जनजातियों में क्रमशः साक्षर हैं। पुरुष-महिला एसटी साक्षरता दर के बीच अंतर 2001 में 24.41 प्रतिशत अंक से घटकर 2011 में 19.18 प्रतिशत हो गया।

कुल जनसंख्या और अनुसूचित जनजाति की तुलनात्मक साक्षरता दर। (प्रतिशत)।

Source: <https://nacdaor.org/hi/education-employability/?mode=grid>

राष्ट्रीय साक्षरता मिशन

राष्ट्रीय साक्षरता मिशन के दस्तावेजों के मुताबिक, “औपचारिक रूप से साक्षर” होने का मतलब है (i) पढ़ने, लिखने और जोड़-घटाव करने में आत्मनिर्भरता, (ii) गरीबी और अभाव के कारणों के बारे में जागरूकता और विकास की प्रक्रिया में भागीदार बनकर अपने हालात में सुधार के लिए कदम बढ़ाने की योग्यता, (iii) आर्थिक स्थिति और सामान्य जीवन में सुधार के लिए कौशल प्राप्त करना और (iv) राष्ट्रीय एकता, पर्यावरण संरक्षण, महिलाओं के प्रति समानता का व्यवहार और छोटे परिवार के महत्व को समझते हुए उसका पालन करने जैसे मूल्यों को अपने जीवन में उतारना। यूनेस्को भी अब साक्षरता की पारंपरिक परिभाषा से आगे निकल चुका है। यूनेस्को के लिए अब साक्षरता का मतलब, “बढ़ते डिजिटलीकरण और सूचनाओं से भरपूर माहौल के बीच तेजी से बदलते विश्व में पहचान, समझ, विवरण, सृजन और संचार एवं संपर्क का एक साधन है” जाहिर है कि यह सभी बातें एनईपी 2020 में भी समाहित हैं।

(<https://www.orfonline.org/hindi/research/nep-2020-achieving-universal-literacy-in-india-by-2047/>)

अनुसूचित जनजातियों के प्रावधान

संविधान का अनुच्छेद 46 प्रावधान करता है कि राज्य समाज के कमजोर वर्गों में शैक्षणिक और आर्थिक हितों विशेषतः अनुसूचित जातियों और अनुसूचित जनजातियों का विशेष ध्यान रखेगा और उन्हें सामाजिक अन्याय एवं सभी प्रकार के शोषण से संरक्षित रखेगा। शैक्षणिक संस्थानों में आरक्षण का प्रावधान अनुच्छेद 15(4) में किया गया है जबकि पदों एवं सेवाओं में आरक्षण का प्रावधान संविधान के अनुच्छेद 16(4), 16(4क) और 16(4ख) में किया गया है। विभिन्न क्षेत्रों में अनुसूचित जनजातियों के हितों एवं अधिकारों को संरक्षण एवं उन्नत करने के लिए संविधान में कुछ अन्य प्रावधान भी समाविष्ट किए गए हैं जिससे कि वे राष्ट्र की मुख्य धारा से जुड़ने में समर्थ हो सके।

अनुच्छेद 24 जो किसी फैक्ट्री या खान या अन्य किसी जोखिम वाले कार्य में 14 वर्ष से कम आयु वाले बच्चों के नियोजन को निषेध करता है, का भी अनुसूचित जनजातियों के लिए विशेष महत्व है क्योंकि इन कार्यों में संलग्न बाल मजदूरों का अत्यधिक भाग अनुसूचित जनजातियों का ही है। संविधान की 5वीं और 6वीं अनुसूचियों में उल्लिखित प्रावधानों के साथ पठित अन्य विशिष्ट सुरक्षण अनुच्छेद 244 में उपलब्ध हैं।

राज्य विशेष प्रावधान

अनुच्छेद 371क

नागालैंड राज्य के संबंध में विशेष प्रावधान करता है।

अनुच्छेद 371ख

असम राज्य के संबंध में विशेष प्रावधान करता है।

अनुच्छेद 371ग

मणिपुर राज्य के संबंध में विशेष प्रावधान करता है।

अनुच्छेद 371च

सिक्किम राज्य के संबंध में विशेष प्रावधान करता है। (स्रोत: राष्ट्रीय अनुसूचित जनजाति आयोग (<http://www.ncst.nic.in/>))

भारतीय संविधान के अनुच्छेद 45 में निहित शिक्षा की अनिवार्यता संबंधी तथ्य “14 वर्ष की आयु पूरी करने तक सभी बच्चों के लिए निःशुल्क और अनिवार्य शिक्षा” महत्वपूर्ण कदम है। आजादी के बाद से भारत की सरकारों ने इस लक्ष्य को पूरा करने के लिए माध्यमिक स्तर पर औपचारिक और अनौपचारिक शिक्षा के प्रावधान का विस्तार किया है। माध्यमिक विद्यालयों में सकल नामांकन दर का रवैया अधिक है, फिर भी यह लक्ष्य लागू होने के आधी सदी के बाद भी पूरा नहीं हुआ है। हालाँकि इन सभी प्रयासों के बावजूद अधिकांश लोग शिक्षा से वंचित हैं। यह भी गंभीर चिंता का विषय है कि आदिवासी समुदाय में साक्षरता दर 50 प्रतिशत से भी कम है और बच्चों के एक बड़े वर्ग को प्राथमिक शिक्षा के स्वीकार्य स्तर के बिना ही जाना पड़ता है (राष्ट्रीय शिक्षा नीति, 1986)।

सुझाव

1. जनजातीय समुदाय की शिक्षा को बढ़ावा देने के लिए विभिन्न आदिवासी क्षेत्रों में साक्षरता अभियान चलाया जाना चाहिए।
2. जनजातीय समुदाय के छात्रों को पढ़ाने के लिए स्थानीय भाषा में अद्यतन अध्ययन सामग्री का उपयोग किया जाना चाहिए।
3. जनजातीय समुदाय के क्षेत्रों में स्कूलों को स्थानीय शिक्षक और स्कूल में महिला शिक्षिका को भी नियुक्त किया जाना चाहिए।
4. विद्यार्थियों को स्कूल की ओर आकर्षित करने के लिए विभिन्न छात्रवृत्ति दिया जाना चाहिए।
5. जनजातीय समुदाय के क्षेत्र में परिवहन की समस्या व्याप्त है, इसे दूर करने के लिए आवासीय विद्यालय होने चाहिए।
6. जनजातीय समुदाय के लिए सभी योजनाओं का समुचित क्रियान्वयन हो, इसकी समुचित निगरानी की जाए।

निष्कर्ष

उपरोक्त तथ्यों के आधार पर निष्कर्ष रूप में यह कहा जा सकता है कि अभी भी अनुसूचित जनजाति के विद्यार्थियों के शिक्षा स्तर एवं साक्षरता कौशल को बढ़ाने के लिए बहुत कुछ करने की जरूरत है तभी हम इनका शिक्षा के संदर्भों में उन्नयन कर सकने में समर्थ हो सकेंगे और स्वाभाविक सी बात है कि जब शिक्षा का उन्नयन होगा तभी इनका सामाजिक, आर्थिक, धार्मिक एवं राजनैतिक उन्नयन भी हो सकेगा। निश्चित रूप से सरकार के द्वारा नीतियां लाई गई हैं। वह तो अपने स्थान पर प्रभावशाली हैं ही लेकिन उनका क्रियान्वयन अभी भी धीमी गति से हो रहा है। अगर हम चाहते हैं कि इनको समाज के मुख्यधारा से जोड़ा जाए तो जो भी विशेष प्रधान दिए गए हैं उसको वास्तविक रूप में लागू करना। अगर हमें जनजातीय समुदाय का उन्नयन करना है तो सबसे पहले उन तक शिक्षा की पहुंच बनानी पड़ेगी शिक्षा के माध्यम से सब कुछ संभव है। इससे उनके साक्षरता कौशल का विकास हो सकेगा और इस प्रकार जनजातीय समुदाय का सामाजिक, आर्थिक, राजनैतिक, एवं परिवारिक विकास संभव हो सकेगा।

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25. पारंपरिक शिक्षा प्रणाली बनाम आधुनिक शिक्षा प्रणाली (21 वीं सदी की शिक्षा): भारतीय शिक्षा प्रणाली का संदर्भ

डॉ. पूनम केसरवानी³⁶

सारांश

पारंपरिक शिक्षा संस्कृति, परंपराओं और रीति-रिवाजों का अध्ययन है जबकि 21 वीं सदी की शिक्षा स्कूल में छात्रों को अपने कौशल को बढ़ाने के लिए सिखाती है। शिक्षक यह जांचने के लिए लिखित परीक्षा आयोजित करते हैं कि छात्र ठीक से सीख रहे हैं या नहीं। आधुनिक शिक्षा के कारण परम्परागत शिक्षा की उपेक्षा हो रही है। स्मार्टफोन, लैपटॉप और नोटपैड आजकल शिक्षा का माध्यम बन गए हैं। आजकल दूरस्थ शिक्षा भी विद्वानों का चयन बन गया है और छात्र ऑनलाइन समीक्षा करने के लिए सबसे अधिक सक्रिय हैं क्योंकि ऑनलाइन उन्हें कहीं भी और कभी भी उनके पास मौजूद सभी ज्ञान और विवरण मिलते हैं। वीडियो व्याख्यान और ग्राफिक प्रतिनिधित्व भी कॉलेज के बच्चों और शिक्षकों के लिए सबसे सरल विकल्प बन गया है।

Keywords: पारंपरिक शिक्षा, आधुनिक शिक्षा, 21 वीं सदी की शिक्षा, बुनियादी जरूरत, संस्कृति

प्रस्तावना

शिक्षा शिक्षण और सीखने के माध्यम से ज्ञान प्रदान करना और प्राप्त करना है, खासकर एक स्कूल या इसी तरह के संस्थान में। शुरुआती शैक्षिक प्रक्रियाओं में भोजन इकट्ठा करने और आश्रय प्रदान करने के बारे में जानकारी साझा करना शामिल था; हथियार और अन्य उपकरण बनाना; भाषा सीखना; और किसी दिए गए संस्कृति के मूल्यों, व्यवहार और धार्मिक संस्कारों या प्रथाओं को प्राप्त करना। पढ़ने और लिखने के आविष्कार से पहले, लोग एक ऐसे वातावरण में रहते थे जिसमें वे प्राकृतिक शक्तियों, जानवरों और अन्य मनुष्यों के खिलाफ जीवित रहने के लिए संघर्ष करते थे। जीवित रहने के लिए, पूर्वसाक्षर लोगों ने कौशल विकसित किए जो सांस्कृतिक और शैक्षिक पैटर्न में विकसित हुए।

शिक्षा अस्तित्व और ज्ञानोदय के लिए मानव संघर्ष से विकसित हुई। यह औपचारिक या अनौपचारिक हो सकता है। अनौपचारिक शिक्षा सामान्य सामाजिक प्रक्रिया को संदर्भित करती है जिसके द्वारा मनुष्य अपनी संस्कृति में कार्य करने के लिए आवश्यक ज्ञान और कौशल प्राप्त करता है। औपचारिक शिक्षा उस प्रक्रिया को संदर्भित करती है जिसके द्वारा शिक्षक संस्थानों के भीतर अध्ययन के पाठ्यक्रमों में छात्रों को निर्देश देते हैं।

पारंपरिक शिक्षा

पारंपरिक शिक्षा को प्रथागत शिक्षा या पारंपरिक शिक्षा भी कहा जाता है। पारंपरिक शिक्षा का मुख्य उद्देश्य मूल्यों, शिष्टाचार कौशल और सामाजिक अभ्यास को अगली पीढ़ी तक पहुंचाना है जो उनके अस्तित्व के लिए आवश्यक है। पारंपरिक शिक्षा में छात्र उस

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समाज के रीति-रिवाजों और परंपरा के बारे में सीखता है जिसमें वह रहता है। इस प्रकार की शिक्षा ज्यादातर मौखिक पाठ के माध्यम से छात्रों को प्रदान की जाती है। लिखित कार्य या व्यावहारिक कार्य बहुत कम है। छात्र बस एक साथ बैठते हैं और शिक्षक या किसी अन्य को सुनते हैं जो पाठ पढ़ेंगे। पारंपरिक में लिखित परीक्षा शामिल नहीं है लेकिन इसमें कुछ मौखिक परीक्षण शामिल हैं जो बहुत औपचारिक नहीं हैं।

पारंपरिक शिक्षा प्रणाली के फायदे

समय की पाबंदी: छात्रों के पास ब्रेक लेने के लिए हर अवधि और समय के लिए एक विशिष्ट समय होगा। यह समय सभी शुरुआत में योजनाबद्ध है, छात्र इस दिनचर्या का पालन करते हैं और उन्हें समय के पाबंद और अनुशासित बनाते हैं।

सामाजिक संपर्क: छात्र अपने साथियों के साथ बातचीत करते हैं जो उन्हें चरित्र निर्माण में मदद करते हैं। वे दूसरों को साझा करना और सम्मान करना सीखते हैं।

पाठ्येतर गतिविधियां: यह छात्रों को दूसरों को अपनी छिपी प्रतिभा दिखाने का अवसर देता है। यह उन्हें अपनी प्रतिभा के लिए पहचानने में मदद करता है और अपने जीवन में उत्कृष्टता प्राप्त करने में सक्षम हैं।

आमने-सामने बातचीत: छात्र अपने शिक्षकों के साथ सीधे बातचीत करने में सक्षम हैं। वे उन क्षेत्रों पर प्रश्न और अधिक स्पष्टीकरण पूछने में सक्षम हैं जिन्हें उन्हें संदेह है।

पारंपरिक शिक्षा प्रणाली के नुकसान

सामान्यीकृत शिक्षा: सभी छात्रों के लिए सामान्यीकृत शिक्षा उनके लिए उन चीजों को सीखना मुश्किल बनाती है जिनमें वे रुचि रखते हैं। विभिन्न छात्रों के पास अलग-अलग प्रतिभा और रुचियां हैं जो यह सामान्य शिक्षा प्रदान करने में विफल रहती हैं। छात्र अध्ययन करने के लिए अधिक समय और प्रयास खर्च करेंगे जिसमें वे अच्छे नहीं हैं, और इससे उन्हें अपने भविष्य के कैरियर में मदद नहीं मिलेगी।

निष्क्रिय श्रोता: पारंपरिक शिक्षा में, छात्रों को अपने शिक्षकों को सुनना चाहिए। कई बार विद्यार्थी शिक्षकों की बात सुनने का प्रयास नहीं करते। वे व्याख्यान में रुचि की कमी है और निष्क्रिय श्रोता बन जाते हैं।

कोई लचीला समय नहीं: पारंपरिक शिक्षा एक कठोर अनुसूची का अनुसरण करती है जो अध्ययन करने के लिए चुनौतीपूर्ण है। स्टूडेंट्स को इससे जूझना पड़ रहा है।

महंगा: यह बहुत महंगा है क्योंकि स्कूल कुछ सुविधाएं प्रदान करता है और अपने प्रशिक्षकों आदि के लिए ट्यूशन फीस प्रदान करता है। हर कोई इसे बर्दाश्त नहीं कर सकता है और अंत में ऋण लेता है।

शिक्षक-केंद्रित शिक्षा: शिक्षक और पुस्तकें सूचना के मुख्य स्रोत हैं। छात्र नई चीजें सीखने में असमर्थ हैं, और उनका ज्ञान पुस्तकों और व्याख्याताओं द्वारा प्रदान किए गए ज्ञान तक ही सीमित है।

आधुनिक शिक्षा (21 वीं सदी की शिक्षा)

भारत में शिक्षा ने हाल के दिनों में एक प्रतिमान बदलाव देखा है। एक समय था जब गुरु, उनके ज्ञान और अनुभव को अचूक और समग्र माना जाता था। आज, शिक्षा समाज के सभी वर्गों से अभूतपूर्व जांच का गवाह बन रही है। दुनिया पहले की अकल्पनीय गति से बदल रही है। हमें अब यह समझ लेना चाहिए कि हम अपने बच्चों को अज्ञात, अनदेखे और अप्रत्याशित के लिए तैयार कर रहे हैं। यह पचाना आसान नहीं है। इसलिए, 21वीं सदी की स्कूली शिक्षा को छात्रों को यह सिखाने में सक्षम होना चाहिए कि अप्रत्याशितता और परिवर्तन से कैसे निपटा जाए। 21 वीं सदी की शिक्षा, पारंपरिक शिक्षा से बहुत अलग है। आज स्कूलों में जो शिक्षा पढ़ाई जाती है, वह आधुनिक शिक्षा है। आधुनिक शिक्षा आज आवश्यक कौशल के बारे में सिखाती है जो विज्ञान और प्रौद्योगिकी के कौशल, चिकित्सा विज्ञान का विज्ञान आदि है।

आधुनिक शिक्षा का लक्ष्य:

आधुनिक शिक्षा का लक्ष्य यह सुनिश्चित करने पर ध्यान केंद्रित करना है कि बच्चे समस्या का समाधान करने वाले, निर्णय लेने वाले और समर्थ बनाने वाले हों। छात्रों को जीवन कौशल के साथ स्कूल छोड़ने की जरूरत है जो उन्हें चुनौतियों का सामना करने में मदद करते हैं, भले ही वे उनका समाधान नहीं जानते हों। सबसे महत्वपूर्ण बात यह है कि उन्हें अपने आसपास के लोगों के साथ काम करने में सहज होने की जरूरत है, जिनके पास अलग-अलग पृष्ठभूमि और जीवन के अनुभव हैं।

खोज का लगभग कोई क्षेत्र नहीं बचा है जो एक आयामी या व्यक्तिवादी हो। यहां तक कि अगर आप एक खिलाड़ी का सबसे चरम उदाहरण लेते हैं जो टेनिस या एथलेटिक्स जैसे किसी व्यक्तिगत खेल का अनुसरण करता है, तो उन्हें मनोवैज्ञानिकों, प्रशिक्षकों, बड़े डेटा प्रौद्योगिकीविदों आदि के साथ इंटरफेस करने और एक टीम के रूप में काम करने की आवश्यकता होती है।

सुनने के अलावा, आधुनिक शिक्षा में लेखन, कल्पना, कल्पना और सोच कौशल शामिल हैं। इस प्रकार की शिक्षा में यह जांचने के लिए लिखित परीक्षा भी शामिल है कि छात्र ठीक से सीख रहे हैं या नहीं। यह बहुत ही औपचारिक तरीके से किया जाता है। शिक्षण के लिए उपयोग की जाने वाली पद्धति बहुत इंटरैक्टिव है। आधुनिक शिक्षा कुछ साल पहले छात्रों को दी जाने वाली पारंपरिक शिक्षा का विकास मात्र है।

कौशल आधारित शिक्षा भविष्य की जरूरत है-

शिक्षा, मोटे तौर पर, केवल निर्धारित पाठ्यक्रम को पढ़ाना नहीं है बल्कि जीवन के हर क्षेत्र में जीवन कौशल और उद्यमशीलता की तैयारी के लिए कई संभावनाओं के लिए दिमाग खोलना है। शास्त्रीय अर्थों में उद्यमिता को उद्यम निर्माण पर केंद्रित किया गया है, लेकिन उद्यम प्रबंधन और स्केलिंग भी परिभाषा का एक हिस्सा है।

भविष्य व्यक्तिगत शिक्षा, अनुकूलित उपभोग और छोटे सीखने के स्थान हैं जहां छात्र एक तरल वातावरण में सीख सकते हैं और एक-दूसरे से सीख सकते हैं - सहकर्मी सीख सकते हैं। शिक्षक-छात्र संबंध एक गतिशील परिवर्तन का सामना करेंगे, जब फ्लिप कक्षाएँ स्कूलों में एक अपवाद के बजाय एक आदर्श बन जाएंगी।

विचार, पाठ्यपुस्तक से परे होंगे और प्रतिधारण के आकलन के बजाय ज्ञान के अनुप्रयोग के अधिक अनुरूप होंगे। लचीले शिक्षण मार्ग, जीवन कौशल प्रदान करने पर ध्यान केंद्रित करना, छात्र केंद्रित सीखने के तरीके और प्रौद्योगिकी का उपयोग शिक्षा की अवधारणा में ला रहे हैं।

आधुनिक शिक्षण पद्धति को शामिल करना

आधुनिक शिक्षण पद्धति, सोच और विश्लेषणात्मक कौशल पर केंद्रित है। छात्रों में हस्तांतरणीय सार सोच कौशल और चिंतनशील अवलोकन भविष्य के करियर को विकसित करने में मदद करता है। इस प्रक्रिया में परियोजना निर्माण, क्षेत्र भ्रमण और नियंत्रित वातावरण में चुनौतियों का सामना करना शामिल है। यह भविष्य की सफलता का आधार है क्योंकि यह सीखने और करने के बीच की खाई को पाटता है। सिद्धांत और व्यवहार के बीच की विसंगति दूर हो जाती है। सीखने की अवस्था को बढ़ाया जाता है, और कार्यप्रणाली स्पष्ट मानसिकता और व्यवहारिक परिवर्तन पैदा करने में सहायक होती है।

यह समग्र शैक्षिक प्रथाओं की नींव रखता है जो एक ऐसा वातावरण बनाता है जो जीवन भर सीखने की सुविधा देता है, छात्र की प्राकृतिक जिज्ञासा को बढ़ाता है और नाटकीय रूप से अवधारण को बढ़ाता है। मूल्यांकन प्रणाली भी मजबूत है और आधुनिक पद्धति के उपयोग के साथ व्यक्तिगत स्तर पर प्रत्येक बच्चे के लिए मुख्य शक्तियों और सुधार के क्षेत्रों का मूल्यांकन करने में मदद करती है।

शिक्षण कार्यक्रम में प्रौद्योगिकी का उपयोग

प्रौद्योगिकी ने समुदायों के बीच बेहतर संपर्क को सक्षम किया है, और शिक्षाविदों को तकनीक को अधिक कार्यप्रणाली और नए युग के शिक्षण के रूप में देखना चाहिए, न कि शिक्षक के विकल्प के रूप में। सीखने को अधिक स्वाभाविक बनाने के लिए प्रौद्योगिकी का उपयोग भविष्य की कुंजी है। जब हमारा दैनिक जीवन तकनीक से सशक्त होता है, तो कोई कारण नहीं है कि शिक्षण-अधिगम को इससे वंचित रखा जाए।

अंतर तब बना रहता है जब छात्रों को केवल पारंपरिक तरीकों का उपयोग करके पढ़ाया जाता है, और कार्यस्थल प्रौद्योगिकी के उपयोग से भरा होता है। कक्षाओं में प्रौद्योगिकी के उपयोग से छात्रों के सीखने की अवस्था में कई सकारात्मक बदलाव आए हैं। एआर/वीआर, एआई, ब्लॉकचेन वर्तमान है, न कि केवल भविष्य। आर्टिफिशियल इंटेलिजेंस, ऑगमेंटेड रियलिटी, ऑटोमेशन, रोबोटिक्स, वर्चुअल रियलिटी, डिजिटल मार्केटिंग आदि के समामेलन ने शिक्षा क्षेत्र में क्रांति ला दी है। स्कूल इन विषयों के लिए निर्मित प्रयोगशालाओं को शामिल कर रहे हैं। प्रौद्योगिकी के उपयोग ने अंतःविषय सीखने और शोध-आधारित नवाचार पर प्रभाव डाला है।

एक और बात का ध्यान रखना चाहिए: आप कक्षा में मानवीय हस्तक्षेप की जगह नहीं ले सकते। कई 'परामर्शदाताओं' ने अक्सर सलाह दी है कि स्कूल प्रणाली में पाठ योजनाएँ स्वतः संचालित होनी चाहिए, जो शिक्षकों को अप्रासंगिक बना देंगी। यह एक मिथक है। कक्षा में एक अंतःक्रिया भावनाओं, नेतृत्व और टीम कौशल, साथियों से सीखने, कक्षा प्रबंधन और प्रश्न पूछने से भरी होती है। सिमुलेशन के उपयोग से सीखने को कक्षा से बाहर उपलब्ध होने की ओर ले जाता है। यह तेजी से छात्र जुड़ाव बढ़ाता है और

उच्च प्रतिधारण सुनिश्चित करता है। फ्लिप की गई कक्षा की अवधारणा जहाँ सीखना बच्चे को जाता है न कि इसके विपरीत, पारंपरिक शिक्षण विधियों की तुलना में निवेश पर अधिक लाभ होता है। यह नए करियर विकल्पों के लिए विस्ता खोलता है जो औद्योगिक क्रांति के लिए स्वाभाविक रूप से महत्वपूर्ण हैं

जरूरत है बच्चे को नए विचारों से परिचित कराने की और उन्हें विपरीत परिस्थितियों और चुनौतियों के लिए तैयार करने की। सबसे बड़ी चुनौती न केवल छात्रों बल्कि शिक्षकों का भी विकास करना है। शिक्षक संवेदीकरण कार्यक्रम शिक्षा के भविष्य के लिए एक आवश्यकता है।

अनिश्चितता, नई नौकरी की भूमिकाएं और जिम्मेदारियां, कार्यक्रम और सामग्री के अनुकूल होने की क्षमता आधुनिक शिक्षा का मूल रूप बनेगी। एक स्मार्ट और गतिशील पाठ्यक्रम सबसे अच्छा निवेश है जो एक स्कूल छात्रों को कल की ज्ञान अर्थव्यवस्था के लिए तैयार करने के लिए कर सकता है।

आधुनिक शिक्षा प्रणाली (21 वीं सदी की शिक्षा) के फायदे

दूरस्थ शिक्षा: आप किसी भी विश्वविद्यालय में अध्ययन कर सकते हैं। यहां तक कि अगर आप वहां नहीं जा सकते हैं या आप इसके लिए भुगतान नहीं कर सकते हैं, तो यह आपको घर से ऑनलाइन अध्ययन करने में सक्षम बनाता है। हर विश्वविद्यालय दूरस्थ शिक्षा को भी महत्व देता है। दूरस्थ शिक्षा आपको किसी भी पाठ्यक्रम को चुनने में मदद करती है जो आपको और आपके करियर को फिट करती है।

लचीलापन: आप किसी भी समय कहीं से भी सीख सकते हैं, परिसर की यात्रा करने की कोई आवश्यकता नहीं है। आप अपनी गति से एक सुविधा सीखने में सक्षम हैं।

छात्र-केंद्रित: ऑनलाइन शिक्षा छात्र-केंद्रित है। छात्र उन क्षेत्रों पर अधिक ध्यान केंद्रित करता है जहां उन्हें सुधारने की आवश्यकता होती है और उन्हें गहरा ज्ञान देता है।

कम लागत: कोई यात्रा लागत नहीं है क्योंकि आप घर से सीख सकते हैं। कक्षा और प्रशिक्षकों के लिए फीस का भुगतान करने की आवश्यकता नहीं है।

आधुनिक शिक्षा प्रणाली (21 वीं सदी की शिक्षा) के नुकसान

सामाजिक संपर्क की कमी: ऑनलाइन शिक्षण पाठ्यक्रम स्व-पुस्तक पाठ्यक्रम हैं। यह शिक्षार्थियों को अपने साथियों के साथ संबंध विकसित करना मुश्किल बनाता है। सीमित सामाजिक संपर्क और कोई आमने-सामने बातचीत नहीं।

विचलित होने का मौका: शिक्षार्थी जो कम दृढ़ हैं और आत्म-प्रेरणा की कमी है, उनके विचलित होने का मौका बहुत अधिक है। शिक्षार्थी अपनी पढ़ाई का ट्रैक खो देते हैं और कुछ और करते हैं।

शिक्षार्थी अलग-थलग हो जाते हैं: शिक्षार्थियों की बाहरी दुनिया के साथ कोई बातचीत नहीं होती है, इससे शिक्षार्थी को अकेला और अलग-थलग महसूस करने का एक उच्च मौका मिलता है।

पारंपरिक शिक्षा बनाम आधुनिक शिक्षा

पारंपरिक और आधुनिक शिक्षा दोनों एक-दूसरे से संबंधित हैं और एक-दूसरे से अलग भी हैं। हमारे देश के शुरुआती इतिहास में, एक समय था जब स्कूल नहीं थे। बच्चों ने अपने पूर्वजों से शिक्षा या ज्ञान प्राप्त किया। उस समय यह ज्ञान केवल जीवित रहने के लिए आवश्यक कौशल पर केंद्रित था। जंगलों में रहने वाले लोगों को अपने पूर्वजों से शिक्षा मिली, जिन्होंने उन्हें सिखाया कि अपने भोजन के लिए जानवरों का शिकार कैसे करें, विभिन्न उद्देश्यों के लिए जानवरों की खाल का उपयोग कैसे करें, उपकरण कैसे बनाएं। उन्हें उनके अनुष्ठानों या उनके द्वारा पालन किए जाने वाले रीति-रिवाजों के बारे में सिखाया गया था। उन्हें पालन किए गए धर्मों के बारे में सिखाया गया था।

उन्होंने उन्हें अपने देवताओं और राजाओं की कहानियां सिखाईं जिनसे वे अच्छी नैतिकता सीख सकते थे। राजा अपने बेटों को उन स्कूलों में भेजते थे जिन्हें भारत में गुरुकुल कहा जाता था। इन गुरुकुलों में उन्हें सिखाया गया कि विभिन्न हथियारों का उपयोग कैसे करें, अपनी रक्षा कैसे करें और अपने दुश्मनों पर कैसे हमला करें। उन्हें साम्राज्य पर शासन करने का मूल सिद्धांत भी सिखाया गया था। इस प्रकार के स्कूल स्थानीय आबादी के लिए नहीं थे। इसे केवल शाही परिवारों द्वारा ही एक्सेस किया जा सकता था।

साम्राज्य के बाकी बच्चों ने वह कौशल सीखा जो उनके माता-पिता के पास था। जैसे-जैसे आने वाले वर्षों में लोकतांत्रिक सरकार की स्थापना हुई, शिक्षा का महत्व पूरे देश में फैल गया। स्कूल ऐसे खोले गए जहां किसी भी तरह के विद्यार्थी आकर पढ़ाई कर सकें। यह आधुनिक शिक्षा की स्थापना थी।

आज का परिदृश्य

शिक्षा का परिदृश्य जो अब कुछ वर्ष पहले के परिदृश्य से बिल्कुल अलग है, उस समय आधुनिक शिक्षा को अच्छा नहीं माना जाता था और आज पारंपरिक शिक्षा को पर्याप्त नहीं माना जाता है। जैसे-जैसे लोगों की जरूरतें बदल रही हैं, वैसे-वैसे शिक्षा व्यवस्था को भी बदलना होगा। इस बदलाव को जनता को स्वीकार करना चाहिए। पहले लोग अपने बच्चों को सिखाते थे कि उनकी जरूरतों को कैसे पूरा किया जाए। शिक्षा के पीछे यही बुनियादी उद्देश्य था। और अब लक्ष्य वही है। केवल एक चीज जो बदल गई है वह है लोगों की जरूरत। बीतते समय के साथ, जो चीजें उस समय एक लक्ष्य थीं, उन्होंने अब बुनियादी जरूरतों का गठन किया है। जैसे-जैसे जरूरतें बढ़ती गईं, शिक्षा को बढ़ाना पड़ा। अगर शिक्षा का विकास नहीं हुआ तो आज की जरूरतों को पूरा करना मुश्किल होगा।

शिक्षा में समानता

स्कूलों में प्रदान की जाने वाली पारंपरिक शिक्षा सभी बच्चों के लिए नहीं थी। बच्चों के बीच काफी भेदभाव होता था। यह माना जाता था कि शिक्षा केवल उच्च समाज के लोगों के लिए है। निचले समाज के परिवारों से ताल्लुक रखने वाले बच्चों को स्कूलों में प्रवेश की अनुमति नहीं थी। पारंपरिक शिक्षा हर किसी के लिए नहीं थी। आधुनिक शिक्षा सभी के द्वारा सुलभ है। कोई भी स्कूल में

प्रवेश ले सकता है और आधुनिक शिक्षा सीख सकता है। हम कह सकते हैं कि आधुनिक शिक्षा के कारण ही आधुनिक शिक्षा सभी बच्चों तक पहुंच पाती है। जैसे-जैसे आधुनिक शिक्षा का प्रसार हुआ, समानता का सिद्धांत सिखाया गया।

जैसा कि ऊपर उल्लेख किया गया है, पारंपरिक शिक्षा में छात्रों को परंपराओं, रीति-रिवाजों, अनुष्ठानों और धर्म के बारे में पढ़ाया जाता है। आधुनिक शिक्षा में छात्रों को विज्ञान, प्रौद्योगिकी, भाषा कौशल और गणित आदि के बारे में पढ़ाया जाता है। पारंपरिक शिक्षा प्रणाली में दिया जाने वाला ज्ञान अपने जीवन यापन के लिए पर्याप्त था, लेकिन यह पूरी दुनिया से मेल खाने के लिए पर्याप्त नहीं था।

आधुनिक शिक्षा प्रणाली और पारंपरिक शिक्षा प्रणाली के बीच तुलना

आधुनिक शिक्षा प्रणाली में, शिक्षार्थी लचीले समय में सीखने में सक्षम होते हैं, जबकि पारंपरिक शिक्षा में एक निश्चित समय होता है।

ऑनलाइन शिक्षा में शिक्षार्थी अलग-अलग उम्र, विभिन्न राष्ट्रीयता, विभिन्न व्यवसायों आदि वाले लोगों का एक विषम समूह है। जबकि पारंपरिक शिक्षा में शिक्षार्थी एक ही आयु वर्ग के लोगों का एक सजातीय समूह हैं।

- पारंपरिक शिक्षा महंगी है, पाठ्यक्रम की किताबें, ट्यूशन फीस, कक्षा सेटअप, आदि ऑनलाइन शिक्षा की तुलना में बड़ी मात्रा में धन राशि है। आधुनिक शिक्षा प्रणाली के लिए किसी भी कक्षा सेटअप, पाठ्यक्रम की किताबों आदि की आवश्यकता नहीं है, इसलिए यह तुलनात्मक रूप से कम लागत है।

ऑनलाइन शिक्षार्थी एक ही समय में विभिन्न विश्वविद्यालयों द्वारा पेश किए जाने वाले पाठ्यक्रमों को सीखने में सक्षम हैं। पारंपरिक शिक्षा शिक्षार्थियों को वापस रखती है क्योंकि वे एक समय में केवल एक ही पाठ्यक्रम सीखने में सक्षम होते हैं। पारंपरिक शिक्षा में विदेशी विश्वविद्यालयों से पाठ्यक्रम सीखना बहुत मुश्किल है। इसलिए एक ऑनलाइन शिक्षार्थी कम समय में विभिन्न पाठ्यक्रमों के प्रमाण पत्र प्राप्त करने में सक्षम होता है जबकि पारंपरिक में इसमें बहुत अधिक समय लगता है।

पारंपरिक शिक्षा में, परीक्षाएं समय की अवधि के बाद आयोजित की जाती हैं, एक शब्द या सेमेस्टर कर्से पाठ्यक्रमों का मैन्युअल रूप से मूल्यांकन किया जाता है। जबकि आधुनिक शिक्षा में स्वचालित मूल्यांकन के साथ प्रत्येक विषय के बाद परीक्षा आयोजित की जाती है।

ऑनलाइन सीखना सीखने की सामग्री का एक असीमित स्रोत प्रदान करता है जबकि पारंपरिक में सीखने के स्रोत सीमित होते हैं।

कौन सी शिक्षा सबसे अच्छा से बेहतर है?

दोनों प्रकार की शिक्षा का अपना स्थान और महत्व है। हम किसी भी प्रकार की शिक्षा को अच्छा या बुरा घोषित नहीं कर सकते। पारंपरिक अपने काल में अच्छा था और आधुनिक शिक्षा अपने काल में अच्छी है। वास्तव में, यह व्यक्ति पर निर्भर करता है। यह इस बात पर निर्भर करता है कि व्यक्ति क्या सीखना चाहता है। यदि कोई व्यक्ति अपने रीति-रिवाजों और धर्म के बारे में जानना चाहता है, तो निश्चित रूप से पारंपरिक शिक्षा उसके लिए बेहतर है। वहीं अगर कोई व्यक्ति विज्ञान या गणित के बारे में सीखना

चाहता है तो आधुनिक शिक्षा उसके लिए अच्छी है। दोनों प्रकार की शिक्षाएं समान रूप से महत्वपूर्ण हैं। पारंपरिक शिक्षित अक्सर हमारी संस्कृति से जुड़ा होता है। और यह अच्छा है या हम कह सकते हैं कि अपनी संस्कृति के बारे में जानना महत्वपूर्ण है। हर किसी को चाहिए कि उनकी परंपराएं, संस्कृति और उनके धर्म की कहानियां और मान्यताएं क्या हैं। इसी तरह, आज होने वाले आधुनिक विकास के संदर्भ में दुनिया के साथ पकड़ना भी उतना ही महत्वपूर्ण है। यह आधुनिक शिक्षा के महत्व का वर्णन करता है। पूरी दुनिया के संपर्क में रहने और यह देखने के लिए आधुनिक शिक्षा की आवश्यकता है कि दुनिया में क्या हो रहा है।

समाप्ति

यह अनुमान लगाना मुश्किल है कि कौन सी शिक्षा बेहतर है। दोनों प्रकारों का अपना महत्व है। दोनों प्रकार भी एक-दूसरे के समान और एक-दूसरे से भिन्न हैं। आधुनिक शिक्षा पारंपरिक शिक्षा से विरासत में मिली है। लेकिन आधुनिक शिक्षा के कारण, पारंपरिक शिक्षा की उपेक्षा की जा रही है जिसके परिणामस्वरूप हमारी संस्कृति खो जाएगी। परम्परागत शिक्षा और आधुनिक शिक्षा दोनों को समान महत्व दिया जाना चाहिए।

संदर्भ

"शिक्षण के तरीके, शैक्षिक अनुसंधान की समीक्षा, वॉल्यूम 6, नंबर 3, पीपी। सीखने का मनोविज्ञान, शिक्षण के सामान्य तरीके और पर्यवेक्षण। जून 1936।

"शिक्षण विधियां: इतिहास और स्थिति। शिक्षण विधियां: सीखने के लिए डिज़ाइन "एक शांत एचके, 5 मिलियन कमना चाहते हैं? हांगकांग ट्यूटोरियल स्कूल प्रतिद्वंद्वी संस्थान से शीर्ष शिक्षक का शिकार करने की कोशिश करता है"। साउथ चाइना मॉर्निंग पोस्ट 9 अक्टूबर 2015।

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26. आत्मनिर्भर भारत निर्माण में भारतीय संस्कृति का योगदान: २१ वीं सदी कौशल विकास के सन्दर्भ में

डॉ.शिवदत्त आर्य³⁷

सारांश

भारतीय संस्कृति विश्व की प्राचीन संस्कृति है। यह संस्कृति सभी के कल्याण की सद्भावना के साथ ही आत्म कल्याण, आत्मोन्नति, आत्मज्ञान स्वजागरण एवं आत्मनिर्भरता हेतु दिशा प्रदान करती है। भारतीय संस्कृति एक सुदीर्घ संस्कार परंपरा का नाम है। भारतीय संस्कृति मानव समुदाय की आत्मा है। भारतीय संस्कृति के नाम से हम जिस संस्कृति का स्मरण करते हैं, उस संस्कृति का परिचय वेद, उपवेद, वेदांग, दार्शनिक, पौराणिक, ऐतिहासिक और धार्मिक साहित्य की अनेक विधाओं का परिशीलन करने से प्राप्त हो सकता है। भारतीय संस्कृत साहित्य यथा वेद, उपनिषद्, पुराण, वाल्मीकिरामायण, महाभारत, श्रीमद्भगवद्गीता में आत्मनिर्भर हेतु अनेक अनुकरणीय उदाहरण दिए गए हैं, जिनका अनुकरण मानव वर्तमान में कर सकता है। श्रीमद्भगवद्गीता में भगवान् श्रीकृष्ण ने स्वनिर्माण हेतु उपदेश दिया है-

उद्धरेदात्मनात्मानं नात्मानमवसादयेत् ।

आत्मैव ह्यात्मनो बन्धुरात्मैव रिपुरात्मनः ॥ (अध्याय-6 श्लोक 5)

अर्थात् व्यक्ति अपना स्वयं ही मित्र है स्वयं ही शत्रु है, वह अपना विकास एवं नाश स्वयं ही करता है, अतः मानव को स्व जागरण हेतु दृढ संकल्प लेते हुए सार्थक कार्यों में निरंतर संलग्न रहना चाहिए।

२१ वीं सदी में विविध क्षेत्रों में कौशल विकास के माध्यम से एक ऐसे सशक्त आत्मनिर्भर भारत का निर्माण हो रहा है जो कि पूरे विश्व को एक समुचित दिशा प्रदान कर सकता है। विश्व समुदाय के लिए इस महत्वपूर्ण कार्य सम्पादन हेतु भारत को विविध कौशलों तथा वर्तमान की शिक्षा तकनीकों से समृद्ध होना होगा तथा मार्ग में आने वाले विविध कठिनाइयों को भी दृष्टिगत रखना होगा। विविध समस्याओं के समाधान हेतु भारतीय संस्कृति में निहित उदात्त तत्वों का अनुसरण करना होगा। इसी संदर्भ में इस पत्र में चर्चा की जाएगी।

Keywords: भारतीय संस्कृति, आत्मनिर्भर भारत, कौशल विकास, NEP 2020

भूमिका

भारतीय संस्कृति

भारतीय संस्कृति एक सुदीर्घ संस्कार परंपरा का नाम है। भारतीय संस्कृति विश्व की प्राचीन संस्कृति है। यह संस्कृति सभी के कल्याण की सद्भावना के साथ ही आत्म कल्याण, आत्मोन्नति, आत्मज्ञान एवं आत्म निर्भरता हेतु दिशा प्रदान करती है। भारतीय संस्कृति

³⁷ सहायक आचार्य, शिक्षापीठ, श्री ला.ब.शा.रा.संस्कृत विश्वविद्यालय, नई दिल्ली

मानव समुदाय की आत्मा है। भारतीय संस्कृति के नाम से हम जिस संस्कृति का स्मरण करते हैं, उस संस्कृति का परिचय वेद, उपवेद, वेदांग, दार्शनिक, पौराणिक, ऐतिहासिक और धार्मिक साहित्य की अनेक विधाओं का परिशीलन करने से प्राप्त हो सकता है। भारतीय संस्कृति का मूल वेदों में सन्निहित है। वेदों की अपौरुषेय वाणी स्पष्ट रूप से यह निर्देश देती है की मानव को अपना आत्मिक विकास सामाजिक नियमों के अनुरूप तथा भारतीय संस्कृति के मर्यादाओं के अनुरूप करना है और अपना जीवन सार्थक बनाना है। वैदिक अनुसंधान से हमें मूलभूत तत्त्वों की उपलब्धि होती है जो वैदिक संस्कृति का परिचय प्राप्त करने में बहुत उपयोगी सिद्ध होती है। शरीर पर आवरण धारण करने से लेकर आत्मा पर से अनात्म तत्त्व का निवारण करने तक जो जो समीचीन क्रियाएं की जाती हैं, उन सब का संस्कृति में समावेश हो जाता है।

मानव जीवन अधिक अनमोल है इस जीवन को सार्थक बनाने हेतु अपने में निहित शक्तियों एवं गुणों की पहचान करना अत्यंत आवश्यक है। अपने स्वत्व को पहचान कर अपनी सामर्थ्य के अनुसार मानव स्वकल्याण के साथ-साथ विश्व कल्याण में निरंतर संलग्न रहे, यही मानव जीवन का परम कर्तव्य है परंतु वर्तमान जीवन में व्यक्ति अनेकानेक सुविधाओं का लाभ लेने के उपरांत भी अपने कर्तव्य कार्यों में संलग्न नहीं हो रहा है, जिसके कारण सामाजिक संरचनाओं में परिवर्तन परिलक्षित हो रहा है। भारतीय संस्कृति में व्यक्ति के सर्वांगीण विकास हेतु शिक्षा के विविध स्वरूपों के महत्व पर बल दिया गया है, जिससे मानव नैसर्गिक गुणों के अनुरूप व्यक्तित्व विकास करता था तथा सामर्थ्य अनुसार सामाजिक विकास के लिए भी तत्पर रहता था। तकनीकी सुविधाओं के कारण व्यक्ति आत्म को जानने का प्रयास न करके निरर्थक कार्यों में अधिकाधिक संलग्न रहता है। विवेकानंद जी ने कहा है कि उठो, जागो और लक्ष्य प्राप्ति हेतु निरंतर प्रयास करते रहो। वाल्मीकि रामायण की कथा से प्राप्त शिक्षा मानव हेतु उपादेय है, उसको अपने जीवन में उतारने से सच्ची मानवता आती है। भारतीय संस्कृति हमें धर्म निष्ठ आध्यात्मिक मार्ग का अनुसरण करते हुए आसक्ति रहित कर्म योग की ही शिक्षा प्रदान करती है। रामायण और महाभारत को भारतीय संस्कृति का स्पष्ट चित्र माना गया है। आज भी मानवीय संस्कारों के उद्बोधन और संरक्षण के लिए रामायण, महाभारत और श्रीमद्भगवद्गीता जैसे अनेक महत्वपूर्ण धार्मिक ग्रन्थों के उपाख्यानों को समाहित किया गया है।

- गुरुकुल प्रणाली का योगदान
- चौसठ कलाओं का योगदान

आत्मनिर्भरता हेतु पुरुषार्थ चतुष्टय का योगदान

मानव जीवन का लक्ष्य पुरुषार्थ चतुष्टय की प्राप्ति ही है, क्योंकि प्रवृत्ति में प्रयोजन कारण है। प्रवृत्ति इष्टात्मक होती है, निवृत्ति अनिष्टात्मक प्रत्येक मानव इष्ट साधना के बिना किसी कर्म में प्रवृत्त नहीं होता। ऐसी स्थिति में प्रत्येक प्राणी के लिए 'धर्म, अर्थ, काम' ये तीन लौकिक प्रयोजन माने गए हैं तथा अन्तिम प्रयोजन मोक्ष है, जिससे अभ्युदय और निःश्रेयस् की सिद्धि हो, वह धर्म कहा जाता है (यतोऽभ्युदय निःश्रेयससिद्धिः स धर्मः, (कणादसूत्र- १/१/२) अथवा चोदनालक्षणोऽर्थो धर्मः पूर्वमीमांसा-१/१/२ के अनुसार शास्त्रोक्त कर्म में प्रवृत्त होना धर्म है। अर्थात् वेदों में प्रयुक्त अनुशासनों के अनुसार चलना ही धर्म है। धर्म का सम्बन्ध उन क्रिया संस्कारों से है, जिनसे आनन्द की प्राप्ति होती है और जो वेदों द्वारा प्रेरित एवं प्रशंसित है। महर्षि वेद व्यास ने धार्मिक भावना की ओर संकेत करते हुए कहा है-जो तुम्हारे लिए प्रतिकूल हो वह दूसरों के साथ मत करो, यही धर्म है। इसी के अनुरूप तुम्हें आचरण करना चाहिए।

श्रूयतां धर्मं सर्वस्वं श्रुत्वा चाप्यवधार्यताम्।
आत्मनः प्रतिकूलानि परेषां न समाचरेत् ॥ (महाभारत)

कहने का तात्पर्य यह है कि धर्म, मानव को राग-द्वेष, असत्य भाषण, अनैतिक -व्यवहार, पापाचार में प्रवृत्ति और ईश्वर अथवा उसके अंश रूप में परिलक्षित मानव जाति के प्रति अनास्था पर अंकुश लगाते हुए सत् कार्यों और सद्-वृत्ति में प्रवृत्त करता है। आदि शंकराचार्य ने कहा भी है- जो जगत् की स्थिरता और प्राणियों के उत्कर्ष और समृद्धि का कारण है, वही धर्म है। मानव-जाति के उत्कर्ष के लिए धर्म एकमात्र ऐसा कारण है, जो विभिन्न जातियों और सम्प्रदायों में विभक्त लोगों को बिना किसी भेद-भाव के समान रूप से मानवता के सूत्र में पिरोते हुए विश्व बन्धुत्व की भावना को विकसित करता है तथा आपसी सहयोग, सह-अस्तित्व और सद्भाव से रहने की प्रेरणा प्रदान करता है। छान्दोग्योपनिषद् में सद्-वृत्ति के विधान को स्पष्ट करते हुए धर्म को तीन शाखाओं में विभक्त किया किया है।

धर्म वह मानसिक गुण है, जो व्यक्ति को व्यक्ति से जोड़ता है। 'धारणाद् धर्मः' यह उसकी अर्थानुकूल व्युत्पत्ति है। श्रुति, स्मृति, सदाचार और उन्नत आत्मा को अभीष्ट लगने वाले कार्य धर्म हैं। शास्त्र और लोक ने जिस कार्य को उचित ठहराया है, वह धर्म है और जिसका निषेध किया है, वह अधर्म है। इस प्रकार धृति, क्षमा, दम, अस्तेय, शौच, इंद्रिय निग्रह, धी, विद्या, सत्य और अक्रोध यह धर्म के दस लक्षण हैं। ये दस लक्षण समाज के निर्माण, सभ्यता के विकास और संस्कृति के लिए परम आवश्यक हैं। धर्म मानव जीवन के विकास का एक प्रमुख स्तंभ है। महाभारत में महर्षि व्यास ने धर्म को काम और अर्थ को पवित्र बनाने का साधन मानते हैं उनका अभिप्राय है की धर्म से अनुशासित कार्य भी पवित्र पुरुषार्थ बन जाता है।

अध्यात्म के माध्यम से आत्मनिर्भरता

भारतीय संस्कृति में अध्यात्म एक ऐसा तत्व है जिसके माध्यम से लौकिक और पारलौकिक जीवन सफल बनाया जा सकता है। मानव जीवन विषयों के भोगों के लिए नहीं अस्तित्व देवत्व की प्राप्ति तथा मोक्ष की प्राप्ति हेतु होता है। परंतु वर्तमान समय में मनुष्य मोक्ष प्राप्ति के लक्ष्य से हट गया है तथा वह लौकिक जीवन व्यतीत कर रहा है तथा अनेक माननीय अवगुणों से ग्रसित हो गया है। विश्व के कण-कण में ईश्वर व्याप्त हैं अतः इस संपूर्ण संसार के चर अचर जीवों में ईश्वरी भावना का विकास करना ही अध्यात्म कहलाता है और जब यह भाव व्यक्ति के अंतर्गत आ जाता है तब उस व्यक्ति का स्व जागरण होता है। सदाचार का पालन करना, वर्ण व्यवस्था, आश्रम व्यवस्था, कर्म वाद, मोक्ष, वेदों में निहित ज्ञान, यज्ञ का महत्व, सत्य का परिपालन करना, अहिंसा पालन, त्याग का महत्व, तपोमय जीवन, माता पिता एवं गुरु भक्ति, प्रकृति के अनुरूप कार्य करना, छोटे बड़ों का सम्मान करना, धैर्य रखना, परोपकार करना और सर्वत्र शांति बनाए रखने में सहयोग करना यह सभी कार्य हमें भारतीय संस्कृति सिखाती है तथा आत्मनिर्भर बनने में सहयोग भी करती है।

आत्मनिर्भर भारत निर्माण में NEP 2020 की संकल्पना

आत्मनिर्भरता का तात्पर्य व्यापार और रोजगार नहीं है। आत्मनिर्भरता का तात्पर्य स्वाभिमान और आत्मरक्षा है। हम सुरक्षित हम स्वाभिमानी रहेंगे, हम परावलंबी नहीं होंगे, हम अपनी रक्षा करेंगे, अपने जीवन को बेहतर बनाएंगे और जीवन को बेहतर बनाने के यत्न करेंगे, यह कर सकने की क्षमता भारत के पास है। आत्मनिर्भर भारत के लिए एक ऐसी शिक्षा प्रणाली की आवश्यकता है जो

सतत् सीखने रहने की कला को विकसित कर सके, जिससे रोजगार के क्षेत्र में आ रहे विविध परिवर्तनों को समझने और उसका मुकाबला करने की योग्यता निर्मित हो सके। जब दुनिया तेजी से परिवर्तन के दौर से गुजर रही है बिग डेटा, मशीन लर्निंग, आर्टिफिशियल इंटेलिजेंस आदि वैज्ञानिक ज्ञान विधियों और तकनीकी के कारण से सर्वत्र अकुशल कामगारों के स्थान मशीनें लेने लगी है। तो दूसरी ओर ज्ञान और तकनीकी के क्षेत्र में उभर रहे उपर्युक्त नए क्षेत्रों में कुशल और निपुण मनुष्यों की आवश्यकता बढ़ी है, इसकी पूर्ति के लिए समूची शिक्षा का बदला जाना आवश्यक है। इस परिवर्तन के संकेत राष्ट्रीय शिक्षा नीति 2020 में दिखाई दे रहे हैं।

आत्मनिर्भर भारत की निर्मित के लिए ऐसे युवाओं को तैयार किया जाये जो समस्याओं के समाधान में निपुण हो, समीक्षात्मक बुद्धि, सृजनात्मक कल्पना से सम्पन्न हो, नया सोचे और नयी जानकारियों को निरंतर बदलती परिस्थितियों और क्षेत्रों में उपयोग कर सके। जिसका विकास एक ऐसे संतुलित व्यक्ति के रूप में हो जो जीवन के सभी पक्षों और समय की सभी आवश्यकताओं की पूर्ति करने में सक्षम हो तथा सीखने की प्रक्रिया को रुचिकर बनाए। इसके लिए शिक्षा नीति ने यह प्रस्तावित किया है कि सभी पाठ्यक्रम में विज्ञान, गणित, बुनियादी कला शिल्प के साथ-साथ मानविकी और खेल का भी समावेश हो। इस प्रकार की शिक्षा ही उत्पादकता के गुणों का विकास करेगी। इस प्रकार की शिक्षा ही भारत को संपूर्ण विश्व के परिदृश्य में एक ऐसे राष्ट्र के रूप में स्थापित करेगी, जो आत्मनिर्भर तो होगा ही संपूर्ण विश्व के संचालन में श्रेष्ठ और बेहतर योगदान करने वाला होगा। इसको हम गांधी की बुनियादी शिक्षा का 21वीं शताब्दी की आवश्यकताओं के अनुरूप भारत की निर्मित के रूप में एक विस्तार भी समझ सकते हैं।

यह सब केवल और केवल तभी संभव होगा जब पढ़ाई का अर्थ नौकरी नहीं रोजगार होगा रोजगार का अर्थ दूसरे के द्वारा काम के अवसर उपलब्ध कराना नहीं है अपितु इसका एकमात्र अर्थ है ज्ञान और कौशल से सम्पन्न युवा में उसे उद्यमिता का विकास हो, जो उनको साहस के साथ दूसरों को रोजगार देने में सक्षम बना सके। ऐसी ही शिक्षा की कल्पना संपूर्ण मनुष्य के निर्माण के लिए स्वामी विवेकानंद ने की थी। आत्मनिर्भर भारत, मनुष्य और समाज की निर्मित के लिए ही पंडित मदनमोहन मालवीय ने एक ऐसे विश्वविद्यालय की कल्पना की थी जिसमें वेद से लेकर परमाणु ऊर्जा, विज्ञान तक की पढ़ाई एक छत के नीचे हो और इन सभी विद्या स्थानों की सूचना से समन्वित ऐसे युवाओं का निर्माण होगा जो नया भारत गढ़ेंगे। यह नया भारत ही स्वातंत्र्य समर का स्वप्न था जिसको शिक्षा नीति में आमूल-चूल परिवर्तन कर साकार करने का यत्न प्रारंभ हो गया है।

राष्ट्रीय शिक्षा नीति में यह कठिन किन्तु संभव बात यह है कि वह विद्यार्थियों को वास्तविक अर्थों में सीखने के लिए प्रेरित करे एवं उनमें वैश्विक क्षमताओं एवं भारतीय जीवन मूल्यों पर आधारित कौशलों के विकास द्वारा उनके जीवन को सार्थक बनाये। अधिगम की सैद्धान्तिकी एवं विमर्श, ज्ञान की बदलती संरचनाओं के सापेक्ष एक नए प्रतिमान को गढ़ रहा है, जिसमें ज्ञान के विषय-वस्तु के साथ-साथ अधिगमकर्ता की 'अधिगमार्थ तत्परता एवं कौशल दक्षता' एक बुनियादी आवश्यकता है, जहाँ सीखने के साथ ही क्या और कैसे सीखना है' के प्रश्न केंद्रीय भूमिका में है। सीखना महज एक मानसिक कौशल नहीं अपितु एक ज्ञानमीमांसीय परिघटना और जीवन पर्यंत चलने वाली बौद्धिक सर्जना (लाइफ लॉन्ग लर्निंग) है। 'जीवन पर्यंत सीखना' अधिगम की यह अनुभाविक प्रक्रिया ही भारतीय ज्ञान संस्कृति की मूल प्रविधि रही है, जहां सीखना एक सहयोगात्मक एवं उद्देश्यपरक परियोजना के रूप में उद्घाटित होती है। जो अपने आप में जीवन कौशल एवं मूल्यों को संवर्धित करने की एक गत्यात्मक संज्ञानात्मक प्रक्रिया है। अतएव राष्ट्रीय शिक्षा नीति-2020 अधिगम के इस समुच्चय के सांस्कृतिक अधिष्ठान की पुनर्स्थापक सिद्ध हो सकती है। अतएव कहा जा सकता है कि

भारत विद्यार्थी केन्द्रित, कौशल विकास आधारित एवं भारत को पुनः जगत गुरु बनाने की क्षमता रखने वाली राष्ट्रीय शिक्षा नीति 2020 ने भारत को आत्म-निर्भर बनने का मार्ग प्रशस्त कर दिया है।

भारतीय संस्कृति जहाँ एक ओर राष्ट्रीय विकास के लिए वैयक्तिक और सामाजिक उत्थान की अनिवार्यता सिद्ध करते हुए आचरण सम्बन्धित शिक्षा प्रदान करती है, वहाँ विभिन्न व्यावसायिक क्षेत्रों से सम्बन्धित ज्ञान-सरिता का बोध करा कर आत्म-निर्भरता प्रदान करती है। आत्म निर्भरता के अभाव में कोई भी राष्ट्र उत्कर्ष को प्राप्त नहीं कर सकता। इसी दृष्टि से जहाँ एक ओर नागरिकों के वैयक्तिक आचरण को उन्नत करने के लिए नैतिक शिक्षा की अनिवार्यता पर बल दिया गया है, वहाँ राष्ट्रीय आवश्यकताओं की पूर्ति हेतु औपचारिक शिक्षा के माध्यम से ज्ञान पक्ष को भी महत्त्व दिया गया है। ज्ञान पक्ष के विकास के माध्यम से ही आज राष्ट्र वैज्ञानिक उपलब्धियों के माध्यम से उन्नत शिखर पर पहुँचने का प्रयास कर रहा है। यह राष्ट्रीय भावना की ही महिमा है कि आज मानव राष्ट्र-गौरव को उन्नत करता हुआ चाँद पर पहुँच गया है। यह सब वैज्ञानिक और व्यावसायिक कुशलता का ही फल है कि राष्ट्र आत्मनिर्भरता को प्राप्त होता हुआ स्वावलम्बी बन गया है। स्व० लालबहादुर शास्त्री के हरित क्रान्ति के नारे ने खाद्यान्न पूर्ति की समस्या का समाधान कृषि विज्ञान में सक्षम वैज्ञानिकों ने निकाल लिया है। आज हमें खाद्यान्न पूर्ति के लिए किसी अन्य राष्ट्र पर निर्भर नहीं होना पड़ता। रोटी, कपड़ा और मकान की पूर्ति का दायित्व राष्ट्रीय शासन व्यवस्था पर है, जिसे उपलब्ध करने में राष्ट्रीय सरकार उन्नत योजनाओं को क्रियान्वित कर रही है। योजनाओं के क्रियान्वयन में यही राष्ट्रीय भावना कार्य कर रही है कि राष्ट्र को किस प्रकार उन्नत बनाया जाय।

भारतीय संस्कृति अखंड राष्ट्रीय भावना की सम्पोषिका और संवर्द्धिका है। राष्ट्रीय भावना ही राष्ट्र उत्थान के लिए अमोघ बीज मंत्र है। सभी राष्ट्रों नायक समाजसेवी नागरिक इस मूलमंत्र को दृढ़ता पूर्वक धारण करते हुए देश जनपद तथा गांव आदि में राष्ट्र हित हेतु जन जागरण के लिए तथा आत्मनिर्भरता हेतु अनवरत प्रयत्नशील है। क्योंकि जनमानस में राष्ट्रीय भावना के अभाव में असामाजिक प्रवृत्तियां विकसित होने लगती हैं, जिससे राष्ट्र में विभिन्न प्रकार के उपद्रव, अशांति और भय का वातावरण उत्पन्न होने लगता है। इन दुष्ट प्रवृत्तियों के उपशमन के लिए नागरिकों में राष्ट्रीय भावना का उद्बोधन करना अनिवार्य हो जाता है। अतः वेद, पुराण आदि ग्रंथों में राष्ट्रहित से ओतप्रोत उपदेशात्मक वाक्य परिलक्षित होते हैं। इन ग्रंथों के कल्पवृक्ष की शीतल छाया में ना केवल भारत अपितु विश्व के समस्त राष्ट्र शांति लाभ करते हैं। क्योंकि जनमानस को आदर्श व्यवहारों से नियंत्रित करने में भारतीय संस्कृति की जो अहम भूमिका रही है उसका समग्र विश्व मुक्त कंठ से अभिनंदन करता है। भारतीय संस्कृति के अनुसार सर्वोत्कृष्ट भारत भूमि पर देवगण भी जन्म लेना चाहते हैं। इस पवित्र भूभाग की रक्षा के लिए हमारे पूर्वज ऋषि मनीषियों ने नीति तथा आध्यात्मिक विचारधारा से युक्त प्रवाह को समाज में अनवरत प्रवाहित किया। मातृभूमि के वीर सपूतों ने राष्ट्र सेवा में अपने प्राणों को समर्पित कर दिया। क्योंकि राष्ट्रीय संरक्षण में ही समस्त मानव जाति का संवर्धन और सम्पोषण सन्निहित है।

उपरोक्त तथ्यों से यह स्पष्ट होता है कि आत्मनिर्भर भारत निर्माण में भारतीय संस्कृति का महत्वपूर्ण योगदान है तथा यह संस्कृति आत्मिक कल्याण के साथ-साथ परिवार, समाज, राष्ट्र तथा विश्व के कल्याण के लिए सर्वदा सजग रहने वाली संस्कृति है, अतः हमें अपने राष्ट्र के विकास में सहयोग देने हेतु संस्कृति में सन्निहित उदात्त तत्वों का अनुसरण करना चाहिए जिससे हमारा मानव जीवन सफल, सार्थक एवं उपयोगी होवे।

संदर्भ ग्रंथ

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27. 21वीं सदी की 'शिक्षा' का स्वरूप एवं कौशल विका 'विद्यालय शिक्षकों से अपेक्षा'

डॉ.परमानन्द त्रिपाठी³⁸

सारांश

21वीं सदी की शिक्षा का उद्देश्य, विद्यार्थी को ज्ञान के साथ ही साथ उसमें ऐसे कौशलों का विकास करना है, जिनके द्वारा वह इस युग में होने वाले अप्रत्याशित परिवर्तनों के अनुरूप समायोजन कर सके, उत्पन्न चुनौतियों का सामना कर सके एवं कुशल नागरिक बन समाज एवं राष्ट्र के विकास में योगदान दे सके। आज की प्रतिस्पर्धा ने अत्यधिक कार्यकुशलता की आवश्यकता को बढ़ा दिया है, इसलिए विद्यार्थी के जीवन को सुगम बनाने के लिए शिक्षा में विभिन्न कौशलों के समायोजन की आवश्यकता है। माननीय प्रधानमंत्री ने भी कहा है कि- “आज के युवा, जिनका जन्म 21वीं सदी में हुआ है, भारत की आजादी के 100 वर्ष तक विकास की यात्रा को आगे बढ़ाने जा रहे हैं। इसलिए इस नई युवा पीढ़ी का कौशल विकास एक राष्ट्रीय आवश्यकता है; यह आत्मनिर्भर भारत की आधारशिला है। राष्ट्रीय शिक्षा नीति 2020 में भी उल्लेख है कि- “शिक्षा का उद्देश्य न केवल संज्ञानात्मक विकास होगा, बल्कि चरित्र निर्माण और 21वीं सदी के प्रमुख कौशल से लैस समग्र और बहुमुखी प्रतिभा वाले व्यक्तियों का निर्माण करना होगा”। राष्ट्रीय शिक्षा नीति ने यह लक्ष्य निर्धारित किया है कि 2025 तक स्कूल और उच्च शिक्षा प्रणाली के माध्यम से कम से कम 50% शिक्षार्थियों को व्यवसायिक शिक्षा दी जाएगी, जिससे वे कम से कम एक व्यवसाय सीख सकें तथा अगले दशक में चरणबद्ध तरीके से व्यवसायिक शिक्षा को सभी स्कूलों और उच्च शिक्षण संस्थानों में शामिल किया जायेगा। राष्ट्रीय शिक्षा नीति 2020, स्कूलों में व्यवसायिक शिक्षा के विभिन्न मॉडलों को प्रोत्साहित करती है। इस प्रकार 21वीं सदी की शिक्षा में, 21वीं सदी की जरूरतों के अनुरूप, छात्रों को तैयार करने के लिए कौशल विकास को प्रमुखता देने की आवश्यकता है। इसमें विद्यालय और शिक्षक की भूमिका महत्वपूर्ण होगी क्योंकि विद्यार्थी के जीवन में सबसे अधिक प्रभाव उसके शिक्षक और विद्यालय का पड़ता है।

Keywords: कौशल, परिवर्तन, चुनौती, समायोजन, विकास

प्रस्तावना-

21वीं सदी में वैश्वीकरण, औद्योगीकरण, भौतिकतावाद, तकनीकी, ज्ञान, व्यवसाय और रोजगार की बढ़ती प्रतिस्पर्धा ने अत्यधिक कुशल कार्यबल की आवश्यकता को बढ़ा दिया है, जिस कारण सभी देशों में अपनी गुणवत्ता के मानक को पूरा करने के लिए, विदेशी व्यापार को बढ़ाने के लिए, औद्योगिक और आर्थिक विकास को बढ़ावा देने के लिए, पहले से अधिक कुशल कर्मचारियों की आवश्यकता बढ़ी है। इस प्रकार आज की परिस्थिति में कौशल और ज्ञान किसी भी देश की सामाजिक और आर्थिक विकास के लिए प्रमुख प्रेरक शक्ति बन गया है। इसी कारण 21वीं सदी की शिक्षा प्रणाली का उद्देश्य, विद्यार्थियों को केवल ज्ञान देना नहीं रह गया है, बल्कि उनमें ऐसी कुशलताओं को विकसित करना है, जिनके द्वारा वह आज के युग में होने वाले अप्रत्याशित परिवर्तनों

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से उत्पन्न चुनौतियों का पूर्वानुमान कर सकें, उनका आकलन कर सकें, उसके अनुरूप अपने व्यवहार में वांछित परिवर्तन लाते हुए उनका सामना कर सकें और वह एक कुशल नागरिक के रूप में अपना विकास करते हुए, अपने समाज को वांछित दिशा देने व समाज तथा राष्ट्र के विकास में महत्वपूर्ण भूमिका का निर्वहन कर सकें |

21वीं सदी में मानवता को सामाजिक, आर्थिक और व्यक्तिगत स्तर पर गंभीर चुनौतियों का सामना करना पड़ रहा है | प्रौद्योगिकी के धुआंधार विकास, अविश्वसनीय परिवर्तनों तथा इनसे उत्पन्न परिस्थितियों में आज के विद्यार्थी के जीवन को सुगम बनाने के लिए, शिक्षा के माध्यम से उनमें विभिन्न कौशलों के समायोजन की आवश्यकता है |

आधुनिक शिक्षा का लक्ष्य-

21वीं सदी की शिक्षा का उद्देश्य बच्चों को श्रेष्ठ नागरिक, निर्णायक, समस्या निवारक तथा सक्षम बनाना है | आज के विद्यार्थियों को चाहिए कि वह विद्यालय से ज्ञान प्राप्त करने के साथ ही, अपने अन्दर ऐसी क्षमताओं को विकसित करें जो उसे जीवन में आने वाली चुनौतियों का सामना करने में भी सक्षम बनाये, इसके लिए विद्यालयों को भी पूरी तरह से तैयार रहना होगा | राष्ट्रीय शिक्षा नीति 2020 में भी इस बात का उल्लेख किया गया है कि- इस शिक्षा का उद्देश्य न केवल संज्ञानात्मक विकास होगा बल्कि चरित्र निर्माण और 21वीं सदी के प्रमुख कौशलों से युक्त, समग्र और बहुमुखी प्रतिभा वाले व्यक्तियों का निर्माण करना होगा | स्कूलों में कौशल शिक्षा इस उद्देश्य की दिशा में एक साधन है |

21वीं सदी की शिक्षा का स्वरूप-

शिक्षा सिर्फ पाठ्यक्रम पूर्ण कराने पर ही आधारित नहीं होनी चाहिए, अपितु यह विद्यार्थियों को जीवन में आने वाले विभिन्न प्रकार के उतार-चढ़ाव, चुनौतियों व कठिनाइयों पर जीत दिलाने में भी सक्षम बनाने वाली व जीवन कौशलों को सुधारने वाली होनी चाहिए | 21वीं शताब्दी अतीत की दुनिया की तुलना में थोड़ा भिन्न, प्रतिस्पर्धात्मक और चुनौतीपूर्ण है | इसीलिए 21वीं सदी की शिक्षा में भी बिबिधता, गहराई और बहुमुखी प्रतिभा पर जोर दिया गया है | 21वीं शताब्दी की जरूरतों को पूरा करने एवं चुनौतियों से निपटने की शिक्षा के लिए पाठ्यक्रम निर्माण में शिक्षा के सभी आयामों जैसे- ज्ञान, कौशल, चरित्र और मेटा लर्निंग की गहराई से रीडिजाइन करने की आवश्यकता है | इसका मतलब है- प्रत्येक आयाम और उसके परस्पर क्रिया को फिर से देखना |

ज्ञान- ज्ञान वह है जिसे हम जानते और समझते हैं या जानने और समझने का प्रयास करते हैं, जिस पर पाठ्यक्रम और पाठ्य सामग्री के पारंपरिक दृष्टिकोण द्वारा सबसे अधिक जोर दिया जाता है | वर्तमान में जो पाठ्यक्रम है वह 21वीं सदी के छात्रों की सामाजिक और आर्थिक जरूरतों को पूरा करने के लिए प्रासंगिक नहीं हो पा रहा है | इसलिए वर्तमान के पाठ्यक्रम में जो कुछ पढ़ाया जा रहा है उसके महत्व और प्रयोजन पर फिर से विचार करने की आवश्यकता है, और साथ ही सैद्धांतिक और व्यावहारिक पक्षों के बीच बेहतर संतुलन बनाने की आवश्यकता है |

पारंपरिक विषय यद्यपि बहुत ही महत्वपूर्ण है किंतु जो अन्य तीन आयाम (कौशल, चरित्र, मेटा लर्निंग) है, उनको उत्पन्न करने के लिए आधुनिक विषयों जैसे कि- प्रौद्योगिकी, इंजीनियरिंग, मीडिया, उद्यमिता और व्यापार, वित्त, कल्याण, सामाजिक प्रणाली आदि जो कि वर्तमान और भविष्य की मांगों को पूरा करते हैं, को पाठ्यक्रम के सामान्य भाग के रूप में समायोजित किया जाना चाहिए न

कि सहायक या वैकल्पिक विषय के रूप में | ज्ञान के लिए अंतर विषयक दृष्टिकोण, शिक्षार्थियों की अवधारणाओं के बीच संबंध बनाने में मदद करेगा | समकालीन महत्व की विषय वस्तुओं को ज्ञान के आधुनिक और पारंपरिक दोनों पाठ्यक्रमों में परस्पर समाहित करना चाहिए | इनमें वैश्विक साक्षरता, पर्यावरणीय साक्षरता, सूचना साक्षरता, डिजिटल लिटरेसी, सिस्टम थिंकिंग और डिजाइन थिंकिंग आदि शामिल है |

4c अर्थात् सृजनात्मकता, आलोचनात्मक चिंतन, सम्प्रेषण, सहयोग को 21वीं शताब्दी का कौशल के रूप में जाना जाता है | यह कौशल, ज्ञान को समझने के साथ-साथ प्रदर्शन के माध्यम से गहराई से सीखने के लिए भी आवश्यक है | लगातार बदलती सामाजिक एवं आर्थिक परिस्थितियों के अनुरूप, छात्रों की क्षमता एवं योग्यता में वृद्धि करने के लिए शिक्षा के माध्यम से इन कौशलों के विकास एवं प्रशिक्षण की आवश्यकता है और इन कौशलों को विद्यार्थियों, उद्योगों तथा समुदायों के लिए प्रासंगिक बनाए रखने की भी आवश्यकता है | राष्ट्रीय शिक्षा नीति की परिकल्पना के अनुरूप विद्यार्थियों के समग्र विकास के लिए कौशल, पाठ्यक्रम, कार्यप्रणाली और मूल्यांकन प्रभावी बने रहना चाहिए |

चरित्र- आज दुनिया भर में ज्ञान और कौशल के साथ ही साथ व्यक्ति के चारित्रिक गुणों के विकास की आवश्यकता भी तेजी से बढ़ रही है | सामान्यता चरित्र, शिक्षा के व्यापक उद्देश्य होते हैं-आजीवन सीखने के लिए एक आधार बनाएं, घर में समुदाय में और कार्यस्थल में सफल संबंधों का समर्थन करें, वैश्विक दुनिया में स्थाई भागीदारी के लिए व्यक्तिगत मूल्य और चरित्र का विकास करें |

सी.सी.आर ने छः आवश्यक चारित्रिक गुणों पर अध्ययन करने के लिए दुनिया भर के 32 से अधिक फ्रेमवर्क, अनुसंधान और प्रतिक्रिया को संश्लेषित किया है | जिसमें प्रत्येक की एक विस्तृत श्रृंखला है | ये चरित्र गुण हैं- चैतन्य, जिज्ञासा, साहस, लचीलापन, आचार-विचार और नेतृत्व |

- चैतन्य (बुद्धिमत्ता, आत्म-जागरूकता, आत्म-प्रबंधन, आत्म-साक्षात्कार, अवलोकन, प्रतिबिंब, चेतना, करुणा, कृतज्ञता, सहानुभूति, देखभाल, विकास-दृष्टि, अंतर्दृष्टि, समानता, खुशी, उपस्थिति, प्रासंगिकता, सूचना साझा करना, परस्पर-संबंध, निर्णय, एकता, स्वीकृति, सौंदर्य, संवेदनशीलता, धैर्य, शांति, संतुलन, आध्यात्मिकता, अस्तित्व, सामाजिक-जागरूकता, सांस्कृतिक जागरूकता आदि),
- जिज्ञासा (खुलापन, अन्वेषण, जुनून, आत्म-निर्देशन, प्रेरणा, पहल, नवाचार, उत्साह, आश्चर्य, प्रशंसा, सहायता आदि)
- साहस (बहादुरी, दृढ़-संकल्प, आत्म-विश्वास, जोखिम लेना, दृढ़ता, उत्साह, आशावाद, प्रेरणा, ऊर्जा, हंसमुख, दृढ़ता, धैर्य आदि)
- लचीलापन (शीलता, आत्मानुशासन, प्रयास, परिश्रम, प्रतिबद्धता, आत्म-नियंत्रण, आत्मसम्मान, आत्मविश्वास, स्थिरता, अनुकूलनीयता, स्पष्टता, प्रतिक्रिया आदि)
- आचार-विचार (परोपकार, मानवता, अखंडता, सम्मान, न्याय, समता, निष्पक्षता, दयालुता, परोपकारी, समावेशी, सहिष्णुता, स्वीकृति, निष्ठा, ईमानदारी, सच्चाई, सत्यता, प्रामाणिकता, वास्तविकता, विश्वसनीयता, शालीनता, विचार, क्षमा, सदगुण, प्रेम, सहायता, उदारता, दान, भक्ति, विचार, नागरिकता, समानता, आदि)

- नेतृत्व (उत्तरदायित्व, जवाबदेही, निर्भरता, विश्वसनीयता, कर्तव्यनिष्ठ, निःस्वार्थता, विनम्रता, समृद्धता, कौशल, आत्म-प्रतिबिंब, प्रेरणा, संगठन, प्रतिनिधिमंडल, मेंटरशिप, प्रतिबद्धता, बीरता, लक्ष्य, अभिविन्यास-परिणाम, अभिविन्यास-परिशुद्धता, निष्पादन, सामाजिकरण, समाजिक-सुरक्षा, विविधता, सज्जा) आदि

मेटा लर्निंग- मेटा लर्निंग से आशय है कि हम किसी विषय को कैसे प्रतिबिंबित करते हैं या हम अपना अनुकूलन किस रूप में करते हैं | मेटा लर्निंग किसी भी सीखने को दर्शाने और समायोजित करने से संबंधित प्रक्रियाओं की बात करता है | इसमें मेटा कागानिशन, भविष्यवाणी करना, निगरानी करना और किसी के सीखने का मूल्यांकन करना के साथ-साथ किसी की क्षमता के बारे में ग्रोथ माइंडसेट को आंतरिक बनाना भी शामिल है | मेटा लर्निंग आजीवन सीखने की आदतें बनाने, अन्य तीन आयामों को सीखने के लिए अपने मूल संदर्भ से परे सीखने के हस्तांतरण को सुनिश्चित करने के लिए आवश्यक है |

इस प्रकार 21वीं शिक्षा की प्रणाली विश्लेषणात्मक, कौशल व चिंतन पर आधारित है | अर्जित ज्ञान का अपने जीवन में सही प्रकार से रूपांतरण व उपयोग करना ही बेहतर कैरियर व उज्ज्वल भविष्य की नींव है | कौशल शिक्षा को लगातार बदलती सामाजिक व आर्थिक परिस्थितियों के अनुरूप बनाए रखने और इसे विद्यार्थियों, उद्योगों और समुदायों के लिए प्रासंगिक बनाए रखने की आवश्यकता है | राष्ट्रीय शिक्षा निति 2020 की परिकल्पना के अनुरूप विद्यार्थियों के समग्र विकास के लिए कौशल, पाठ्यक्रम, शिक्षण प्रणाली और मूल्यांकन प्रणाली प्रभावी बने रहने चाहिए | भविष्य के कार्यबल के कौशल की आवश्यकताओं को पूरा करने के लिए, आज जिन क्षेत्रों पर अधिक ध्यान देने की आवश्यकता है, वह हैं अक्षय ऊर्जा, हरित ऊर्जा, बिजली, पर्यटन, इलेक्ट्रॉनिक्स, हरित कौशल, सतत खनन, दूरसंचार, हरित कृषि, डिस्पोजल आदि |

21वीं सदी के कौशल के अलावा इंटरनेट आफ थिंग्स, मशीन लर्निंग, आर्टिफिशियल इंटेलिजेंस और रोबोटिक प्रोसेस ऑटोमेशन जैसे उभरते रुझानों को भी तराशने की जरूरत है | डिजिटल स्केल इन सभी कौशल विकास गतिविधियों का मुख्य कार्यक्रम बनना चाहिए | कृत्रिम बुद्धिमत्ता के प्रशिक्षण प्रदान करने की प्रणाली को विकसित करने और बढ़ावा देने की आवश्यकता है, ताकि प्रशिक्षण को शिक्षार्थी की आवश्यकताओं के अनुसार अनुकूलित किया जा सके और इसकी पहुंच को बढ़ाया जा सके | हमें क्लाउड कंप्यूटिंग, गेमिफिकेशन आदि के माध्यम से कोडिंग, एडिटिंग, मैनुफैक्चरिंग ऑपरेटर, टेलीमेटिक्स डाटा एनालिटिक्स, ड्रोन टेक्नोलॉजी, ऑगमेंटेड रियलिटी, वर्चुअल रियलिटी, ए,आई, जैसे भावी कौशल पर भी काम करने की जरूरत है | सी.बी.एस.ई पहले से ही डाटा साइंस, कोडिंग और आर्टिफिशियल इंटेलिजेंस जैसे पाठ्यक्रम शुरू कर चुका है |

विद्यालय एवं शिक्षकों से अपेक्षाएं-

जॉन डीवी ने कहा है कि विद्यालय समाज का लघुरूप है तथा समाजीकरण की प्रक्रिया के द्वारा यह बालकों में उन आदतों, अभिवृत्ति और भावनाओं को जागृत करती है जो उसके जीवन का अभिन्न अंग बन जाती है | इसलिए 21वीं सदी की शिक्षा के लक्ष्य को प्राप्त करने में विद्यालय और शिक्षक की भूमिका महत्वपूर्ण है, क्योंकि विद्यालय ही वह साधन है जो सामाजिक, नैतिक, राष्ट्रीय, अंतरराष्ट्रीय, और सशक्त जनतांत्रिक मूल्यों की शिक्षा देते हैं | विद्यालय में रहकर बालक शिक्षकों एवं सहपाठियों के व्यवहारों एवं आदर्शों का प्रत्यक्षीकरण कर उन कौशलों का अनुसरण करता है, जो उसे समाज की दृष्टि से श्रेष्ठ प्रतीत होते हैं | जॉन डीवी का कथन है कि- विद्यालय ऐसा विशिष्ट वातावरण है जहां जीवन के कुछ महत्वपूर्ण गुणों, कुछ विशेष प्रकार की क्रिया और

व्यवस्थाओं की शिक्षा दी जाती है जिससे कि बालक का विकास वांछित दिशा में हो सके। स्वामी विवेकानंद जी ने भी शिक्षा के उद्देश्य को स्पष्ट करते हुए कहा था कि- सभी शिक्षकों एवं अभ्यासों का अंतिम ध्येय बालक का सर्वांगीण विकास करना है। यह शिक्षक का ही दायित्व है कि वह छात्रों में विभिन्न कौशलों का विकास कर, उसे भविष्य के लिए तैयार करें। शिक्षण संस्थाएं राष्ट्र के निर्माण का आधार हैं। नागरिकों की सामाजिक, सांस्कृतिक, आर्थिक, राजनीतिक, तकनीकी, भौतिक, नैतिक, आध्यात्मिक उन्नति में यह संस्थाएं योगदान करती हैं। शिक्षा मनुष्य के विकास के लिए उसको प्रशिक्षित करने की प्रक्रिया है। इसके द्वारा लोगों में आत्मसात करने, ग्रहण करने, बोध करने तथा रचनात्मक कार्य करने की कुशलता का विकास होता है। यह सर्वमान्य तथ्य है कि विद्यार्थी के जीवन में सबसे अधिक प्रभाव उसके शिक्षक और विद्यालय का ही पड़ता है इसलिए 21वीं सदी की शिक्षा में शिक्षक और विद्यालय की भूमिका बहुत महत्वपूर्ण है।

विद्यालय और शिक्षकों को चाहिए कि वह कक्षा में भी प्रौद्योगिकी के भरपूर प्रयोग को बढ़ावा दें। प्रौद्योगिकी वर्तमान की शिक्षा का एक अभिन्न अंग है कृत्रिम बुद्धिमत्ता, संवर्धित वास्तविकता, स्वचालन, आभासी वास्तविकता, व डिजिटल मार्केटिंग इन सभी का एकीकरण 21वीं सदी की शिक्षा में मुख्य भूमिका निभाता है तथा यह संपूर्ण शिक्षा जगत में एक नवीन क्रांति को जन्म देता है। विद्यालय में प्रौद्योगिकी का सही प्रकार से उपयोग व प्रयोग, विषय को आंतरिक रूप से सीखने व उसके नवीनीकरण में ईंधन की भूमिका निभाता है। प्रौद्योगिकी का सही प्रकार से उपयोग शोधकर्ताओं के समय को भी बचाता है और इन सब में शिक्षक की अपनी अहम भूमिका रहती है। इस प्रकार विद्यार्थी के लिए शिक्षक एक सहायक व आदर्श पथ प्रदर्शक के रूप में है।

निष्कर्ष-

निष्कर्षतः हम कह सकते हैं कि वर्तमान की शिक्षा में कौशल को प्राथमिकता देने की आवश्यकता है। विद्यार्थी जब स्कूल से निकलकर उच्च शिक्षा, रोजगार या आजीविका के क्षेत्र में जाएंगे तब कौशल शिक्षा के परिणाम सामने आएंगे। आज महत्वकांक्षी पेसे की ओर बढ़ने के लिए व्यवसायिक कौशल के बारे में उपलब्ध रास्ते और कैरियर परामर्श के बारे में विद्यार्थियों, उद्योगों और संस्थानों के बीच जागरूकता पैदा करने की आवश्यकता है। जैसा कि प्रधानमंत्री नरेंद्र मोदी ने भी प्रकाश डाला है कि- व्यवसायिक शिक्षा के माध्यम से विशेष रूप से व्यापार में, कौशल विकास भारत के लिए एक आवर्ती और तेजी से बढ़ती हुई महत्वपूर्ण प्राथमिकता के रूप में उभरा है। इसलिए शिक्षा पारिस्थितिकी तंत्र के माध्यम से स्कूलों में ऐसे कौशलों की शिक्षा प्रदान करने की आवश्यकता है, जो समग्र शिक्षा के विभिन्न महत्वपूर्ण पहलुओं को छूते हैं और व्यवसायिक शिक्षा से जुड़े अवरोधों को दूर कर समाधान का मार्ग प्रशस्त करते हैं। भारत भी व्यवसायिक शिक्षा को, सामान्य शिक्षा के साथ एकीकृत करने और मुख्यधारा में लाने के लिए महत्वपूर्ण सुधारों को लागू करने की राह पर है। साथ ही यह सभी स्तरों पर धारकों की भूमिका सुनिश्चित करने के लिए वास्तव में यह बहुत महत्वपूर्ण है, जिससे कि बच्चों को 21वीं सदी के लिए आवश्यक व्यवसायिक जीवन कौशल प्राप्त हो सके।

ग्रंथ सूची-

[21st Century Skills: How can you prepare students for the new ...](#)

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28. व्यक्तिमत्व विकासावर शिकण्याच्या कौशल्यांचा प्रभाव

डॉ. के.व्ही. देवरे³⁹, सौ प्रिया कापडणे⁴⁰

सारांश

21 व्या शतकात कौशल्ये महत्त्वाची भूमिका बजावतात. मुख्यतः ही कौशल्ये शिकण्याची कौशल्ये, साक्षरता कौशल्ये आणि जीवन कौशल्ये १२ क्षमतांचा समावेश असलेल्या तीन श्रेणींमध्ये विभागली आहेत. ही कौशल्ये विद्यार्थी केंद्रित आहेत. प्रत्येक कौशल्य त्याच्या वापरात अद्वितीय आहे. गंभीर विचार, सर्जनशीलता, सहयोग आणि संप्रेषण यांचा शिकण्याच्या कौशल्यांमध्ये समावेश आहे. शिकण्याची कौशल्ये स्मरणशक्तीशी निगडित असतात आणि व्यक्तिमत्व विकासात मूल्ये वाढवतात. संशोधकाच्या मते, शिकण्याच्या कौशल्याच्या मदतीने विद्यार्थी किंवा एखादी व्यक्ती त्याचे व्यक्तिमत्व विकसित करू शकते कारण ते गतिशील रचना आणि एकात्मिक वैशिष्ट्यांचे विघटन यांचा समावेश करते, जे एखाद्या व्यक्तीला परस्पर वर्तनात्मक वैशिष्ट्यांच्या बाबतीत वेगळे करतात.

जर आपण संप्रेषण कौशल्या बद्दल बोललो तर तो व्यक्तिमत्त्वाचा मुख्य भाग आहे. तुमचे यश आणि अपयश शिकण्याच्या पैलूंवर संभाषण कौशल्यावर अवलंबून असते. तुमच्या व्यक्तिमत्त्वाची पहिली छाप संभाषण कौशल्यापासून सुरू होते. जर आपण गंभीर विचारसरणीबद्दल बोललो तर असे म्हटले जाते की "विजेते वेगळ्या गोष्टी करू शकत नाहीत ते वेगळ्या पद्धतीने करतात". अशा गोष्टी एखाद्या व्यक्तीकडे असलेल्या सर्जनशीलते मधून येतात. शेवटी, सहयोग ही सर्वात कठीण संकल्पना आहे. याचा अर्थ इतरांसोबत काम करणे किंवा एकत्र काम करणे, तडजोड करणे आणि शक्य तितके चांगले परिणाम मिळवणे. सहकार्याचा मुख्य घटक म्हणजे इच्छा. सर्व सहभागींना त्यांच्या स्वतःच्या कल्पनांचे काही भाग इतरांसोबत चर्चा करून त्याचा अवलंब करण्यास तयार असले पाहिजे.

या सध्याच्या संशोधन अभ्यासासाठी संशोधकाने शिकण्याचे कौशल्य निवडले आहे. या सध्याच्या संशोधन अभ्यासाद्वारे संशोधकाला विद्यार्थ्यांच्या व्यक्तिमत्व विकासावर शिकण्याच्या कौशल्याचा काय परिणाम होतो याचा अभ्यास करायचा आहे.

मुख्य शब्द: शिकण्याची कौशल्ये, व्यक्तिमत्व विकास

प्रस्तावना:

व्यक्तिमत्व म्हणजे चिरस्थायी वैशिष्ट्ये आणि वर्तन ज्यामध्ये प्रमुख वैशिष्ट्ये, मूल्ये, स्व-संकल्पना, क्षमता आणि भावनिक नमुन्यांसह एखाद्या व्यक्तीचे जीवनातील अद्वितीय समायोजन समाविष्ट असते. व्यक्तिमत्व, विचार, भावना आणि वागण्याचा एक वैशिष्ट्यपूर्ण मार्ग. व्यक्तिमत्व मूड, वृत्ती आणि मते आत्मसात करते आणि इतर लोकांशी संवाद साधताना स्पष्टपणे व्यक्त होते. यात अंतर्भूत आणि अधिग्रहित अशा दोन्ही प्रकारच्या वर्तणुकीची वैशिष्ट्ये समाविष्ट आहेत जी एका व्यक्तीला दुसऱ्यापासून वेगळे करतात आणि ते पर्यावरण आणि सामाजिक गटाशी लोकांच्या संबंधांमध्ये पाहिले जाऊ शकतात.

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व्यक्तिमत्व या शब्दाची व्याख्या अनेक प्रकारे केली गेली आहे, परंतु मानसशास्त्रीय संकल्पना म्हणून दोन मुख्य अर्थ विकसित झाले आहेत. प्रथम लोकांमध्ये अस्तित्वात असलेल्या सातत्यपूर्ण फरकांशी संबंधित आहे: या अर्थाने, व्यक्तिमत्त्वाचा अभ्यास तुलनेने स्थिर मानवी मनोवैज्ञानिक वैशिष्ट्यांचे वर्गीकरण आणि स्पष्टीकरण यावर केंद्रित आहे. दुसरा अर्थ त्या गुणांवर जोर देतो जे सर्व लोकांना एकसारखे बनवतात आणि मनुष्याला इतर प्रजातींपासून वेगळे करतात.

व्यक्तिमत्त्वाच्या अभ्यासाचा उगम या मूलभूत कल्पनेतून झाला आहे - व्यक्ती ज्या विशिष्ट मार्गांनी चालतात, बोलतात, वागतात किंवा त्यांची इच्छा व्यक्त करतात, त्यांच्या वागण्याच्या वैशिष्ट्यपूर्ण वैयक्तिक नमुन्यांद्वारे त्यांचे व्यक्तिमत्त्व ओळखले जाते. वर्तन काहीही असो, व्यक्तिमत्त्वाचा पद्धतशीर अभ्यास करणाऱ्यांना व्यक्तिशास्त्रज्ञ म्हणतात - लोक त्यांच्या अभिव्यक्तीच्या पद्धतींमध्ये कसे भिन्न आहेत याचे परीक्षण करतात आणि या फरकांची कारणे निश्चित करण्याचा प्रयत्न करतात. जरी मानसशास्त्राची इतर क्षेत्रे लक्ष, विचार किंवा प्रेरणा यासारख्या अनेक समान कार्ये आणि प्रक्रियांचे परीक्षण करतात, परंतु व्यक्तिशास्त्रज्ञ या भिन्न प्रक्रिया एकत्र कशा बसतात आणि एकत्रित होतात यावर भर देतात जेणेकरून प्रत्येक व्यक्तीला एक विशिष्ट ओळख, किंवा व्यक्तिमत्व मिळेल.

सदर संशोधन निबंध हा तीन कौशल्या पैकी शिकण्याच्या कौशल्यावर मुख्य लक्ष केंद्रित करणार आहे. संशोधन निबंधांमधून संशोधकाला व्यक्तिमत्व विकासावर शिकण्याच्या कौशल्यांचा प्रभाव कसा होतो या बाबत सविस्तर माहिती द्यावयाची आहे.

1. गंभीर विचार आणि व्यक्तिमत्व विकास:

गंभीर विचार आणि व्यक्तिमत्व विकास यांचा खूप जवळचा संबंध आहे. सखोल, विविधांगी, नाविन्यपूर्ण विचार निश्चितच व्यक्तिमत्व विकासात हातभार लावतात. अशा व्यक्ती इतरांपेक्षा आपली वेगळीच छाप इतरांवर सोडतात. गंभीर विचार हे कौशल्य विकसित करून आपण व्यक्तिमत्व विकास सहज घडवून आणू शकतो. यासाठी मुख्य गंभीर विचार कौशल्ये जसे; विश्लेषण, मूल्यमापन, अनुमान, स्पष्टीकरण, स्व-नियमन, खुले विचार आणि समस्या सोडवणे यांचे उपयोजन कसे करावे यावर भर द्यावा लागेल ज्यातून गंभीर विचारामधून व्यक्तिमत्व विकास सहज घडून आणता येऊ शकतो.

विश्लेषण:

विश्लेषण म्हणजे माहिती आणि ज्ञान गोळा करण्याची आणि त्यावर प्रक्रिया करण्याची क्षमता. ही क्षमता असलेली व्यक्ति नेहमीच इतरांपेक्षा आपली स्वतःची वेगळीच छाप निर्माण करत असते. विश्लेषणाकरिता सर्व प्रथम त्या वस्तु अगर परिस्थिती बाबत संपूर्ण आणि सखोल माहिती असणे महत्वपूर्ण ठरते. सखोल माहिती करिता चौकसपणा, चौफेर नजर, अवलोकन, विषयज्ञान, याबाबत अद्यावत माहिती मिळवणे महत्वाचे असते. विश्लेषण हे आपण जे वाचतो, लिहितो आणि ऐकतो ते तर्कशुद्ध आणि तार्किक पद्धतीने विघटित करण्याची प्रक्रिया आहे. त्यासाठी वर्णन आणि विश्लेषण करण्यापलीकडे जाऊन त्यावर मूल्यमापन, टीका या प्रक्रिया करणे आवश्यक ठरते. विश्लेषणासाठी सर्व प्रयत्नांमध्ये खालील गोष्टी करणे आवश्यक आहे:

- पुस्तके आणि पुनरावलोकन केलेले संशोधन लेख यासारख्या विश्वासाहर् शैक्षणिक संसाधनांमधून पुरावे आणि कल्पनांद्वारे समर्थित माहितीपूर्ण तर्क प्रदान करा.
- संदर्भ, पार्श्वभूमी आणि पूर्वाग्रह ओळखा ज्यामुळे तुम्ही जे वाचता आणि ऐकता त्यामध्ये विकृती निर्माण होणार नाही.

- इतरांनी काढलेल्या निष्कर्षांचे महत्त्व आणि परिणाम स्पष्ट करा. निराधार गृहीतके ओळखा आणि प्रश्न करा.

मूल्यमापन:

तुमच्याकडे असलेले ज्ञान पुरेसे आणि विश्वासाह आहे की नाही याचे मूल्यांकन करणे फार महत्वाचे असते. उपलब्ध माहितीच्या आधारे निर्णय घेण्याची क्षमता म्हणजे मूल्यमापन होय. मूल्यमापन शक्य तितके पद्धतशीर आणि निष्पक्ष असावे. मूल्यमापन पद्धतशीर आहे, जी माहिती प्रदान करते ती विश्वासाह आहे आणि वापरकर्ते आणि निधीधारकांच्या निर्णय प्रक्रियेत अगोदर शिकलेल्या धड्यांचा समावेश सक्षम करण्यासाठी उपयुक्त आहे की नाही याची खात्री करून घेतल्यास मूल्यमापनातून योग्य निर्णय घेता येऊ शकतात. अशा रीतीने मूल्यमापन करणारी व्यक्ति इतरापेक्षा अधिक प्रभावी दिसते .

स्पष्टीकरण:

स्पष्टीकरण म्हणजे, तुमचे निष्कर्ष आणि तर्क स्पष्टपणे सांगणे. स्पष्टीकरण कौशल्याचे सर्वात महत्वाचे वैशिष्ट्य म्हणजे उदाहरणे देण्याची क्षमता. तुम्ही उदाहरणे देता तेव्हा ते एक मानसिक प्रतिमा तयार होते, ज्यामुळे इतरांना माहिती अधिक चांगल्या प्रकारे समजायला मदत होते. प्रभावी स्पष्टीकरण कौशल्य असेल तर व्यक्ति आपले म्हणणे इतरांना पटवून देऊ शकते. एखादी समस्या, कार्य प्रणाली अधिक सोप्या रितने समजून देऊ शकते. अशा स्पष्टीकरणातून आपण व्यक्तिमत्व विकसीत करू शकतो.

स्व-नियमन:

स्व-नियमन म्हणजे, दीर्घकालीन उद्दिष्टांच्या पूर्ततेसाठी एखाद्याचे वर्तन, भावना आणि विचार नियंत्रित करण्याची क्षमता. अधिक विशिष्टपणे, स्व-नियमन म्हणजे व्यत्यय आणणाऱ्या भावना आणि आवेग व्यवस्थापित करण्याची क्षमता होय. स्व-नियमन असलेली व्यक्ति निराशेतून परत येण्याची आणि आपल्या मूल्यांशी सुसंगतपणे कार्य करण्याची क्षमता देखील विकसित करू शकते. आत्म-नियमनामध्ये भावना आणि कृती दरम्यान विराम देणे समाविष्ट आहे - गोष्टींवर विचार करण्यासाठी, योजना बनवण्यासाठी, संयमाने प्रतीक्षा करण्यासाठी वेळ काढणे महत्वाचे असते. स्व-नियमन तुम्हाला तुमच्या खोलवर धारण केलेल्या मूल्यांनुसार किंवा सामाजिक विवेकानुसार कार्य करण्यास आणि स्वतःला योग्यरित्या व्यक्त करण्यास अनुमती देते. जर तुम्ही शैक्षणिक कामगिरीला महत्त्व देत असाल, तर ते तुम्हाला परीक्षेपूर्वी शिथिल होण्याऐवजी अभ्यास करण्यास अनुमती देईल. जर तुम्ही इतरांना मदत करण्याला महत्त्व देत असाल, तर ते तुम्हाला एखाद्या प्रकल्पात सहकाऱ्याला मदत करण्यास अनुमती देईल,

2. सर्जनशीलता आणि व्यक्तिमत्व विकास:

सर्जनशीलता म्हणजे, संदर्भित लक्ष केंद्रित करण्यात सक्षम असणे - विचलन आणि अभिसरण यांच्यातील समतोलाने लक्ष ठेवणे. सर्जनशीलता नवीन आणि मूळ कल्पना शोधणे आणि समस्यांचे निराकरण शोधण्याची क्षमता होय. सर्जनशीलतेची कृती भव्य आणि प्रेरणादायी असू शकते, जसे की सुंदर पेंटिंग तयार करणे किंवा एखाद्या नाविन्यपूर्ण कंपनीची रचना करणे. परंतु एखादी कल्पना सर्जनशील मानण्यासाठी कलात्मक किंवा जग बदलणारी नसावी. जीवनासाठी कल्पकतेची दैनंदिन कृती आणि नवीन उपाय आवश्यक

आहेत; या अर्थाने, जवळजवळ प्रत्येकाकडे काही प्रमाणात सर्जनशीलता असते.पुढील काही कृतीमधुन आपण सर्जनशीलता वाढवून सर्जनशील व्यक्तिमत्व विकसीत करू शकतो.

विचारमंथन:

छोट्या किंवा मोठ्या समस्यांमध्ये हे तंत्र खूप उपयुक्त ठरू शकते. विचारमंथनाची सर्वसाधारण कल्पना अशी आहे की, सर्जनशील संभाव्य उपायांचा जास्त प्रमाणात वापर करून, उच्च दर्जाच्या गुणवत्तेपर्यंत पोहोचणे सोपे होते. जे तुम्हाला तुमच्या सर्जनशील विचार कौशल्याचा वापर करण्यात मदत करू शकतात. सुरुवातीच्यासाठी, अतिशय अनौपचारिक असल्याने, कार्य करण्यासाठी कठोर रचना आवश्यक नाही. तथापि, योग्य मार्गदर्शनाद्वारे ते सुलभ केले जाऊ शकते. चांगले कार्य करण्यासाठी, सर्व सहभागींना सर्जनशील समाधानाची आवश्यकता असलेल्या समस्येची जाणीव असणे आवश्यक आहे . अनेकदा एखाद्या समस्येचे उत्तर समोर नसते, परंतु विचारमंथन तसेच पार्श्व विचारांची सामान्य कल्पना असल्यास त्यातून सर्जनशील आणि नाविन्यपूर्ण योजना तयार करून आपण प्रभावी बनू शकतो.

समवयस्कांशी संवाद:

सर्जनशील विचारसरणी आणि तांत्रिक कौशल्ये सतत विकसित करण्यासाठी इतरांची मदत घ्या. तुम्ही समान उद्दिष्टे असलेल्या लोकांचे नेटवर्क तयार करू शकता आणि या सर्व टिपा गट म्हणून कृतीत आणू शकता.तुमच्या समवयस्कांशी संवाद साधणे हा तुमची सर्जनशीलता वापरण्याचा उत्तम मार्ग आहे. हे लोक कल्पकतेने-देणारे असतात आणि नेटवर्कच्या रूपात मूळ कल्पना आणण्यात योगदान देतात तेव्हा ते अधिक चांगले असते. एखाद्या सामान्य समस्येचे निराकरण करण्यासाठी किंवा कामाच्या विशिष्ट पैलूवर नवीन शोध घेण्यासाठी गट प्रकल्पांसह येण्याचा प्रयत्न करा.

जे लोक तुमच्यासारखेच विचार करतात अशा लोकांमध्ये स्वतःला वेढू नये याची काळजी घ्या. हे नेटवर्क तयार करताना तुम्हाला शक्य तितकी विविधता शोधा, कारण ही सर्व विविधता प्रत्येकाच्या कल्पनांसाठी अत्यंत फायदेशीर ठरू शकते. सर्जनशील विचार कौशल्ये ओळखण्यासाठी सतत प्रशिक्षण आवश्यक आहे हे आपण नवीन कल्पना कशा प्रकारे आणता हे सुधारण्याची पहिली पायरी आहे. या कौशल्याचा अनुभव असलेले लोक प्रत्येक क्षेत्रात आपले व्यक्तिमत्व सुधारू शकतात.

3. सहयोग कौशल्य आणि व्यक्तिमत्व विकास:

सहयोग म्हणजे विविध विभाग, स्थाने आणि संघातील लोकांना एकत्र आणणे, त्यानंतर त्यांचे प्रयत्न एका समान ध्येयावर केंद्रित करणे. सहयोग ही एक प्रक्रिया आहे, परंतु चांगले सहकार्य करणे हे एक कौशल्य आहे जे कालांतराने सन्मानित होते.जेव्हा दोन किंवा अधिक लोक एक समान ध्येय साध्य करण्यासाठी एकत्र काम करतात तेव्हा सहयोग होतो. म्हणून, सहयोग कौशल्ये इतरांसह चांगले काम करण्यासाठी आणि एक संघ म्हणून परिणाम प्रदान करण्यासाठी लागणाऱ्या सर्व गोष्टींचा समावेश करतात. एक व्यक्ती जी कामाच्या ठिकाणी सहकार्य करण्यात चांगली असते ती एक प्रभावशाली कार्यसंघ सदस्य, संवादक, निर्णय घेणारा आणि नेता बनू शकते..

सहयोग करणे म्हणजे प्रकल्प पूर्ण करण्यासाठी इतरांसोबत काम करणे असा नाही तर चांगले सहकार्य करण्यासाठी, तुम्हाला सहकार्यांसोबत नातेसंबंध निर्माण करण्याची आवश्यकता आहे, संघर्ष उद्भवल्यावर ते कसे सोडवायचे हे जाणून घेणे आणि सर्वसमावेशक, आदरपूर्ण कामाचे वातावरण तयार करणे आवश्यक आहे. जेव्हा संघातील सदस्यांमध्ये तणाव असतो तेव्हा हस्तक्षेप करणे आणि ते विसर्जित करण्यासाठी कार्य करणे. एखाद्या व्यक्तीने संस्थेत येऊन एकट्याने समस्या सोडवाव्यात अशी त्यांची अपेक्षा नसते. त्याऐवजी, त्यांनी इतरांसोबत सहकार्य करावे अशी त्यांची इच्छा आहे. मदत केव्हा मागायची आणि ती मदत कोणाकडे मागायची हे एका चांगल्या सहकार्याला माहित असते. कामाच्या ठिकाणी प्रत्येक व्यक्ती अद्वितीय कौशल्ये आणि दृष्टीकोन आणते. सहयोग कौशल्य-सामायिकरणाला प्रोत्साहन देते जेणेकरून प्रत्येकजण एकमेकांकडून शिकू शकेल.

काही महत्त्वपूर्ण सहयोग कौशल्ये खालील प्रमाणे-

मोकळेपणा:

काही व्यक्ति नवीन कल्पनांचे थोडे अधिक प्रतिरोधक आहेत ते प्रकल्प सुरू होण्याआधीच थांबवू शकतात किंवा अन्यथा व्यत्यय आणू शकतात. परंतु उत्तम नेता किंवा प्रभावी व्यक्तिमत्व असलेली व्यक्ति जिज्ञासा आणि मोकळेपणाला प्रोत्साहन देऊन नवीन कल्पनांना स्वीकारण्यास प्रोत्साहन देण्यासाठी चर्चा करण्याची, टीका करण्याची किंवा विस्तारित करण्याची समान संधी उपलब्ध करून देतो.

संघटना:

जोपर्यंत लोक कामाचा भार सोपवण्यात, त्यांच्या जबाबदाऱ्या सांभाळण्यास आणि स्वतःला व्यवस्थित ठेवण्यास सक्षम नसतील तोपर्यंत सहयोग यशस्वी होऊ शकत नाही - आणि म्हणूनच संघटना हे आणखी एक महत्त्वपूर्ण सहयोग कौशल्य आहे. सहयोगाला प्रत्येकाच्या दैनंदिन दिनचर्येचा भाग बनवून नेते लोकांना अधिक संघटित होण्यासाठी प्रशिक्षित करू शकतात. जर तुमच्या लोकांना नियमितपणे एकमेकांशी प्रकल्पाच्या जबाबदाऱ्यांचे समन्वय साधावे लागत असेल, तर शक्यता अशी आहे की ते त्यांचा वेळ आणि कामाचा भार कसा व्यवस्थित करायचा हे खूप लवकर शिकतील.

दीर्घकालीन विचार:

सहकार्याचा आणखी एक अत्यंत महत्त्वाचा घटक म्हणजे दीर्घकालीन विचार करणे आणि तुमच्या सहयोगी कार्याच्या अंतिम परिणामाची कल्पना करणे. सहयोग म्हणजे एक समान ध्येय किंवा सामायिक उद्देशासाठी कार्य करणे आणि तुमचे योगदान त्या ध्येयामध्ये कसे बसते हे ओळखणे. ज्या कर्मचाऱ्यांना त्यांची सहयोग कौशल्ये सुधारायची आहेत त्यांच्यासाठी याचा अर्थ प्रकल्पाची व्याप्ती आणि त्यातील प्रत्येकाची भूमिका समजून घेणे. दिलेल्या प्रकल्पाच्या फोकसबद्दल तुम्हाला जितके अधिक माहिती असेल, तितके तुम्ही ते पूर्ण करण्यासाठी अधिक सुसज्ज असाल.

सामायिक दृष्टी:

"कर्मचार्यांना सहयोगी प्रक्रियेत गुंतवण्याचा सर्वोत्तम मार्ग म्हणजे त्यांना सामायिक दृष्टी आणि उद्देशासाठी योगदान देण्याची संधी देणे. सर्व कर्मचार्यांना त्यांचे कार्य कार्यसंघ आणि संस्थेच्या उद्दिष्टांमध्ये कसे योगदान देते आणि सहयोग त्यांना त्यांची उद्दिष्टे पूर्ण करण्यास कशी मदत करेल हे सर्व कर्मचार्यांना समजते याची नेत्यांनी खात्री केली पाहिजे. जेव्हा कर्मचार्यांना त्यांचा व्यापक उद्देश समजतो, तेव्हा ते त्यांच्या संघांमध्ये अधिक अर्थपूर्ण योगदान देऊ शकतात.

प्रामाणिकपणा:

प्रामाणिकपणा हे एक कौशल्य आहे जे तुम्ही तुमच्या व्यक्तिगत आणि व्यावसायिक जीवनातील सर्व पैलूंमध्ये समाविष्ट करण्याचा प्रयत्न केला पाहिजे.

नियमानुसार, प्रामाणिकपणाने तुमच्या कामाच्या नैतिकतेचे स्पष्ट कारण दाखवले पाहिजे, सर्वात महत्वाचे म्हणजे तुमची कौशल्ये आणि पात्रता याबद्दल खोटे बोलणे ही यशासाठी सर्वात कमी विश्वासाह पद्धत आहे. तुमच्या सहकार्यांशी आणि पर्यवेक्षकांशी कामाशी संबंधित कोणत्याही गोष्टीबद्दल प्रामाणिक राहणे हे दाखवते की तुम्ही पारदर्शकतेला महत्त्व देता. हे देखील सिद्ध करते की आपण आपल्या चुका स्वीकारण्यास आणि आपल्या कृतींची जबाबदारी घेण्यास आत्मविश्वासू आहात.

4. संप्रेषण कौशल्य आणि व्यक्तिमत्व विकास:

यशस्वी संप्रेषणासाठी स्पष्ट आणि विचारशील संवाद असणे आवश्यक आहे. यासाठी एकमेकांशी व्यक्त होण्यास सक्षम असणे आवश्यक आहे. लोक वेगळ्या पद्धतीने संवाद साधतात. काहींना गटांमध्ये बोलणे पूर्णपणे आरामदायक वाटते; काहींना न बोलणे, कमी बोलणे, तर काहींना फक्त ऐकणे आवडते. इतरांशी त्या प्रकारे ते संवाद साधण्यास प्राधान्य देतात. उदाहरणार्थ, लाजाळू लोक, मौखिक संप्रेषणापेक्षा लिखित संप्रेषणाला प्राधान्य देतात. जर एखादी व्यक्ती उत्तम संवादक नसेल आणि तुम्हाला त्यांची कल्पना किंवा दृष्टिकोन समजून घेण्यात अडचण येत असेल, तर त्यांना समजून घेण्याचा प्रयत्न करा. नेहमी कुशलतेने संपर्क साधा. एखाद्याचे विचार मांडण्यात त्यांना अडचण येत असल्याने त्यांना कमी लेखू नका. संप्रेषण कौशल्य व त्यामधून व्यक्तिमत्व विकास घडवून आणण्यासाठी आत्मविश्वास, स्पष्टता, उत्तम श्रोता असणे अत्यंत महत्वाचे असते. आयुष्यातील इतर सर्व गोष्टींप्रमाणेच, संप्रेषण कौशल्य देखील सरावाने सुधारू शकते. पुढील उपक्रमाद्वारे आपण संप्रेषण कौशल्य आणि त्यातून व्यक्तिमत्व विकास घडवून आणू शकतो.

उत्तम श्रोता बना:

उत्तम श्रोता हाच उत्तम वक्ता बनू शकतो. प्रभावी व्यक्तिमत्व घडवण्यासाठी आपण प्रभावी श्रोता असणे फार महत्वाचे ठरते. ऐकणे ही संप्रेषण प्रक्रियेचा अक्षरशः अर्धा भाग आहे कारण प्रभावी संवाद साधण्यासाठी स्पष्ट वक्ता आणि सक्रिय श्रोता लागतो. ऐकण्यास बोलण्यापेक्षा जास्त संयम लागतो, तर प्रत्यक्षात ऐकण्याचे नाटक करण्याऐवजी ऐकणे हे फार कमी लोक करतात. त्यामुळे संवादावर ताण येतो. ज्याप्रमाणे आपण नेहमी एक चांगला श्रोता असलेल्या मित्राची निवड करतो त्याचप्रमाणे, आपण आपला संवाद सुधारण्यासाठी शक्य तितक्या सक्रिय ऐकण्याचा सराव केला पाहिजे.

तुमचे ऐकण्याचे कौशल्य सुधारण्यासाठी येथे काही टिपा आहेत:

- वक्ता व त्याचे विचार यावर आपले पूर्ण लक्ष केंद्रित करा
- तुम्हाला काय बोलले जात आहे ते समजत नसल्यास स्पष्टीकरण करणारे प्रश्न विचारा
- भाषांतरात काहीही गमावले जाणार नाही याची खात्री करण्यासाठी स्पीकरच्या शब्दांचा अर्थ लावा, अशाब्दिक संकेतांकडे लक्ष द्या

जेव्हा एखादी व्यक्ती बोलत असते तेव्हा ते त्यांच्या देहबोलीतून बरेच काही बोलत असतात. अर्थातच - आपण जेव्हा बोलतो तेव्हा स्वतःच्या अशाब्दिक संकेतांकडे आणि आपल्या आजूबाजूच्या लोकांकडे लक्ष देऊन आपण संप्रेषण अधिकच प्रभावी करून आपले व्यक्तिमत्व उचावू शकतो. या करिता खालील गोष्टी चा अवलंब करता येईल .

- तुम्ही बोलता तेव्हा शांत रहा.
- डोळा संपर्क स्थापित करा. सहसा, डोळ्यांचा संपर्क टाळणे हे दर्शविते की आपल्याकडे लपवण्यासाठी काहीतरी आहे. जेव्हा तुम्हाला मुद्दा मांडायचा असेल तेव्हा तुम्ही लोकांवर लक्ष केंद्रित करू इच्छिता आणि जेव्हा तुम्ही बोलता आणि ऐकता तेव्हा त्यांच्या डोळ्यात पहा.
- प्रतिक्रियाशील नसावे.. तणावपूर्ण किंवा तीव्र परिस्थितीत, आपल्या भावनांवर नियंत्रण ठेवणे इष्टतम आहे. याचा अर्थ आवाजाचा शांत स्वर राखणे.
- गैर-मौखिक संवादाचा फायदा घ्या. इतर कोणत्याही प्रकारच्या गैर-मौखिक संकेतांप्रमाणेच तुम्ही तुमच्या हातांनी आणि आवाजाने काय करता हे महत्त्वाचे आहे. यामुळे, तुम्ही तुमची देहबोली कशी वापरता याकडे लक्ष देण्याची खात्री करा, शक्यतो आगाऊ सराव करून.

तोंडी संवादाचा सराव करा

बोलून विचार करण्या पेक्षा ,बोलण्याआधी विचार करणे हे उत्तम व्यक्तिमत्वाचे लक्षण आहे. कामाच्या ठिकाणी प्रभावी संप्रेषण म्हणजे परिणामकारक परिणाम निर्माण करण्यासाठी सर्व संस्थात्मक स्तरावरील विविध भागधारकांसोबत आणि त्यांच्यामध्ये माहितीची प्रभावी देवाणघेवाण आणि मुक्त प्रवाह निर्माण करण्याची क्षमता. कोणत्याही कामासाठी काही महत्त्वाची संभाषण कौशल्ये म्हणजे सादरीकरण, सक्रिय ऐकणे, मौखिक संवाद, अभिप्राय देणे/घेणे आणि इतर गुण आवश्यक आहेत.

- वेळ ही सर्वात मौल्यवान संपत्ती आहे आणि बर्बाद प्रकरणांमध्ये आपण ती अनावश्यकपणे वाया घालवतो. एक चांगला शाब्दिक संप्रेषक असा असतो जो संक्षिप्त, तरीही विशिष्ट असू शकतो. याचा अर्थ समोरच्या व्यक्तीला जास्त वेळ न घालवता, त्यांना समजण्यासाठी योग्य प्रमाणात माहिती देतो .त्यामुळे प्रभावी व्यक्तिमत्वा करिता संक्षिप्त व्हा.
- इतर दृष्टीकोन विचारात घेण्यास सक्षम असणे आपल्या मौखिक संप्रेषणासाठी चमत्कार करू शकते, विशेषतः जेव्हा आपण एखाद्याला पटवून देण्याचा प्रयत्न करतो तेव्हा इतर दृष्टीकोनांचा विचार करणे फार महत्त्वाचे ठरते.

आत्मविश्वास:

आपल्या प्रभावी व्यक्तिमत्त्वची चांगली पहिली छाप पडण्यासाठी आत्मविश्वास हे कौशल्य आहे. आत्मविश्वास हा एक चारित्र्य वैशिष्ट्य आहे जो दर्शवितो की आपण आपल्या शब्द, कृती आणि निर्णयांबद्दल खात्री शीर आहोत. अधिक आत्मविश्वासू दिसण्याचे काही मार्ग पुढील प्रमाणे आहेत :

- ताठ खांद्यावर सरळ बसणे
- मैत्रीपूर्ण - पण ठाम - आवाजात बोलणे
- सकारात्मक प्रतिसाद देतात.
- आगाऊ तयारी करणे जेणेकरून तुम्ही तुमच्या शब्दांना अडखळणार नाही

लक्षात असु द्या की , जर तुम्ही नैसर्गिकरित्या आत्मविश्वासू असाल, तर काहीवेळा, खूप जास्त आत्मविश्वास अहंकार किंवा असभ्यपणाच्या रूपात येऊ शकतो आणि तो बहुतेक लोकांसोबत बसणार नाही.

स्पष्टता /सार्वजनिक बोलणे:

स्पष्टता हा मौखिक संवादाचा अपरिहार्य भाग आहे. यामध्ये तुमच्या विचारांची तार्किक रचना करणे आणि ते शक्य तितक्या प्रभावीपणे व्यक्त करण्यासाठी योग्य शब्द वापरणे समाविष्ट आहे.जर तुम्ही स्पष्टपणे संवाद साधू शकत नसाल, ते व्यस्त विचारांच्या पद्धतीमुळे किंवा अयोग्य भाषेमुळे असो, त्याचा आपल्याला त्रास होऊ शकतो. सार्वजनिक बोलणे ही अनेक लोकांची सर्वात वाईट भीती असते. खरे सांगायचे तर, आपल्यातील सर्वात बहिर्मुख व्यक्तींना जेव्हा गर्दीला संबोधित करण्याची आवश्यकता असते तेव्हा त्यांच्या हृदयाचे ठोके वाढतात.

सार्वजनिक बोलणे हे सर्वात महत्त्वाचे संभाषण कौशल्य आहे.

- तुमच्या प्रेक्षकांना जाणून घ्या. तुमची शब्द निवड, माहितीचे प्रमाण आणि तुमच्या भाषणातील इतर घटक त्यानुसार तयार करण्यासाठी तुमच्या प्रेक्षकांसाठी शक्य तितके शिका. उदाहरणार्थ, जर तुम्ही हजारो लोकांच्या गर्दीला सादर करत असाल, तर तुम्ही तुमचे भाषण लहान, मुद्देसूद आणि हलके-फुलके ठेवणे चांगले होईल. दुसरीकडे, जर तुम्ही अधिक गंभीर विषयाबद्दल बोलत असाल, तर तुम्ही जरा जास्त गंभीर टोन ठेवू इच्छित असाल,
- तुमची सामग्री व्यवस्थित करा. तुमच्या प्रेक्षकांचे लक्ष वेधून घेण्यासाठी विषय, उद्देश, सामान्य कल्पना आणि मुख्य मुद्दे यासह तुमच्या सादरीकरणासाठी प्रेमवर्क तयार करा.
- अभिप्रायाकडे लक्ष द्या आणि त्याच्याशी जुळवून घ्या.

तुमचे व्यक्तिमत्त्व उजळू द्या. तुम्ही स्वतःसारखे वागल्यास तुमचे संभाषण तुमच्या प्रेक्षकांना खूप आवडेल. तुमच्या बोलण्यात तुमचा स्वभाव, वागणूक आणि व्यक्तिमत्त्व वापरा आणि तुम्ही अधिक अस्सल वाटाल.

निष्कर्ष:

कौशल्ये तुमची प्रतिभा, क्षमता आणि योग्यता दर्शवतात. थोडक्यात, आपण काय करण्यात चांगले आहात. बऱ्याच लोकांचा असा विश्वास आहे की त्यांच्याकडे काही कौशल्ये आहेत किंवा त्यांच्याकडे योग्य कौशल्ये नाहीत. किंबहुना, सरासरी व्यक्तीकडे असंख्य कौशल्ये असतात ज्यांचे श्रेय ते स्वतःला देत नाहीत, परंतु तरीही ती आहेत. ही कौशल्ये तुम्ही आयुष्यभर आत्मसात करत आहात. तुमची कौशल्ये आणि क्षमता शोधणे ही करिअरची निवड करण्यासाठी आणि व्यक्तिमत्व विकासाची एक महत्त्वाची गुरुकिल्ली आहे.

संदर्भ:

<https://www.panoramaed.com/blog/comprehensive-guide-21st-century-skills#:~:text=Learning>

<https://www.aeseducation.com/blog/what-are-21st-century-skills>

29. एकविसाव्या शतकातील कौशल्यांच्या अध्यापनासाठी छात्र शिक्षकांना प्रशिक्षणाची गरज - एक अभ्यास

डॉ. राकेश अशोक रामराजे⁴¹

सारांश

एकविसाव्या शतकामध्ये सद्य स्थितीत अध्ययन करणारे छात्र शिक्षक भविष्यात आत्मनिर्भर भारत बनविण्याच्या दृष्टीने महत्वपूर्ण भूमिका निभावणार आहेत. सद्य स्थितीमधील अभ्यासक्रमाचा अभ्यास करता त्यांना मिळत असणारे शिक्षण हे परंपरागत आलेले आणि कोव्हीड मध्ये ऑनलाईन पध्दतीने अध्ययन अशा स्वरूपाचे दिसून येते. आज ज्ञानाच्या कक्षा विस्तृत झालेल्या आपणास दिसून येतात. आज छात्र शिक्षकाने स्वतः शिकण्याची तयारी ठेवली पाहिजे. त्याची शिकण्याची प्रक्रिया कधीही बंद पडू नये. पुढील आयुष्यात शिक्षक म्हणून कार्य करित असतांना आयुष्याच्या अंतापर्यंत विद्यार्थी म्हणूनच जगायला हवे. कारण शाळेचा दर्जा हा शिक्षकाच्या दर्जावर अवलंबून असतो. शिक्षण विषयक कुठल्याही योजनेच्या केंद्रस्थानी शिक्षकच असतो. कोणतीही शिक्षण योजना शिक्षकाशिवाय राबविली जाऊ शकत नाही म्हणून शिक्षणाशी संबंधित सर्व विषयावर त्याचे सखोल चिंतन हवे. त्यासाठी भरपूर वाचन, भरपूर श्रवण करायला हवे. आपल्या दैनंदिन अध्यापनात त्याचा वापर करावा. या सर्व बाबी महत्वपूर्ण आहेत तसेच त्यांना असणारे संगणकीय ज्ञान व त्यांची कौशल्ये सुध्दा महत्वाची आहेत. ही कौशल्ये किती प्रमाणात छात्र शिक्षकांत आत्मसात झाली, त्यांना याची माहिती आहे का, असल्यास किती याचा अभ्यास होण्याच्या दृष्टीकोणातून “एकविसाव्या शतकातील कौशल्यांच्या अध्यापनासाठी छात्र शिक्षकांना प्रशिक्षणाची गरज - एक अभ्यास“ हे संशोधन उपयोगी ठरणार आहे..

मुख्य शब्द: कौशल्य, अध्यापन, प्रशिक्षण

प्रस्तावना

बालकांच्या शिक्षणाची खरी सुरुवात माता-पिता व कुटुंबानंतर समाजातच होत असते. शिक्षण पूर्ण झाल्यानंतर विद्यार्थ्यांला समाजातच कार्यरत व्हावे लागते, त्यामुळे त्यांच्या सामाजिक पैलूंचा विकास होणे, सामाजिक स्थितीची त्याला जाणिव असणे महत्वाची ठरते. समाजातील इतर आर्थिक, धार्मिक, राजकिय, सामाजिक व शैक्षणिक संस्थांशी विद्यार्थी संबंधित असतो. बालकांच्या विकासात कुटुंब, शाळा, सामाजिक परिसर महत्वाची भूमिका बजावतात, म्हणून शाळेतच बालकांच्या भावना अविष्कारास संधी देणे व वळण लावणे अपेक्षित आहे. शाळांमधून शिक्षणाची भावना, कृती, प्रेरणा यांना शिक्षकाकडून मार्गदर्शन केले जाते. विद्यार्थी आपले आचार, विचार, वर्तन व कृती समाजामध्ये, कुटुंबामध्ये प्रदर्शित करित असतो. कुटुंब तसेच समाज यांचेकडून मिळणाऱ्या प्रेरणेवर त्याचा सर्वांगीण विकास होण्यास मदत होत असते.

संशोधनाची गरज व महत्व

⁴¹ सहाय्यक प्राध्यापक, पी.व्ही.डी.टी. कॉलेज ऑफ एज्युकेशन फॉर वूमेन, एस.एन.डी.टी. महीला विद्यापीठ, चर्चगेट, मुंबई

संशोधक बी.एड् विद्यार्थ्यांचे सराव पाठ बघण्यास महानगरपालिकेच्या प्राथमिक, उच्च प्राथमिक तसेच अनुदानित, विनाअनुदानित प्राथमिक व माध्यमिक मराठी, हिंदी, इंग्रजी व उर्दू शाळांवर जात असे, त्यावेळी शाळेतील विद्यार्थ्यांचे विचार मांडण्याची शैली, संस्कृतीप्रमाणे झालेले सोपस्कर, त्यावर धार्मिकतेचा पगडा, राहणीमानामध्ये आर्थिकतेच्या बाबीतून दिसणारे बदल यातून गुणवत्तेवर होणारा परिणाम नजरेस पडत होता. त्यास अध्यापन करणारे छात्र शिक्षक अध्यापनात ज्या गाभाभूत घटकांचा व मूल्यांचा अर्थ सांगून त्यासाठी उदाहरणांचा वापर करत असे. एकविसाव्या शतकामध्ये सद्य स्थितीत अध्ययन करणारे छात्र शिक्षक भविष्यात आत्मनिर्भर भारत बनविण्याच्या दृष्टीने महत्वपूर्ण भूमिका निभावणार आहेत. म्हणूनच एकविसाव्या शतकातील कौशल्यांच्या अध्यापनासाठी छात्र शिक्षकांना प्रशिक्षणाची गरज - एक अभ्यास हे संशोधन महत्वाचे आहे.

संशोधनाचे समस्या विधान

एकविसाव्या शतकातील कौशल्यांच्या अध्यापनासाठी छात्र शिक्षकांना प्रशिक्षणाची गरज - एक अभ्यास हे संशोधन महत्वाचे आहे.

कार्यात्मक व्याख्या

कौशल्य - कौशल्य म्हणजे निश्चित केलेल्या परिणामांसह कृती करण्याची शिकलेली क्षमता.

अध्यापन - शिकवण्याची कृती, किंवा विद्यार्थ्यांना शिकवण्याची भावना.

प्रशिक्षण - स्वतःला किंवा इतर कोणाला शिक्षित करणे किंवा कौशल्ये विकसित करणे ज्यामुळे कार्यात प्रवीणता येते.

संशोधनाची गृहितके

शिक्षणशास्त्र महाविद्यालयात बी.एड्. अभ्यासक्रमात 'सूक्ष्म पाठ' याचा समावेश आहे.

शिक्षणशास्त्र महाविद्यालयात 'सूक्ष्म पाठ' या अंतर्गत विद्यार्थी पाठाचे नियोजन करून त्याचे सादरीकरण करतात.

संशोधनाची उद्दिष्टे

कौशल्यांच्या अध्यापनासाठी छात्र शिक्षकांना प्रशिक्षणाच्या गरजेचा अभ्यास करणे.

संशोधनाची व्याप्ती व मर्यादा

संशोधनाची व्याप्ती - संबंधित संशोधन पी. व्ही. डी. टी. कॉलेज ऑफ एज्युकेशन फॉर वूमेन, चर्चगेट, मुंबई या महाविद्यालयापुरतेच व्याप्त आहे.

संशोधनाची मर्यादा - संबंधित संशोधन संबंधित संशोधन पी. व्ही. डी. टी. कॉलेज ऑफ एज्युकेशन फॉर वूमेन, चर्चगेट, मुंबई मधील व्दितीय वर्षातील छात्र विद्यार्थी अध्यापनासाठी जे कौशल्ये वापरतात त्या कौशल्यांच्या गरजेच्या अभ्यासापुरतेच मर्यादीत आहे.

संशोधनाची पध्दती - सर्वेक्षण पध्दती

संशोधनाची साधने - प्रश्नावली

न्यादर्श - संबंधित संशोधन पी.व्ही.डी.टी. कॉलेज ऑफ एज्युकेशन फॉर वूमेन, चर्चगेट, मुंबई येथे व्दितीय वर्षातील अध्ययन करणारे 98 छात्र अध्यापक.

न्यादर्श निवड - सदर संशोधनासाठी संशोधकाने संशोधनासाठी सहेतूक लॉटरी पध्दतीने 48 छात्र विद्यार्थीनींची निवड केली आहे.

सांख्यिकीय परिणाम

उपलब्ध माहितीचे प्रस्तुतीकरण व केलेले सर्वेक्षण प्रस्तुत करण्याठी तसेच संख्याशास्त्रीय माहितीच्या वर्णनात्मक नोंदी करण्यासाठी पुढील सांख्यिकी तंत्राचा वापर केला आहे.

केंद्रीय प्रवृत्तीचे परिमाणे - शेकडा टक्केवारी

अनुमानात्मक विश्लेषण - प्रस्तुत तुलनात्मक स्थितीतून शेकडा टक्केवारी यांच्या माध्यमातून अनुमानात्मक विश्लेषणाचा वापर केलेला आहे.

संशोधनाची कार्यवाही

विद्यार्थी प्रश्नावली तयार करण्यात येवून विद्यार्थ्यांकडून भरुण घेण्यात आली व माहितीचे विश्लेषण करुन निष्कर्ष काढण्यात आले.

संख्याशास्त्रीय विश्लेषण

विद्यार्थ्यांना दिलेल्या प्रतिसादात्मक प्रश्नास विद्यार्थ्यांनी खालील कोष्टकामध्ये दर्शविल्याप्रमाणे शेकडा टक्केवारी प्रमाणे प्रतिसाद नोंदविला आहे.

प्रतिसादात्मक प्रश्नास विद्यार्थ्यांनी दिलेल्या प्रतिसादाची टक्केवारी

अ. क्र.	प्रतिसादात्मक प्रश्न	पूर्ण सहमत	सहमत	असहमत	पूर्ण असहमत
1	अध्यापनात येणाऱ्या अडचणींवर तुम्ही गांभीर्याने विचार (Critical Thinking) करतात.	71	17	8	4
2	गांभीर्याने विचार करणे (Critical Thinking) म्हणजे कोणत्याही गोष्टीचे वस्तुनिष्ठ विश्लेषण करण्याचे कौशल्य असणे. थोडक्यात सांगायचे म्हणजे प्रामाणिकपणा, वैचारिक मोकळेपणा, वैचारिक पातळीवरही सतत क्रियाशील असणे, प्रश्न विचारण्यासाठी किंवा प्रश्नांची उत्तरे देण्याची तयारी असणे, स्वतंत्र वैचारिक बैठक असणे, समस्यांचे निराकारक करण्याचे कौशल्य असणे.	75	13	8	4

3	<p>सर्जनशीलता (Creativity)</p> <p>नवनवीन कल्पना अस्खलितपणे सुचणे, वेगवेगळ्या बाजूंनी विचार करताना कोणत्याही विचाराशी बांधील न राहता लवचिकपणे सर्व बाजू तितक्याच प्रभावीपणे विचारात घेणे, इतरांच्या कल्पनांचा सहजपणे विस्तार करता येणे इत्यादी कौशल्ये सर्जनशीलतेची मुख्य अंग आहेत.</p>	67	25	4	4
4	<p>सहकार्य (Collaboration)</p> <p>सहकार्य म्हणजे इतरांबरोबर एक संघ म्हणून प्रभावीपणे काम करता येण्याची क्षमता असणे. संघ म्हणून काम करत असताना काही निर्णय घेणे आवश्यक असतात त्यावेळी इतरांच्या मतांचा आदर ठेऊन, संघभावनेने कार्य करता येण्याचे कौशल्य असणे.</p>	65	23	8	4
5	<p>संपर्क (Communication)</p> <p>आज संपर्काची माध्यमं बदलली असली तरीही प्रभावी संपर्क करता येण्याची हातोटी असणे आवश्यक आहे. एकच संदेश वेगवेगळ्या लोकांपर्यंत वेगवेगळ्या माध्यमातून पोहोचवणे किंवा स्वतःकडील विचार, कल्पना, भावभावना इत्यादी बाबी प्रभावीपणे इतरांपर्यंत पोहोचवणे ही कौशल्ये प्रभावी संपर्कासाठी आवश्यक आहेत.</p>	84	6	8	2
6	<p>साक्षरता (यशस्वी होण्यासाठी)</p> <p>पारंपरिक पद्धतीने माहिती असलेली साक्षरता महत्वाची आहेच पण त्याच बरोबरीने २१ व्या शतकात साक्षरतेचे काही इतर पैलू देखील आत्मसात करणे आवश्यक आहेत.</p>	79	13	4	4
7	<p>माहिती साक्षरता (Information Literacy)</p> <p>सक्षमपणे माहिती मिळवणे आणि त्या माहितीचे विश्लेषण करण्याची क्षमता असणे (उदाहरणार्थ – इंटरनेटवरून एखाद्या विषयाची विस्तृत माहिती घेऊन त्या माहितीचा अभ्यास/विश्लेषण करणे), माहितीचा योग्य आणि सर्जनशील वापर करून कोणत्याही समस्येचे निराकरण करणे, अनेक ठिकाणहून येणारी माहिती हाताळणे इत्यादी.</p>	84	6	8	2
8	<p>तंत्रज्ञान साक्षरता (Technology Literacy)</p> <p>तंत्रज्ञानाचा वापर संशोधन करण्यासाठी, दैनंदिन जीवनात आवश्यक असणारी माहिती गोळा करण्यासाठी, तिचे विश्लेषण करण्यासाठी करता येण्याचे कौशल्य असणे गरजेचे आहे.</p>	65	23	8	4

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9	जीवन कौशल्ये (यशस्वी होण्यासाठी) नावाप्रमाणेच जीवन कौशल्ये म्हणजे वैयक्तिक जीवनात आवश्यक असणारी कौशल्ये असणे. बहुतांशी हि कौशल्ये वैयक्तिक जीवनात जास्त उपयोगी ठरत असली तरीही त्यांचा वापर व्यावसायिक आयुष्यात देखील होतो.	67	25	4	4
10	लवचिकता (Flexibility) कामाच्या बाबतीत अथवा इतर बाबींमध्ये देखील लवचिकता असणे. सतत आपल्या सभोवताली होणाऱ्या बदलांना सामोरे जाऊन त्या बदलांचा स्वीकार करणे व त्यांच्याशी जुळवून घेणे गरजेचे आहे.	65	23	8	4
11	नेतृत्व (Leadership) काम करून इतरांना पुढे घेऊन जाण्याचे कौशल्य असणे. वेगवेगळ्या पद्धतीने संघाकडून सर्वोत्तम कामगिरी करून घेण्याची क्षमता असणे गरजेचे आहे.	67	25	4	4
12	यशस्वी पुढाकार (Initiative) कोणतेही कार्य करण्यासाठी पुढाकार घेण्याचे कौशल्य असणे. अंतःप्रेरणेतून ऊर्जा घेऊन वेगवेगळी कामं सुरु करण्याचे कौशल्य असणे गरजेचे आहे.	65	23	8	4
13	सामाजिक कौशल्ये (Social Skills) वेगवेगळ्या शहरांत, राज्यात, देशांमध्ये, संस्कृतींमध्ये सहजपणे मिसळून तिथल्या लोकांबरोबर काम करता येण्याचे कौशल्य शिक्षकांमध्ये असावे असे मला वाटते.	67	25	4	4
14	सध्याच्या भारतीय शिक्षण पद्धतीने विद्यार्थ्यांना हि कौशल्ये आत्मसात करता येतातच असे नाही त्यामुळे इतर ठिकाणहून हि कौशल्ये आत्मसात करून स्वतःचा विकास करणे क्रमप्राप्त ठरते.	92	2	4	2
15	बी. एड. अभ्यासक्रमात एकविसाव्या शतकास अनुसरून नवीन कौशल्याचा अभ्यास समावेश केलेला नाही.	100	0	0	0

निष्कर्ष

अध्यापनात येणाऱ्या अडचणींवर छात्र शिक्षक गांभीर्याने विचार (Critical Thinking) करतात.

गांभीर्याने विचार करणे (Critical Thinking) - कोणत्याही गोष्टीचे वस्तुनिष्ठ विश्लेषण करण्याचे कौशल्य असणे म्हणजे प्रामाणिकपणा, वैचारिक मोकळेपणा, वैचारिक पातळीवरही सतत क्रियाशील असणे, प्रश्न विचारण्यासाठी किंवा प्रश्नांची उत्तरे

देण्याची तयारी असणे, स्वतंत्र वैचारिक बैठक असणे, समस्यांचे निराकारक करण्याचे कौशल्य होय असे छात्र शिक्षकांचे म्हणणे आहे.

सर्जनशीलता (Creativity) - नवनवीन कल्पना अस्खलितपणे सुचणे, वेगवेगळ्या बाजूंनी विचार करताना कोणत्याही विचाराशी बांधील न राहता लवचिकपणे सर्व बाजू तितक्याच प्रभावीपणे विचारात घेणे, इतरांच्या कल्पनांचा सहजपणे विस्तार करता येणे इत्यादी कौशल्ये सर्जनशीलतेची मुख्य अंग आहेत असे छात्र शिक्षक मानतात.

सहकार्य (Collaboration) - सहकार्य म्हणजे इतरांबरोबर एक संघ म्हणून प्रभावीपणे काम करता येण्याची क्षमता असणे. संघ म्हणून काम करत असताना काही निर्णय घेणे आवश्यक असतात त्यावेळी इतरांच्या मतांचा आदर ठेऊन, संघभावनेने कार्य करता येण्याचे कौशल्य असणे गरजेचे आहे.

संपर्क (Communication) - आज संपर्काची माध्यम बदलली असली तरीही प्रभावी संपर्क करता येण्याची हातोटी असणे आवश्यक आहे. हा संदेश वेगवेगळ्या लोकांपर्यंत वेगवेगळ्या माध्यमातून पोहोचवणे किंवा स्वतःकडील विचार, कल्पना, भावभावना इत्यादी बाबी प्रभावीपणे इतरांपर्यंत पोहोचवणे ही कौशल्ये प्रभावी संपर्कासाठी आवश्यक आहेत.

साक्षरता (यशस्वी होण्यासाठी) - पारंपरिक पद्धतीने माहिती असलेली साक्षरता महत्वाची आहेच पण त्याच बरोबरीने 21 व्या शतकात साक्षरतेचे काही इतर पैलू देखील आत्मसात करणे आवश्यक आहेत.

लवचिकता (Flexibility) - कामाच्या बाबतीत अथवा इतर बाबींमध्ये देखील लवचिकता असणे. सतत आपल्या सभोवताली होणाऱ्या बदलांना सामोरे जाऊन त्या बदलांचा स्वीकार करणे व त्यांच्याशी जुळवून घेणे गरजेचे आहे.

नेतृत्व (Leadership) - काम करून इतरांना पुढे घेऊन जाण्याचे कौशल्य असणे. वेगवेगळ्या पद्धतीने संघाकडून सर्वोत्तम कामगिरी करून घेण्याची क्षमता असणे गरजेचे आहे.

यशस्वी पुढाकार (Initiative) - कोणतेही कार्य करण्यासाठी पुढाकार घेण्याचे कौशल्य असणे. अंतःप्रेरणेतून ऊर्जा घेऊन वेगवेगळी कामं सुरु करण्याचे कौशल्य असणे गरजेचे आहे.

सामाजिक कौशल्ये (Social Skills) - वेगवेगळ्या शहरांत, राज्यात, देशांमध्ये, संस्कृतींमध्ये सहजपणे मिसळून तिथल्या लोकांबरोबर काम करता येण्याचे कौशल्य शिक्षकांमध्ये असावे असे छात्र शिक्षकांना वाटते.

सध्याच्या भारतीय शिक्षण पद्धतीने विद्यार्थ्यांना हि कौशल्ये आत्मसात करता येतातच असे नाही त्यामुळे इतर ठिकाणहून हि कौशल्ये आत्मसात करून स्वतःचा विकास करणे क्रमप्राप्त ठरते.

बी. एड. अभ्यासक्रमात एकविसाव्या शतकास अनुसरून नवीन कौशल्याचा अभ्यास समावेश केलेला नाही.

शिफारशी

आज संपर्काची माध्यमं बदलली असली तरीही प्रभावी संपर्क करता येण्याची हातोटी असणे आवश्यक आहे. हा संदेश वेगवेगळ्या लोकांपर्यंत वेगवेगळ्या माध्यमातून पोहोचवणे किंवा स्वतःकडील विचार, कल्पना, भावभावना इत्यादी बाबी प्रभावीपणे इतरांपर्यंत पोहोचवणे हि कौशल्ये प्रभावी संपर्कासाठी आवश्यक आहेत. त्याबाबत छात्र शिक्षकांना मार्गदर्शन करावे.

छात्र शिक्षकांना पारंपरिक पद्धतीने माहिती असलेली साक्षरता महत्वाची आहेच पण त्याच बरोबरीने 21 व्या शतकात साक्षरतेचे काही इतर पैलू देखील आत्मसात करणे आवश्यक आहेत हे माहित असून अन्य अध्यापन दूरस्थ शिक्षणाने देता येते याबाबत अधिक माहिती द्यावी.

कामाच्या बाबतीत अथवा इतर बाबींमध्ये देखील लवचिकता असणे. सतत आपल्या सभोवताली होणाऱ्या बदलांना सामोरे जाऊन त्या बदलांचा स्वीकार करणे व त्यांच्याशी जुळवून घेणे गरजेचे आहे. त्याबाबत छात्र शिक्षकांना सूक्ष्म अध्यापन पद्धतीमध्ये माहिती द्यावी.

काम करून इतरांना पुढे घेऊन जाण्याचे कौशल्य असणे. वेगवेगळ्या पद्धतीने संघाकडून सर्वोत्तम कामगिरी करून घेण्याची क्षमता असणे गरजेचे आहे. याबाबत छात्र शिक्षकांना सूक्ष्म अध्यापन पद्धतीमध्ये माहिती द्यावी.

सध्याच्या भारतीय शिक्षण पद्धतीने विद्यार्थ्यांना हि कौशल्ये आत्मसात करता येतातच असे नाही त्यामुळे इतर ठिकाणहून हि कौशल्ये आत्मसात करून स्वतःचा विकास करणे क्रमप्राप्त ठरते याची माहिती छात्र शिक्षकांना द्यावी.

बी. एड. अभ्यासक्रमात एकविसाव्या शतकास अनुसरून नवीन कौशल्याचा अभ्यासक्रमामध्ये करण्यात यावा.

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30. हायस्कूलच्या विद्यार्थ्यांमध्ये जीवशास्त्राचे रेखाचित्र तयार करण्याचे कौशल्य वाढवणे

मुगधा सांगलेकर⁴²

सारांश

विज्ञान विषयाचे महत्त्व विज्ञान विद्यार्थ्यांना त्यांचे जग शोधू देते आणि नवीन गोष्टी शोधू देते. हा एक सक्रिय विषय देखील आहे, ज्यामध्ये हँड-ऑन लॅब आणि प्रयोग यासारख्या क्रियाकलापांचा समावेश आहे. आवश्यक कौशल्ये आकृती काढायला शिकण्यासाठी आवश्यक कौशल्ये म्हणजे ऐकण्याची कौशल्ये, निरीक्षण कौशल्ये, वाचन कौशल्ये, रेखाचित्र कौशल्ये आणि लेखन कौशल्ये. सध्याच्या स्पर्धात्मक जगात रेखाचित्रे काढण्याचे स्थान आणि त्यासाठी रेखाचित्र कौशल्य का महत्त्वाचे आहे. इंग्रजी माध्यमाच्या विद्यार्थ्यांना आकृती काढण्यात येणाऱ्या समस्या या संशोधनातून असे दिसून आले आहे की शालेय विज्ञान शिक्षकांना त्यांच्या विद्यार्थ्यांना आकृती काढण्याचे दर्जेदार शिक्षण देण्यासाठी पुरेसे प्रशिक्षण नाही. या शोधातून असा निष्कर्ष काढला जाऊ शकतो की अशी संसाधने शाळेत न वापरण्याचे हे एक कारण असू शकते. पुढे संशोधनातून असे दिसून आले आहे की, संशोधनाधीन असलेल्या शाळेला धड्यांदरम्यान शिक्षकांद्वारे वापरण्यासाठी तक्ते, नमुने आणि पाठ्यपुस्तके यासारखी अध्यापन/शिक्षण संसाधने खरेदी करण्यासाठी पुरेसा निधी उपलब्ध नव्हता. अध्यापन/अध्ययन संसाधनांच्या उपलब्धतेच्या दृष्टीने, पाठ्यपुस्तके आणि उपकरणे यासारख्या मूलभूत सुविधांच्या बाबतीत उच्च माध्यमिक शाळांमध्ये संसाधने कमी होती हे देखील दिसून आले. या परिस्थितीचा अनुक्रमे शिक्षक आणि विद्यार्थी या दोघांसाठी अध्यापन आणि शिकण्यावर खूप परिणाम झाला आहे. विद्यार्थी आणि शिक्षकांसाठीही संशोधन पुरेसे नाही. संशोधनात असेही आढळून आले की बहुतेक शिक्षक त्यांच्या अध्यापनासाठी अध्यापन/शिक्षण संसाधने सुधारू शकत नाहीत आणि त्यांनी इतर शाळांकडून काही अध्यापन/शिक्षण संसाधने देखील घेतली नाहीत. यावरून असा निष्कर्ष काढला जाऊ शकतो की हायस्कूलच्या शिक्षकांकडे वेळ आणि योग्य उपकरणांची कमतरता होती जी ते त्यांच्या शाळेच्या बजेटमधून घेऊ शकत नाहीत. सर्वात लोकप्रिय अध्यापन/शिक्षण संसाधनांच्या संदर्भात संशोधनातून असे दिसून आले की तेथे नेहमीची पाठ्यपुस्तके आणि काही वॉल तक्ते आहेत. यातूनच विद्यार्थी आणि शिक्षकांना इतर स्रोतांकडून माहितीच्या अभावाचे गांभीर्य दिसून येते. या संशोधनात असे देखील दिसून आले आहे की डॉईंग एड्स शिकवण्याची/शिकण्याची संसाधने जसे की टीव्ही, सीडी आणि संगणक या शाळेत नव्हते आणि त्यामुळे शिक्षक आणि विद्यार्थी दोघेही अनुक्रमे शिकवण्यासाठी आणि शिकण्यासाठी वापरू शकत नाहीत. या संशोधनातून असेही दिसून आले आहे की शाळांमध्ये आयसीटी आणि इंटरनेटचा वापर अद्याप लोकप्रिय नव्हता. संशोधनाच्या निष्कर्षांवरून असे दिसून आले आहे की आयसीटीच्या वापरासाठी प्रशिक्षित शिक्षक फारच कमी आहेत, त्यामुळे हायस्कूलमधील शिक्षक हायस्कूलमध्ये शिकवण्यासाठी वापरल्या जाणाऱ्या सॉफ्टवेअर पॅकेजेसच्या प्रकारांवर चर्चा करू शकत नाहीत.

मुख्य शब्द: रेखाचित्र, हायस्कूल, आयसीटी, कौशल्ये

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प्रस्तावना:

रेखाचित्र रेखाचित्रांची भूमिका आणि परिचय: आकृती हे मूलतः एक चित्र आहे जे माहिती संप्रेषण करते आणि अनेकदा सांख्यिकीय डेटा, इतर महत्त्वाची माहिती, संसाधनांवर कमी ताणासह विशिष्ट प्रणाली कशी कार्य करते हे स्पष्ट करते. विज्ञान विषयाचे महत्त्व विज्ञान विद्यार्थ्यांना त्यांचे जग शोधू देते आणि नवीन गोष्टी शोधू देते. हा एक सक्रिय विषय देखील आहे, ज्यामध्ये हँड-ऑन लॉब आणि प्रयोग यासारख्या क्रियाकलापांचा समावेश आहे. आवश्यक कौशल्ये आकृती काढायला शिकण्यासाठी आवश्यक कौशल्ये म्हणजे ऐकण्याची कौशल्ये, निरीक्षण कौशल्ये, वाचन कौशल्ये, रेखाचित्र कौशल्ये आणि लेखन कौशल्ये. हायलाइट रेखाचित्र कौशल्यांवर प्रकाश टाकणे आवश्यक आहे.

अभ्यासाची गरज:

सध्याच्या स्पर्धात्मक जगात रेखाचित्रे काढण्याचे स्थान आणि त्यासाठी रेखाचित्र कौशल्य का महत्त्वाचे आहे. आकृती काढताना इंग्रजी माध्यमाच्या विद्यार्थ्यांना भेदसावणाऱ्या समस्या. त्यामुळे स्पर्धात्मक जगात आकृत्या काढण्याचे महत्त्व लक्षात घेऊन, विद्यार्थ्यांना आकृती काढताना येणाऱ्या अडचणी ओळखणे आणि रेखाचित्रे सुधारण्यासाठी उपाययोजना करणे हे सध्याच्या अभ्यासाचे उद्दिष्ट आहे.

समस्या विधान:

हायस्कूलच्या विद्यार्थ्यांमध्ये जीवशास्त्राचे आरेखन तयार करण्याचे कौशल्य वाढवणे

मुख्य शब्दांच्या ऑपरेशनल कार्यात्मक व्याख्या:

- 1) वर्धित करणे: सध्याच्या अभ्यासामध्ये, रेखाचित्र आणि लेबलिंग गती आणि अचूकतेसह वाढवणे आणि आकृती आणि लेबलिंग लक्षात ठेवणे
- 2) कौशल्य: आकृती तयार करण्याची क्षमता किंवा कौशल्य.
- 3) आकृती तयार करणे: जीवशास्त्रातील आकृती योग्यरित्या काढणे आणि लेबल करणे.
- 4) जीवशास्त्र: हे राज्य मंडळाच्या इयत्ता 8 वी मध्ये शिकवलेल्या विषयाचा संदर्भ देते.
- 5) हायस्कूलचे विद्यार्थी: हे पाल राजेंद्र इंग्लिश हायस्कूलमध्ये शिक्षण घेत असलेल्या 8 वी च्या विद्यार्थ्यांचा संदर्भ देत

अभ्यासाची उद्दिष्टे:

1. पाल राजेंद्र इंग्लिश हायस्कूलच्या 8वीच्या विद्यार्थ्यांना आकृती तयार करताना येणाऱ्या अडचणी ओळखणे.
2. उपचारात्मक उपाय देऊन आकृती तयार करण्याचे कौशल्य वाढवणे.
3. 8वी इयत्तेतील पाल राजेंद्र इंग्लिश हायस्कूलच्या विद्यार्थ्यांच्या पूर्व-चाचणी आणि उत्तर चाचणीतील गुणामधील फरक अभ्यासणे परीक्षेनंतरच्या स्कोअरमधील फरक शोधण्यासाठी आकृती रेखाटणे.

शून्य परिकल्पना गृहितकः

HO1: 8वी इयत्तेच्या विद्यार्थ्यांना आकृती काढण्यात कोणतीही अडचण येत नाही.

HO2: उपायात्मक अध्यापनानंतरही आकृती तयार करण्यात विद्यार्थ्यांमध्ये कोणतीही सुधारणा झालेली नाही.

HO2: रेखांकन आकृतीमध्ये 8वी इयत्तेच्या विद्यार्थ्यांच्या पूर्व चाचणी स्कोअर आणि उत्तर चाचणीतील गुणा मध्ये चाचणी नंतरच्या स्कोअरमध्ये कोणताही फरक नाही.

अभ्यासाचे परिसीमनः

1. सध्याचा अभ्यास मुंबई शहरातील एका शाळेपुरता मर्यादित आहे, म्हणजे पाल राजेंद्र इंग्लिश हायस्कूल.
2. सध्याचा अभ्यास केवळ 8वी इयत्तेतील पाल राजेंद्र इंग्लिश हायस्कूलच्या विद्यार्थ्यांवर केंद्रित आहे. 3. सध्याचा अभ्यास हा जीवशास्त्रातील चित्र रेखाटण्याच्या कौशल्याशी संबंधित अडचणीपुरता मर्यादित आहे.
4. अभ्यासात फक्त 31 विद्यार्थी आहेत.
5. हा सध्याचा अभ्यास सत्र 2018-2019 च्या विद्यार्थ्यांपुरता मर्यादित आहे.
6. सध्याचा अभ्यास इंग्रजी माध्यमाच्या विद्यार्थ्यांपुरता मर्यादित आहे.
7. सध्याचा अभ्यास S.S.C. पुरता मर्यादित आहे. बोर्डाचे विद्यार्थी.

संबंधित साहित्याचे पुनरावलोकनः

संशोधन प्रकल्प हाती घेताना संबंधित साहित्याचा आढावा घेणे ही सर्वात आवश्यक पायरी आहे. हे संबंधित अभ्यासाचे संक्षिप्त आणि गंभीर मूल्यांकन प्रदान करते आणि या विशिष्ट क्षेत्रातील उपलब्ध ज्ञानामध्ये अभ्यास कसा योगदान देते हे दर्शविते. संशोधकाला उपयुक्त संकल्पना, साधने, तंत्रे आणि अभ्यासात वापरल्या जाणाऱ्या पद्धती समजून घेण्यास ते मदत करते तितकेच ते मौल्यवान आहे. संबंधित साहित्य संशोधनासाठी आवश्यक पार्श्वभूमी तयार करते आणि आवश्यक ज्ञानाचे मार्गदर्शन म्हणून काम करते ज्याचा संशोधकाला परिचय असणे आवश्यक आहे. वेगवेगळ्या अध्यापन पद्धती, मानसशास्त्र, विविध जर्नल्स, शैक्षणिक वर्षाची पुस्तके, प्रबंध, गोषवारा, वेब साईट्स इ. इतरत्र तत्सम अभ्यास किंवा तुलनात्मक स्वरूपाचे अभ्यास आयोजित केले गेले आहेत की नाही हे शोधून काढण्यात आले. असे आढळून आले की कला आणि चित्रकला कौशल्यावर आधारित शिक्षणात्मक दृष्टिकोनाचा अभ्यास फारच दुर्मिळ आहे. तथापि, अध्यापनाच्या अशा पद्धती, पध्दती आणि रणनीती याविषयीचे संक्षिप्त साहित्य उपलब्ध अभ्यासासोबत सादर केले गेले आहे जरी ते चित्रकला कौशल्याभिमुख निर्देशात्मक दृष्टिकोनाशी थेट संबंधित नसले तरी.

साहित्य सर्वेक्षण मेयर (1939) यांनी कलात्मकदृष्ट्या प्रतिभावान व्यक्तींच्या विकासासाठी प्रोत्साहन, संगोपन आणि मॉडेलिंगच्या महत्त्वावर चर्चा केली. कलात्मकदृष्ट्या प्रतिभावान लोक वारशाने मिळालेल्या, मिळवलेल्या आणि शिकलेल्या अनेक घटकांनी

प्रभावित होतात. कार्लसन (1963) यांनी असे निरीक्षण केले की चौथी, पाचवी आणि सहावी इयत्तेचे विद्यार्थी ज्यांना विशेष उत्तेजक साहित्य (चित्रे, रेकॉर्ड, खेळणी) प्रदान करण्यात आले होते त्यांनी दीर्घ आणि अधिक मूळ रचना लिहिल्या आणि नियंत्रण गटातील विद्यार्थ्यांपेक्षा अधिक बहुमुखी शब्दसंग्रह वापरले जे नियुक्त विषयावर लिहित होते. . ओल्सन (1968) यांना असे आढळून आले की मुलांना रेखाचित्रांचे नियम शिकवल्याने त्यांच्या रेखाचित्रे बनवण्याच्या क्षमतेत लक्षणीय सुधारणा झाली. असे काही पुरावे आहेत की मुले चित्र काढताना नियम वापरतात.

संबंधित साहित्याचे पुनरावलोकन:

संशोधन प्रकल्प हाती घेताना संबंधित साहित्याचा आढावा घेणे ही सर्वात आवश्यक पायरी आहे. हे संबंधित अभ्यासाचे संक्षिप्त आणि गंभीर मूल्यांकन प्रदान करते आणि या विशिष्ट क्षेत्रातील उपलब्ध ज्ञानामध्ये अभ्यास कसा योगदान देते हे दर्शविते. संशोधकाला उपयुक्त संकल्पना, साधने, तंत्रे आणि अभ्यासात वापरल्या जाणाऱ्या पद्धती समजून घेण्यास ते मदत करते तितकेच ते मौल्यवान आहे. संबंधित साहित्य संशोधनासाठी आवश्यक पार्श्वभूमी तयार करते आणि आवश्यक ज्ञानाचे मार्गदर्शन म्हणून काम करते ज्याचा संशोधकाला परिचय असणे आवश्यक आहे. वेगवेगळ्या अध्यापन पद्धती, मानसशास्त्र, विविध जर्नल्स, शैक्षणिक वर्षाची पुस्तके, प्रबंध, गोषवारा, वेब साईट्स इ. इतरत्र तत्सम अभ्यास किंवा तुलनात्मक स्वरूपाचे अभ्यास आयोजित केले गेले आहेत की नाही हे शोधून काढण्यात आले. असे आढळून आले की कला आणि चित्रकला कौशल्यावर आधारित शिक्षणात्मक दृष्टिकोनाचा अभ्यास फारच दुर्मिळ आहे. तथापि, अध्यापनाच्या अशा पद्धती, पद्धती आणि रणनीती याविषयीचे संक्षिप्त साहित्य उपलब्ध अभ्यासासोबत सादर केले गेले आहे जरी ते चित्रकला कौशल्याभिमुख निर्देशात्मक दृष्टिकोनाशी थेट संबंधित नसले तरी.

साहित्य सर्वेक्षण मेयर (1939) यांनी कलात्मकदृष्ट्या प्रतिभावान व्यक्तींच्या विकासासाठी प्रोत्साहन, संगोपन आणि मॉडेलिंगच्या महत्त्वावर चर्चा केली. कलात्मकदृष्ट्या प्रतिभावान लोक वारशाने मिळालेल्या, मिळवलेल्या आणि शिकलेल्या अनेक घटकांनी प्रभावित होतात. कार्लसन (1963) यांनी असे निरीक्षण केले की चौथी, पाचवी आणि सहावी इयत्तेचे विद्यार्थी ज्यांना विशेष उत्तेजक साहित्य (चित्रे, रेकॉर्ड, खेळणी) प्रदान करण्यात आले होते त्यांनी दीर्घ आणि अधिक मूळ रचना लिहिल्या आणि नियंत्रण गटातील विद्यार्थ्यांपेक्षा अधिक बहुमुखी शब्दसंग्रह वापरले जे नियुक्त विषयावर लिहित होते. . ओल्सन (1968) यांना असे आढळून आले की मुलांना रेखाचित्रांचे नियम शिकवल्याने त्यांच्या रेखाचित्रे बनवण्याच्या क्षमतेत लक्षणीय सुधारणा झाली. असे काही पुरावे आहेत की मुले चित्र काढताना नियम वापरतात.

खालील साहित्याचे पुनरावलोकन केले गेले:

शीर्षक: इम्युनोग्लोब्युलिनच्या पाठ्यपुस्तकाच्या आकृतीच्या व्याख्याने विद्यार्थ्यांना अडचणी

संशोधकाचे नाव: कोनराड जे. शॉनबॉर्न, ट्रेव्हर आर. अँडरसन आणि डियान जे. ग्रेसन वर्ष: 2000 नमुना आणि नमुना पद्धत: मिश्र पद्धत

वापरलेली साधने: पूर्व-चाचणी आणि पोस्ट-चाचणी

उद्दिष्ट: इम्युनोग्लोब्युलिन जी च्या संरचनेचे प्रतिनिधित्व करणाऱ्या विविध प्रकारच्या आकृत्यांच्या स्पष्टीकरणासह विद्यार्थ्यांच्या वैचारिक आणि तर्कशुद्ध अडचणी ओळखणे आणि त्यांचे वर्गीकरण करणे.

परिणाम: या अभ्यासात ओळखल्या गेलेल्या अडचणी असे सूचित करतात की विद्यार्थ्यांच्या आकृतीचा अर्थ लावण्याची क्षमता, विद्यार्थ्यांची आकृतीसह तर्क करण्याची क्षमता, विद्यार्थ्यांच्या समर्पकतेच्या संकल्पनांची समज (किंवा त्याची कमतरता) यावर परिणाम करणारे किमान तीन घटक आहेत. आकृती, आणि मोड ज्यामध्ये इच्छित घटना रेखाचित्रानुसार दर्शविली जाते. हे तीन घटक परस्परावलंबी आहेत; कोणता घटक प्रमुख भूमिका बजावत आहे हे स्थापित करणे कठीण बनवते. तरीही, अडचणी कुठे आहेत आणि त्या कशा दूर केल्या जाऊ शकतात याची स्पष्ट कल्पना विकसित करण्यासाठी प्रत्येक घटकाचा स्वतंत्रपणे विचार करणे उपयुक्त आहे.

निष्कर्ष: निष्कर्षानुसार, या पेपरमध्ये सादर केलेले निष्कर्ष इतर अभ्यासांच्या परिणामांची पुष्टी करतात, जे दर्शविते की विज्ञानातील आकृत्यांचा चुकीचा अर्थ लावणे आणि तर्क करणे यामुळे गैरसमज आणि संकल्पनात्मक अडचणी निर्माण होऊ शकतात. भविष्यातील संशोधन बायोकेमिस्ट्रीमधील इतर आकृत्यांसह विद्यार्थ्यांच्या अडचणींवर लक्ष केंद्रित करेल जेणेकरून बायोकेमिस्ट्रीमधील अभिप्रेत समज आणि शिकण्याचे परिणाम साध्य करण्यासाठी आकृत्यांच्या परिणामकारकतेचे मूल्यांकन करण्यासाठी निकष तयार केले जातील. अशा संशोधनाचे परिणाम शिक्षक आणि शिकणाऱ्यांनी आणि पाठ्यपुस्तक लेखकांद्वारे डिझाइन केलेले आकृती सर्वोत्तम कसे वापरावेत याबद्दल मार्गदर्शक तत्त्वे मिळतील अशी आशा आहे.

संशोधन पद्धतीची निवड: सध्याचा अभ्यास करण्यासाठी प्रायोगिक संशोधन पद्धती निवडण्यात आली. प्रायोगिक संशोधन डिझाइनमध्ये प्रायोगिक पूर्व डिझाइन म्हणजेच एक गट पूर्व-चाचणी पोस्ट-टेस्ट डिझाइन वापरला जातो. एक-समूह पूर्व-चाचणी - चाचणीनंतरची रचना या डिझाइनमध्ये संशोधक एक पूर्व-चाचणी, नंतर उपचार आणि शेवटी एक पोस्ट-टेस्ट आयोजित करतो. प्रीटेस्ट आणि पोस्ट-टेस्ट स्कोअरमधील फरकानुसार उपचारांचे परिणाम ठरवले जातात.

डिझाइन खालीलप्रमाणे दर्शविले आहे: O1 X O2

कुठे O1 - पूर्व-चाचणी X - उपचार O2 - पोस्ट-टेस्ट

नमुना आणि नमुना तंत्र

नमुना: नमुना हा लोकसंख्येचा एक छोटासा भाग असतो जो निरीक्षण आणि विश्लेषणासाठी निवडला जातो. नमुन्यात पाल राजेंद्र इंग्लिश हायस्कूलमधून ३१ विद्यार्थ्यांचा समावेश आहे..

नल हायपोथिसिस (HO1): 8वी इयत्तेच्या विद्यार्थ्यांना आकृती काढण्यात कोणतीही अडचण येत नाही.

क्र.	चाचणी	विद्यार्थ्यांची एकूण संख्या	मीन(M1)
1	पूर्व चाचणी	31	9 .03

Proceeding: National Seminar on Development of 21st-century skills for Atmanirbhar Bharat (Self-reliant India), 23,24 December 2022

विद्यार्थ्यांच्या पूर्व चाचणी गुणांचे विश्लेषण

व्याख्या

पूर्व परीक्षेत विद्यार्थ्यांनी मिळवलेले सरासरी गुण 9.03 असल्याचे तक्ता दर्शविते. इयत्ता 8वीच्या विद्यार्थ्यांना आकृती तयार करताना अडचणी येतात हे यावरून दिसून येते. शून्य गृहितक 1 नाकारले आहे.

उद्दिष्ट २: उपायात्मक उपाय देऊन आकृती तयार करण्याचे कौशल्य वाढवणे.

नल हायपोथिसिस (HO2): उपायात्मक शिकवल्यानंतरही आकृती तयार करण्यात विद्यार्थ्यांमध्ये कोणतीही सुधारणा होत नाही.

क्र.	चाचणी	विद्यार्थ्यांची एकूण संख्या	मीन(M1)
1	उत्तर-चाचणी	31	18.19

व्याख्या:

तक्ता रेखांकन आकृतीमध्ये इयत्ता 8 वी च्या परीक्षेनंतरचे गुण दर्शविते. विद्यार्थ्यांनी मिळवलेले सरासरी गुण 18.19 आहे. यावरून असे दिसून येते की उपचारात्मक उपायांनंतर आकृती तयार करण्यात उल्लेखनीय सुधारणा झाली आहे. त्यामुळे शून्य गृहितक (२) नाकारले जाते.

उद्दिष्ट 3: 8वी इयत्ता पाल राजेंद्र इंग्लिश हायस्कूलच्या विद्यार्थ्यांच्या पूर्व-चाचणी आणि परीक्षेनंतरच्या स्कोअरमधील फरक शोधणे. नल हायपोथिसिस (HO3): रेखांकन आकृतीमध्ये 8वी इयत्तेच्या विद्यार्थ्यांच्या पूर्व चाचणी स्कोअर आणि पोस्ट-टेस्ट स्कोअरमध्ये फरक नाही.

पूर्व-चाचणी आणि उत्तर-परीक्षेमध्ये विद्यार्थ्यांनी मिळवलेल्या स्कोअरच्या सरासरी मूल्यांमधील फरक

क्र.	Test	विद्यार्थ्यांची एकूण संख्या	मीन (M1)	Difference of Mean (M2-M1)
1	पूर्व चाचणी	31	9.0	9.16
2	उत्तर-चाचणी	31	18.19	

व्याख्या:

विद्यार्थ्यांच्या पूर्व-चाचणी आणि उत्तर-परीक्षेचा अर्थ तक्ता 4.3 मध्ये काढला आहे. हे स्पष्ट आहे की चाचणीनंतर गुणांची सरासरी (18.19) पूर्व चाचणी स्कोअरच्या सरासरीपेक्षा (9.03) जास्त आहे. सरासरीमधील फरक 9.16 आहे शून्य गृहितक 3 नाकारले आहे. हे दर्शविते की उपचारात्मक उपायांचा परिणाम म्हणून विद्यार्थ्यांच्या कार्यक्षमतेत उल्लेखनीय सुधारणा झाली आहे. पूर्व-चाचणी आणि उत्तर-परीक्षेमध्ये विद्यार्थ्यांनी मिळवलेल्या स्कोअरच्या सरासरी मूल्यामध्ये ग्राफिकल प्रतिनिधित्व दिलेले आहे.

सारांश आणि निष्कर्ष

संशोधनातून असे दिसून आले आहे की शालेय विज्ञान शिक्षकांना त्यांच्या विद्यार्थ्यांना आकृती काढण्याचे दर्जेदार शिक्षण देण्यासाठी पुरेसे प्रशिक्षण नाही. या शोधातून असा निष्कर्ष काढला जाऊ शकतो की अशी संसाधने शाळेत न वापरण्याचे हे एक कारण असू शकते. पुढे संशोधनातून असे दिसून आले आहे की, संशोधनाधीन असलेल्या शाळेला धड्यांदरम्यान शिक्षकांद्वारे वापरण्यासाठी तक्ते, नमुने आणि पाठ्यपुस्तके यासारखी अध्यापन/शिक्षण संसाधने खरेदी करण्यासाठी पुरेसा निधी उपलब्ध नव्हता. अध्यापन/अध्ययन संसाधनांच्या उपलब्धतेच्या दृष्टीने, पाठ्यपुस्तके आणि उपकरणे यासारख्या मूलभूत सुविधांच्या बाबतीत उच्च माध्यमिक शाळांमध्ये संसाधने कमी होती हे देखील दिसून आले. या परिस्थितीचा अनुक्रमे शिक्षक आणि विद्यार्थी या दोघांसाठी अध्यापन आणि शिकण्यावर खूप परिणाम झाला आहे. विद्यार्थी आणि शिक्षकांसाठीही संशोधन पुरेसे नाही.

संशोधनात असेही आढळून आले की बहुतेक शिक्षक त्यांच्या अध्यापनासाठी अध्यापन/शिक्षण संसाधने सुधारू शकत नाहीत आणि त्यांनी इतर शाळांकडून काही अध्यापन/शिक्षण संसाधने देखील घेतली नाहीत. यावरून असा निष्कर्ष काढला जाऊ शकतो की हायस्कूलच्या शिक्षकांकडे वेळ आणि योग्य उपकरणांची कमतरता होती जी ते त्यांच्या शाळेच्या बजेटमधून घेऊ शकत नाहीत. सर्वात लोकप्रिय अध्यापन/शिक्षण संसाधनांच्या संदर्भात संशोधनातून असे दिसून आले की तेथे नेहमीची पाठ्यपुस्तके आणि काही वॉल तक्ते आहेत. यातूनच विद्यार्थी आणि शिक्षकांना इतर स्रोतांकडून माहितीच्या अभावाचे गांभीर्य दिसून येते

या संशोधनात असे देखील दिसून आले आहे की डॉईंग एड्स शिकवण्याची/शिकण्याची संसाधने जसे की टीव्ही, सीडी आणि संगणक या शाळेत नव्हते आणि त्यामुळे शिक्षक आणि विद्यार्थी दोघेही अनुक्रमे शिकवण्यासाठी आणि शिकण्यासाठी वापरू शकत नाहीत. या संशोधनातून असेही दिसून आले आहे की शाळांमध्ये आयसीटी आणि इंटरनेटचा वापर अद्याप लोकप्रिय नव्हता. संशोधनाच्या निष्कर्षांवरून असे दिसून आले आहे की आयसीटीच्या वापरासाठी प्रशिक्षित शिक्षक फारच कमी आहेत, त्यामुळे हायस्कूलमधील शिक्षक हायस्कूलमध्ये शिकवण्यासाठी वापरल्या जाणाऱ्या सॉफ्टवेअर पॅकेजेसच्या प्रकारांवर चर्चा करू शकत नाहीत.

निष्कर्ष:

1. संशोधनातून असा निष्कर्ष निघाला की व्हिज्युअल एड्स, चार्ट पेपर्स, कॉम्प्युटरचा वापर करून रेखाचित्रे काढण्याचे आणि लक्षात ठेवण्याचे योग्य प्रशिक्षण दिले जाते, यामुळे विचारांना चालना मिळते आणि विद्यार्थ्यांचे आरेखन कौशल्य सुधारते.
2. शिक्षकांद्वारे योग्य रेखाचित्र पद्धतींचा प्रभावी वापर नीरस शिक्षण वातावरणाचा पर्याय बनवतो.
3. जेव्हा विद्यार्थी वर्गात यशस्वी आणि आनंददायी शिक्षण घेतात तेव्हा ते शिकण्याच्या क्षेत्रांची वैयक्तिक समज विकसित करतात आणि वाढवतात.
4. विद्यार्थ्यांना रेखाचित्र सत्रांचे प्रशिक्षण उपयुक्त आणि संबंधित वाटते जेव्हा त्यांचा अभ्यासक्रमाच्या सामग्रीशी थेट संबंध असतो.

सूचना:

संशोधनातून हे स्पष्ट झाले आहे की अभ्यासात असलेल्या विद्यार्थ्यांच्या आजूबाजूच्या प्रत्येकाने आकृतीची मूळ संकल्पना समजून घेण्यासाठी आवश्यक उपाययोजना केल्या पाहिजेत. सामान्य सूचना:

शिक्षकांसाठी:

- 1) शाळा व्यवस्थापनाने उपचारात्मक शिकवणी वर्ग उपलब्ध करून द्यावेत.
- 2) सायन्स क्लब आणि सायन्स फेअर आणि सायन्स लॅबचे आयोजन करण्यासाठी शाळा व्यवस्थापनाने पुढाकार घ्यावा.
- 3) शालेय व्यवस्थापनाला सर्जनशील शिक्षणासाठी विज्ञानाच्या छोट्या सहलींचे आयोजन करावे लागते.
- 4) शिक्षकांनी रेखाचित्रात्मक प्रतिनिधित्व समजून घेण्याबाबत विद्यार्थ्यांच्या मताला महत्त्व दिले पाहिजे.
- 5) शाळा, महाविद्यालय आणि विद्यापीठ प्रशासन प्राधिकरणाने सुधारित रेखाचित्र तंत्रांच्या वापराबाबत विद्यार्थ्यांची मते सामायिक करणे आवश्यक आहे जे शिक्षण प्रणाली वाढविण्यासाठी उपयुक्त ठरतील.
- 6) विद्यार्थ्यांच्या गरजेनुसार योग्य रेखाचित्र तंत्र वापरण्याचे कौशल्य सुधारण्यासाठी शिक्षकांसाठी रिफ्रेशर कोर्सेस, कार्यशाळा आणि परिषदा आयोजित केल्या जाऊ शकतात.

विद्यार्थ्यांसाठी:

- 1) विद्यार्थ्यांना आकृती काढण्याचे महत्त्व समजले पाहिजे.
- 2) विद्यार्थ्यांनी शिक्षकांनी दिलेल्या सूचनांचे पालन करावे.

पुढील अभ्यासासाठी सूचना:

- 1) संशोधन इतर शाळांमध्ये, इतर जिल्ह्यांच्या इतर शाळांमध्ये आणि इतर राज्यांमध्ये केले जाऊ शकते.
- 2) संशोधकाला ICSE किंवा CBSE बोर्डांचे नमुने देखील निवडता येतील.
- 3) इतर विषयांवर अभ्यास करता येतो.
- 4) अभ्यास हा उच्च माध्यमिक विद्यार्थ्यांवर आधारित असू शकतो.
- 5) भौतिकशास्त्र, रसायनशास्त्र इत्यादी इतर विषयांवर अभ्यास करता येईल.

संदर्भसूची

पुस्तके: इयत्ता 8 वी साठी विज्ञान पाठ्यपुस्तक रेखाचित्र हँडबुक रेखांकनाचा सराव आणि विज्ञान

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31. दूरस्थ शिक्षणातील प्रशिक्षणार्थींच्या प्राथमिक तंत्रज्ञान कौशल्य विकासासंबंधीच्या सदयस्थितीचा अभ्यास

डॉ.पांडे विद्युलता ज्ञानेश्वर⁴³, श्रीमती.जोगदनकर सुनिता मारुती⁴⁴

सारांश

२१ व्या शतकातील विविध कौशल्यांमध्ये तंत्रज्ञान कौशल्य हे महत्वपूर्ण आणि मूलभूत असून त्याचे ज्ञान हे शिक्षणातील विविध घटकांच्या ज्ञानाबरोबरच आवश्यक आहे.शालेय शिक्षणापासून तसेच आज प्रसार माध्यमांच्या वाढत्या वापरामुळे तंत्रज्ञान कौशल्याचे ज्ञान विद्यार्थ्यांना सहज येते.परंतु प्रौढ विद्यार्थी त्या तुलनेत जरासा कमी पडतो. तो तंत्रज्ञान वापरताना तो विकास तितका सक्षमतेने काम करत नाही मनात थोडी भीती दडपण इ. भावना निर्माण होऊन तो सक्षमतेने तंत्रज्ञान वापरात कमी पडतो. आज अध्यापनाचे कार्य करणारे शिक्षक आपला व्यावसायिक विकास सातत्याने होत राहावा म्हणून विविध प्रशिक्षण तसेच शिक्षण घेत असतात ते काळानुरूप राष्ट्राचा तसेच पुढील बढतीसाठी शिक्षण प्राप्त करतात त्यामध्ये सेवा अंतर्गत बी. एड प्रशिक्षण हा एक अभ्यासक्रम असून सेवेत असणाऱ्या शिक्षकांना ह्या प्रशिक्षणाला प्रवेश मिळतो. हे प्रशिक्षण काळरूप असून यामध्ये एकविसाव्या शतकातील कौशल्याचे विकसन यावरही भर देण्यात आलेला आहे. सदर प्रशिक्षण प्रौढ विद्यार्थी प्रशिक्षणार्थी घेत असताना निश्चित त्यांची तंत्रज्ञान विषयात ज्ञान तसेच सद्यस्थिती कशी आहे त्यांना कौशल्य आणि तंत्रज्ञान साक्षरता प्राप्त करताना कोणकोणत्या अडचणी येतात? सत्य तसेच काळानुरूप विकासासाठी तंत्रज्ञान साक्षरता विषय हा बीएड अभ्यासक्रम प्रौढ प्रशिक्षणातील उपयुक्त होतो? वरील सर्व बाबी जाणून घेण्यासाठी संशोधकाने हाती घेतल्या तसेच या लघुसंशोधनातून प्रौढ प्रशिक्षणार्थींमध्ये तंत्रज्ञान कौशल्य साक्षरता कौशल्यासंबंधीची जाणीजागृती होण्यास मदत होईल.

मुख्य शब्द: २१ व्या शतकातील कौशल्य, बी.एड प्रशिक्षणार्थी, दूरस्थ शिक्षण, शैक्षणिक तंत्रविज्ञान,

प्रस्तावना

आज तंत्रज्ञान कौशल्य प्राप्त करणे ही काळाची असून तंत्रज्ञानाच्या अभावी आपण निरक्षर म्हणून घेवू को काय? अशी भीती निर्माण झाली आहे. २१ व्या शतकातील विविध कौशल्यांमध्ये तंत्रज्ञान कौशल्य हे महत्वपूर्ण आणि मूलभूत असून त्याचे ज्ञान हे शिक्षणातील विविध घटकांच्या ज्ञानाबरोबरच आवश्यक आहे.

शालेय शिक्षणापासून तसेच आज प्रसार माध्यमांच्या वाढत्या वापरामुळे तंत्रज्ञान कौशल्याचे ज्ञान विद्यार्थ्यांना सहज येते. परंतु प्रौढ विद्यार्थी त्या तुलनेत जरासा कमी पडतो. तो तंत्रज्ञान वापरताना तो विकास तितका सक्षमतेने काम करत नाही मनात थोडी भीती दडपण इ. भावना निर्माण होऊन तो सक्षमतेने तंत्रज्ञान वापरात कमी पडतो.

काळानुसार बदल स्वीकारणे आपणास तितकेसे कठीण असते त्याचाच परिणाम प्राथमिक तंत्रज्ञानाची कौशल्य प्रौढ शिक्षणार्थींमध्ये आपणास कमी प्रमाणात दिसून येतात. त्यांना ही कौशल्य तितकीशी कुशलतेणे वापरता तसेच दाखविता येत नाही.

⁴³ प्राचार्या, उमा शिक्षण शास्त्र महाविद्यालय पंढरपूर.

⁴⁴ संशोधक विद्यार्थी, कॉलेज ऑफ एज्युकेशन बार्शी, सोलापूर

बाल्यावस्थेत हे शिक्षण प्राप्त न झाल्यामुळे त्याच्या शारीरिक विकासाबरोबरच तंत्रज्ञान कौशल्याचा विकास होणे आवश्यक असते. परंतु त्या काळात तंत्रज्ञानाचा विकास झालेला नसल्याने आज प्रौढ विद्यार्थी या समस्या सामोरे जातात.

आज अध्यापनाचे कार्य करणारे शिक्षक आपला व्यावसायिक विकास सातत्याने होत राहावा म्हणून विविध प्रशिक्षण तसेच शिक्षण घेत असतात ते काळानुरूप राष्ट्राचा तसेच पुढील बढतीसाठी शिक्षण प्राप्त करतात त्यामध्ये सेवा अंतर्गत बी. एड प्रशिक्षण हा एक अभ्यासक्रम असून सेवेत असणाऱ्या शिक्षकांना ह्या प्रशिक्षणाला प्रवेश मिळतो. हे प्रशिक्षण काळरूप असून यामध्ये एकविसाव्या शतकातील कौशल्याचे विकसन यावरही भर देण्यात आलेला आहे. सदर प्रशिक्षण प्रौढ विद्यार्थी प्रशिक्षणार्थी घेत असताना निश्चित त्यांची तंत्रज्ञान विषयात ज्ञान तसेच सद्यस्थिती कशी आहे त्यांना कौशल्य आणि तंत्रज्ञान साक्षरता प्राप्त करताना कोणकोणत्या अडचणी येतात? सत्य तसेच काळानुरूप विकासासाठी तंत्रज्ञान साक्षरता विषय हा बीएड अभ्यासक्रम प्रौढ प्रशिक्षणातील उपयुक्त होतो? वरील सर्व बाबी जाणून घेण्यासाठी संशोधकाने दूरस्थ शिक्षणातील प्रशिक्षणार्थीच्या प्राथमिक तंत्रज्ञान कौशल्य विकासासंबंधीच्या सद्यस्थितीचा अभ्यास करण्याचे निश्चित केले आहे.

२१ व्या शतकातील कौशल्य

२१ व्या शतकातील कौशल्ये" ही संकल्पना अनेक दशकांपासून शिक्षणक्षेत्रात गंभीर विचार, सहयोग, सर्जनशीलता आणि समस्या सोडवणे यासारखी कौशल्ये शिकवली जात आहेत.

२१ व्या शतकात साक्षरतेचे काही इतर पैलू देखील आत्मसात करणे आवश्यक आहेत. साक्षरतेचे ३ उप-प्रकारांत विभागणी केली आहे.

२१ व्या शतकातील कौशल्ये

(संदर्भ <https://marathi.plus/21st-century-skills/>)

तंत्रज्ञान साक्षरता:- तंत्रज्ञान साक्षरता म्हणजे तंत्रज्ञानाचा सुरक्षितपणे, प्रभावीपणे आणि जबाबदारीने वापर करण्याची, समजून घेण्याची, व्यवस्थापित करण्याची आणि विश्लेषण करण्याची क्षमता. या साक्षरतेमध्ये माहितीचे मूल्यमापन, निर्मिती आणि एकत्रित करण्यासाठी तंत्रज्ञानाचा वापर करणे समाविष्ट आहे.

दुरस्थ शिक्षण

"विद्यार्थी आणि शिक्षक या दोन घटकांतील भौतिक अंतरामुळे छापील साहित्य व आधुनिक तंत्रज्ञान यांच्या दुव्यामुळे ह्या दोन घटकांमध्ये सुसंवाद साधला जाऊन जे शिक्षण मिळते ते दूरस्थ शिक्षण होय."

प्रौढ शिक्षण (Andragogy) संकल्पना

१. माल्कम शेफर्ड नोल्स (1913 1997) हे एक अमेरिकन शिक्षक होते जे प्रौढ शिक्षणासाठी समानार्थी शब्द Andragogy वापरण्यासाठी प्रसिद्ध होते.

२. माल्कम नोल्सच्या मते, अॅन्ड्रॅगॉजी ही प्रौढांच्या शिक्षणाची कला आणि विज्ञान आहे, अशा प्रकारे अॅन्ड्रॅगॉजी म्हणजे प्रौढ शिक्षणाच्या कोणत्याही स्वरूपाचा संदर्भ.

(संदर्भ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Andragogy>)

दुरस्थ शिक्षण शिक्षणशास्त्र अभ्यासक्रम (शैक्षणिक तंत्रविज्ञान)

उद्दिष्टे

१. शैक्षणिक तंत्रविज्ञानाचे स्वरूप स्पष्ट करणे.
२. संज्ञापन प्रक्रीया व त्यातील विविध घटकांची माहिती देणे.
३. प्रणाली उपागमाचा होणारा परिणाम स्पष्ट करणे.
४. अध्यापन घटकासाठी अध्यापन अनुदेशन प्रणाली रचना तयार करण्याची कौशल्य विकसित करणे.
५. दृक्-श्राव्य साधन विकसनासाठी साहित्य लेखनाचे कौशल्य विकसित करणे.
६. शैक्षणिक तंत्रविज्ञानातील साधनांचा अध्यापनात योग्य वापर करून त्यांचे व्यवस्थापन करण्याचे कौशल्य विकसित करणे.
७. शिक्षणातील नवे विचार प्रवाह सांगून ते विद्यार्थ्यांमध्ये समजण्याची क्षमता विकसित करणे.

अभ्यासक्रम

१. अध्यापनातील दृक्श्राव्य साधने

२. स्लाईड प्रोजेक्टर

३. स्लाईड्स/फिल्म स्ट्रिप्स

४. शीर्ष प्रक्षेपक

५. विविध माध्यमांचा अध्यापनात उपयोग

६. दृक् श्राव्य साधनांची कार्ये-

७. शैक्षणिक साहित्याचे प्रस्तुतीकरण

८. शैक्षणिक तंत्रविज्ञान साधनांचे व्यवस्थापन

९. अनेक तंत्रांचा मिलाफ

१०. दूरदर्शन व व्हिडीओ पाठ

(संदर्भ <https://ycmou.ac.in/pages/index/228>)

संशोधनाची गरज व महत्व:-

गरज

सदर लघुसंशोधनमध्ये संशोधकाला प्रौढ प्रशिक्षणार्थीमध्ये शैक्षणिक तंत्रविज्ञानच्या जाणीवजागृतीची गरज निर्माण झाली.

महत्व

१. दुरस्थ शिक्षणातील शिक्षणशास्त्र अभ्यासक्रमात प्राथमिक तंत्रज्ञान कौशल्य अभ्यासक्रमाचा समावेश असल्याबाबतची माहिती जाणून घेणे.

२. दुरस्थ शिक्षणातील शिक्षणशास्त्र अभ्यासक्रमात प्राथमिक तंत्रज्ञान कौशल्य अभ्यासक्रम अंमलबजावणी संबंधीची सद्यस्थिती जाणून घेणे.

३. दुरस्थ शिक्षणातील शिक्षणशास्त्र अभ्यासक्रमात प्राथमिक तंत्रज्ञान कौशल्य घटक प्रात्यक्षिक कार्ये अंमलबजावणी संबंधित प्रगती जाणून घेणे.

संशोधनाची उद्दिष्टे

१. दुरस्थ शिक्षणातील शिक्षणशास्त्र अभ्यासक्रमातील तंत्रज्ञान कौशल्याच्या विविध घटकांचे विश्लेषण करणे.

२. दुरस्थ शिक्षणातील शिक्षणशास्त्र अभ्यासक्रमातील तंत्रज्ञान कौशल्यावर आधारित विविध प्रात्यक्षिक घटकांचे विश्लेषण करणे.

३. दुरस्थ शिक्षणातील शिक्षणशास्त्र अभ्यासक्रमातील प्रात्यक्षिक कार्ये करताना प्रशिक्षणार्थ्यांना येणाऱ्या अडचणींचा अभ्यास करणे.

४. दुरस्थ शिक्षणातील शिक्षणशास्त्र अभ्यासक्रमातील प्रात्यक्षिकांची पूर्ती करून घेताना मार्गदर्शकांना येणाऱ्या अडचणींचा अभ्यास करणे.

५. दुरस्थ शिक्षणातील प्रौढ वर्गातील शिक्षणशास्त्र अभ्यासक्रमात शैक्षणिक तंत्रविज्ञान कौशल्य आधारित प्रात्यक्षिक अभ्यासक्रम अंमलबजावणी प्रगतीसाठी उपाययोजना सुचवणे.

संशोधनाची व्याप्ती

सदर लघुसंशोधनमध्ये दुरस्थ शिक्षणातील शिक्षणशास्त्र महाविद्यालयातील शिक्षक आणि प्रशिक्षणार्थी चा समावेश केला आहे.

संशोधनाची मर्यादा

१. सदर लघुसंशोधन दुरस्थ शिक्षणातील शिक्षणशास्त्र महाविद्यालयापुरते मर्यादित आहे.

२. सदर लोकसंशोधनात दुरस्थ शिक्षणातील शिक्षणशास्त्र अभ्यासक्रमातील प्राथमिक तंत्रज्ञान कौशल्य या घटकापूर्ते मर्यादित आहे.

संशोधन कार्यपद्धती

संशोधन पद्धती

सदर संशोधनासाठी वर्णनात्मक संशोधन पद्धतीमधील सर्वेक्षण पद्धतीचा वापर करण्यात आला आहे.

न्यायदर्श

सदर संशोधनात असंभाव्यतरे आधारित सहेतुक नमुना निवड पद्धतीच्या आधारे सोलापूर शहरातील यशवंतराव चव्हाण महाराष्ट्र मुक्त विद्यापीठ अंतर्गत दुरस्थ शिक्षणातील शिक्षणशास्त्र विभागातील एका महाविद्यालयाची निवड करण्यात आली आहे. शिक्षणशास्त्र महाविद्यालयातील १० प्रशिक्षणार्थींची आणि २ शैक्षणिक विषयाचे अध्यापन करणारे मार्गदर्शकांची नमुना निवड करण्यात आली आहे.

साधने

१. दुरस्थ शिक्षणातील बी.एड अभ्यासक्रमातील शैक्षणिक तंत्रविज्ञान च्या विषयाचे विश्लेषण करण्यासाठी विश्लेषण तक्ता हे साधन वापरण्यात आले आहे.

२. सदर संशोधनामध्ये माहिती संकलित करण्यासाठी बी.एड प्रशिक्षणार्थी साठी प्रश्नावली आणि शैक्षणिक तंत्रविज्ञान अध्यापन करणारे मार्गदर्शक यांच्यासाठी मुलाखत या साधनाचा वापर केलेला आहे.

निष्कर्ष

२१ व्या शतकातील कौशल्य यांच्या प्रमुख आव्हानांना शैक्षणिक क्षेत्रात भरीव परिणाम देऊन जागतिक डिजिटल संचालन तयार करण्यासाठी आणि अभ्यासक्रमाच्या प्रगतीच्या दृष्टिकोनाने प्रौढ वर्गातील शिक्षणात प्राथमिक तंत्रज्ञान कौशल्य अभ्यासक्रम नेमके

कशाप्रकारे राबवले जाते याचा अभ्यास करण्यासाठी काही बी. एड मार्गदर्शकांची मुलाखत आणि प्रशिक्षणार्थींना दिलेल्या प्रश्नावलीतील माहितीचे विश्लेषण अर्थनियोजन करून निष्कर्ष काढण्यात आले.

१. अभ्यासक्रम विश्लेषण

शैक्षणिक तंत्रविज्ञान च्या विविध घटकांचा समावेश सैद्धांतिक आणि प्रात्यक्षिक कार्यांच्या आधारे केला असून तो प्रशिक्षणार्थींच्या विकासासाठी उपयुक्त व गुणवत्तापूर्ण आहे.

२. बी.एड प्रशिक्षणार्थी प्रश्नावली

१.शैक्षणिक तंत्रविज्ञान कौशल्य आधारित अभ्यासक्रमातील प्रात्यक्षिक कार्य करताना अडचणी येतात असे ६०% प्रशिक्षणार्थींचे मत आहे.

२.४०% प्रशिक्षणार्थी च्या मतानुसार शैक्षणिक तंत्रविज्ञान प्रात्यक्षिक साठी स्वतंत्र सोई सुविधा उपलब्ध आहे.

३.शैक्षणिक तंत्रविज्ञान कौशल्य आधारित अभ्यासक्रमातील प्रात्यक्षिक कार्य राबवले जाते.असे १००% प्रशिक्षणार्थींचे मत आहे. हि बाब चांगली आहे.

४. शैक्षणिक तंत्रविज्ञान कौशल्य आधारित अभ्यासक्रमातील प्रात्यक्षिक कार्य करताना मार्गदर्शक मार्गदर्शन करतात असे ६०% प्रशिक्षणार्थींचे मत आहे.

५.PPT वापर करून सादरीकरण करण्यावर भर दिले जाते. असे १००% प्रशिक्षणार्थी सांगतात. हि बाब चांगली आहे.

६. PPT वापर करून सादरीकरण करताना अडचणी येतात असे ८०% प्रशिक्षणार्थी सांगतात

७. PPT वापर करून सादरीकरण करण्यासाठी नाविन्यपूर्ण स्रोतांचा वापर केला जातो असे ४०% प्रशिक्षणार्थी सांगतात

८.लेखन कौशल्य आणि भाषिक कौशल्य विकसित करताना तंत्रज्ञान कौशल्याचा उपयोग होतो. असे १००% प्रशिक्षणार्थींचे मत आहे.

९.१००% प्रशिक्षणार्थींच्या मतानुसार दुरस्थ शिक्षणात तंत्रज्ञान कौशल्य घटक प्रशिक्षणार्थींच्या कौशल्य विकसनात प्रभावी घटक आहे. हि बाब चांगली आहे.

१०. २० % प्रशिक्षणार्थींच्या मतानुसार मार्गदर्शकांच्या सहयोगातून विशेष दिवसाचे अहवाल,संशोधन लेख ई-प्रकाशनच्या माध्यमातून प्रकाशित करतात.

३. मार्गदर्शक मुलाखत

१.१००% मार्गदर्शकांच्या मतानुसार प्राथमिक तंत्रज्ञान कौशल्य आधारित अभ्यासक्रमातून प्रात्यक्षिक घटकांचे विकसन होते. हि बाब चांगली आहे.

२. ४०% शिक्षक सांगतात की, शैक्षणिक तंत्रविज्ञान प्रात्यक्षिक साठी स्वतंत्र सोई सुविधा उपलब्ध आहे. सोई सुविधा उपलब्ध करून दिल्या पाहिजेत.
३. प्रशिक्षणार्थीच्या लेखन कौशल्य आणि भाषिक कौशल्य विकसित करताना तंत्रज्ञान कौशल्याचा उपयोग होतो. असे १००% मार्गदर्शकांचे मत आहे. हि बाब चांगली आहे.
४. १००% मार्गदर्शकांच्या मतानुसार दुरस्थ शिक्षणात तंत्रज्ञान कौशल्य घटक प्रशिक्षणार्थीच्या कौशल्य विकसनात प्रभावी घटक आहे. हि बाब चांगली आहे.
५. ३० % मार्गदर्शकांच्या मतानुसार प्रशिक्षणार्थीच्या सहयोगातून विशेष दिवसाचे अहवाल, संशोधन लेख ई-प्रकाशनच्या माध्यमातून प्रकाशित करतात.
६. शैक्षणिक तंत्रविज्ञान कौशल्य आधारित अभ्यासक्रमातून विद्यार्थ्यांचा सर्वांगीण विकास प्रभावीपणे होतो. असे १००% मार्गदर्शकांनी सांगितले आहे. हि बाब चांगली आहे.
७. प्रशिक्षणार्थीच्या तंत्रज्ञान कौशल्य साक्षरतासाठी विविध माध्यमातून (उदा. web library, blog) अधिकाधिक स्रोत उपलब्ध केले जातात असे १०% मार्गदर्शकांनी सांगितले. नवनवीन स्रोतांचा संदर्भ घेऊन तंत्रज्ञान कौशल्य साक्षरता विकसित करावे.
८. PPT वापर करून सादरीकरण करण्यावर भर दिले जाते. असे १००% मार्गदर्शक सांगतात. हि बाब चांगली आहे.
९. १००% मार्गदर्शकांच्या मतानुसार प्रशिक्षणार्थींना तंत्रज्ञान कौशल्य साक्षरतासाठी प्रबलन तसेच नवनवीन संधी उपलब्ध करून दिल्या जातात. हि बाब चांगली आहे.
१०. १००% मार्गदर्शकांच्या मतानुसार प्रशिक्षणार्थी तंत्रज्ञानयुक्त पद्धत वापर योग्य पध्दतीने करतात. हि बाब चांगली आहे.
११. शिक्षणशास्त्र अभ्यासक्रमातील सर्व प्रात्यक्षिक घटकांचे अध्यापन आणि मूल्यमापन केले जाते. असे ८०% मार्गदर्शक सांगतात.

उपाययोजना

१. प्राथमिक तंत्रज्ञान कौशल्य विकसित करण्यासाठी शैक्षणिक तंत्रविज्ञान प्रात्यक्षिकासाठी स्वतंत्र कक्ष अत्याधुनिक सोई सुविधा आणि नावीन्यपूर्ण तंत्रज्ञानयुक्त स्रोत उपलब्धता करण्याचा प्रयत्न करावा.
२. अध्यापनात तंत्रज्ञान कौशल्य आधारित माध्यमांचा वापर करावा.
३. प्रशिक्षणार्थींना तंत्रज्ञान कौशल्य साक्षरतासाठी प्रबलन तसेच नवनवीन संधी उपलब्ध करून दिल्या जाव्यात.
४. तंत्रज्ञान कौशल्य साक्षरता प्रमाण उंचावण्यासाठी शिक्षणशास्त्र अभ्यासक्रमातील सर्व प्रात्यक्षिक घटकांचे अध्यापन आणि मूल्यमापन करावे.

५.प्रशिक्षणार्थीना ई-प्रकाशन करण्यासाठी लघुसंशोधन,प्रकल्प, परिसंवाद या सारख्या उपक्रम राबवले तर तंत्रज्ञान साक्षरता विकसित होईल.

संदर्भ सूची

१.भिंताडे वि. रा. (2005) शैक्षणिक संशोधन, पुणे नुतन प्रकाशन

२.मुळे रा. श्. उमाठे वि.तु. (1998) शैक्षणिक संशोधनाची मुलतत्त्वे, नागपूर श्री.विद्या प्रकाशन.

३.हितेश ब्रीजवाशी ,डाॅ. संतोष खैराडे (2020) डिजिटल शिक्षण संसाधने आणि तंत्रे,प्रशांत पब्लिकेशन्स.

४.सोलापूर विद्यापीठ अंतर्गत शिक्षणशास्त्र अभ्यासक्रम (2019)

वेब सूची: -

<https://ridgeviewcharter.org/what-are-21st-century-skills/>

<https://medium.com/literate-schools/redefining-literacy-in-the-21st-century-139894b14fd4>

32. २१ व्या शतकातील जीवन कौशल्ये यशस्वीतेसाठी प्रशिक्षण व त्याचा परिणामकारकतेचा अभ्यास

प्रोफेसर. कविता साळुंके⁴⁵, डॉ ज्योती आर. लष्करी⁴⁶

सारांश

२१ व्या शतकातील कौशल्ये म्हणजे अनेक शिक्षकांनी, शिक्षण संस्थांनी तसेच इतर शिक्षणविषयक तज्ज्ञांनी एकत्र येऊन ठरवलेल्या कौशल्यांची यादी आहे. २१ व्या शतकात घडणाऱ्या आणि होऊ घातलेल्या बदलांना स्वीकारून आयुष्यात यशस्वी होण्यासाठी ही कौशल्ये आत्मसात करून घेणे आवश्यक आहे असे अनेक तज्ज्ञांचे मत आहे. आजची शालेय शिक्षणपद्धत किंवा त्यात अंतर्भूत असलेले विषय कालबाह्य होत आहेत का हा कदाचित वादाचा मुद्दा असेलही पण आजच्या जगात टिकून राहण्यासाठी आणि यशस्वी होण्यासाठी आवश्यक असलेली कौशल्ये शाळेतून शिकवली जातातच असे नाही. अशा कौशल्यांच्या यादीला तज्ज्ञांनी दिलेले नाव म्हणजेच २१ व्या शतकातील कौशल्ये होय.

सदर संशोधन पेपर मध्ये संशोधिकेने WHO ने सांगितलेली दहा जीवन कौशल्ये म्हणजे 1 समस्या निराकरण, स्वजाणीव, निर्णय क्षमता, प्रभावी संप्रेषण, चिकित्सक विचार प्रक्रिया, सर्जनशीलता कौशल्ये, भावनांनाचे समायोजन, ताण-तणावाचे समायोजन व समानुभूती या कौशल्याबद्दल माहिती दिली आहे आणि प्रयोगासाठी (संशोधनासाठी) 21 व्या शतकात या दहा जीवन कौशल्यपैकी आवश्यक असणारी जीवन कौशल्य 1 समस्या निराकरण क्षमता कौशल्य 2 चिकित्सक विचार क्षमता कौशल्य 3 निर्णय क्षमता कौशल्ये 3 ताण – तणावाचे व्यवस्थापन करण्याचे कौशल्ये या फक्त चार जीवन कौशल्यांचा विचार केला आहे.

मुख्य शब्द: जीवन कौशल्ये

२१ व्या शतकातील कौशल्ये म्हणजे अनेक शिक्षकांनी, शिक्षण संस्थांनी तसेच इतर शिक्षणविषयक तज्ज्ञांनी एकत्र येऊन ठरवलेल्या कौशल्यांची यादी आहे. २१ व्या शतकात घडणाऱ्या आणि होऊ घातलेल्या बदलांना स्वीकारून आयुष्यात यशस्वी होण्यासाठी ही कौशल्ये आत्मसात करून घेणे आवश्यक आहे असे अनेक तज्ज्ञांचे मत आहे. आजची शालेय शिक्षणपद्धत किंवा त्यात अंतर्भूत असलेले विषय कालबाह्य होत आहेत का हा कदाचित वादाचा मुद्दा असेलही पण आजच्या जगात टिकून राहण्यासाठी आणि यशस्वी होण्यासाठी आवश्यक असलेली कौशल्ये शाळेतून शिकवली जातातच असे नाही. अशा कौशल्यांच्या यादीला तज्ज्ञांनी दिलेले नाव म्हणजेच २१ व्या शतकातील कौशल्ये होय.

सदर संशोधन पेपर मध्ये संशोधिकेने WHO ने सांगितलेली दहा जीवन कौशल्ये म्हणजे 1 समस्या निराकरण, स्वजाणीव, निर्णय क्षमता, प्रभावी संप्रेषण, चिकित्सक विचार प्रक्रिया, सर्जनशीलता कौशल्ये, भावनांनाचे समायोजन, ताण-तणावाचे समायोजन व समानुभूती या कौशल्याबद्दल माहिती दिली आहे आणि प्रयोगासाठी (संशोधनासाठी) 21 व्या शतकात या दहा

⁴⁵ संचालक, शिक्षणशास्त्र विद्याशाखा, YCMOU, नाशिक

⁴⁶ प्राचार्या, आर.एफ.एन.एस. महिला बी.एड, महाविद्यालय, अक्कलकुवा

Proceeding: National Seminar on Development of 21st-century skills for Atmanirbhar Bharat (Self-reliant India), 23,24 December 2022

जीवन कौशल्यपैकी आवश्यक असणारी जीवन कौशल्य 1 समस्या निराकरण क्षमता कौशल्य 2 चिकित्सक विचार क्षमता कौशल्य 3 निर्णय क्षमता कौशल्ये 3 ताण — तणावाचे व्यवस्थापन करण्याचे कौशल्ये या फक्त चार जीवन कौशल्यांचा विचार केला आहे.

संशोधन शीर्षक:

२१ व्या शतकातील जीवन कौशल्ये यशस्वीतेसाठी उपक्रम व त्याचा परिणामकारकतेचा अभ्यास

संशोधनाची उद्दीष्ट:

- १ शालेय पाठ्य पुस्तकात जीवन कौशल्याचा शोध घेणे.
- २ शिक्षकांना जीवन कौशल्यांचे ज्ञान आहे का याचा शोध घेणे.
- ३ जीवन कौशल्यावर आधारित प्रशिक्षण कार्यक्रम तयार करणे.
- ४ प्रशिक्षण कार्यक्रमाची परिणामकारकता तपासणे.

संशोधन पद्धती:

उद्दीष्ट	संशोधन पद्धती	संशोधन साधन	नमूना निवड	संख्याशास्त्रीय तंत्र
शालेय पाठ्य पुस्तकात जीवन कौशल्याचा शोध	दस्तावेज विश्लेषण पद्धती	आशय विश्लेषण श्रेणी	-----	-----
शिक्षकांना जीवन कौशल्यांचे ज्ञान व अडचणी	सर्वेक्षण पद्धती	प्रश्नावली	उच्च प्राथमिक स्तर मराठी 100 शिक्षक	टक्केवारी
प्रशिक्षण कार्यक्रमाची निर्मिती	-----	अनुभवी तज्ञांचे मार्गदर्शन व मतावली	१५ जीवन कौशल्यावरील तज्ञ	टक्केवारी
प्रशिक्षण कार्यक्रमाची परिणाम	प्रयोगिक पद्धती	पूर्व चाचणी व उत्तर चाचणी वर्गपाठ निरक्षण	40 शिक्षक सहेतुक नमूना निवड पद्धतीने निवड	टी - टेस्ट

21 व्या शतकातील जीवन कौशल्य आणि ती शालेय अभ्यासक्रमात समाविष्ट केली असून सुद्धा ती यशस्वीरीत्या का विद्यार्थ्यां मध्ये रुजवली जात नाही याचा अभ्यास केला आणि त्यावर उपाय म्हणून जीवन कौशल्य रूजवणुकीसाठी एकूण 8 दिवसाचा प्रशिक्षण कार्यक्रम घेण्यात आला.

प्रशिक्षणार्थी उच्च प्राथमिक स्तरावरील ६ वी ते ८ चे मराठी विषयाचे अध्यापन करणारे शिक्षक होते शिक्षकांना प्रशिक्षण दिल्या नंतर शिक्षकांचे वर्ग पाठाचे निरक्षण करण्यात आले निरीक्षण केल्या नंतर आलेले निष्कर्ष खालील प्रमाणे

वरील पद्धतीने कार्यवाही केल्या नंतर आलेले उद्दिष्टा नुसार निष्कर्ष खालील प्रमाणे

उद्दीष्ट क्र १ वरुण आलेले निष्कर्ष

- इयत्ता सहावी आठवीपर्यंत शालेय अभ्यासक्रमात जागतिक आरोग्य संघटनेने सांगितलेले एकूण १० जीवनकौशल्याचा समावेश दिसून येतो.
- समस्या निराकरण, स्व-जाणीव, सर्जनशीलता, निर्णयक्षमता, प्रभावी संप्रेषण, चिकित्सक विचार प्रक्रिया, भावनांचे समायोजन, ताणतणावाचे समायोजन, आंतरव्यक्तिगत संबंध या जीवन कौशल्यांचा समावेश दिसून येतो.
- या १० जीवन कौशल्यांपैकी शालेय विषयात समस्या निराकरण, ताण तणावाचे समायोजन निर्णयक्षमता व चिकित्सक विचार प्रक्रिया या जीवन कौशल्याचे प्रमाण सर्वात जास्त दिसून येते.
- इयत्ता सहावी ते आठवीपर्यंत मराठी विषयातील पाठ व कविता यांची संख्या ६८ असून यात सर्वात अधिक वेळा आलेली जीवनकौशल्ये म्हणजे समस्या निराकरण हे ५२ पाठात (७६.४७), निर्णयक्षमता ५७ पाठात (८३.८२%), चिकित्सक विचार प्रक्रिया ५३ पाठात (७६.९४%) ते ही ताण तणावाचे समायोजन ४३ पाठात (६३.२३%) प्रमाण दिसून येते.

उद्दीष्ट क्र २ वरुण आलेले निष्कर्ष

- प्रश्नावलीतील गट क्र.१ जीवनकौशल्याचे ज्ञानावर विचारलेल्या प्रश्नानुसार ८०% प्रतिसादकांना जीवनकौशल्ये शिक्षणा विषयी सविस्तर माहित नाही.
- प्रश्नावलीच्या गट क्र.२ जीवनकौशल्ये शिक्षणाचे प्रशिक्षणावर विचारलेल्या प्रश्नानुसार ९०% प्रतिसादकांना जीवन कौशल्याचे प्रशिक्षण व मार्गदर्शिका उपलब्ध नाही म्हणून या जीवनकौशल्ये शिक्षणाच्या प्रशिक्षणाविषयी प्रतिसादकांना सविस्तर माहिती नाही.
- प्रश्नावलीच्या गट क्र. ३ समस्या निराकरण या जीवनकौशल्ये शिक्षणाविषयी माहिती विचारली असता ८५% प्रतिसादकांना समस्या निराकरण विषयी सविस्तर माहिती नाही.
- प्रश्नावलीच्या गट क्र. ४ ताण तणावाचे समायोजन या जीवन कौशल्ये शिक्षणा विषयी माहिती विचारली असता ६०% प्रतिसादकांना सर्जनशील विचार विषयी सविस्तर माहिती नाही. ताण तणावाचे समायोजन विषयी ४०% माहिती आहे.
- प्रश्नावलीच्या गट क्र. पाच चिकित्सक विचार प्रक्रियाया जीवन कौशल्ये शिक्षणा विषयी माहिती विचारली असता चिकित्सक विचार प्रक्रिये विषयी ८९% प्रतिसादकांना चिकित्सक विचार प्रक्रिया विषयी सविस्तर माहिती नाही.
- प्रश्नावलीच्या गट क्र. सहावी निर्णयक्षमता जीवनकौशल्ये शिक्षणा विषयी माहिती विचारली असता निर्णयक्षमता विषयी ७०% प्रतिसादकांना निर्णयक्षमता विषयी सविस्तर माहिती नाही.
- प्रश्नावलीच्या गट क्र. ७ जीवन कौशल्ये शिक्षण रुजवणूकीच्या अडचणी विषयी माहिती विचारली असता ९५ % प्रतिसादकांना जीवन कौशल्ये शिक्षण रुजवणूकीच्या अडचणी विषयी सांगता येत नाही कारण त्यानी कधी जीवन कौशल्य रुजवणुक करण्याच्या दृष्टीने अध्यापन केले नाही.
- प्रश्नावलीच्या गट क्र ८ जीवनकौशल्ये शिक्षण रुजवणुकी चे मूल्यमापन करतांना अडचणी विषयी माहिती विचारली असता ९५ % प्रतिसादकांना जीवनकौशल्ये शिक्षण रुजवणुकीचे मूल्यमापन करतांना अडचणी विषयी सांगता येत नाही प्रतिसादकांना जीवन कौशल्यविषयी माहित नसल्याने आणि प्रतिसादक मूल्यमापन त्यादृष्टीने करत नसल्याने सांगता येत नाही.

- प्रश्नावलीच्या गट क्र. ९ शिक्षक मार्गदर्शिकेत शिक्षकांना अपेक्षित घटक कोणते यावर आधारित प्रश्नविचारले असता ९०% प्रतिसादकांनी जीवनकौशल्ये शालेय विषयात कसे शोधायचे, जीवनकौशल्याचे स्वतंत्र पाठटाचण, जीवनकशल्ये रूजवणुकीविषयी मार्गदर्शन, जीवन कौशल्य रूजवणूक केल्यानंतर विद्यार्थ्यांचे मूल्यमापन कसे करावे याची माहिती, अडचणीवरील उपाय व सर्व विषयासाठी पाठटाचणानुसार जीवन कौशल्य मार्गदर्शिका असावी किंवा प्रशिक्षण कार्यक्रमाची सोय असावी असे मत व्यक्त करण्यात आले.

उद्दीष्ट क्र. ४ नुसार आलेले निष्कर्ष

आशय ज्ञान चाचणी

- निष्कर्ष १ चिकित्सक विचार प्रक्रिया जीवनकौशल्ये

स्वाधीनता मात्रा (df) ३९ साठी ०.०५ सार्थकता स्तरावर सारणी 'टी' मूल्य हे २.०२ असून संख्याशास्त्रीय प्राप्त 'टी' मूल्य १२.५९ आहे.

प्राप्त 'टी' मूल्य १२.५९ हे सारणी मूल्य २.०२ पेक्षा जास्त आहे. म्हणजे प्राप्त 'टी' मूल्य हे ०.०५ स्तरावर सार्थ आहे. प्रस्तुत संशोधनात संख्यात्मक विश्लेषणानुसार प्राप्त 'टी' मूल्य हे सारणी मूल्यापेक्षा अधिक असल्याने सार्थ आहे. म्हणून ०.०५ यासार्थकता स्तरावर शून्य परिकल्पनेचा त्याग करावा लागला. उच्च प्राथमिक स्तरावरील मराठी, शिक्षकांच्या चिकित्सक विचारप्रक्रिया या जीवनकौशल्ये रूजवणुकीसाठीच्या आशयज्ञानात चिकित्सक प्रक्रिया प्रशिक्षण कार्यक्रमाच्या अध्ययनामुळे लक्षणीय वाढ होते ही संशोधन परिकल्पना स्वीकारावी लागली.

चिकित्सक विचारप्रक्रिया वरील प्रशिक्षण कार्यक्रम हे उच्च प्राथमिक स्तरावरील मराठी विषय शिक्षकांना चिकित्सक विचारप्रक्रिया हे जीवन कौशल्य रूजवणुकीसाठी उपयुक्त आहेत.

- निष्कर्ष २ समस्या निराकरण जीवनकौशल्ये

स्वाधीनता मात्रा (df) ३९ साठी ०.०५ सार्थकता स्तरावर सारणी 'टी' मूल्य हे २.०२ असून संख्याशास्त्रीय विश्लेषणानुसार प्राप्त 'टी' मूल्य २३.४२ आहे.

प्राप्त 'टी' मूल्य २३.४२ हे सारणी मूल्य २.०२ पेक्षा जास्त आहे. म्हणजे प्राप्त 'टी' मूल्य हे ०.०५ स्तरावर सार्थ आहे. प्रस्तुत संशोधनात संख्यात्मक विश्लेषणानुसार प्राप्त 'टी' मूल्य हे सारणी मूल्यापेक्षा अधिक असल्याने सार्थ आहे. म्हणून ०.०५ या सार्थकता स्तरावर शून्य परिकल्पनेचा त्याग करावा लागला. उच्च प्राथमिक स्तरावरील मराठी शिक्षकांच्या समस्या निराकरण या जीवनकौशल्ये रूजवणुकीसाठीच्या आशयज्ञानात समस्या निराकरण या प्रशिक्षण कार्यक्रमाच्या अध्ययनामुळे लक्षणीय वाढ होते. ही संशोधन परिकल्पना स्वीकारावी लागली.

समस्या निराकरण वरील प्रशिक्षण कार्यक्रम हे उच्च प्राथमिक स्तरावरील मराठी, विषय शिक्षकांना समस्या निराकरण हे जीवनकौशल्ये रूजवणुकीसाठी उपयुक्त आहेत.

- निष्कर्ष ३ निर्णयक्षमता जीवनकौशल्ये

स्वाधीनता मात्रा (df) ३९ साठी ०.०५ सार्थकता स्तरावर सारणी 'टी' मूल्य हे २.०२ असून संख्याशास्त्रीय विश्लेषणानुसार प्राप्त 'टी' मूल्य १६.३६ आहे. प्राप्त 'टी' मूल्य १६.३६ हे सारणी मूल्य २.०२ पेक्षा जास्त आहे. म्हणजे प्राप्त 'टी' मूल्य हे ०.०५ स्तरावर सार्थ आहे. प्रस्तुत संशोधनात संख्यात्मक विश्लेषणानुसार प्राप्त 'टी' मूल्य हे सारणी मूल्यापेक्षा अधिक असल्याने सार्थ आहे. म्हणून ०.०५ या सार्थकता स्तरावर शून्य परिकल्पनेचा त्याग करावा लागला. उच्च प्राथमिक स्तरावरील मराठी, शिक्षकांच्या निर्णयक्षमता या जीवनकौशल्ये रूजवणुकीसाठीच्या आशयज्ञानात निर्णयक्षमता या वरील प्रशिक्षण कार्यक्रमा मुळे लक्षणीय वाढ होते ही संशोधन परिकल्पना स्वीकारावी लागली.

निर्णयक्षमता वरील प्रशिक्षण कार्यक्रम हे उच्च प्राथमिक स्तरावरील मराठी, विषय शिक्षकांना निर्णयक्षमता हे जीवनकौशल्ये रूजवणुकीसाठी उपयुक्त आहेत.

- निष्कर्ष ४ ताण तणावाचे समायोजन जीवनकौशल्ये

स्वाधीनता मात्रा (df) ३९ साठी ०.०५ सार्थकता स्तरावर सारणी 'टी' मूल्य हे २.०२ असून संख्याशास्त्रीय विश्लेषणानुसार प्राप्त 'टी' मूल्य १२.७१ आहे.

प्राप्त 'टी' मूल्य १२.७१ हे सारणी मूल्य २.०२ पेक्षा जास्त आहे. म्हणजे प्राप्त 'टी' मूल्य हे ०.०५ स्तरावर सार्थ आहे. प्रस्तुत संशोधनात संख्यात्मक विश्लेषणानुसार प्राप्त 'टी' मूल्य हे सारणी मूल्यापेक्षा अधिक असल्याने सार्थ आहे. म्हणून ०.०५ यासार्थकता स्तरावर शून्य परिकल्पनेचा त्याग करावा लागला. उच्च प्राथमिक स्तरावरील मराठी शिक्षकांच्या ताण तणाव समायोजन या जीवनकौशल्ये रूजवणुकीसाठीच्या आशयज्ञानात ताण तणाव वरील प्रशिक्षण कार्यक्रमा मुळे लक्षणीय वाढ होते ही संशोधन परिकल्पना स्वीकारावी लागली.

वरील प्रशिक्षण कार्यक्रम हे उच्च प्राथमिक स्तरावरील मराठी विषय शिक्षकांना हे ताण तणावाचे समायोजन जीवनकौशल्ये रूजवणुकीसाठी उपयुक्त आहेत.

पाठाचे निरीक्षण केल्या नंतर आलेले निष्कर्ष

- निष्कर्ष १ चिकित्सक विचार प्रक्रिया जीवनकौशल्ये

कोष्टक क्र. (४.३४) स्वाधीनता मात्रा (df) ३९ साठी ०.०५ सार्थकता स्तरावर सारणी 'टी' मूल्य हे २.०२ असून संख्याशास्त्रीय विश्लेषणानुसार प्राप्त 'टी' मूल्य २०.२९ आहे.

प्राप्त 'टी' मूल्य २०.२९ हे सारणी मूल्य २.०२ पेक्षा जास्त आहे. म्हणजे प्राप्त 'टी' मूल्य हे ०.०५ स्तरावर सार्थ आहे प्रस्तुत संशोधनात संख्यात्मक विश्लेषणानुसार प्राप्त 'टी' मूल्य हे सारणी मूल्यापेक्षा अधिक असल्याने सार्थ आहे. म्हणून ०.०५ यासार्थकता स्तरावर शून्य परिकल्पनेचा त्याग करावा लागला. चिकित्सक विचारप्रक्रिया जीवनकौशल्ये प्रशिक्षण कार्यक्रमा मुळे मराठी विषय

शिक्षकांच्या अध्यापनातून चिकित्सक विचारप्रक्रिया कौशल्य रुजवणुकी त लक्षणीय वाढ होते ही संशोधन परिकल्पना स्वीकारावी लागली.

चिकित्सक विचारप्रक्रिया जीवनकौशल्ये वरील प्रशिक्षण कार्यक्रम हे उच्च प्राथमिक स्तरावरील मराठी, शिक्षकांना अध्यापनातून चिकित्सक विचारप्रक्रिया जीवनकौशल्याची रुजवणुक करण्यासाठी उपयुक्त आहेत.

निष्कर्ष २ समस्या निराकरण जीवनकौशल्ये

कोष्टक क्र. (४.३९) स्वाधीनता मात्रा (df) ३९ साठी ०.०५ सार्थकता स्तरावर सारणी 'टी' मूल्य हे २.०२ असून संख्याशास्त्रीय विश्लेषणानुसार प्राप्त 'टी' मूल्य २०.८१ आहे.

प्राप्त 'टी'मूल्य २०.८१ हे सारणी मूल्य २.०२ पेक्षा जास्त आहे. म्हणजे प्राप्त 'टी' मूल्य हे ०.०५ स्तरावर सार्थ आहे. प्रस्तुत संशोधनात संख्यात्मक विश्लेषणानुसार प्राप्त 'टी' मूल्य हे सारणी मूल्यापेक्षा अधिक असल्याने सार्थ आहे. म्हणून ०.०५ या सार्थकता स्तरावर शून्य परिकल्पनेचा त्याग करावा लागला. समस्या निराकरण जीवन कौशल्य प्रशिक्षण कार्यक्रमांमुळे मराठी विषय शिक्षकांच्या अध्यापनातून समस्या निराकरण कौशल्य रुजवणुकीत लक्षणीय वाढ होते ही संशोधन परिकल्पना स्वीकारावी लागली.

समस्या निराकरण वरील प्रशिक्षण कार्यक्रम हे उच्च प्राथमिक स्तरावरील मराठी शिक्षकांना अध्यापनातून समस्या निराकरण जीवनकौशल्याची रुजवणुक करण्यासाठी उपयुक्त आहेत

निष्कर्ष ३ निर्णयक्षमता जीवनकौशल्ये

कोष्टक क्र. (४.४४) स्वाधीनता मात्रा (df) ३९ साठी ०.०५ सार्थकता स्तरावर सारणी 'टी' मूल्य हे २.०२ असून संख्याशास्त्रीय विश्लेषणानुसार प्राप्त 'टी'मूल्य १७.६३ आहे.

प्राप्त 'टी'मूल्य १७.६३ हे सारणी मूल्य २.०२ पेक्षा जास्त आहे. म्हणजे प्राप्त 'टी' मूल्य हे ०.०५ स्तरावर सार्थ आहे. प्रस्तुत संशोधनात संख्यात्मक विश्लेषणानुसार प्राप्त 'टी' मूल्य हे सारणी मूल्यापेक्षा अधिक असल्याने सार्थ आहे. म्हणून ०.०५ या सार्थकता स्तरावर शून्य परिकल्पनेचा त्याग करावा लागला. निर्णयक्षमता जीवनकौशल्ये प्रशिक्षण कार्यक्रमांमुळे मराठी विषय शिक्षकांच्या अध्यापनातून निर्णयक्षमता कौशल्य रुजवणुकी त लक्षणीय वाढ होते ही संशोधन परिकल्पना स्वीकारावी लागली.

निर्णयक्षमता वरील प्रशिक्षण कार्यक्रम हे उच्च प्राथमिक स्तरावरील मराठी विषय शिक्षकांना अध्यापनातून निर्णयक्षमता जीवनकौशल्याची रुजवणुक करण्यासाठी उपयुक्त आहेत.

निष्कर्ष ४ ताण तणावाचे जीवनकौशल्ये

कोष्टक क्र. (४.४९) स्वाधीनता मात्रा (df) ३९ साठी ०.०५ सार्थकता स्तरावर सारणी 'टी' मूल्य हे २.०२ असून संख्याशास्त्रीय विश्लेषणानुसार प्राप्त 'टी'मूल्य १८.९७ आहे.

प्राप्त 'टी'मूल्य १८.९७ हे सारणी मूल्य २.०२ पेक्षा जास्त आहे. म्हणजे प्राप्त 'टी'मूल्य हे ०.०५ स्तरावर सार्थ आहे. प्रस्तुत संशोधनात संख्यात्मक विश्लेषणानुसार प्राप्त 'टी' मूल्य हे सारणी मूल्यापेक्षा अधिक असल्याने सार्थ आहे. म्हणून ०.०५ यासार्थकता

स्तरावर शून्य परिकल्पनेचा त्याग करावा लागला. ताण तणावाचे समायोजन जीवनकौशल्ये प्रशिक्षण कार्यक्रमांमुळे मराठी विषय शिक्षकांच्या अध्यापनातून सर्जनशीलता विचार कौशल्य रुजवणुकीत लक्षणीय वाढ होते ही संशोधन परिकल्पना स्वीकारावी लागली ताण तणावाचे समायोजना वरील प्रशिक्षण कार्यक्रम हे उच्च प्राथमिक स्तरावरील मराठी विषय शिक्षकांना अध्यापनातून जीवनकौशल्याची रुजवणुक करण्यासाठी उपयुक्त आहेत.

सारांश

सध्याच्या भारतीय शिक्षण पद्धतीने विद्यार्थ्यांना हि कौशल्ये आत्मसात करता येतातच असे नाही त्यामुळे इतर ठिकाणहून हि कौशल्ये आत्मसात करून स्वतःचा विकास करणे क्रमप्राप्त ठरते. जीवनात यशस्वी होण्यासाठी तुमच्याकडे हि कौशल्ये जर असतील तर एकविसाव्या शतकात यशस्वी होण्यापासून तुम्हाला कोणी थांबू शकणार नाही.

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33. एकविसाव्या शतकातील कौशल्य आणि समाजशास्त्र शिक्षण

सौ. योगिता मिलिंद जोशी⁴⁷

सारांश

इयत्ता सातवीच्या समाजशास्त्र विषयाच्या पाठ्यक्रमात अंतर्भूत एकविसाव्या शतकातील कौशल्यांच्या संदर्भात शिक्षकांच्या दृष्टिकोनाचा अभ्यास केला आहे. आर्थिक सहकार्य व विकास संघटना (OECD) संघटनेने पुरस्कृत केलेले बारा एकविसाव्या शतकातील कौशल्यांना अनुलक्षण संशोधन केले आहे. इयत्ता सातवीच्या इतिहास, नागरिक शास्त्र व भूगोल पाठ्यक्रमाच्या आशयाच्या संदर्भात आहे. इयत्ता सातवीच्या समाजशास्त्र विषयाच्या पाठ्यक्रमात अंतर्भूत आशय व उद्दिष्टे महाराष्ट्र राज्य पाठ्यपुस्तक निर्मिती व अभ्यासक्रम संशोधन मंडळ पुणे यांनी निर्मिलेला आहे. इयत्ता सातवीला समाजशास्त्र विषय शिकवणाऱ्या मराठी माध्यमाच्या दहा शिक्षकांची मुलाखत घेऊन व पाच शिक्षकांच्या वर्ग अध्यापनाच्या पाठांच्या व्हिडीओचे निरीक्षण करून निष्कर्ष काढण्यात आलेले आहेत. शिक्षकांना एकविसाव्या शतकातील कौशल्यांविषयी सखोल माहिती नाही, परंतु विद्यार्थ्यांमध्ये काही कौशल्ये विकसित करण्याचा शिक्षक 100% प्रयत्न करित आहेत. शिक्षक विद्यार्थ्यांच्या व्यक्तिमत्व विकासासाठी सतत जागरूक असून त्यांच्यात सकारात्मक दृष्टिकोनच दिसून येत आहे. सहशालेय उपक्रमांच्या माध्यमातून कौशल्ये विकासाच्या अधिक संधी दिल्या जात आहे. परंतु वर्ग अध्यापन करताना कश्या पद्धतीने अध्ययन अनुभव दिल्यास विद्यार्थ्यांमध्ये या कौशल्यांचा परिपोष होऊ शकतो याबाबत 30% शिक्षक अनभिज्ञ आहेत. विद्यार्थ्यांमध्ये विकसित झालेल्या कौशल्यांचे मूल्यांकन करण्यासाठी प्रामुख्याने निरीक्षण पद्धतीचा वापर केला जात आहे. परंतु इतर मूल्यमापन साधने व तंत्रांचा वापर कशा पद्धतीने करता येऊ शकतो ही माहिती पुरविणे आवश्यक आहे. जीवन कौशल्यां संदर्भात 70% शिक्षकांचे प्रशिक्षण शासनामार्फत झालेले आहे. परंतु पुन्हा प्रशिक्षण घेऊन अध्यापनात त्याचा वापर कसा करावा याबाबत मार्गदर्शन होणे आवश्यक आहे. शिक्षणाचा हेतू भावी पिढी घडविणे. देशाला भविष्यात सुनागरिक प्राप्त होणे हा आहे. यासाठी अभ्यासक्रमात नागरिकशास्त्र विषय अधिक गुणांसाठी करणे आवश्यक आहे. आत्मनिर्भर भारत बनवायचा असेल तर सक्षम नागरिक घडविण्यासाठी शिक्षक ही तितकाच सक्षम असणे आवश्यक आहे. भविष्यामध्ये शिक्षक प्रशिक्षणात अभ्यासक्रमात आमूलाग्र बदल घडून आणणे आवश्यक आहे.

मुख्य शब्द: एकविसाव्या शतकातील कौशल्य, समाजशास्त्र शिक्षण

प्रस्तावना

शिक्षण म्हणजे फक्त वही पेन नव्हे तर बुद्धीला सत्याकडे., भावनेला माणुसकीकडे आणि शरीराला श्रमाकडे नेण्याचा मार्ग होय. शिक्षण म्हणजे वर्तन बदल अशी व्याख्या शिक्षण तज्ज्ञांनी केलेली आहे. माध्यमिक शिक्षणात भाषा गणित हे विषय बोधात्मक

⁴⁷ पीएचडी विद्यार्थी, एस एन डी टी महिला विद्यापीठ मुंबई

विकासासाठी तर समाजशास्त्र, विज्ञान या विषयांचा अंतर्भाव भावात्मक व क्रियात्मक विकासासाठी केलेला आहे. इतिहासातून फक्त भूतकाळातील घटनांचे, महान व्यक्तींचे चरित्र शिकणे एवढाच उद्देश नसून भूतकाळात घडून गेलेल्या घटनांचा वर्तमान काळातील घटनांशी संबंध जोडून भविष्य अधिक उज्ज्वल बनविणे हा आहे. नागरिक शास्त्र म्हणजे नागरिकत्वाचा अभ्यास करणारे शास्त्र होय. नागरिकशास्त्राच्या पाठ्यक्रमातून आदर्श नागरिकत्वा विषयी विद्यार्थ्यांना सजग करणे अभिप्रेत आहे. भूगोलाच्या पाठ्यक्रमातून पृथ्वी हे मानवाचे वस्तीस्थान आहे. या पृथ्वीच्या पृष्ठभागावर व सभोवताली नैसर्गिक व भौतिक घडामोडी होत असतात. या घडणाऱ्या घडामोडींचा मानवाच्या संदर्भात सर्वंकष विचार करणे व सर्व सजीवांचे जीवन सुखकर करणे हा हेतू आहे. शिक्षणातून मानव हा पृथ्वीचा विश्वस्त आहे. ना की मालक आणि म्हणूनच भावी पिढीसाठी पृथ्वीवरील समस्त सजीवांचे जीवन समस्यारहित व आनंददायी राखणे यासाठी एकविसाव्या शतकातील कौशल्य विद्यार्थ्यांमध्ये विकसित करणे ही काळाची गरज आहे.

एकविसावे शतक हे तंत्रज्ञानाचे युग म्हणून ओळखल जाते. या युगाला सामोरे जाण्यासाठी व्यक्तीमध्ये काही क्षमता आणि कौशल्य विकसित करणे अपेक्षित आहे. म्हणूनच इसवी सन 1997 साली जागतिक आरोग्य संघटनेने दहा जीवन कौशल्य पुरस्कृत केली आहेत. जास्तीत जास्त कार्यक्षमतेने व यशस्वीपणे जीवन जगता यावे यासाठी विद्यार्थ्यांची अंगभूत कौशल्ये विकसित करण्याचा सातत्यपूर्ण प्रयत्न म्हणजेच जीवन कौशल्य शिक्षण होय. स्व:जागृती , समानुभूती , समस्या निराकरण, निर्णय घेणे , प्रभावी संप्रेषण, चिकित्सक विचार प्रक्रिया ,सर्जनशील विचार प्रक्रिया, आंतर व्यक्ति संबंध, भावनांचे समायोजन, ताणतणावांचे समायोजन ही दहा जीवन कौशल्ये पुरस्कृत केली. त्यानुसार 2005 मध्ये अभ्यासक्रमाची पुनर्रचना करण्यात आली, त्यानुसार 2009 पासून जीवन कौशल्यांवर आधारित राष्ट्रीय अभ्यासक्रम राबविण्यात आला. इसवी सन १९६१ मध्ये स्थापन केलेली आर्थिक सहकार्य व विकास संघटना (OECD) ही आंतरराष्ट्रीय संघटना चांगल्या जीवनासाठी धोरणे तयार करते, आंतरराष्ट्रीय मानके प्रस्थापित करणे आणि सामाजिक आर्थिक आणि पर्यावरणीय समस्यांवर उपाय शोधण्याचे कार्य करते.आर्थिक कामगिरीत सुधारणा व रोजगार निर्मिती करण्यापर्यंत सशक्त शिक्षणाला चालना देते. त्यांनी एकविसाव्या शतकातील बारा कौशल्ये पुरस्कृत केली. त्यांचा राष्ट्रीय शैक्षणिक धोरण २०२० याच्या प्रास्ताविकात आढावा घेण्यात आला आहे. त्यानुसार आजचा विद्यार्थी जो देशाचा भावी नागरिक आहे तो नीतिवान, तर्कशुद्ध, सहानुभूतीशील, सहृदय, आर्थिक दृष्ट्या सक्षम व समाधानी होण्यासाठी या कौशल्यांचा परिपोष करणे ही काळाची गरज आहे. विद्यार्थ्यांच्या सर्वांगीण विकासासाठी पाठांतरावर भर न देता ,कसे समजून घेतो येईल यावर भर दिला जाईल. आवश्यक तेवढीच माहिती पुरवून चिकित्सक विचार, संवाद, कल्पनाशक्ती, सर्जनशीलता, ज्ञानाचे समस्या सोडवण्यासाठी उपयोजन करण्यावर अधिक भर दिला जाईल. वर्ग अध्यापनासाठी विषय समन्वय, सहकार्यात्मक , शोधन, कृतीयुक्त शिक्षण , अनुभवातून शिक्षण या अध्यापन पध्दती उपयुक्त ठरतील असे नमुद केले आहे.

बीज संकल्पना -

२१व्या शतकातील कौशल्ये

एकविसाव्या शतकामध्ये व्यक्तीला यशस्वी जीवन जगण्यासाठी दैनंदिन जीवनातील समस्या व आव्हानांना प्रभावीपणे सामोरे जाण्यासाठी बदलत्या काळानुरूप व्यक्तीने स्वतःच्या वर्तनात घडवून आणलेले सकारात्मक बदल आणि विकसित केलेल्या क्षमता व कौशल्यांचा संच म्हणजे एकविसाव्या शतकातील कौशल्ये होय.

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शिकण्याची कौशल्ये	साक्षरता	जीवन कौशल्ये
चिकित्सक विचार	माहिती	लवचिकता
सहयोग	माध्यम	नेतृत्व
संप्रेषण	तंत्रज्ञान	पुढाकार
सर्जनशीलता		उत्पादकता
		सामाजिक कौशल्ये

शिक्षकांचा दृष्टिकोन: - शिक्षकांचा समाजशास्त्र विषयाकडे एकविसाव्या शतकातील कौशल्यांच्या अनुषंगाने पाहण्याचा किंवा विचार करण्याचा रोख म्हणजे शिक्षकांचा दृष्टिकोन होय.

समाजशास्त्र :- इतिहास ,नागरिक शास्त्र भूगोल या विषयांच्या समुच्चयास समाजशास्त्र असे म्हणतात.

संशोधन शीर्षक :-

इयत्ता सातवीच्या समाजशास्त्र विषयाच्या पाठ्यक्रमात अंतर्भूत एकविसाव्या शतकातील कौशलयांच्या संदर्भात शिक्षकांच्या दृष्टिकोनाचा अभ्यास

संशोधन उद्दिष्टे :-

१. इयत्ता सातवीच्या समाजशास्त्र विषयाच्या पाठ्यक्रमात अंतर्भूत एकविसाव्या शतकातील जीवन कौशल्यांचा शोध घेणे.
२. इयत्ता सातवीच्या समाजशास्त्र विषयाच्या पाठ्यक्रमात अंतर्भूत एकविसाव्या शतकातील जीवन कौशल्यांबाबत समाजशास्त्र विषय शिकवणाऱ्या शिक्षकांचा दृष्टिकोन जाणून घेणे.

परिकल्पना :-

१. इयत्ता सातवीच्या इतिहास ,नागरिक शास्त्र भूगोल पाठ्यक्रमातील आशय विद्यार्थ्यांच्या एकविसाव्या शतकातील जीवन कौशल्ये शिक्षण विकासास पोषक आहे.
२. इयत्ता सातवीला इतिहास, नागरिक शास्त्र भूगोल विषय शिकवणाऱ्या शिक्षकांचा एकविसाव्या शतकातील जीवन कौशल्ये शिकविण्याचा सकारात्मक दृष्टिकोन आहे.

संशोधनाची व्याप्ती आणि मर्यादा

व्याप्ती –

१. महाराष्ट्र राज्य पाठ्यपुस्तक निर्मिती व अभ्यासक्रम संशोधन मंडळ पुणे यांनी इयत्ता सातवीला इतिहास, नागरिक शास्त्र भूगोल विषयात नेमून दिलेल्या पाठ्यक्रमासाठी आहे.
२. आर्थिक सहकार्य व विकास संघटना (OECD) संघटनेने पुरस्कृत केलेले बारा जीवन कौशल्यां संदर्भात आहे.

मर्यादा-

१. आर्थिक सहकार्य व विकास संघटना (OECD) संघटनेने पुरस्कृत केलेले बारा एकविसाव्या शतकातील कौशल्यां पुरते मर्यादित आहे.
२. इयत्ता सातवीच्या इतिहास ,नागरिक शास्त्र भूगोल पाठ्यक्रमाच्या आशया पुरते मर्यादित आहे .
३. इयत्ता सातवीला समाजशास्त्र विषय शिकवणाऱ्या मराठी माध्यमाच्या शिक्षकां पुरते मर्यादित आहे.
४. उद्दिष्टे व पाठ्यक्रम महाराष्ट्र राज्य पाठ्यपुस्तक निर्मिती व अभ्यासक्रम संशोधन मंडळ पुणे यांनी निर्मिलेला आहे त्या पुरतेच मर्यादित आहे.

संशोधन पध्दती :-

सदर संशोधनासाठी इयत्ता सातवीच्या समाजशास्त्र विषयाच्या शालेय पाठ्यपुस्तकातील एकविसाव्या शतकातील कौशल्ये विश्लेषण पद्धतीने शोधली .इयत्ता सातवीला समाजशास्त्र हा विषय शिकवणाऱ्या दहा शिक्षकांचे मुलाखतीद्वारे सर्वेक्षण केले. पाच शिक्षकांच्या वर्ग अध्यापनाच्या पाठांच्या व्हिडीओचे निरीक्षण केले. संशोधन लेखनासाठी गुणात्मक संशोधन पद्धतीचा उपयोग केला. एकविसाव्या शतकाला सामोरे जाण्यासाठी विद्यार्थ्यांमध्ये जीवन कौशल्य विकसित करण्यास समाजशास्त्र विषयाचा पाठ्यक्रम उपयुक्त आहे का? यासाठी जीवन कौशल्यांना अनुलक्षून आशयाचे विश्लेषण केले गेले. इयत्ता सातवीला समाजशास्त्र हा विषय शिकवणाऱ्या दहा शिक्षकांची मुलाखत घेऊन त्यांचा एकविसाव्या शतकातील कौशल्यां संदर्भातला दृष्टिकोन जाणून घेतला. पाच शिक्षकांच्या वर्ग अध्यापनाच्या पाठांच्या व्हिडीओचे निरीक्षण केले गेले. त्यानंतर पुढील निष्कर्ष आढळले.

उद्दिष्ट :-

१. इयत्ता सातवीच्या समाजशास्त्र विषयाच्या पाठ्यक्रमात अंतर्भूत एकविसाव्या शतकातील जीवन कौशल्यांचा शोध घेणे.
- इयत्ता सातवीला इतिहास या विषयात मध्ययुगीन भारताचा इतिहास अंतर्भूत केलेला आहे. मध्ययुगीन भारताच्या जडणघडणीत महाराष्ट्राचे स्थान व भूमिका केंद्रस्थानी ठेवून पाठ्यपुस्तकाची मांडणी करण्यात आलेली आहे. प्रामुख्याने छत्रपती शिवाजी महाराजांच्या कालखंडातील प्रमुख घटना नमूद केलेल्या आहेत. आशयानुसार प्रत्येक पाठातून विकसित होणाऱ्या एकविसाव्या शतकातील कौशल्यांचे वर्गीकरण खालील तक्त्यात दिलेले आहे.

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क्र.	पाठाचे नाव	कौशल्य
१	इतिहासाची साधने	चिकित्सक विचार, साक्षरता, जबाबदारीची जाणीव
२	शिवपूर्वकालीन भारत	चिकित्सक विचार, नेतृत्व, पुढाकार, जबाबदारीची जाणीव
३	धार्मिक समन्वय	चिकित्सक विचार, सर्जनशीलता, नेतृत्व, जबाबदारीची जाणीव
४	शिवपूर्वकालीन महाराष्ट्र	चिकित्सक विचार, सर्जनशीलता, नेतृत्व
५	स्वराज्य स्थापना	चिकित्सक विचार, नेतृत्व, सहकार्य, जबाबदारीची जाणीव, विश्वासार्हता , सचोटी
६	मुघलांशी संघर्ष	नेतृत्व, सहकार्य, जबाबदारीची जाणीव, विश्वासार्हता, सचोटी
७	स्वराज्याचा कारभार	चिकित्सक विचार, नेतृत्व, सहकार्य, जबाबदारीची जाणीव, विश्वासार्हता , सचोटी
८	आदर्श राज्यकर्ता	नेतृत्व, पुढाकार, चिकित्सक विचार, सर्जनशीलता, जबाबदारीची जाणीव, विश्वासार्हता, सचोटी

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९	मराठ्यांचा स्वातंत्र्य संग्राम	नेतृत्व, पुढाकार, जबाबदारीची जाणीव
१०	मराठ्यांच्या सत्तेचा विस्तार	नेतृत्व, पुढाकार, जबाबदारीची जाणीव
११	राष्ट्ररक्षक मराठे	नेतृत्व, पुढाकार, जबाबदारीची जाणीव
१२	साम्राज्याची वाटचाल	नेतृत्व, पुढाकार, जबाबदारीची जाणीव
१३	महाराष्ट्रातील समाज जीवन	सहकार्य, नेतृत्व, पुढाकार, सर्जनशीलता, कार्यकारण, विश्वासार्हता, सचोटी
	नागरिकशास्त्र	
१	आपल्या संविधानाची ओळख	चिकित्सक विचार, नेतृत्व, पुढाकार, सर्जनशीलता, विश्वासार्हता
२	संविधानाची उद्देशिका	कार्यकारण, चिकित्सक विचार,
३	संविधानाची वैशिष्ट्ये	साक्षरता, चिकित्सक विचार, सर्जनशीलता

४	मूलभूत हक्क भाग १,२	चिकित्सक विचार, साक्षरता, संप्रेषण, कार्यकारण, साक्षरता, जबाबदारीची जाणीव
५	मार्गदर्शक तत्वे आणि मूलभूत कर्तव्ये	चिकित्सक विचार, साक्षरता, संप्रेषण, साक्षरता, जबाबदारीची जाणीव, विश्वासार्हता, सचोटी

इयत्ता सातवीच्या भूगोलाच्या पाठ्यपुस्तकात प्राकृतिक भूगोल प्रादेशिक भूगोल प्रात्यक्षिक भूगोल खगोलीय भूगोल व मानवी भूगोल या घटकांचा समावेश करण्यात आलेला आहे. आपल्या पृथ्वीची माहिती या पाठ्यपुस्तकात देण्यात आलेली आहे. खालील तक्त्यात एकविसाव्या शतकातील कौशल्यांना अनुलक्षण वर्गीकरण केलेले आहे.

क्र.	पाठाचे नाव	कौशल्य
१	ऋतू निर्मिती भाग एक व दोन	तार्किक विचार, कार्यकारण
२	सूर्य चंद्र आणि पृथ्वी	तार्किक विचार, साक्षरता, कार्यकारण
३	भरती ओहटी	तार्किक विचार, कार्यकारण
४	हवेचा दाब	तार्किक विचार, कार्यकारण
५	वारे	तार्किक विचार, कार्यकारण
६	नैसर्गिक प्रदेश	तार्किक विचार, सर्जनशीलता, समस्या समाधान, जबाबदारीची जाणीव, कार्यकारण, सहयोग, नेतृत्व, पुढाकार
७	मृदा	तार्किक विचार, सर्जनशीलता, समस्या

Proceeding: National Seminar on Development of 21st-century skills for Atmanirbhar Bharat (Self-reliant India), 23,24 December 2022

		समाधान, जबाबदारीची जाणीव, कार्यकारण, सहयोग नेतृत्व पुढाकार, उत्पादकता
८	कृषी	तार्किक विचार, सर्जनशीलता, समस्या समाधान, सहयोग , नेतृत्व , पुढाकार, जबाबदारीची जाणीव, कार्यकारण, सहयोग , नेतृत्व , पुढाकार, उत्पादकता
९	मानवी वस्ती	तार्किक विचार, साक्षरता, सर्जनशीलता, समस्या समाधान, जबाबदारीची जाणीव, कार्यकारण सहयोग नेतृत्व पुढाकार
१०	समोच्च रेषा नकाशा आणि भूरूपे	तार्किक विचार, सर्जनशीलता, कार्यकारण

वरील आशय विश्लेषणावरून असे दिसून येते की महाराष्ट्र राज्य पाठ्यपुस्तक निर्मिती व अभ्यासक्रम संशोधन मंडळ पुणे, यांनी इतिहास, नागरीकशास्त्र व भूगोल विषयाचा पाठ्यक्रम तयार करताना एकविसाव्या शतकातील कौशल्यांचा जाणीव पूर्वक समावेश पाठ्यपुस्तकात केलेला आहे. शिक्षकांनी विषयाचे अध्यापन करताना या एकविसाव्या शतकातील कौशल्यांचा विकास करण्यासाठी विशिष्ट अध्ययन अनुभवांची रचना करणे व अध्यापन पद्धती वापरणे आवश्यक आहे. ज्ञानरचनावाद ,कृतियुक्तअध्यापन , आशययुक्तअध्यापन, चर्चा , परिसंवाद , नाट्यीकरण,कथन, गोष्ट पद्धती, भूमिकाअभिनय, आधार पद्धती, प्रवास वर्णन, क्षेत्रभेट, प्रकल्प, सहल, लोक पद्धती, पदार्थ पद्धती, शोधन व मिश्र पद्धती, बुद्धीमंथन, चर्चा, वाद-विवाद, मिश्रित दृष्टिकोन, एकात्मिक शिक्षण , सहसंबंधात्मक शिक्षण, या पद्धतींचा वापर केल्यास वरील कौशल्यांच्या विकासासाठी अधिक पोषक वातावरण वर्ग अध्यापनात निर्माण करता येऊ शकते. म्हणून शिक्षकांनी समाजशास्त्र विषयाचे अध्यापन नाविन्यपूर्ण पद्धतींचा वापर करून करणे

आवश्यक आहे.अध्ययन अनुभव प्रत्यक्ष, प्रतिकृतीद्वारे , कृतीतून, नकाशे , पृथ्वीगोल, क्षेत्रभेट इत्यादीद्वारे विद्यार्थ्यांना द्यावे ज्यायोगे एकविसाव्या शतकातील कौशल्य विकसित होण्यासाठी विविध संधी उपलब्ध होऊ शकतील.

इतिहासाच्या पाठ्यपुस्तकातील साम्राज्याची वाटचाल या पाठात मल्हाराव होळकर, पुण्यश्लोक अहिल्याबाई होळकर, रघुजी भोसले, राणोजी शिंदे, नाना फडणवीस इत्यादींनी छत्रपती शिवाजी महाराजांनी स्थापन केलेल्या साम्राज्याचे अखेरपर्यंत संरक्षण करण्याचे आटोकाट प्रयत्न केले, या पाठात पुढाकार ,नेतृत्व, जबाबदारीची जाणीव , इत्यादी बाबी ठळक पणाने रुजविता येतील. सद्यस्थितीतही जेव्हा समाजाला नेतृत्वाची गरज असेल तेव्हा आपल्या परीने ते देण्याचा प्रयत्न प्रत्येकाने करणे गरजेचे आहे. जर नेतृत्व करू शकत नसेल तर निदान चांगल्या कृतीसाठी सहकार्य करण्याचे योगदान देणे आवश्यक आहे. ही जबाबदारीची जाणीव करावी. माधवराव पेशव्यांच्या मृत्यूनंतर नाना फडणवीस व महादजी शिंदे यांनी मराठ्यांची सत्ता टिकून ठेवली., परंतु त्यांच्या मृत्यूनंतर मात्र उतरती कळा लागली या कारणांचा शोध घेणे आवश्यक आहे. यासाठी विद्यार्थ्यांना चिकित्सक विचार करायला लावणे आवश्यक आहे सत्य स्थितीतही आपल्या महाराष्ट्रात अशीच घटना घडून गेली शिवसेनेतील काही नेते फुटून त्यांनी स्वतंत्र सरकार निर्माण केले. यामागची कारणं शोधून काढता येतील त्यामुळे कोणती संकटे निर्माण होऊ शकतात याबाबत समस्या समाधान करता येऊ शकते कार्यकारण, युक्तिवाद, पद्धतशीर विचार अशा प्रकारे मानसिक क्रिया विद्यार्थ्यांकडून या विषयाच्या संदर्भात करून घेता येतील यातूनच पुढे नेतृत्व अनुयायित्व यासंदर्भात सचोटीने वागणे व निर्णय घेणे शक्य होईल.

मृदा हा विषयांश शिकवण्यासाठी शिक्षकांनी विविध माती नमुने दाखवून निरीक्षण करण्याची संधी द्यावी. मातीचे मृदेचे रंग वेगवेगळे आहेत., यासंदर्भात चिकित्सक विचार प्रक्रिया करावी. मातीचे मृदेत रूपांतर करण्यासाठी काय करावे ? यासंदर्भात सर्जनशील विचार प्रक्रिया घडवून आणावी. शहरातील जैविक कचऱ्याचे व्यवस्थापन करून मातीचे मृदेमध्ये रूपांतर करता येईल का? यासंदर्भात समस्या निराकरण करावे. शहरातील कचरा व मृदेचे अपक्षरण कसे रोखता येईल? यासंदर्भात मी कोणती भूमिका घ्यावी? याबाबत स्व जागृती करावी. शेतकऱ्यांच्या समस्या यातून आंतरव्यक्ती संबंध स्नेहपूर्ण राखण्याचा प्रयत्न करावा. स्थानिक पातळीवरील अशा अनेक समस्या ताणतणाव रहित राहून आपण सोडवू शकतो याबाबतआपली मते योग्य प्रकारे मांडून प्रभावी संप्रेषण साधावे व आत्मविश्वास निर्माण करावा .

उद्दिष्ट:- २. इयत्ता सातवीच्या समाजशास्त्र विषयाच्या पाठ्यक्रमात अंतर्भूत एकविसाव्या शतकातील जीवन कौशल्यांबाबत समाजशास्त्र विषय शिकवणाऱ्या शिक्षकांचा दृष्टिकोन जाणून घेणे.

इयत्ता सातवीला समाजशास्त्र विषय शिकवणाऱ्या दहा शिक्षकांची मुलाखत घेतली असता असे निदर्शनास आले की शिक्षकांना जीवन कौशल्य संदर्भात प्रशिक्षण दिले गेलेले आहे. पण 40 टक्के शिक्षकांनी एकविसाव्या शतकातील कौशल्य संदर्भात यादी सांगितली आहे. परंतु वर्ग अध्यापन करताना नेतृत्व, जबाबदारीची जाणीव, पुढाकार, सहकार्य ,संप्रेषण, कार्यकारण, साक्षरता ,समस्या समाधान या कौशल्यांच्या विकासाला ते प्राधान्य देतात. उपलब्ध साधन सामग्रीचा वापर करून अधिकाधिक अध्ययन समृद्ध अध्यापन करण्याचा शिक्षक प्रयत्न करताना दिसतात. विविध अध्यापन पद्धतींचा वापर करतात उदाहरणार्थ नाट्यीकरण, भूमिकाकरण, प्रकल्प या पद्धतींचा उपयोग 80 टक्के शिक्षक करतात. शाळेमध्ये मतदान प्रक्रियेने विद्यार्थी प्रतिनिधी निवडून नेतृत्वगुण, पुढाकार, जबाबदारीची जाणीव या कौशल्यांचा विकास करण्याची संधी 100 टक्के शाळांमध्ये दिली जाते. सहशालेय

उपक्रमात थोर नेत्यांची जयंती व पुण्यतिथी साजरी करणे, वाचन प्रेरणा दिन, बालिका दिन वृक्षारोपण, वृक्षदिंडी, प्रभात फेरी, स्वच्छता अभियान ,नाट्यीकरण स्पर्धा, निबंध स्पर्धा, वक्तृत्व स्पर्धा, पथनाट्य , प्रश्नमंजुषा या उपक्रमातून कौशल्य विकसनाच्या संधी 100 टक्के शाळांमध्ये दिल्या जातात.

विद्यार्थ्यांच्या कौशल्ये विकासाची पातळी मोजण्यासाठी मूल्यमापन तंत्रांचा वापर केला जातो. विद्यार्थ्यांमध्ये कौशल्य विकसन झाल्याच्या नोंदी दैनिकात केल्या जातात. प्रामुख्याने निरीक्षण पद्धतीचाच वापर केला जातो. प्रासंगिक नोंद किंवा पडताळा सूची हीच तंत्रे वापरली जातात 100 टक्के शाळांमध्ये मूल्यमापनासाठी वरील तंत्रांचा वापर केला जातो. प्लिकर अॅपच्या सहाय्याने 10 टक्के शिक्षकांनी विद्यार्थ्यांचे मूल्यांकन केलेले दिसून आले.

एकविसावे शतक तंत्रज्ञानाचे युग आहे या काळात शिक्षकही तंत्रस्नेही होणे आवश्यक आहे, त्यासाठी त्यांना प्रशिक्षणही दिले गेलेले आहे. करोना काळात सद्य परिस्थितीला सामोरे जाण्यासाठी शिक्षकांनी स्वतःहूनच चुका आणि शिका या पद्धतीने तंत्रज्ञानाचे ज्ञान मिळविले. विद्यार्थ्यांना पाठ्यपुस्तकातील क्यू आर कोड व दिशा अॅपच्या सहाय्याने विश्वासार्थ व अचूक माहिती मिळवण्या विषयी मार्गदर्शन 60% शिक्षकांनी केले आहे.

शिक्षकांच्या प्रत्यक्ष पाठाचे निरीक्षण न करता आल्यामुळे शिक्षकांनी वर्ग अध्यापनासाठी तयार केलेल्या व्हिडिओनचे निरीक्षण केले. निरीक्षणा अंती असे आढळले की 40% शिक्षक वर्ग अध्यापन करताना एकविसाव्या शतकातील कौशल्यांचा अंतर्भाव करतात त्याप्रमाणे काही उदाहरणे देतात. विद्यार्थ्यांना कृती करण्याच्या संधी देतात. वर्ग अध्यापन करताना नेमका एकविसाव्या शतकातील कौशल्यांचा आशयाशी कसा समन्वय साधावा याबाबत 40% शिक्षक अनभिज्ञ होते. इतिहास व भूगोलाचे शिक्षक मराठी विषयाच्या अध्यापन पद्धती प्रमाणेच पाठाचे वाचन करून त्यातील नवीन शब्दांचा अर्थ सांगत होते., परंतु इतिहास व भूगोल या विषयात संकल्पना आहेत आणि त्या संकल्पना स्पष्ट करण्यासाठी विविध उदाहरणे देणे अपेक्षित आहे. संकल्पना स्पष्ट करण्यासाठी काही शैक्षणिक साधनांची आवश्यकता असते उदाहरणार्थ प्रतिकृती, नकाशे , तक्ते, प्रत्यक्ष वस्तू, पृथ्वीगोल इत्यादी दैनंदिन जीवनातील उदाहरणे देऊन 20% शिक्षकांनी वर्ग अध्यापन केले. शैक्षणिक साधनांचा वापर पीपीटी द्वारे 80% शिक्षकांनी केला. इतिहास अध्यापनाच्या कथन, व्याख्यान, गोष्ट अशा पद्धती आहेत त्याचा वापर अध्यापनासाठी करणे अपेक्षित होते. परंतु ३० टक्के शिक्षक या पद्धतींचा वापर करताना दिसले. भूगोल अध्यापनाच्या प्रवास वर्णन पद्धत, लोक पद्धत, पदार्थ पद्धत, या पद्धतीने वर्ग अध्यापन कसे करावे याबाबत 60 टक्के शिक्षक अनभिज्ञ आहेत. शिक्षक वर्ग अध्यापन करताना तंत्रज्ञानाचा शैक्षणिक साधन म्हणून खूप छान उपयोग करून घेत आहे. शिक्षक बौद्धिक विकास करण्यासाठी तत्पर आहेत. परंतु विद्यार्थ्यांच्या भावनिक, क्रियात्मक व आंतरक्रियात्मक क्षमता व कौशल्य विकसनासाठी तरतूद फारच कमी दिसली. तसेच मूल्य निर्मिती करण्यासाठी आशयाचे स्पष्टीकरण करताना समर्पक उदाहरणे व अध्ययन अनुभव देण्याचा प्रयत्न अल्प होता., पाठ्यक्रम शिकवणे म्हणजे फक्त आशय विद्यार्थ्यांपर्यंत पोहोचणे एवढाच हेतू नाही. सूज सुनागरिक घडवायचे असतील तर शिक्षकांना 'जीवन कौशल्यांना' पुन्हा नव्याने उजाळा देण्याची गरज आहे.काही उदाहरणे दिल्यास किंवा विषयानुसार प्रशिक्षण कार्यक्रम आखल्यास नव्याने उजाळा मिळेल. शिक्षक अष्टपैलू व्यक्तिमत्वाचा असेल तरच भावी पिढी अष्टपैलू बनेल म्हणूनच आधी शिक्षकांना आत्मनिर्भर करणे गरजेचे आहे. तरच आपले भावी नागरिक आत्मनिर्भर भारत बनवायला सक्षम बनतील.

निष्कर्ष:-

एकविसाव्या शतकासाठी आपण ज्या विद्यार्थ्यांना अध्यापन करत आहोत ते सक्षम होणे आवश्यक आहे. याबाबत सर्व शिक्षक सजग आहेत. परंतु नेमकी कोणती कौशल्ये विद्यार्थ्यांमध्ये विकसित करावीत याबाबत अधिक मार्गदर्शन होणे गरजेचे आहे. आधुनिक काळाला अनुलक्षून कोणत्या अध्यापन पद्धतीचा कशा प्रकारे करावा? मूल्यमापनासाठी कोणत्या तंत्रांचा वापर करावा? वर्ग अध्यापनासाठी व मूल्यमापनासाठी आधुनिक तंत्रज्ञानाविषयी प्रशिक्षण कार्यक्रम आखणे आवश्यक आहे यातून नक्कीच पुढील पिढी ही आत्मनिर्भर भारत बनवण्यासाठी सक्षम असेल.

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डॉ सुरेश करंदीकर व डॉ मीना मंगरूळकर- इतिहास आशय अध्यापन पद्धती , फडके प्रकाशन, कोल्हापूर.

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